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ANALELE UNIVERSITĂȚII DIN ORADEA, FASCICULA PROTECȚIA MEDIULUI
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QUALITATIVE ENHANCEMENTS IN AGRICULTURAL CROPS FOLLOWING EUROPEAN FUNDING

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The present study analyzes the impact of accessing European funds on a sample of 60 agricultural holdings in Romania, examining the transformations that occurred before and after the implementation of financing projects, based on a comprehensive questionnaire addressing crop quality, soil health, resource use, applied treatments, organic production, certifications, and perceptions related to consumer health and satisfaction.

The results highlight a profound shift in farm performance, reflected in a notable improvement in crop quality, described after financing through terms such as “very good,” “much superior,” “high,” or “excellent,” in contrast to the earlier situation marked by technological limitations, lack of mechanization, and structural soil issues.

Soil health improved from low levels—affected by the absence of natural fertilizers and the excessive use of chemicals—to high levels due to the application of organic fertilizers and the elimination of chemical treatments.

Funding stimulated the mechanization of agricultural holdings, evident in the increased diesel consumption and the introduction of high-performance machinery that enabled more efficient agricultural work. At the same time, investments led to the diversification of energy resources through the adoption of photovoltaic panels and the expansion of water resources through well drilling.

The transition toward organic farming represents one of the most significant developments: from a 98% absence of such practices before financing, farmers reached a level of organic farming adoption of approximately two-thirds following project implementation.

These findings demonstrate the role of European funds in strengthening the sustainability, modernization, and competitiveness of Romanian agriculture, while also contributing to increased consumer satisfaction and the production of foods with a positive impact on health.

Keywords: agricultural funds, financing analysis, young farmers

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INTRODUCTION

Romanian agriculture is undergoing a rapid transformation driven largely by access to European funds, which have reshaped how farmers prepare soil, select crops, apply treatments and manage natural resources. Before these funds became available, most farmers relied on traditional methods, outdated machinery and often inadequate resource management — conditions that translated into lower crop quality, poor soil health and limited capacity to adopt organic practices.

Romanian agricultural products, as part of the European market, must meet EU quality standards. Several factors have contributed to declining productivity and lower product quality in Romania’s agricultural sector, the

most important being financial difficulties in purchasing inputs, fragmentation of cultivated land and a widespread lack of technological, managerial and marketing skills among many family holdings and small farms. These issues underpin the urgent need to reform agro-food quality standards. (Istudor et al., 2006)

Romania’s agricultural potential has consistently been high, thanks to favourable geography, climate conditions and soil quality. Given this advantage, there is a clear need for agricultural policies focused on regional development. Public policies must capitalize on Romania’s agricultural potential through coherent investment strategies and adaptation to environmental changes. (Strijek, 2025)

At both national and EU levels, public policy displays limited coherence. For example,

while genetically modified organisms are largely restricted in the EU to protect biodiversity, subsidy schemes are sometimes structured in ways that indirectly reduce biodiversity. Subsidies intended to support agriculture can create market distortions: they frequently benefit large producers disproportionately, leaving smallholders at a competitive disadvantage. (Năsulea et al., 2024)

Current agri-food policies and programs point to the need for a shift towards approaches that promote socially and ecologically sustainable food production. Quality labeling schemes have emerged as local or regional solutions for rural economies. Public institutions promote quality food products to support small-scale, sustainable agriculture. The motivation for focusing on quality schemes and promotional tools stems from the state of Romania's agri-food sector since late 2016, characterized by weak coherence in rural development program measures and a lack of market-oriented public policies, while European producers increasingly target new markets using indirect support mechanisms for farmers. To reposition Romania away from a vulnerable food-security profile, policymakers will need to adopt concrete sustainability measures. (Pădure, 2020)

Accelerating the structural adjustment of the agri-food sector remains a constant pressure on Romanian agriculture. This presents an unprecedented challenge for decision-makers over the coming years, who must continue and speed up the institutional preparations required for implementing the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and managing associated funds. Cost-benefit and impact assessments of CAP adoption can provide useful quantified guidance and a basis for choosing appropriate agricultural policy instruments in both the pre- and post-accession periods, while offering benchmarks for producers and consumers. (Giurcă, 2007)

It is also essential to analyse the direct and indirect effects of EU integration and CAP implementation on agricultural developments at both macroeconomic and microeconomic levels. Consideration must be given to post-accession economic trends, the market for agricultural goods, absorption of EU funds, technical-financial performance of farms, income dynamics and food consumption patterns. (Toma et al., 2010)

The empirical survey conducted for this article - based on 60 farmers who received EU

agricultural grants - shows marked changes. Many respondents described the pre-funding quality of their crops as "good," but that assessment was relative, measured against low technological standards and clear financial limitations. Notably, 26% reported that a crop essentially "did not exist" or was only in an early stage, indicating that funding enabled the establishment of some farms, not merely their modernization.

Soil health before funding was seriously problematic: 10% explicitly described it as low, and many responses repeatedly mentioned the absence of organic fertilizers, widespread chemical use or even the practical absence of healthy topsoil (comments such as "the soil was not healthy because many chemicals were used" or "soil was poor due to lack of natural fertilizer" were common). This degradation reflects an intensive, quantity-oriented agriculture where ecosystem health was not a priority prior to funding.

Lack of mechanization and modern technical resources is also apparent from fuel-use data before grants: almost a quarter of farmers reported using no fuel at all, suggesting either the absence of agricultural machinery, reliance on manual labour, or extremely low levels of development. Those who did use fuel often operated old, inefficient equipment that limited ploughing depth, the quality of soil work and production efficiency. Water and energy access was precarious: farmers depended mainly on the public electricity grid (insufficient for modern agricultural needs) and on ad hoc wells or network supply not designed for sustainable irrigation. Organic production was virtually nonexistent before funding: 98% of respondents said they did not practice organic or mountain agriculture, either from lack of interest or lack of possibility; certified products were therefore absent, restricting access to specialty markets.

Within this broader context, EU funding functioned as a powerful catalyst — not only improving farm performance but also shifting production philosophies toward sustainability, quality and stewardship of natural resources. Across the dataset, farmers consistently reported that funding led to "much higher" crop quality, in some cases "excellent" soil health, substantial gains in energy autonomy and a clear move toward organic production. This study aims to examine these changes in detail, discuss each result, and provide a comprehensive picture of how European

financing contributes to the sustainable development of Romanian farms.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study's methodology is based on a questionnaire composed of both closed and open-ended questions, administered to 60 farmers who received European funding. The questionnaire evaluated the condition of the farms before and after accessing the funds, focusing on key components of agricultural activity: crop quality, soil health, fuel use, energy sources, access to water resources, the existence of organic production, certifications, the introduction of new varieties, the types of treatments applied before and after funding, the presence of soil and water analyses, and farmers' perceptions of how their products affect consumer health and satisfaction.

The research employed a descriptive and interpretative approach, oriented toward a before–after comparative analysis. Rather than constructing a complex statistical model, it examined the values reported by farmers, integrated their perspectives both qualitatively and quantitatively, and formulated interpretations that reflect their actual experiences. Open-ended responses were used to complement and clarify statistical data, providing a more nuanced understanding of the transformations observed.

The methodology allows for correlations between practices and resource use on the one hand, and farmers' perceptions of consumer health and product quality on the other. This offers a holistic view of the impact of European funds, extending the analysis beyond technical or quantitative aspects to include the cultural, technological and ecological changes generated by the financing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Crop quality before and after accessing European funds

Before receiving funding, crop quality varied widely, though most respondents described it as “good” (54%), which might initially suggest a favourable situation. However, a contextual analysis shows that this “good” quality was assessed relative to the limited resources of the farms, the absence of modern machinery and insufficient inputs. In reality, many answers reveal clear

shortcomings: 26% stated that “there was no real crop,” in the sense that no consolidated agricultural system existed; 6% reported average quality, while others used terms such as “weak,” “acceptable,” “decent,” “it was good but not organic,” or “the crop quality was lower because the machinery was old.” These nuances highlight a significant discrepancy between farmers' perceptions and actual agricultural production standards.

After receiving funding, perceptions of crop quality change dramatically. Responses become overwhelmingly positive, with frequent mentions of “very good,” “much superior,” “high,” “superior quality,” “excellent,” “the quality is much better,” “the products are organic,” and “quality increased considerably.” A notable observation is the repeated idea that new machinery enables more efficient work, such as deeper ploughing, which results in better soil preparation and stronger crop development. Farmers also emphasize that the transition to organic cultivation significantly enhanced crop quality, fully aligning with the specialized literature on organic farming. The improvement in crop quality is one of the most evident effects of accessing European funds, and the consistency of the responses strongly supports this conclusion. (figures 1)

1a

1b

Figures 1 Crop quality before and after accessing European funds

Soil health before and after funding

The condition of soil health prior to accessing funds was deeply problematic. The responses overwhelmingly reveal severe deficiencies: poor soil (10%), low or reduced quality (6–8% nominally, but repeatedly

emphasized in many open-ended responses), the absence of organic fertilizers, intensive use of chemicals and even descriptions such as “nonexistent” or “the land was not worked.” Several farmers explicitly stated that their soil “was not healthy because many chemicals were used,” while others noted that soil health was compromised by the lack of natural fertilizers. The frequent recurrence of terms like “reduced,” “lack of natural fertilizer,” “weak,” “very low,” or “moderate to low” paints a clear picture of a degraded agricultural environment.

After receiving funding, the transformation is remarkable. Farmers describe their soil as “very good,” “good,” “perfectly healthy,” “100% healthy,” “high,” “medium to

high,” or “significantly improved due to organic fertilizers.” A systematic approach to soil treatment becomes evident, involving manure, natural fertilizers and ecological practices that restore the biological structure of the soil. Many farmers emphasize that they no longer use chemical fertilizers, herbicides or pesticides, which directly explains the substantial improvement in soil health. Overall, the data indicate a clear shift from degraded soil to healthy soil, supporting the conclusion that European funds directly contribute to sustainable agricultural practices. (figures 2)

2a

2b

Figures 2 **Soil health before and after funding**

Fuel use before and after accessing funds

Before receiving funding, fuel use reflects a low level of mechanization: a significant share of farmers reported that they “did not use fuels,” which essentially indicates the absence of machinery. At the same time, 70% reported using diesel, but this typically corresponded to limited fieldwork carried out with old or inefficient equipment. After accessing the funds, 94% of farmers use diesel, a clear sign of intensified mechanization necessary for efficient land exploitation. The appearance of combinations such as diesel +

gasoline + oil or diesel + solar energy also points to a diversification of agricultural activities.

Energy sources before and after accessing funds

Before receiving funding, farmers relied almost entirely on the electricity grid. Many even stated that they “did not use energy” for agricultural activities. After the investments, the situation changes significantly:

photovoltaic panels become the primary energy source for a substantial share of farmers. The high frequency of responses mentioning photovoltaic energy—either alone or combined with grid electricity—shows a clear transition toward energy sustainability. (figures 3)

Water resources before and after funding

Before receiving financial support, water resources came mainly from the public network or simple wells. Many respondents stated that they “did not use water,” which indicates a lack of irrigation altogether.

3a

Distribution of energy sources used

3b

Figures 3 **Energy sources before and after accessing funds**

After purchasing the necessary equipment and infrastructure, farmers now rely on drilled wells or on combinations of drilled wells and the public network. The introduction of drilled wells represents a major improvement, enabling more efficient and reliable irrigation. (figures 4)

4a

4b

Figures 4 **Water resources before and after funding**
Organic production and certifications

Before accessing the funds, the vast majority of beneficiaries did not engage in organic, ecological, or mountain production, either due to limited financial resources, lack of interest, or insufficient technical capacity. The data show that approximately 98% of respondents did not carry out such activities prior to funding. After project implementation, the situation changed significantly: around two-thirds of beneficiaries reported transitioning to organic production, either across the entire farm or only for specific crops. This shift demonstrates a direct impact of the funds on steering farmers toward more sustainable practices. At the same time, one-third of respondents continue to operate conventional systems, either due to operational constraints or insufficient resources for full conversion.

Before using the funds, almost all respondents (98%) did not hold any organic certifications, indicating a very low level of certification in their sector, restricted by limited resources, experience, or infrastructure. After the funds were implemented, the situation improved considerably, with about 32% of beneficiaries reporting that they hold at least one certified organic product or that their entire farm has become certified organic—evidence of the positive impact of financial support. However, the majority (68%) have still not completed the certification process, whether due to

administrative, logistical, or timing constraints, indicating that full transition requires more time. Overall, the data reveal that the funds created a clear opportunity for adopting organic certification, even if the process is gradual. Thus, there is a significant difference between the initial situation and the post-funding stage, highlighting the role of financial support in encouraging organic certification among farmers.

Introduction of new varieties

Most farmers did not introduce new varieties, but approximately 18% diversified their crops with green beans, peas, peppers, cucumbers, zucchini, pumpkins, tomatoes, watermelon, and sweet corn, reflecting an adaptation to market demand.

After accessing the funds, most respondents (around 62%) reported that they improved their existing production, either by increasing the quantity or by enhancing product quality, with outputs becoming healthier and more ecological. A small percentage, between 6% and 8%, made no improvements, suggesting financial or technical barriers. Detailed responses indicate that some farms diversified their cultivated varieties or adopted ecological practices, contributing to higher-quality products (2–4%). Thus, the funds clearly stimulated production improvements—both quantitative and qualitative—for most farmers. Overall, the data show a significant difference between the initial situation and the post-funding stage, demonstrating the role of funds in increasing agricultural performance.

A majority of respondents (approximately 70%, including “No,” “no,” and “I did not introduce new varieties”) did not introduce new varieties in agriculture or livestock, indicating that crop diversification remained limited for many farms. In contrast, around 18% did introduce new varieties, with detailed responses citing green beans, peas, peppers, cucumbers, zucchini, pumpkins, sweet corn, watermelon, tomatoes, and cabbage. This reflects meaningful diversification in certain farms. The data suggest that the funds facilitated the introduction of new crops only for a subset of beneficiaries, while most retained their existing structure. The impact is more pronounced in farms that adopted high-value or ecologically oriented varieties. Thus, the introduction of new varieties was selective

but significant for those who implemented changes.

Agricultural treatments before and after accessing funds

Before funding, chemical treatments predominated: herbicides, pesticides, nitrogen, and chemical fertilizers. After accessing the funds, many farmers shifted to organic treatments, particularly manure, while some abandoned chemical treatments entirely. Others combined traditional and ecological methods during the transition.

Before receiving funds, most respondents applied standard chemical treatments—including herbicides, insecticides, chemical fertilizers, nitrogen, pesticides, and foliar treatments—representing approximately 46% of responses. Another group (around 20%) stated that they did not apply any treatments or that treatments “were not needed,” either due to the absence of crops or because they did not use chemicals. Individual responses listed foliar treatments, fertilizers, herbicides, insecticides, nitrogen, pesticides, chemical fertilizers, or combinations of these, illustrating the diversity of conventional practices used for crop protection and fertilization. Some respondents reported applying herbicides alone, nitrogen alone, or foliar treatments combined with herbicides and nitrogen, confirming that farmers used chemicals based on crop needs. At the same time, a considerable number of farms applied no treatments at all, indicating less intensive or more conservative operations. Overall, the initial situation reflects predominantly conventional agriculture, with a broad range of chemical treatments, but also a segment of farms without chemical interventions.

After using the funds, some farmers (approximately 20%, including “We do not use,” “We no longer use,” “I do not use,” and similar responses) no longer apply any chemical treatments, maintaining ecological crops or aiming for full transition to organic farming. Another significant group (approximately 28%, including various mentions of “natural fertilizers” and “manure”) applies organic fertilizers such as manure, in different forms and combinations. A smaller group (approximately 14%, including “chemical treatments, nitrogen, herbicides”) continues to apply partial chemical treatments, combining nitrogen, herbicides, and sometimes manure. There are also responses indicating exclusive use of eco or bio treatments, such as

“eco and bio treatments” or “treatments permitted in eco agriculture” (around 6%). Some farmers combine manure with herbicides or pesticides, using both organic and chemical substances in reduced doses (about 4%). Treatments listed also include nitrogen alone, nitrogen with herbicides, or nitrogen combined with herbicides and pesticides, showing that fertilization and crop protection remain partially conventional in some farms (around 6%). Other responses describe ecological manure applications, foliar treatments, and natural fertilizers, reflecting a diverse set of adopted techniques. Some farms use only natural fertilizers without chemicals, while others combine chemical and organic fertilization methods for a gradual transition. Overall, the data indicate a mix of ecological practices, natural fertilizers, and controlled chemical treatments, demonstrating a progressive adaptation after accessing the funds. Thus, the funds enabled farmers to reduce chemical use and adopt more ecological practices while maintaining crop productivity and protection.

Correlation with consumer health and satisfaction

Farmers believe that organic products have a positive impact on health, and customers are generally very satisfied with product quality, with many reporting satisfaction levels of 100%.

Most respondents (approximately 28%, including “No” and “We cannot assess”) believe they cannot directly correlate their products with clients’ health outcomes, or they do not know how to evaluate this. In contrast, a significant share (around 44%, including “Very good,” “Very good/very healthy if we have organic crops,” “Very good,” and “Excellent”) believe that organic products have a strong positive impact on health, mainly due to the high quality of crops and raw materials. Another group (approximately 28%, including responses mentioning high-quality vegetables and seeds, as well as detailed comments about satisfied customers) emphasizes that organic products—including honey—contribute to consumer health, reduce disease risk, and provide beneficial vitamins and nutrients. Detailed responses highlight that the quality of raw materials and final products is correlated with consumer health and satisfaction. Numerous examples describe vegetables and organic products as “very healthy” or “superior

quality,” indicating a positive effect on customers. Overall, the data suggest a broad consensus that organic and high-quality products contribute to health and well-being, even if some respondents cannot quantify the effect. Thus, the funds and the shift toward organic production appear to have facilitated the creation of products that positively impact consumer health.

Most respondents (around 22%, including “No” and “We cannot assess”) state that they cannot determine a clear correlation between their products and customer satisfaction, or they do not know how to evaluate it (“I don’t know,” “I cannot say”). However, a significant portion (around 42%, including “Very satisfied,” “Very good,” “100% satisfied,” and “Very satisfied according to what they tell us”) indicate that customers are very pleased with the products offered, emphasizing the positive impact of quality and price-quality ratio. Furthermore, responses mentioning “increased satisfaction level,” “significantly increased satisfaction,” or “high satisfaction level” (around 24%) show that the products contribute to higher customer satisfaction and farmer confidence, reflecting positive perceptions of ecological and high-quality products. Other detailed responses highlight that a diet rich in vegetables and organic products not only improves health but also enhances mood, energy, and overall well-being, confirming the link between food and general satisfaction. Examples referencing “loyal customers” or “good price-quality products” indicate that satisfaction is also influenced by consumer loyalty and perceived value. (figure 5)

Figure 5 **Effective young farmers in North-West**

Overall, the data suggest a clear correlation between ecological/high-quality products and high customer satisfaction. Thus, the funds that facilitated organic production indirectly contributed to increased consumer satisfaction and strengthened producers’ reputations.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the data collected from the questionnaire applied to the 60 farmers clearly shows that accessing European funds has become a central driver of modernization in Romanian agriculture, profoundly influencing both the quality of production and the organization and functioning of farms. Before funding, most farms faced outdated infrastructure, lacked mechanization, and poorly managed natural resources, which directly affected crop quality and soil condition. Soil degradation, described in numerous responses with terms such as “poor,” “low,” or “depleted,” resulted from a chemical-dependent agriculture lacking organic fertilization and a clear sustainability focus. After accessing European funds, a systematic and consistent improvement is observed, with farmers repeatedly reporting that their soil is “very healthy,” “perfect,” or “highly fertile,” due to the abandonment of chemicals and the adoption of natural fertilizers. Crop quality has significantly improved, reflected in the frequent use of positive descriptors in responses and the recognition that modern machinery allows for more efficient work, supporting optimal plant development.

The funds have also been decisive in modernizing farm energy systems, with photovoltaic panels becoming widely adopted, as well as in establishing stable water supply systems through the expansion of drilled wells. At the same time, farm mechanization accelerated, evidenced by increased diesel consumption and the adoption of new technologies that enable better control over agricultural operations. The transition to organic farming is one of the most important effects of the funding, as farmers not only adopted ecological methods but also began to abandon chemical treatments, use natural fertilizers, and pursue certifications for their products, even though the process remains ongoing for many respondents. The importance of this transition is further highlighted by farmers’ perceptions of the beneficial effects of their products on consumer health and satisfaction.

The study paints a picture of an agricultural sector in transformation, where European funding not only addresses past deficiencies but also creates the conditions for sustainable, high-performing, quality-oriented

agriculture. The impact is observable at all levels—from soil and technologies to consumers and markets—demonstrating that agricultural investment is a fundamental pillar of rural development. The transformations recorded confirm that Romanian agriculture, supported by European funds, is increasingly aligned with Western standards, strengthening its capacity to produce healthy food, responsibly utilize natural resources, and meet the growing demands of contemporary consumers.

Overall, the study demonstrates that accessing European funds has generated essential, multidimensional transformations. Improvements in crop quality, soil health, access to resources, energy modernization, crop diversification, reduction of chemical treatments, and increased orientation toward organic farming are clear evidence of the positive impact of these funds. Farmers have adopted modern technologies, enhanced soil structure, and become active participants in sustainable agriculture. Increased consumer satisfaction and a shift toward organic products confirm the success of the implemented changes.

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COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION OF THE ANTIOXIDANT PROFILE OF MULTI-COMPONENT HERBAL EXTRACTS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Multi-component ethanolic plant extract mixtures derived from *Artemisia absinthium L.*, *Viola tricolor L.*, and *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* were assessed for their phytochemical composition and antioxidant potential. Plant materials were collected from unpolluted habitats in Bihor County, Romania, and extracts were obtained via Soxhlet extraction and concentrated under reduced pressure. Four mixtures (M1–M4) were evaluated for total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, and DPPH radical scavenging activity. Among the mixtures, M2, containing *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* and *Viola tricolor L.*, exhibited the highest levels of total phenolics (154.82 ± 1.01 mg GAE/g dry extract) and flavonoids (30.20 ± 0.10 mg QE/g dry extract), as well as the greatest antioxidant activity (85.21 ± 0.39 % DPPH inhibition). These findings indicate a strong correlation between polyphenolic and flavonoid content and radical scavenging capacity, suggesting synergistic interactions within the mixtures. The results support the potential application of multi-component plant extract formulations as natural antioxidants in functional foods, nutraceuticals, and phytopharmaceuticals, warranting further mechanistic and bioavailability studies.

Keywords: *Artemisia absinthium L.*, *Viola tricolor L.*, *Vaccinium myrtillus L.*, phenolic compounds
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INTRODUCTION

Polyphenols are a diverse group of bioactive compounds widely recognized for their potent antioxidant properties, capable of neutralizing reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), thereby protecting cells and tissues from oxidative damage and associated pathological conditions. These compounds, including flavonoids, phenolic acids, and anthocyanins, contribute not only to antioxidant defense but also to a broad range of pharmacological effects, such as anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and cytoprotective activities. The biological potential of plant-derived polyphenols is closely linked to their abundance, chemical diversity, and synergistic interactions within complex herbal matrices (Ciupei et al., 2024; Hassanpour and Doroudi, 2023; Sun et al., 2024).

Herbal extracts derived from *Artemisia absinthium L.* (*Absinthii herba*), *Viola tricolor L.* (*Violae tricoloris herba*), and *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* (*Myrtilli fructus*) exhibit a wide spectrum of therapeutic effects, combining common activities with species-specific properties. *Artemisia absinthium L.* is characterized by the presence of sesquiterpene lactones, flavonoids, and phenolic acids, which

collectively underlie its digestive stimulant, antioxidant, and anthelmintic actions (Kosakowska et al., 2025; Liu et al., 2023; Saunoriūtė et al., 2023). *Viola tricolor L.* contains flavonoids, cyclotides, and phenolic acids, conferring antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytotoxic properties (Batiha et al., 2023; Godara, 2022; Supty et al., 2025). *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* is particularly rich in anthocyanins, flavonoids, and chlorogenic acid, which support its potent antioxidant, antidiabetic, hypolipidemic, and vasoprotective effects (Chan and Tomlinson, 2020; Pires et al., 2020; Scalzo et al., 2015). Most of these bioactivities have been confirmed through in vitro and preclinical models, highlighting the pharmacological relevance of these species.

The combination of these three herbal extracts into multi-component formulations offers the potential for additive or synergistic effects, enhancing their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities while preserving their species-specific therapeutic actions (Karole et al., 2019; Palla et al., 2021). Understanding the phytochemical composition and bioactivity of such complex extracts is essential for their potential application as natural functional ingredients or as complementary therapeutic agents. Therefore,

the present study aims to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the phytochemical profiles and antioxidant potential of multi-component extracts derived from *Absinthii herba*, *Violae tricoloris herba*, and *Myrtilli fructus*, contributing to the scientific basis for their use in functional foods, nutraceuticals, or phytopharmaceutical development.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

PLANT MATERIAL

The aerial parts of *Artemisia absinthium* L. and *Viola tricolor* L., as well as the fully ripened fruits of *Vaccinium myrtillus* L., were collected from unpolluted natural habitats in Bihor County, Romania. *Artemisia absinthium* L. was harvested in Podgoria (47.057441, 22.015630) in July 2022, collecting basal leaves and flowering tips up to 4 mm in diameter. *Viola tricolor* L. was gathered in Sititelec, Husasău de Tinca (46.886105, 21.900203) in June 2022, focusing on flowering aerial parts. *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. fruits were manually collected in Ponoară, Bratca (46.891488, 22.682169) in July 2022 at full ripeness. Plant material was carefully selected under optimal conditions to ensure health and integrity. Voucher specimens were deposited in the Herbarium of the Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, University of Oradea, under the codes UOP 05.708 for *Artemisia absinthium* L., UOP 05.709 for *Viola tricolor* L., and UOP 05.710 for *Vaccinium myrtillus* L.

REAGENTS AND EQUIPMENT

All chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade. The reagents included ethanol (p.a., Chimreactiv, Romania), gallic acid (Silver Chemicals, Romania), quercetin (Silver

Chemicals, Romania), 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH, Merck, Germany), Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (Merck, Germany), sodium carbonate 20% (freshly prepared, Chimreactiv, Romania), sodium nitrite 5% (freshly prepared, Chimreactiv, Romania), aluminum chloride 10% (Merck, Germany), sodium hydroxide 1 M (Chimreactiv, Romania), and distilled water. Extracts were concentrated using a Hei-VAP Advantage rotary evaporator (Heidolph, Germany), and spectrophotometric analyses were performed using a PG Instruments T70+ UV-VIS spectrophotometer (UK).

METHODS

Extraction and Preparation of Extract Mixtures: The aerial parts of *Artemisia absinthium* L., *Viola tricolor* L., and the fruits of *Vaccinium myrtillus* L., previously air-dried in a well-ventilated room at room temperature, were finely ground separately to enhance the extraction of bioactive compounds. For each plant, 20 g of the dried material were subjected to Soxhlet extraction using ethanol as solvent. The extraction was carried out for 4 hours for *Artemisia absinthium* L. and *Viola tricolor* L., and 3 hours for *Vaccinium myrtillus* L., ensuring complete recovery of the active constituents. The resulting extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator and subsequently re-dissolved in ethanol to a defined volume for further analysis. To investigate the potential additive or synergistic effects, the individual extracts were combined according to the ratios indicated in Table 1 to obtain multi-component formulations. Each mixture was homogenized to ensure uniform distribution of bioactive compounds prior to further analyses.

Table 1

Composition of Extract Mixtures Studied

Mixtures	Constituent Species
M ₁	<i>Artemisia absinthium</i> L. + <i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L. – 1:1
M ₂	<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L. + <i>Viola tricolor</i> L. – 1:1
M ₃	<i>Artemisia absinthium</i> L. + <i>Viola tricolor</i> L. – 1:1
M ₄	<i>Artemisia absinthium</i> L. + <i>Viola tricolor</i> L. + <i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L. – 1:1:1

Total Phenolic Content: The total phenolic content of the prepared extract mixtures (M₁–M₄) was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu assay. For each mixture, 0.3 mL of the solution was combined with 0.45 mL of Folin–Ciocalteu reagent and 1.2 mL of distilled water, and the reaction was allowed to proceed in the dark for 10 minutes. Subsequently, 1.5 mL of freshly prepared 20% sodium carbonate solution was added, and the samples were

incubated at room temperature for 60 minutes. Absorbance was recorded at 765 nm, and a blank containing ethanol was included for reference. All determinations were performed in triplicate. The total phenolic content was calculated using a gallic acid calibration curve (10–50 mg/mL), and results were expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents per milliliter of extract mixture (Elferjane et al., 2024; Gonçalves et al., 2012; Hbika et al., 2022).

Total Flavonoid Content: The flavonoid content of the extracts and extract mixtures was determined using the aluminum chloride colorimetric method. Briefly, 1 mL of each extract was mixed with 4 mL of distilled water and 0.3 mL of 5% sodium nitrite, and allowed to react in the dark for 5 minutes. Then, 0.3 mL of 10% aluminum chloride was added and the mixture incubated for 6 minutes. Subsequently, 2 mL of 1 M sodium hydroxide was added, and the final volume was adjusted to 10 mL with distilled water. Absorbance was measured at 510 nm against a blank prepared with ethanol (Altiok et al., 2022; Msaada et al., 2015). All measurements were performed in triplicate, and flavonoid content was quantified using a quercetin calibration curve (2–10 mg/mL).

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay: The antioxidant activity of the mixtures of extracts was evaluated using the DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging method. Each mixture of extracts (0.5 mL) was combined with 3 mL of 0.1 mM DPPH solution and incubated in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes. A blank containing ethanol instead of the extract mixture was prepared. Absorbance was measured at 517 nm, and the

percentage of radical scavenging was calculated relative to the blank. All measurements were performed in triplicate to ensure reproducibility (Ciulca et al., 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The total phenolic content of the extract mixtures was assessed using the Folin-Ciocalteu method. Quantification was based on a calibration curve prepared with gallic acid ($Y = 0.007X + 0.0671$, $R^2 = 0.9918$), which confirmed a linear relationship between absorbance and concentration within the tested range. The results obtained for the different extract mixtures are presented in Table 2. Evaluation of the data indicates that the total phenolic content varied significantly among the mixtures. Mixture M2 exhibited the highest phenolic concentration, with a mean value of 154.82 ± 1.01 mg GAE/g dry extract, followed by M3 at 121.89 ± 0.96 mg GAE/g, M4 at 108.89 ± 0.53 mg GAE/g, and M1 displaying the lowest value of 85.74 ± 0.64 mg GAE/g. These findings suggest that the combination of plant constituents in M2 may contribute to additive or synergistic effects on phenolic content.

Table 2

Determination of total phenolic content in the extract mixtures

Sample	Sample absorbance measured at 765 nm	Sample concentration (mg GAE/g dry extract)	Mean concentration (mg GAE/g dry extract) \pm SD
M ₁	0,608	85,85	85,74 \pm 0,64
	0,603	85,06	
	0,611	86,33	
M ₂	0,989	154,94	154,82 \pm 1,01
	0,994	155,78	
	0,982	153,76	
M ₃	0,905	122,14	121,89 \pm 0,96
	0,896	120,83	
	0,909	122,72	
M ₄	0,886	108,32	108,89 \pm 0,53
	0,891	108,98	
	0,894	109,37	

The quantification of total flavonoids in the analyzed extract mixtures was performed through the aluminum chloride colorimetric assay, a well-established method for assessing flavonoid concentration. The calibration curve obtained for quercetin standard solutions demonstrated good linearity within the tested concentration range, as expressed by the regression equation $Y = 0.033X + 0.1418$ ($R^2 = 0.9873$). The results of the spectrophotometric determinations, expressed as milligrams of quercetin equivalents per gram of dry extract (mg QE/g), are presented in Table 3. Distinct

differences were observed among the mixtures regarding their flavonoid content. The M2 mixture exhibited the highest value (30.20 ± 0.10 mg QE/g dry extract), suggesting an enhanced accumulation of flavonoid compounds, potentially due to synergistic interactions between *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* and *Viola tricolor L.* Intermediate values were recorded for M3 (24.11 ± 0.09 mg QE/g) and M4 (18.13 ± 0.07 mg QE/g), while M1 showed the lowest flavonoid concentration (16.44 ± 0.08 mg QE/g).

Table 3

Total flavonoid content of the analyzed extract mixtures

Sample	Sample absorbance measured at 510 nm	Sample concentration (mg QE/1 g dry extract)	Mean concentration (mg QE/g dry extract) \pm SD
M ₁	0,628	16,37	16,44 \pm 0,08
	0,630	16,43	
	0,633	16,53	
M ₂	0,986	30,09	30,2 \pm 0,10
	0,992	30,31	
	0,989	30,20	
M ₃	0,925	24,21	24,11 \pm 0,09
	0,921	24,09	
	0,919	24,03	
M ₄	0,786	18,06	18,13 \pm 0,07
	0,789	18,15	
	0,791	18,21	

The antioxidant capacity of the extract mixtures was determined by the DPPH assay, with the percentage of inhibition calculated from the absorbance values of the samples and the blank. The obtained results are presented in Table 4. The highest radical scavenging activity was observed for mixture M2 (85.21 \pm 0.39%),

followed by M3 (79.98 \pm 0.18%) and M4 (78.28 \pm 0.28%). The lowest activity was recorded for M1 (66.31 \pm 0.28%). These results suggest that the combination of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* and *Viola tricolor L.* (M2) shows superior antioxidant potential compared to the other formulations.

Table 4

DPPH radical scavenging activity of the analyzed extract mixtures

Sample	Blank absorbance	Sample absorbance	Inhibition %	Mean inhibition % \pm SD
M ₁	0,895	0,304	66,03	66,31 \pm 0,28
		0,299	66,59	
		0,301	66,33	
M ₂	0,895	0,132	85,25	85,21 \pm 0,39
		0,129	85,58	
		0,136	84,80	
M ₃	0,895	0,178	80,11	79,98 \pm 0,18
		0,181	79,77	
		0,176	80,06	
M ₄	0,895	0,192	78,54	78,28 \pm 0,28
		0,194	78,32	
		0,197	77,98	

The mean values obtained for total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, and DPPH radical scavenging activity in the analyzed extract mixtures were systematized and represented graphically in Figure 1. Mixture M2 consistently exhibited the highest levels of phenolic compounds (154.82 \pm 1.01 mg GAE/g dry extract), flavonoids (30.2 \pm 0.10 mg

QE/g dry extract), and antioxidant activity (85.21 \pm 0.39%). These results suggest a strong correlation between the total phenolic and flavonoid contents and the radical scavenging activity, indicating that the synergistic combination of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* and *Viola tricolor L.* contributes significantly to the overall antioxidant potential.

Figure 1. Comparative evaluation of total phenolic and flavonoid contents and antioxidant activity (DPPH) of the extract mixtures

CONCLUSIONS

The present study provides a comprehensive assessment of the phytochemical profiles and antioxidant properties of selected plant extract mixtures. Quantitative analyses revealed that mixture M2 consistently exhibited the highest concentrations of total phenolic compounds (154.82 ± 1.01 mg GAE/g dry extract) and flavonoids (30.2 ± 0.10 mg QE/g dry extract), which corresponded with markedly superior DPPH radical scavenging activity (85.21 ± 0.39 %). This strong correlation between polyphenolic and flavonoid contents and antioxidant performance underscores the critical role of these bioactive compounds in modulating free radical neutralization.

The results further suggest that synergistic interactions among the constituent extracts, particularly between *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* and *Viola tricolor L.*, potentiate the overall bioactivity of the mixtures beyond the additive effects of individual components. Such findings emphasize the potential of multi-component phytochemical formulations as promising natural functional ingredients with enhanced therapeutic efficacy. The data support the rationale for the development of standardized, synergistic plant-based preparations and warrant further investigation, including in vivo and mechanistic studies, to elucidate their pharmacokinetics, bioavailability, and safety profiles for potential clinical applications.

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THE IMPACT OF OIL ACTIVITIES ON SOIL QUALITY AND ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION SOLUTIONS – CASE STUDY: WELL 560 MIHAI BRAVU, BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study presents the assessment of soil quality in the area of well 560 Mihai Bravu Vest (Bihor County), abandoned after oil extraction and transport. The research aimed to identify the degree of contamination with total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) and to establish measures for the ecological remediation of the affected land. Five soil sampling drills were carried out (one located near the well casing and four at the main points within the well pad) at depths ranging from 0.05 to 0.90 m, with determinations performed in accordance with current standards. The analysis results revealed localized exceedances of alert and intervention thresholds for less sensitive land uses, as established by MAPPM Order no. 756/1997, particularly at points P2 and P3. The distribution of TPH values suggests the migration of petroleum products into deeper layers and natural attenuation processes in clayey zones. Based on these findings, excavation of the contaminated soil was undertaken, followed by transport to authorized bioremediation facilities, along with the restoration of the land's morphology. The study demonstrates the importance of post-abandonment monitoring of oil wells and provides a model of best practices for the ecological assessment and rehabilitation of sites affected by petroleum activities.

Keywords: contaminated soil, petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH), environmental monitoring, land remediation, abandoned oil wells.

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INTRODUCTION

The exploitation, transportation, and storage activities of crude oil carried out over time in Romania have generated a considerable number of potentially contaminated sites affected by petroleum hydrocarbons (Brejea et al., 2020; Ranieri et al., 2016). Soil represents one of the most vulnerable environmental compartments to this type of pollution, as it accumulates contaminants that can impact ecosystem quality, land productivity, and human health. For this reason, assessing the soil quality around abandoned oil wells is an essential step in environmental risk management and in implementing effective remediation solutions (Sabău & Șandor, 2014, 2015).

In Romania, the legislative framework for managing potentially contaminated sites is regulated by Law No. 74/2019 and Order of the Ministry of Waters, Forests and Environmental Protection (MAPPM) No. 756/1997, which establish alert and intervention thresholds for various pollutants, including total petroleum

hydrocarbons (TPH), differentiated according to land use categories (Rusu et al., 2017). Compliance with these regulations is mandatory when abandoning oil wells, in order to ensure the restoration of the land to its initial condition and to reduce the risks of persistent pollution.

Well 560 Mihai Bravu Vest is located outside the built-up area of Mihai Bravu commune (Bihor County) and is part of the OMV Petrom S.A. perimeter. It operated between 1984 and 1998, serving for the extraction and transportation of crude oil, and starting in 2014, well abandonment works were carried out in depth based on the approval of the National Agency for Mineral Resources (ANRM). The land associated with the well, covering an area of approximately 900 m², falls into the category of "construction yards/permanent pastures," with its previous use being agricultural (Sabău & Șandor, 2013).

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the impact of oil-related activities on soil quality within the perimeter of Well 560 Mihai

Bravu Vest by determining the total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) content and identifying the most appropriate ecological restoration measures. The study contributes to understanding the spatial and vertical distribution of contaminants in the soil, as well

as to substantiating technical remediation solutions, potentially serving as a model for other similar sites in Romania.

Figure no. 1.1. Geographical position of the well 560 Mihai Bravu Vest

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To assess the degree of soil contamination within the perimeter of Well 560 Mihai Bravu Vest (Bihar County), field investigations and laboratory analyses were carried out in accordance with current standards and regulations. The well site, located outside the built-up area of Mihai Bravu, covers a total area of approximately 900 m², classified as “construction yards/permanent pastures.”

Five sampling points (P1–P5) were established: one located near the well casing (P1) and four distributed across the main zones of the well platform, depending on the pollution potential determined by past

operational activities. From each point, soil samples were collected at four distinct depths—0.05 m, 0.30 m, 0.60 m, and 0.90 m—to capture the vertical distribution of contaminants.

Sampling, handling, labeling, and storage of the samples were performed in compliance with the requirements of SR EN ISO 10381 and applicable national legislation. The sampling points were georeferenced in the field using a high-precision GPS device (e.g., Stonex S9 GNSS). The soil stratification was visually described during sampling, revealing a brown topsoil layer (0–0.30 m) and a brown clay layer (0.30–0.90 m).

Table 1.

Data on TPH concentration of samples taken for well 560 Mihai Bravu Vest

Sample	TPH (mg/Kg s.u.)			
	Sampling depth A 0,05 (m)	Sampling depth B 0,3 (m)	Sampling depth C 0,6 (m)	Sampling depth D 0,9 (m)
S1	235	928	137	64
S2	8638	973	71	72
S3	866	361	1417	4315
S4	133	185	1799	144
S5	224	32	<27.1	<27.1

The analyses of total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) content in the soil samples were carried out in an accredited laboratory, using standardized methods for the determination of volatile and semi-volatile organic compounds. The analytical procedures included all the requirements of the applicable method and product standards, adhering to the minimum detection limits and reporting ranges.

The obtained results were compared with the reference values, alert thresholds, and intervention thresholds established by Order of the Ministry of Waters, Forests and Environmental Protection (MAPPM) No. 756/1997 - "Regulation on Environmental Pollution Assessment", corresponding to less sensitive land-use categories.

Figure 2 The values of TPH concentrations identified at different depths for probe 560 Mihai Bravu Vest

Figure .3 Leveling the replaced soil in the vicinity of well 560 Mihai Bravu Vest

Figure 4 Excavation of polluted soil in the vicinity of well 560 Mihai Bravu Vest

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The determinations of total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) content in the soil samples collected from the area of Well 560 Mihai Bravu Vest are presented in Table 1.1. The obtained values were compared with the alert and intervention thresholds for less sensitive land-use categories, as established by Order of the Ministry of Waters, Forests and Environmental Protection (MAPPM) No. 756/1997.

The analysis of TPH concentration distribution by depth and sampling point highlights the following:

In boreholes P1 and P5, TPH values at all depths (0.05–0.90 m) are below the alert threshold, indicating a low level of contamination.

In borehole P2, the TPH concentration at 0.05 m exceeds the intervention threshold, while at greater depths the values drop below the alert threshold, suggesting superficial contamination with natural attenuation in the lower soil layers.

In borehole P3, values up to 0.30 m are below the alert threshold; at 0.60 m, the alert threshold is exceeded, and at 0.90 m, the intervention threshold is exceeded, indicating migration of petroleum products toward the deeper clay layers.

In borehole P4, TPH values are below the alert threshold at 0.05 m and 0.90 m, but exceed the alert threshold at 0.60 m, while still remaining below the intervention threshold.

The results show a significant variability in contamination levels, influenced by the location of sampling points and the stratigraphic characteristics of the soil. The presence of a brown clay layer between 0.30–0.90 m contributes to the retention of petroleum products and natural attenuation through physicochemical processes.

To reduce the risk of secondary contamination, the excavation of polluted soil was carried out in areas with significant exceedances (particularly P2) and the excavated material was transported to authorized bioremediation facilities. The affected areas were backfilled with clean soil, leveled, and prepared for the reestablishment of natural vegetation.

These results confirm the necessity of post-abandonment monitoring of oil wells and the implementation of rapid corrective measures to prevent the spread of pollution into the geological environment or groundwater systems.

CONCLUSIONS

The investigations carried out within the perimeter of Well 560 Mihai Bravu Vest revealed the presence of total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) concentrations that locally exceed the alert and intervention thresholds established for less sensitive land-use categories.

The vertical distribution of TPH indicates both surface contamination and migration of pollutants into the lower clay layers, where natural processes contribute to the partial attenuation of pollution.

Areas with significant exceedances were subjected to excavation works and the transport of polluted soil to authorized bioremediation facilities, while the site was morphologically restored through backfilling with clean soil and leveling.

The implemented measures have contributed to reducing the risk of further contamination and improving the ecological restoration conditions of the site.

This study provides a model of good practice for the assessment and ecological rehabilitation of sites affected by oil-related activities, emphasizing the importance of post-abandonment monitoring and timely intervention.

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MORPHOBOTANICAL EVALUATION OF *ECHINACEA PURPUREA* (L.) MOENCH

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Echinacea purpurea (L.) Moench, a member of the Asteraceae family, is a medicinal plant widely recognized for its immunostimulatory and anti-inflammatory properties. This study presents a morphobotanical evaluation aimed at identifying key diagnostic features useful for pharmacognostic authentication.

Macroscopic examination showed that *E. purpurea* has an erect, cylindrical stem covered with fine hairs, alternate leaves with serrated margins and prominent venation, and a characteristic solitary capitulum with purple ligulate ray florets and brown tubular disk florets. Microscopically, the stem exhibits a uniseriate epidermis with glandular and non-glandular trichomes, a collenchymatous cortex, and a continuous ring of vascular bundles. The leaf is dorsiventral with anomocytic stomata, capitate trichomes, and a clearly differentiated mesophyll.

These morphological and anatomical traits provide reliable criteria for the identification and standardization of *Echinacea purpurea*, supporting its quality control and safe use in pharmaceutical and herbal preparations.

Keywords: *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench, Morphobotanical evaluation, Diagnostic features, Pharmacognostic authentication

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INTRODUCTION

The purple coneflower, *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench, is a perennial herbaceous species from the Asteraceae family, widely recognized for its horticultural and medicinal significance. Although native to the prairies of North America, *E. purpurea* is now cultivated globally due to its attractive inflorescences and its extensive use in traditional and modern phytotherapy (Burlou-Nagy, 2022). Among its various medicinal applications, the species is prized for its immunostimulant, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, making it a cornerstone in the formulation of herbal remedies aimed at preventing and alleviating upper respiratory tract infections and other immune-related conditions (Choirunnisa, 2021; Burlou-Nagy, 2023).

With the increasing demand for herbal products containing *E. purpurea*, the need for precise identification and quality control has become paramount (Kornievskiy, 2021; Pidoux, 2021). Many commercial preparations may be

subject to adulteration or substitution with related species or morphologically similar taxa, which can compromise therapeutic efficacy and consumer safety. In this context, morphobotanical evaluation serves as a fundamental tool for ensuring the authenticity and purity of raw materials (Lin-na, 2013).

Leaves and stems, as primary vegetative organs, offer a wealth of diagnostic morphological and anatomical features. The leaves of *E. purpurea* typically exhibit a distinctive lanceolate to ovate shape, with serrated margins and a pronounced venation pattern. The stem is generally erect, robust, and covered by characteristic trichomes. Detailed analysis of these organs—encompassing attributes such as surface texture, trichome type and distribution, venation, tissue organization, and vascular arrangement—provides essential criteria for distinguishing *E. purpurea* from other *Echinacea* species or potential adulterants (Belaeva, 2013).

This study seeks to conduct an in-depth morphobotanical assessment of the leaves and

stems of *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench. Through comprehensive macroscopic and microscopic examination, the research aims to document and analyze the specific structural features of these organs. Macromorphological observations will be complemented by anatomical investigations, including the study of epidermal patterns, mesophyll structure, and vascular tissue distribution. By establishing a robust set of diagnostic markers, this work will support the development of reliable identification protocols for *E. purpurea*, thereby enhancing quality assurance in both pharmacognostic research and the herbal product industry (Ragažinskienė 2001).

Ultimately, the findings from this study will contribute to a deeper understanding of the morphobotanical distinctiveness of *E. purpurea* leaves and stems, facilitating their recognition in both raw and processed forms. This is particularly relevant for the standardization and authentication of herbal medicines, supporting the safe and effective use of *Echinacea purpurea* in contemporary healthcare.

The leaves exhibit a dorsiventral structure, with a thin but continuous cuticle and a single-layered epidermis on both surfaces. The stomata are predominantly anomocytic and occur more frequently on the abaxial surface. Non-glandular trichomes are uniseriate and multicellular, while glandular trichomes are capitate, each composed of a short stalk and a rounded head of secretory cells responsible for the production of essential oils and phenolic compounds. The mesophyll is differentiated into an upper palisade parenchyma and a lower spongy parenchyma, the latter with abundant intercellular spaces to facilitate gas exchange. The vascular bundles are collateral and embedded within a parenchymatous sheath, forming a distinct reticulate venation pattern throughout the lamina (Manayi, 2015).

The diagnostic combination of features—such as the presence of capitate glandular trichomes, anomocytic stomata, well-developed collenchyma, and a continuous ring of vascular bundles—confirms the structural identity of *Echinacea purpurea* and ensures its reliable recognition in pharmacognostic evaluation. These morphological and anatomical traits not only serve as taxonomic markers but also underline the plant's physiological adaptations and its role in the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites of therapeutic significance.

Overall, the findings of this study highlight the relevance of detailed morphobotanical characterization of stem and leaf structures in establishing the authenticity, quality, and standardization of *Echinacea purpurea* raw material used in medicinal and pharmaceutical applications.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Fresh leaves were used for morphological examinations. For the microscopic study, tiny transverse sections were manually excised from fresh leaves and stems with a razor blade. The preparations were looked at under a light microscope with 40X and 20X magnifications to see diagnostic anatomical features such as the structure of the epidermis, the arrangement of the mesophyll, and the placement of the vascular tissues in stem. A digital camera attached to the microscope took microphotographs. Images obtained from the morphobotanical observations were compared with literature descriptions to confirm the identification of *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench and to highlight its characteristic features relevant for pharmacognostic authentication and quality control. Observations and image acquisition were performed using an optical microscope (Optika, model C-B10+ 24010, Ponteranica, Italy) equipped with 10×, 20×, and 40× objectives and an Optika B10 digital camera.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The morphobotanical assessment of *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench concentrated on the comprehensive examination of its vegetative structures—the leaf **Figure 1** and stem **Figure 2**—displaying a synthesis of diagnostic characteristics significant for taxonomy and pharmacognosy within the *Echinacea* genus.

The stem of *E. purpurea* is upright, cylindrical, and fairly branched at the apex, with an average height between 70 and 120 cm. It is dense and has a green- to reddish-green hue.

The surface has a slightly rough texture owing to the visibility of small, short hairs, resulting in a scabrous quality. The epidermis exhibits longitudinal striations, indicative of the configuration of the underlying vascular bundles and the overall sturdiness of the plant.

The transverse section of the stem has a characteristic dicotyledonous structure. The outermost layer consists of a unilaminar epidermis, enveloped by a delicate cuticle and featuring both non-glandular and glandular trichomes. The non-glandular trichomes are uniseriate, multicellular, and somewhat curved, whereas the glandular trichomes are capitate, featuring a short stalk and a rounded head of secretory cells. Below the epidermis, many layers (3–5) of collenchymatous cells offer mechanical support, particularly in ridged areas. The cortex consists of 6–10 layers of parenchymatous cells interspersed with intercellular gaps, some of which contain microscopic oil droplets or calcium oxalate crystals. The circulatory system has a continuous loop of collateral bundles interspersed with slender medullary rays. The phloem is positioned externally, whereas the xylem is the predominant majority of the vascular tissue, facilitating effective water and nutrient transport. The middle pith consists of big, thin-walled parenchyma cells containing extensive intercellular gaps. This interior structure offers both stability and adaptability, aiding the plant's vertical growth and enabling the movement of metabolites.

The leaves of *E. purpurea* are simple, alternating, and polymorphic on the stem. Basal leaves are more substantial and attached to elongated petioles, whereas cauline leaves diminish in size and are either sessile or subsessile. The leaf morphology ranges from ovate to lanceolate, including a coarsely serrated border. The adaxial surface is dark green and shiny, while the abaxial surface is lighter and has stiff, non-glandular trichomes, especially along the veins, which gives it a rough texture. The venation is reticulate, including a pronounced midrib and subsidiary veins that create a net-like configuration.

The leaf has a dorsiventral architecture characteristic of dicotyledonous plants at the microscopic level. The adaxial and abaxial epidermises are composed of a single layer of

polygonal cells featuring straight to slightly undulating anticlinal walls and are enveloped by a thin, continuous cuticle. Stomata are anomocytic and mostly located on the abaxial surface, representing a xeromorphic adaptation that facilitates efficient gas exchange while reducing water loss. Non-glandular trichomes are uniseriate and multicellular, characterized by thicker walls and pointed tips, whereas glandular trichomes are capitate, consisting of a short stalk and a spherical head composed of 4–8 secretory cells that synthesize volatile oils and other secondary metabolites.

The mesophyll is distinctly organized into a single layer of elongated palisade parenchyma situated under the adaxial epidermis and 4–6 layers of spongy parenchyma below, abundant in intercellular gaps that promote gas passage. The vascular system of the midrib comprises a substantial collateral bundle encased in a parenchymatous bundle sheath, with sclerenchymatous cells offering structural support and protection. Minor vascular bundles diverge into the lamina, leading to the distinctive reticulate venation.

The integrated macroscopic and microscopic features of the stem and leaf validate the identification of *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench. Diagnostic features encompass the presence of capitate glandular trichomes, anomocytic stomata, calcium oxalate crystals, and well-developed collenchyma. These anatomical characteristics facilitate the plant's adaptation to its environment and align with its established capacity to synthesize physiologically active chemicals, notably phenolic derivatives like caffeic acid and its conjugates.

This morphobotanical characterization offers critical diagnostic information for the accurate identification and verification of *Echinacea purpurea* vegetative material utilized in herbal preparations, hence ensuring its appropriate standardization in phytotherapeutic applications (Kim, 2019).

Figure 1. Leaf - transversal section of *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench, observed under microscope with 40X objective

Figure 2. Stem section of *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench, observed under microscope with 20X objective

CONCLUSIONS

The present morphobotanical study of *Echinacea purpurea* (L.) Moench provides a comprehensive description of the macro- and microscopic characteristics of its vegetative organs—stem and leaf—offering valuable data for accurate identification and authentication in pharmacognostic and botanical research. The species exhibits distinctive diagnostic features in both organs, which are essential for differentiating it from closely related taxa within the genus *Echinacea*.

The stem presents a typical dicotyledonous organization, characterized by a single-layered epidermis covered with a thin cuticle and bearing both glandular and non-glandular trichomes. Beneath the epidermis, a collenchymatous hypodermis provides mechanical strength, while the cortex consists of several layers of parenchymatous cells, some containing calcium oxalate crystals. The vascular system forms a continuous ring of collateral bundles surrounding a well-developed parenchymatous pith. These structural features reflect the plant's adaptation to support large aerial biomass and maintain physiological stability under variable environmental conditions.

The leaves exhibit a dorsiventral structure, with a thin but continuous cuticle and a single-layered epidermis on both surfaces. The stomata are predominantly anomocytic and occur more frequently on the abaxial surface. Non-glandular trichomes are uniseriate and multicellular, while glandular trichomes are capitate, each composed of a short stalk and a rounded head of secretory cells responsible for the production of essential oils and phenolic compounds. The mesophyll is clearly differentiated into an upper palisade parenchyma and a lower spongy parenchyma, the latter with abundant intercellular spaces to facilitate gas exchange. The vascular bundles are collateral and embedded within a parenchymatous sheath, forming a distinct reticulate venation pattern throughout the lamina.

The diagnostic combination of features—such as the presence of capitate glandular trichomes, anomocytic stomata, well-developed collenchyma, and a continuous ring of vascular bundles—confirms the structural identity of *Echinacea purpurea* and ensures its reliable recognition in pharmacognostic evaluation. These morphological and anatomical traits not

only serve as taxonomic markers but also underline the plant's physiological adaptations and its role in the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites of therapeutic significance.

Overall, the findings of this study highlight the relevance of detailed morphobotanical characterization of stem and leaf structures in establishing the authenticity, quality, and standardization of *Echinacea purpurea* raw material used in medicinal and pharmaceutical applications.

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AUTOMATION OPTIMIZATION OF A CASCADE UTILIZATION SYSTEM USING GEOTHERMAL WATER WITH MODERATE TEMPERATURE

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Abstract

This paper presents detailed studies and analyses aimed at optimizing the automatic control system of a cascade utilization with thermal energy from moderate-temperature geothermal water. Ensuring the stable and efficient operation of the thermal installation requires the development of an automation program that continuously monitors, regulates, and coordinates all functional parameters. This technological approach is fundamental for the sustainable and economic exploitation of geothermal resources, reducing human intervention and minimizing the risk of operational errors.

Keywords: geothermal water; cascade utilization; automation loop, moderate temperature

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INTRODUCTION

Geothermal energy represents the heat stored within the Earth, originating from the planet's internal structure and the physical processes occurring beneath its surface. Although this thermal energy exists in vast quantities, it is unevenly distributed and, in many cases, located at depths too great for practical industrial exploitation.

However, in certain regions the heat can accumulate near accessible zones, making these areas economically attractive for exploration and utilization.

Geothermalism encompasses all aspects related to the study, identification, exploitation, and efficient use of geothermal resources. According to Hochstein, a geothermal reservoir can be schematically defined as "convecting water in the Earth's upper crust that, within a confined space, transfers heat from a deep thermal source to an accumulation zone, which is generally the planet's surface." (Elena Zierler, 2008; J. W. Tester et al., 2006; Kailash N. et al., 2008; Marcel Roșca, 2007)

Thus, a geothermal reservoir consists of three essential components: a heat source, a storage reservoir, and a fluid that serves as the transport medium responsible for transferring thermal energy. Due to the complexity of the

issues involved, geothermal studies form an interdisciplinary domain that requires expertise from geology, drilling engineering, energy systems, agronomy, medicine, and other related fields. (Elena Zierler, 2008; J. W. Tester et al., 2006; Kailash N. et al., 2008; Marcel Roșca, 2007)

Current research interests in geothermal energy can be grouped into the following main areas:

- a) understanding the origin of geothermal energy as a manifestation of the Earth's internal heat;
- b) identifying geographic regions with geothermal potential;
- c) methods and technologies for exploiting geothermal reservoirs;
- d) direct and indirect applications of geothermal resources;
- e) economic and environmental considerations.

a) The origin of geothermal energy, as an expression of terrestrial thermal processes, must be examined from a multidisciplinary perspective. A significant contribution in this regard comes from the theory of global tectonics, which has revealed that the Earth's surface is divided into a mosaic of lithospheric plates whose nature and movement strongly

influence the distribution of the planet's thermal field. (Elena Zierler, 2008; J. W. Tester et al., 2006; Kailash N. et al., 2008; Marcel Roşca, 2007)

b) The identification of geographic zones with geothermal potential involves accurately determining those areas where geothermal resources can be effectively utilized. The geothermal resource base represents the total amount of geothermal energy stored in the Earth's crust beneath a given region (typically down to depths of about 10 km), relative to the local mean annual temperature. This resource base is classified into several categories: inaccessible resource base, accessible resource base, useful accessible resource base, and residual accessible resource base. From an economic perspective, geothermal resources are further classified into sub-economic resources, economic resources, undiscovered economic resources, and identified economic resources. (Elena Zierler, 2008; J. W. Tester et al., 2006; Kailash N. et al., 2008; Marcel Roşca, 2007)

c) The exploitation of geothermal deposits primarily concerns the development of production and reinjection wells, along with the drilling methods employed. This research area closely parallels the techniques used in drilling wells for oil and natural gas.

d) The utilization of geothermal deposits encompasses all ways in which geothermal energy can be harnessed for community and industrial purposes. Key applications include electricity generation, district heating systems, industrial processes, agricultural uses—particularly greenhouse heating, fish farming, and aquaculture—as well as balneology and various therapeutic applications.

e) Economic and ecological considerations focus on evaluating geothermal energy use in terms of cost-effectiveness and environmental impact. The recognition of geothermal energy as a viable alternative to fossil fuels has been strengthened by its technical and economic advantages, as well as by the fact that approximately 80 countries possess significant geothermal resources. (Elena Zierler, 2008)

The utilization of geothermal energy is generally based on extracting heat from geothermal reservoir waters and using it either directly as a thermal source or indirectly through conversion into electricity. Compared

to other energy sources, geothermal energy presents three defining characteristics:

1. It is, in principle, renewable, making it practically inexhaustible under appropriate management conditions;

2. It is a clean energy source, resulting in minimal environmental impact;

3. It represents an existing form of latent thermal energy that requires only to be accessed and harnessed.

Renewable energy represents the portion of natural energy resources that is continuously replenished and can be economically exploited under present or foreseeable conditions. Among renewable sources, hydropower has been used for many decades; however, its further expansion is increasingly limited due to ecological constraints and significant social impacts associated with large hydropower installations. Within the spectrum of renewable energies, geothermal energy occupies a distinct and important position. (Elena Zierler, 2008; J. W. Tester et al., 2006; Kailash N. et al., 2008)

Specialists classify geothermal energy utilization into two main categories: direct use and indirect use.

Direct use refers to the application of geothermal heat through direct transfer to the consumer or via an intermediate fluid. It includes four major subcategories:

1. Space heating and domestic hot water supply;

2. Agricultural applications (greenhouses, aquaculture, fish farming);

3. Balneology and therapeutic uses;

4. Industrial applications.

Indirect use involves converting the energy of geothermal fluids into electricity, either by driving turbines directly or by employing binary-cycle power plants. (J. W. Tester et al., 2006; Kailash N. et al., 2008; Marcel Roşca, 2007)

The range of possible applications is determined primarily by the temperature of the geothermal fluid. Lindal analyzed the main technological fields in which geothermal energy can be used efficiently both technically and economically according to fluid temperature. His findings were synthesized into a diagram known as the Lindal Diagram, illustrated in Figure 1. (Elena Zierler, 2008).

Figure 1. Linda Chart I

The utilization of geothermal energy in Romania currently takes place in 38 localities where geothermal resources have been identified, with 98 wells in operation—37 of which serve bathing and balneological purposes. The average temperature of the geothermal water is approximately 71 °C at intake and 28 °C at discharge. (Kailash N. et al., 2008; Marcel Roșca, 2007)

The total installed thermal capacity is 152 MWt, generating approximately 2,870 TJ per year. Direct uses of geothermal energy in Romania are distributed as follows: space heating - 37.4%, bathing and swimming including balneology - 30.4%, greenhouse heating - 23.1%, industrial applications - 7%, and fish farming and aquaculture - 2.1%, with an average capacity factor of 0.6%. (J. W. Tester et al., 2006)

One of the secondary beneficiaries considered in this study is a greenhouse complex that utilizes geothermal wastewater discharged from the geothermal power plant. (Elena Zierler, 2008) In the design phase, a crucial aspect is the evaluation of the energy or thermal balance across the greenhouse structure.

The study of system behavior always begins with a real, physical system created to solve various problems that arise in all areas of human activity. The ability of physical systems to address a particular type of problem depends on their intrinsic characteristics. In general, a physical system interacts with human activity as a tool designed to facilitate work, a function

achieved through the time-dependent modification of certain internal parameters.

Although any set of interacting physical bodies or real objects can be considered a physical system, this paper focuses on those systems intended to replace human observation, decision making, and action—known as automatic systems. These systems are designed, through the appropriate selection of their components, either to perform a predetermined sequence of events (in which case they are called automatic control systems) or to maintain prescribed values of one or several system variables that tend to change over time due to specific conditions such as disturbances. In this case, the systems are referred to as automatic regulation systems.

Since, in our case, the objective is to maintain certain parameters constant, the physical systems developed for this purpose are primarily automatic regulation systems. Therefore, throughout this work, the term physical system should be understood as referring to a physical automatic regulation system, unless explicitly stated otherwise.

The problem of regulating a real process may be described as follows: the variable or parameter that must be maintained at a desired value will, at a given moment during the process, take on a value different from that target value. This value is called the system response. The difference between the system response—i.e., the value measured by a sensor—and the reference value, which is the desired value of the parameter, is called the error. The appearance of this error is due to various disturbances that affect the real process. The main purpose of any regulation system is to reduce this error and keep it as close to zero as possible.

To achieve this, the error is transmitted to a physical system capable of acting on the real process in such a way as to decrease the error. This component is known as the controller (or regulator). The generic term controller may also include components that are not part of the controller in the strict sense but are essential elements of the regulation loop. These include the sensor, the comparison element, and the actuator.

The sensor retrieves the instantaneous value from the real process and converts it into a physical quantity that can be compared with another value of the same quantity, corresponding to the desired setpoint. This

comparison is performed by the comparison element, which provides the input to the actual controller. The controller then issues a command to an actuator, which adjusts the state of the physical system in order to keep the actual value as close as possible to the desired one.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Solving the problem of automatic regulation involves the following steps:

1. Selecting appropriate sensors for acquiring the real variable from the process (the system response);
2. Selecting actuating elements capable of modifying the state and behavior of the system;
3. Describing the system components using mathematical equations;
4. Designing the actual controller based on these mathematical equations;

Analytical evaluation of the regulation design (possibly through simulation) and verification of the behavior of the real system.

A mathematical model of a real process consists of a set of equations that describe the relationships between various parameters characterizing the system. In general, these are differential equations with time as the independent variable, since regulation concerns the temporal evolution of the system parameters. A real process or system can be represented by multiple mathematical models, depending on which parameters are considered essential, which disturbances are taken into account, and how the evolution of the real process is interpreted.

Thus, for the same physical system, both simple and complex mathematical models may be formulated, depending on the level of detail incorporated into the model's structure. In practice, no mathematical model can fully describe a physical system; however, more complex models can approximate the real system with satisfactory accuracy. Due to the inherent limitations with which mathematical models approximate the real behavior of a physical system, if real-world tests of the designed regulation system fail to produce the expected results, it becomes necessary to revisit the choice of the mathematical model, seeking a more detailed and comprehensive representation of the real process.

STRUCTURAL HEAT BALANCE

In addressing climate control within a greenhouse, the heat balance and the thermal response of the crop, the indoor air, the roof structure, and the soil play a particularly important role. The greenhouse's hemispherical shape also affects the associated energy and mass transfer processes. (Crispin Allen, 1990; Curtis D. J., 1988; F. S. Blaga, 2009; Iancu Carmen, 2010)

The heat balance reflects the exchanges of heat and mass between the greenhouse and its surrounding environment. All parameters governing the physical processes inside the greenhouse are in energetic equilibrium with the external environment, and collectively they contribute to establishing the internal thermal balance. The principal heat exchange processes can be represented schematically as shown in Figure 2. (Crispin Allen, 1990; Danfoss, 1986; Iancu Carmen, 2010; T.-J. Yeh et al., 2009)

The energy balance in a greenhouse can be simplified expressed:

$$Q_{\text{tot}} = Q_{\text{gain}} - Q_{\text{loss}}$$

where: Q_{tot} = total amount of energy (net energy exchange) [W];

Q_{gain} = the amount of energy entering the greenhouse [W];

Q_{loss} = the amount of energy coming out of the greenhouse [W]

Determining the heating requirements of a greenhouse under various internal and external climatic conditions involves calculating all heat transfer processes included in the energy balance, as well as the climatic parameters that influence them. (Crispin Allen, 1990)

These processes depend on heat transfer coefficients, interior-exterior temperature and humidity differences, material properties, radiation, form factors, the characteristics of the plant canopy, and the specifications of heating and cooling systems. (Crispin Allen, 1990)

Some of these factors remain constant or nearly constant and can be calculated directly. Others vary with temperature and humidity and therefore must be evaluated under changing or so called dynamic conditions. Solar radiation and outdoor air temperature vary independently of the internal conditions of the greenhouse.

The amount of heat entering the greenhouse is:

$$Q_{\text{gain}} = Q_h + Q_l + Q_w$$

unde: Q_h = heat produced by the heating system [W];
 Q_i = heat obtained from solar radiation [W];
 Q_w = căldura datorată transpirației [W]

Figure 2. Energy transfer through the structure, greenhouse, condensation energy; energy of the heating system; infiltration energy; transmission through the roof; solar radiation; Evaporation; ventilation energy; Transmission through soil

MECHANISMS OF THERMAL ENERGY LOSS IN GREENHOUSE STRUCTURES

The amount of energy leaving the greenhouse can be estimated with the following equation::

$$Q_{\text{loss}} = Q_k = Q_s = Q_{\text{cond}} = Q_v = Q_{\text{inf}}$$

Q_k = heat lost by convection outwards [W];

Q_s = heat lost through conduction to the ground [W];

Q_{cond} = heat loss due to condensation [w];

Q_v = heat transfer due to ventilation [W];

Q_{inf} = heat transfer due to infiltration [W].

MECHANISMS OF OUTWARD CONVECTIVE HEAT LOSS

t represents the heat lost through the greenhouse envelope, from the interior air to the exterior environment, and can be quantified using the following equation:

$$Q_k = hxA_c(T_{\text{in}} - T_0)$$

where: T_0 = outside temperature [k];

h = overall heat exchange coefficient [w/m²k];

A_c = Area of the greenhouse shell [m²];

T_{in} = indoor air temperature [k].

In the equation above, the overall heat transfer coefficient incorporates the combined effects of convection, conduction, and thermal radiation. It does not account for air infiltration through cracks or openings around windows and doors of the greenhouse. (Ertuğrul Çam, 2007; F. S. Blaga, 2009; H. Silaghi et al., 2009; İlhan Kocaarslan, 2006; Michael Anderson et al., 2007; Szymon Ogonowski, 2010)

For practical calculations, the overall heat transfer coefficient can be determined using the following equation, in which w represents the wind speed [m/s]: $H = 2,8 + 1,2w$

Heat lost in the soil

The flow of heat to the ground is complicated to determine because it is associated with water circulation. In most cases, it is enough to consider the flow of heat to the ground using apparent thermal conductivity, which includes the effect of water flow. (Crispin Allen 1990, G. Ionescu, et al, 1983, H. Silaghi et al, 2009, Iancu Carmen, 2010)

In the calculations, it is considered that the earth is divided into 3 uniform layers in depth and the temperature in the center of each layer is T_1 , T_2 and T_b respectively. The temperature T_b at the lower layer is a boundary condition and the temperature at the soil surface is considered the indoor temperature of the greenhouse. (Crispin Allen 1990, H. Silaghi et al, 2009)

According to the energy balance equation, the heat flow in the soil during dt is expressed by dq/dt , and is adapted to the temperature exchange using mass properties:

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = C_p \times \rho \times \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

In heat transfer by conduction the energy balance can be written as:

$$C_p V_s \frac{dT_1}{dt} = K_s A_s \left(\frac{2(T_{\text{in}} - T_1)}{dz} + \frac{T_2 - T_1}{dz} \right)$$

$$C_p V_s \frac{dT_2}{dt} = K_s A_s \left(\frac{(T_1 - T_2)}{dz} + \frac{T_B - T_2}{dz} \right)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To ensure the correct and efficient operation of the thermal energy system serving the greenhouse complex, an automation program must be developed to monitor and regulate its functional parameters. The main objective is to maintain the desired indoor temperature of the greenhouse, monitored by the TT6 temperature transducer. This measurement enables the correlation between the recorded parameters and the control actions applied to the actuating elements.

Figure 3 illustrates the automation loop, as well as the fault detection loop, associated with the thermal energy supply system for the greenhouse complex..

Figure 3. Automation and fault loops for the thermal energy supply installation for the greenhouse complex

A. AUTOMATION LOOP

The automation loop of the thermal energy supply installation for the greenhouse complex aims to achieve the condition: maintaining the temperature in the greenhouse within 18... 20°C. Geothermal water feeds the heating system from the ground surface and then passes into the ground heating system. The temperature inside the greenhouse must be maintained within 18... 20°C; This condition is achieved by regulating the geothermal water flow, obtained by opening/closing the RB6 tap, mounted on the geothermal water pipe that short-circuits the greenhouse.

If the temperature transducer TT6 located inside the greenhouse shows a temperature higher than the maximum permissible limit for this temperature, i.e. lt_6 ($lt_6=20^\circ\text{C}$), after the TTMP 2 delay time has elapsed ($ttmp\ 2=240\ \text{sec}$) since the last setting command was executed, and if the automatic valve controller on the geothermal water supply route meets the $ra_6 - 100\ \%$ inequality (the valve is not fully open), Open the RB6 valve with XRB6 value ($XRB_6=0,25\ \text{rot.}$) by the control given by the RA6 controller. if the tt_6 transducer shows a temperature lower than the minimum permissible limit for this temperature, i.e. lt_6 ($lt_6=18^\circ\text{C}$), after the TTMP 2 delay time has elapsed since the last setting command was executed, and if the automatic valve regulator on the geothermal water supply route satisfies the RA6-0% condition (valve not closed), Close the RB6 valve with XRB6 value by the given command.

B. FAULT SIGNALLING AND SYSTEM RESPONSE IN THIS CAZ.

During operation, discrepancies may arise between the functional parameters of the installation and the prescribed operating conditions—discrepancies that the automation program is unable to correct on its own. In such situations, the operator is alerted to the

malfunction and must intervene to restore normal operating conditions. The fault-signalling system (Figure 3) and the corresponding system response represent a critical component of the automation program, as they prevent potential accidents and provide timely warnings regarding abnormal operation.

The most critical fault that may occur during operation is an increase in geothermal water pressure at the greenhouse inlet beyond the maximum permissible limit. If the TP6 pressure transducer, mounted on the geothermal water pipe at the entrance to the greenhouse, indicates a pressure higher than the maximum permissible value Lp_6 ($Lp_6=4\ \text{bar}$), for more than $ttmp\ av_2$ ($ttmp\ av_2=60\ \text{sec.}$) (situation caused by possible obstruction of the geothermal water circuit, especially in the area of the ground surface heating system or ground heating system), the system signals "FAILURE OF DEFECTIVE PIPES".

If the TT6 transducer shows a temperature lower than the minimum permissible limit for this temperature, i.e. lt_6 ($lt_6=18^\circ\text{C}$), after the TTMP2 delay time has elapsed since the last setting command was executed, and if the automatic valve controller on the geothermal water route corresponds to RA6=0% equality (valve is closed), the system signals "FAILURE of faulty RB6 valve".

In order to determine the possible variations for the T_i parameter, several measurements were made, corresponding to a number of 20 experiments. It should be noted that each value was calculated as an average of 16 different measurements carried out on a case-by-case basis. In figure 4. a graphical representation of the results of the determinations made for parameter T1 is made.

Figure 4. Graphical representation of the results of the determinations carried out for parameter LT6

In figure 5. a graphical representation of the results of the determinations made for parameter T3

Figure 5. Graphical representation of the results of determinations made for parameter Ti

CONCLUSIONS

A central aspect in addressing climate control within a greenhouse is the evaluation of the heat balance and the thermal response of the crop, the internal air, the roof structure, and the soil. The geometric shape of the greenhouse, particularly its hemispherical configuration, also influences the associated energy and mass transfer processes. The heat balance is determined by the exchanges of heat and mass between the greenhouse and its surrounding environment. All parameters governing these physical processes are interrelated and collectively establish the energetic equilibrium between the greenhouse interior and the external environment.

The efficient operation of the thermal energy supply system for the greenhouse complex, it is necessary to implement an automation program capable of continuously monitoring and adjusting the installation's functional parameters. The central objective is to maintain the indoor temperature of the greenhouse—measured by the TT6 temperature transducer—within the prescribed limits. The data provided by this sensor enable the correlation between the monitored parameters and the control commands issued to the actuating elements.

To ensure the efficient operation of the thermal energy supply system for the greenhouse complex, an automation program must be developed to continuously monitor and adjust the functional parameters of the installation. The primary objective is to maintain the indoor temperature measured by the TT6 temperature transducer within the required limits. This measurement enables the synchronization of recorded parameters with the control actions applied to the actuating elements. In order to ensure the proper

functioning of the thermal energy installation for the greenhouse complex, it is necessary to develop an automation program to monitor and adjust its functional parameters. The aim is to maintain the temperature inside the greenhouse, measured using the TT6 temperature transducer. This allows a correlation between the measured parameters and the command of the execution elements. In order to determine the possible variations for the Ti parameter, several measurements were made, corresponding to a number of 20 experiments. It should be noted that each value was calculated as an average of 16 different measurements carried out on a case-by-case basis.

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DANDELION (*TARAXACUM OFFICINALE WEBER*): BOTANICAL STUDY AND PHYTOTHERAPEUTIC CONSIDERATIONS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The common dandelion (*Taraxacum officinale Weber*), designated in this study as TO is a widely distributed medicinal plant traditionally employed in hepatobiliary, digestive, and metabolic disorders. This study aimed to provide a concise botanical characterization of the species based on material collected from spontaneous flora in Bihor County, Romania. Macroscopic evaluation included the examination of roots, leaves, flowering stems, flowers, seeds and pollens, while microscopic analysis focused on diagnostic anatomical elements relevant for pharmacognostic authentication. Plant material was manually sectioned, and transverse anatomical sections were prepared for microscopic examination. were analyzed under light microscopy.

The results confirmed the characteristic morphological traits of TO, including a vertical taproot rich in latex, a basal rosette of deeply pinnatisect leaves, a hollow flowering stem, and a yellow ligulate capitulum. Microscopic analysis revealed inulin-rich parenchyma, latex canals (laticifers), dorsiventral leaf structure with anomocytic stomata, and collateral vascular bundles in the stem. Pollen grains appeared spheroidal and echinulate, consistent with Asteraceae family characteristics.

The anatomical observations support the accurate identification of the species and correlate with its documented phytotherapeutic properties, such as hepatoprotective, diuretic, and antioxidant effects associated with sesquiterpene lactones, triterpenes, phenolic acids, flavonoids, and inulin. These findings highlight the relevance of morphological and anatomical authentication in ensuring the quality and proper use of TO in medicinal preparations.

Keywords: *Taraxacum officinale Weber*; dandelion; botanical and phytochemical profile; ethnopharmacological relevance; phytotherapeutic applications.

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INTRODUCTION

The common dandelion (*Taraxacum officinale Weber*), designated in this study as TO is one of the most widely distributed medicinal plants in the Northern Hemisphere, traditionally used in hepatobiliary, digestive and metabolic disorders (Schutz et al., 2006). Historical sources indicate its therapeutic value since ancient Egyptian, Greek and Roman civilizations, while medieval medical texts describe its utility in liver congestion and urinary complaints (Fan et al., 2023). In Romania TO is abundant in spontaneous flora and is included among the most commonly used

ethnomedicinal species (Pallag, 2015). Current phytochemical studies highlight a rich composition of sesquiterpene lactones (taraxacin, taraxacerin), triterpenes (taraxasterol, taraxerol), phenolic acids (chlorogenic, caffeic), flavonoids (luteolin, apigenin), carotenoids, inulin and significant mineral content, particularly potassium (Popescu et al., 2010; Yan et al., 2024). These compounds correlate with reported diuretic, choloretic, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, hypouricemic and antioxidant effects (Gonzales et al., 2012; Herrera et al. 2025; Zhou et al., 2025).

Previous pharmacological reports suggest that aqueous and hydroalcoholic extracts of TO may modulate lipid metabolism, inhibit

adipogenesis, protect hepatocytes against xenobiotic injury, and reduce oxidative stress through polyphenolic mechanisms (Gruszecki et al., 2024; Telerovska et al., 2025). However, botanical identification and correct anatomical characterization remain essential, given the high morphological variability within the genus *Taraxacum* (over 250 species globally, nine documented in Romania) (Ardelean, 2008; Gruszecki et al., 2024).

The study emphasizes the critical importance of accurately identifying TO through its defining morphological and anatomical features, ensuring that plant material collected from spontaneous flora is correctly distinguished from related or visually similar species; accordingly, it aims to demonstrate that standardized macro- and microscopic pharmacognostic methods provide reliable authentication, supporting proper selection, safe use, and avoidance of accidental substitution during harvesting.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Vegetal material of TO was collected from spontaneous, non-polluted habitats in the Oradea area (Bihar County, Romania), at the coordinates 47°04'28.7"N, 21°56'14.8"E and an altitude of 151 m, during the flowering period (May–June 2025). Only healthy, well developed specimens, free of mechanical damage, chlorosis, desiccation, or parasitic infestation, were selected for analysis. All vegetative organs of the species (roots, leaves, flowering stems, flowers, seeds, pollens) were subjected to both macroscopic and microscopic examination. Whole plants were used for morpho-anatomical analysis, with approximately 100 g fresh weight per specimen.

Macroscopic evaluation was performed according to pharmacognostic requirements, assessing organ morphology, dimensions, colour, texture and latex exudation. The characterization followed the guidelines of the Romanian Pharmacopoeia, 10th edition, including the assessment of appearance, odour and taste for each plant organ (Ph.10th). Plant material was manually cleaned, dried at room temperature, fragmented and stored in paper envelopes under controlled ambient conditions until further use (Szabo, 2007).

For microscopic analysis, thin handmade transverse sections were obtained from the root, leaf flowering stems, flowers, seeds and

pollens using sterile razor blades, and subsequently cleared with chloral hydrate or glycerinated water. Additional preparations were stained with a hydroalcoholic Genevez reagent (Congo red and chrysoidine) for 5 minutes, followed by repeated rinsing with distilled water to remove excess dye (Paşca et al., 2025; Szabo, 2004).

Microscopic observations were performed using an Optika C-B10+ (24010) optical microscope (Ponteranica, Italy) equipped with 10×, 20× and 40× objectives and an Optika B10 digital camera (Gîtea et al., 2023). Diagnostic tissues were identified for each organ, including epidermis, collenchyma, parenchyma, vascular bundles, secretory ducts, articulated laticifers and inulin-containing parenchyma (Pallag, 2015). Pollen grains were collected by gently tapping mature capitula onto glass slides and fixing the material in glycerin jelly (Nemeth et al., 1998). Photographic documentation of both macroscopic and microscopic features was obtained using a Canon EOS R5 camera with a Canon RF 35 mm F1.8 Macro IS STM lens, and images were processed for clarity and documentation (Paşca et al., 2025). Representative voucher specimens from TO were preserved in the Herbarium of the Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, University of Oradea, Romania, and registered in the NYBG Steere Herbarium reference system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Macroscopic characteristics

Macroscopic analysis confirmed the diagnostic features of TO (as follows in Table 1), including fleshy vertical rhizome, producing a milky latex upon sectioning. Leaves form a basal rosette, are simple, lanceolate, deeply pinnatisect with unequal triangular lobes. The flowering stems (scape) is hollow, cylindrical and terminates in a solitary capitulum of bright yellow ligulate florets that open in the morning and close in the evening. These characters match the classical species description from Romanian flora. The seeds are enclosed in globose achenes equipped with an umbrella-like pappus, and measure approximately 0.3–0.5 mm in length, and the pappus facilitates effective wind mediated dispersal of the species in nature.

Microscopic characteristics

Root anatomy

The transverse root section revealed a thick periderm, a broad parenchymatous cortex containing inulin deposits, latex canals (laticifers) distributed irregularly, and a multilayered secondary phloem. Xylem vessels were radially arranged, confirming previously reported structural models for Asteraceae roots.

Leaf anatomy

Microscopy of the lamina showed dorsiventral structure with a single-layered epidermis, abundant anomocytic stomata, well-developed palisade tissue, and spongy parenchyma containing calcium oxalate traces. Latex canals (laticifers) were present along the midrib (Figure 1), a key diagnostic feature for the subfamily *Cichorioideae* (Pallag, 2015).

Flowering stems anatomy

Sections of the flowering stem exhibited a uniseriate epidermis, subepidermal collenchyma and large parenchymatous cortex, with collateral vascular bundles arranged

irregularly along the circumference. Central parenchyma was prominent and aeriferous, consistent with previously published descriptions.

Pollen

Pollen grains were spheroidal, echinulate, characteristic of Asteraceae, and correspond to the genus-specific morphology observed in the literature. These anatomical traits correlate with the plant's phytochemical profile, supporting its therapeutic applications.

Integration with phytotherapeutic relevance

The presence of laticifers correlates with sesquiterpene lactones (taraxacin, taraxacerin), while inulin deposits in the root support its known prebiotic, hypoglycemic and metabolic modulatory effects (Yan et al., 2024; Neagu et al., 2023). Anatomical authentication is essential, given the high interspecific variability within TO, ensuring correct identification for pharmacognostic and industrial use.

Table 1

Macroscopic assessment results of dandelion (<i>Taraxacum officinale</i> Weber)					
Vegetative Organ	Aspect / Form	Surface / Fracture	Dimensions	Colour	Smell / Taste
Root	branched roots	irregular surface	up to 10 cm	light brown exterior	odorless
Leaf	long, lanceolate, deeply incised	smooth surface	10–30 cm	dark green	odorless
Flowering Stem	erect, cylindrical, with nodes	smooth, slightly brittle surface	up to 60 cm	light green	slightly characteristic odor
Flower	Inflorescence, capitulum	smooth, shiny surface	2–5 cm diameter	bright yellow	characteristic, slightly fragrant
Seed	elongated shape	smooth surface	0.3–0.5 mm	brown	odorless
Pollen	fine powder	smooth surface	100–200 μ m	yellow-green	odorless

Figure 1. Transverse section of the leaf of *Taraxacum officinale* Weber (obj. 40 \times) (a = vascular bundles, b = latex tubes, laticifers).

CONCLUSIONS

Morphological and anatomical analyses confirmed the correct identification of TO

collected from spontaneous flora in Bihor County. The consistent presence of articulated laticifers, inulin-rich parenchyma, dorsiventral leaf anatomy and echinulate pollen grains provide reliable diagnostic criteria essential for

preventing species substitution during harvesting and ensuring the botanical authenticity of the vegetal material. Macroscopic examination, performed in accordance with the Romanian Pharmacopoeia (Ph.10th), accurately characterized the organoleptic and morphological features of the species, while microscopic investigations, conducted on transversal, longitudinal and peeled sections stained with Genevez reagent—revealed the specific anatomical structures. The root exhibited a well-defined network of latex tubes and storage parenchyma rich in inulin, whereas leaves and flowering stems displayed irregularly thickened epidermal cells and prominent latex canals (laticifers). Vascular bundle distribution within the leaf differed between the upper and lower lamina, but remained consistent among all collected samples. The correct elucidation of these structures proves essential for a thorough understanding of medicinal plant products and for establishing correlations between morphological traits and bioactive compound content. Overall, the findings support the suitability of TO from Bihor County as authentic vegetal material for phytotherapeutic applications and reinforce the importance of rigorous species identification in preventing misidentification or substitution.

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CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE PLANT ASSORTMENT FOR THE ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION OF SLAG AND ASH DUMPS FROM LIGNITE-FIRED POWER PLANTS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The paper presents several new principles for approaching the restoration of vegetation on slag and ash dumps from lignite-fired power plants, in which the biotic factor is maximally activated. Only where rainwater and wind erosion cannot be controlled are construction elements (masonry, gabions, small fences, geogrids, geotextiles, and other combinations) used, with outcomes that are more or less biological. The results obtained on a 15-hectare dump site at Sânpetru, Brașov—a Romanian priority in this field—are presented. After three years of experimentation, the best results for renaturation on a eutrophic peat substrate were achieved with the grass species *Bromus inermis*, *Onobrychis viciifolia*, *Phalaris arundinacea*, *Arrhenatherum elatius*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Melilotus albus*, *M. officinalis*, and *Lotus corniculatus*; with the shrub *Amorpha fruticosa*; and with the tree *Robinia pseudoacacia*, fertilized appropriately with 150 kg/ha N, 75 kg/ha P₂O₅, and 75 kg/ha K₂O. These results have been successfully applied further in the ecological reconstruction of this type of dump.

Keywords: slag and ash dumps, ecological reconstruction, plant assortment

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INTRODUCTION

The slag and ash dumps resulting from coal combustion in thermal power plants are a major source of pollution of the air, soil, and surrounding vegetation if no measures are taken to restore them. (HARRIS et al., 1996; MARUȘCA et al., 1998; CĂPITANU et al., 1999; DUMITRU et al., 1999; MARUȘCA & DINCĂ, 2000)

The total area of such dumps originating from the 26 coal-fired power plants in our country covers 2,638 hectares. (DINCĂ et al., 2001)

The Brașov Combined Heat and Power Plant (CET Brașov) operates in cogeneration mode and is primarily intended to supply thermal energy (in the form of steam and hot water) to industrial consumers in the Brașov North area, as well as to urban consumers connected to the Brașov North district heating system (residential areas of Brașov Municipality), and to produce electrical energy. (CONSTANTINESCU et al., 1999)

The main equipment and installations of the power plant are:

- Two steam boilers of 420 t/h operating on lignite as the primary fuel and natural gas as

a support fuel (for ignition and flame stabilization);

- Two turbo-generator units of 50 MW each, both in condensation mode with adjustable DSL-50 type bleedings;

- Equipment and installations for fuel handling (solid and gaseous), hydraulic disposal of slag and ash, chemical water treatment, and district heating systems located within the plant premises;

- Electrical and automation systems and installations.

CET Brașov was initially designed to operate on lignite from the Oltenia coal basin, with a lower calorific value of approximately 1,550 kcal/kg, but ultimately used lignite from closer coal basins such as Baraolt, Filipeștii de Pădure, Câmpulung Argeș, and Borsec.

For boiler ignition and flame support, natural gas—with a calorific value of 8,500 kcal/Nm³—is used as an auxiliary fuel, accounting for about 10% of the total fuel consumption at nominal load.

As a result of the fuel combustion process, slag and ash are produced as waste, which are hydraulically transported through pipelines to a specially designed dump site located at the foot

of Lempeș Hill, about 12 km from the plant, in Sânpetru commune.

The slag and ash dump of CET Brașov underwent two main stages of development:

- The initial dump, designed for a maximum height of 15 m and a final capacity of about 2,300,000 m³, which is currently completely filled, with one last height increase of about 4 m planned;

- The new dump, built immediately adjacent to the initial one, with the first section commissioned in 1998 and a final capacity of about 3,500,000 m³.

The paper presents several new aspects and results regarding the ecological restoration of these polluting waste dumps, developed by the Research and Development Institute for Grasslands – Brașov, the Forest Research and Management Institute (ICAS) – Brașov Station, and the Transilvania University of Brașov, in close collaboration with the Institute for Energy Studies and Design (ISPE) – Bucharest (general designer) and the beneficiary CET Brașov, aiming ultimately to:

- control water and wind erosion;
- initiate and accelerate pedogenesis processes after the establishment of herbaceous vegetation;
- enable deep stabilization of the substrate by woody vegetation;
- ensure long-term consolidation of the entire site after shaping the slag and ash and covering them with a vegetative layer (eutrophic peat), through successive stages—grass establishment, shrub planting, and afforestation—either partially or entirely, as the final stage of the investment;
- encourage the appearance and spread of microorganisms, insects, and other organisms in the biogeochemical chain of the newly formed ecosystems;
- provide economic (fodder, timber, etc.), aesthetic (landscape restoration), and recreational (tourism, sports, e.g., golf courses) functions on lands currently occupied by such waste deposits.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Research activities aimed at achieving the proposed objectives were carried out in the field on four experimental plots, each with an area of 2,500 m², located on the main exposures (S, E, N, W) of the first ash dump. After shaping the slopes to an inclination of about 30°, a 15–20 cm thick layer of eutrophic peat from a nearby area was applied.

Part of the research was conducted in MITSCHERLICH-type vegetation pots in the ICDP Brașov micro-greenhouse, while agrochemical analyses of the substrate were performed at OSPA Brașov, following the current methodology.

Initially, several types of slag and ash from coal-fired power plants in Oradea, Timișoara, and Doicești-Dâmbovița were studied and compared with those from CET Brașov, in order to determine the degree to which the research results could later be generalized.

In the experimental plots, during May, a mixture of grasses (15 species of grasses and 8 legumes) was sown at a rate of 160 kg/ha, on a uniform agrochemical base of 75 kg/ha phosphorus and three nitrogen doses (0, 75, and 150 kg/ha), both with and without protective plants (35 kg/ha spring barley + 35 kg/ha rye + 10 kg/ha millet).

On the edges of the slopes within the experimental plots, English-made geogrids were installed to provide additional stabilization of the substrate.

The assortment of shrubs and trees was planted in November within the experimental plots and in April on the dump crest.

In addition, various other herbaceous and woody species were sown and planted to complete the assortment of plants used for vegetation restoration on this type of dump.

During this period, numerous observations and measurements were carried out, as follows:

- evolution of the floristic composition of the grass cover;
- biometric measurements on woody plants;
- planting losses among woody species;
- degree of propagation and spread through rhizomes, stolons, and root suckers of certain herbaceous and woody species;
- routine agrochemical analyses of the substrate (ash + peat) to a depth of 0–30 cm.

Given the novelty of the topic, several techniques and methods from grassland cultivation and forestry on light (sandy) soils were adapted.

The climatic conditions of the area where the dumps are located, according to data from the Bod weather station (508 m altitude), are typical of an intracarpathian depression, with an average annual temperature of 7.8°C, an average January temperature of –5.3°C, and Romania's absolute minimum temperature of –

38.5°C (recorded on January 25, 1942). The average July temperature, the warmest month, is 18.0°C, with an absolute maximum of +37.2°C (September 9, 1946), resulting in an absolute temperature amplitude of 75.7°C, one of the highest in the country.

The average number of summer days (with temperatures above 25°C) is 67, and that of tropical days (above 30°C) is 14 days.

Average annual precipitation is about 680 mm, with large year-to-year fluctuations (1,060 mm in 1912 and 383 mm in 1950) and between seasons, often accompanied by periods of drought.

Under these conditions, the primary vegetation consisted of oak (*Quercus robur*) and sessile oak (*Q. petraea*) forests, interrupted by valleys and wet eutrophic meadows, on which the Sânpetru-Braşov dumps were established, near the Cişmac stream, a tributary of the Olt River.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Following the agrochemical analyses, it was found that the pH in H₂O of the different ash samples is around 8.2 (slightly alkaline), with deviations of ± 0.2–0.3, making them very similar in this respect (Table 1).

Table 1

Agrochemical quality of different slag and ash samples from various coal-fired power plants in Romania

Specification	Unit	1.Braşov		2.Doiceşti DB		3.Timişoara		4.Oradea		Average Value	Aprec. Agro-ch.
		Value	Diff.	Value	Diff.	Value	Diff.	Value	Diff.		
PH in H ₂ O	ind.	8.0	-0.2	8.2	0	8.0	-0.2	8.5	+0.3	8.2	Slightly alkaline
CaCO ₃	%	4.0	+1.9	0.8	-1.3	1.3	-0.8	2.2	+0.1	2.1	Medium
Humus	%	1.04	-0.66	1.16	-0.54	3.19	+1.49	1.39	-0.31	1.7	Low
N Index	ind.	1.04	-0.66	1.16	-0.45	3.19	+1.49	1.39	-0.31	1.7	Low
P-AL	ppm	91.0	-9.5	118.0	+17.5	111	+10.5	82.0	-18.5	100	-
Corrected P-AL	ppm	46.4	+1.3	48.5	+3.4	56.6	+11.5	28.7	-16.4	45.1	High
K-AL	ppm	286	+11.0	242.0	-33.0	306	+31	266	-9.0	275	High

As expected, the potassium content is relatively high, averaging 275 ppm, with maximum deviations of ±30 ppm.

Surprisingly, the phosphorus content is also high, averaging 45 ppm, with the richest ash sample in this element coming from Timişoara (56.6 ppm), and the poorest from Oradea (28.7 ppm).

The very good supply of these two fertilizing elements (P and K) is extremely important for the establishment of vegetation, especially for species in the legume family, which are nitrogen-fixing plants.

The CaCO₃ content averages 2.1% (ranging from 0.7% at Doiceşti to 4.0% at Braşov) and also plays an important role in the establishment of legumes.

The nitrogen content in the ash is very low; therefore, this element must be applied obligatorily on this type of dump until the protective grass cover is established.

Regarding the success of the seed mixtures used for vegetation restoration on these dumps, after three years, out of 25 species sown, 12 species successfully established, including 6 perennial grasses, 5 perennial legumes, and 1 shrub (Table 2).

Table 2

Influence of vegetation factors on the floristic composition of mixtures used for the anti-erosion protection of slag dumps at Sânpetru-Braşov

Species	Average 1999-2000	Exposure		Fertilisation			Cereals	
		Sunny	Shaded	kg/ha			kg/ha	
				0	75	150	0	80
A. Grasses	69	73	65	55	69	81	71	67
<i>Bromus inermis</i>	29	36	22	23	30	34	30	28
<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i>	17	16	18	13	15	21	17	17
<i>Arrhenatherum elatius</i>	12	13	11	10	12	14	12	12
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	9	5	13	9	9	9	9	9
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	1	1	1	+	1	2	1	1
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	1	1	+	+	2	1	1	+
<i>Other grasses</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B. Legumes	31	27	35	45	31	19	29	33
<i>Onobrychis viciifolia</i>	17	18	16	20	18	13	19	15
<i>Melilotus albus</i>	5	3	7	9	5	2	3	7
<i>Melilotus officinalis</i>	3	3	3	4	3	2	3	3
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	2	1	5	7	3	1	2	4
<i>Trifolium hybridum</i>	2	1	3	3	1	1	1	3
<i>Other legumes</i>	1	1	1	2	1	+	1	1
C. Shrubs	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Amorpha fruticosa</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Among the grasses, the best-performing species was smooth brome (*bromus inermis*), followed by reed canary grass (*phalaris arundinacea*), tall oatgrass (*arrhenatherum elatius*), and orchard grass (*dactylis glomerata*). among the legumes, the top performers were sainfoin (*onobrychis viciifolia*), followed by white and yellow sweet clover (*melilotus albus*, *m. officinalis*) and bird's-foot trefoil (*lotus corniculatus*).

While some of these species are commonly propagated for fodder (brome, orchard grass, sainfoin, and bird's-foot trefoil), others are not regularly cultivated in romania (reed canary grass, tall oatgrass, white and yellow sweet clover), making it necessary in the future to produce seeds of these perennial grass species.

The success of the grass mixture is determined by vegetation factors, among which the substrate and its properties play a particularly important role. the powdery material with low water retention is improved by undecomposed organic matter and the water-holding capacity of the eutrophic peat, ultimately creating an aerohydric regime close to optimal for plant growth and development.

on sunny exposures, brome and sainfoin dominate, while on the shaded slopes of the dump, reed canary grass, white sweet clover, and bird's-foot trefoil—more moisture-loving species—participate more actively.

Nitrogen fertilization stimulates perennial grasses (55–81%) but reduces the

participation of legumes (45–19%), a pattern similar to that observed in sown grasslands.

Regarding the presence of cereal crops in the mixture, their protective role is noteworthy, as they shield young perennial grass plants from large fluctuations in moisture and strong insolation, characteristic of the slopes of these dumps.

An interesting achievement is the successful establishment of dwarf japanese false indigo (*amorpha fruticosa*) from seeds, despite strong competition from perennial grasses. after three years of growth, the japanese false indigo reaches an average stem diameter of 5 mm (range 1–10 mm) and a height of 26 cm (range 12–55 cm) in the unharvested vegetation cover.

Similarly, in the future, black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) could be introduced into these mixtures. it has also grown from seeds accidentally brought with river ballast, reaching after three years an average diameter of 18 mm (range 10–30 mm) and a height of 152 cm (range 100–175 cm) on areas with sparser grass cover, which favored its development.

The introduction of shrub or even tree seeds into ecoprotective grass mixtures is a romanian priority in this field, which will revolutionize the current strategy and system for the ecological reconstruction of dumps.

Regarding the success of planting shrub and tree species, some differences are observed between species (table 3).

Table 3

Seedling dimensions and losses recorded in the second year after planting on the ash dumps at Sânpetru-Braşov

Species	Exposure						Average		
	Sunny			Shaded			Diameter	Height	Losses
	Diameter	Height	Losses	Diameter	Height	Losses			
Wild rose	5	49	6	5	40	7	5	45	6
Flowering ash	10	59	6	12	61	8	11	55	7
Honey locust	8	45	7	5	42	9	7	44	8
Hawthorn	9	45	8	10	43	6	11	44	7
Black locust	13	83	-	9	112	-	16	97	-
Russian olive	16	115	-	-	-	-	16	115	-
Poplar	16	130	-	15	132	-	6	131	-
Wild service tree	5	38	-	6	46	-	-	42	-
Average	-	-	7	-	-	7	-	-	7

The best-performing species are Russian olive (*Eleagnus angustifolia*) and flowering ash (*Fraxinus ornus*), followed by wild rose (*Rosa canina*) and hawthorn (*Crataegus monogyna*).

Notably, the seedlings of black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*), honey locust (*Gleditsia triacanthos*), wild service tree (*Sorbus torminalis*), and even poplar (*Populus nigra*) also performed well.

CONCLUSIONS

Mixtures of perennial grasses, cereals, shrubs, and trees, together with chemical fertilizers, can be formulated and applied just once on the dumps to restore vegetation for the purpose of reducing soil erosion.

On slag and ash dumps covered with eutrophic peat, the best-performing perennial grasses are: *Bromus inermis*, *Onobrychis viciifolia*, *Phalaris arundinacea*, *Arrhenatherum elatius*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Melilotus albus*, *M.*

In general, on sunny exposures, woody species exhibit larger diameters, while on shaded exposures, seedlings tend to have greater height.

The dimensions (diameter and height) recorded for the seedlings indicate that they perform surprisingly well under the very difficult soil and climatic conditions—including the excessive drought experienced this year—typical of the region and the slag and ash dumps.

officinalis, and *Lotus corniculatus*, while the woody species from seed are the shrub *Amorpha fruticosa* and the tree *Robinia pseudoacacia*.

Planting allows the establishment of a wider assortment of shrubs and trees, among which the most notable are sea buckthorn, Russian olive, flowering ash, wild rose, hawthorn, honey locust, wild service tree, poplar, and others.

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SUSTAINABLE WINTER WHEAT PRODUCTION: THE INTERACTION OF CROP ROTATION AND NITROGEN FERTILIZATION IN YIELD OPTIMIZATION

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The experiment investigated the effects of preceding crops and nitrogen fertilization on the grain yield and nutrient use efficiency of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) under field conditions at the University of Debrecen, Látókép Experimental Station. The study involved three preceding crops (sweet corn, sunflower, maize) and six nitrogen fertilizer levels (0, 30, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N·ha⁻¹+PK). The results revealed significant differences among preceding crops, with the highest yields observed after sweet corn, while the lowest were obtained after maize. Optimal yield response occurred at 120 kg N·ha⁻¹, beyond which no significant yield increase was detected. These findings highlight that appropriate preceding crop selection can reduce fertilizer requirements without compromising yield, thus improving nitrogen use efficiency and supporting sustainable crop production

Keywords: crop rotation, fertilization, sustainable wheat production

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INTRODUCTION

Winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is one of the most important cereal crops worldwide. The choice of preceding crop and the optimization of nutrient management play a crucial role in achieving high and stable yields. The preceding crop affects soil structure, nutrient availability, and the biotic environment (Liu et al., 2023). Sustainable rotations can enhance nutrient cycling and reduce dependency on synthetic inputs (Al-Musawi et al., 2025; Burton et al., 2024). Nitrogen fertilization remains a key yield determinant but is associated with nitrate leaching and greenhouse gas emissions (Xu et al., 2024; Govindasamy et al., 2023). Studies report that wheat after legumes or sweet corn achieves better nitrogen efficiency compared with maize (Wang et al., 2025; Yao et al., 2023). The present study aimed to assess the effects of three preceding crops and six nitrogen levels on wheat yield under Eastern Hungarian conditions.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The field experiment was conducted in 2024–2025 at the University of Debrecen,

Látókép Experimental Station, on chernozem soil. Three preceding crops (sweet corn, sunflower, maize) and six nitrogen levels (0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 kg N·ha⁻¹+PK) were tested in a split-split-plot design with four replications. Fertilizers were applied manually.

During the growing season (August 2024 – June 2025), total precipitation was 378 mm, and the mean air temperature was 10.8 °C. Monthly mean temperatures ranged from 2 °C (January) to 22.7 °C (June). The average relative humidity was 73%, with moderate fluctuations. The accumulated effective heat sum for autumn cereals reached 2065 °C, corresponding to the long-term regional average.

Data were analyzed with Genstat using ANOVA and Duncan's Multiple Range Test (LSD_{0.05}).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Effect of the preceding crop on grain yield

The results clearly showed that the preceding crop had a decisive impact on winter wheat yield. Among the examined pre-crops, sweet corn resulted in the highest average yield (8748 kg ha⁻¹), followed by sunflower (7229 kg ha⁻¹) and maize (6037 kg ha⁻¹). The differences among these means were statistically significant

(LSD_{5%} = 350.7 kg ha⁻¹). The superior performance after sweet corn can be explained by its moderate residue C/N ratio, faster residue decomposition, and lower pathogen and weed pressure. Conversely, maize as a preceding crop left higher lignified residue amounts with a high C/N ratio, temporarily immobilizing soil nitrogen and slowing early wheat growth.

The 2024/2025 growing season was characterized by a total precipitation of 378 mm and a mean temperature of 10.8 °C, conditions considered moderately dry compared with the 30-year average. Under these circumstances, the better soil structure and moisture retention following sweet corn contributed to maintaining higher yield potential. In contrast, wheat after maize exhibited lower vigor and a delayed tillering phase, particularly under limited autumn rainfall.

Effect of variety

The two tested winter wheat varieties, *Mv Nádor* and *Mv Seuso*, produced comparable yields (7199 and 7477 kg ha⁻¹, respectively), and the differences were not statistically significant (LSD_{5%} = 286.3 kg ha⁻¹). This confirms that both cultivars possess similar adaptation potential to the experimental site

However, a slight tendency toward higher yield stability was observed for *Mv Seuso*, especially under the sunflower and sweet corn pre-crops in the experimental site.

Effect of nitrogen fertilization

Nitrogen fertilization had a strong positive effect on wheat yield up to a certain level. The yield increased from 4282 kg ha⁻¹ at the control (N₀) to 8542 kg ha⁻¹ at N₄ (120 kg N ha⁻¹), after which no further significant increase was detected (N₅ = 8523 kg ha⁻¹). The LSD_{5%} value (495.9 kg ha⁻¹) confirmed significant yield differences among most nitrogen levels.

Table 1

Effects of pre-crop, variety and fertilization on yield		
Effects of pre-crop		Yield kg ha ⁻¹
	Maize	6037 ^a
	Sunflower	7229 ^b
	Sweet Corn	8748 ^c
LSD (5%)		350.7
Effects of hybrids		
	<i>Mv Nádor</i>	7199 [*]
	<i>Mv Seuso</i>	7477 [*]
LSD (5%)		286.3
Effects of fertilizer		
	0	4282 ^a
	1	6813 ^b
	2	7725 ^c
	3	8143 ^{cd}
	4	8542 ^d
	5	8523 ^d
LSD (5%)		495.9

NB: Letters in columns are significant (p<0.05) according to Duncan Multiple Range Test; * No significant differences

Interaction effects of pre-crop, variety, and nitrogen fertilization

The interaction between preceding crop, variety, and nitrogen rate was significant (LSD_{5%} = 1214.7 kg ha⁻¹). Yields exceeded 9 t ha⁻¹ in several sweet corn × medium-N treatments (N₂-N₄) for both varieties, while wheat after maize remained below 8 t ha⁻¹ even at the highest N rate. The data suggest that nutrient uptake efficiency was

determined more by soil biological and structural factors inherited from the preceding crop than by the hybrid genotype itself.

According to Grant et al. (2016) and Burton et al. (2024), such interactions underline the importance of integrating rotation and fertilization management rather than optimizing either factor independently.

Table 2

Interactions effects of pre-crops, varieties and fertilization							
Source of variation		Nitrogen fertilization dosage					
Pre-crop	Hybrid	N0	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5
Maize	MvNádor	2763 ^a	4093 ^a	6195 ^b	6331 ^a	7756 ^a	8186 [*]
	MvSeuso	3056 ^a	5385 ^b	5658 ^a	6881 ^a	7841 ^{ab}	8301 [*]
Sunflower	MvNádor	3940 ^{ab}	6037 ^b	7308 ^b	8455 ^b	8600 ^{ab}	8557 [*]
	MvSeuso	4438 ^b	6779 ^b	7283 ^b	7956 ^b	8736 ^{ab}	8659 [*]
Sweet corn	MvNádor	5602 ^{cb}	9260 ^c	9419 ^c	9414 ^c	9022 ^b	8647 [*]
	MvSeuso	5896 ^c	9324 ^c	10488 ^c	9823 ^c	9299 ^b	8787 [*]
LSD (5%)							1214.7

NB: Letters in columns are significant ($p < 0.05$) according to Duncan Multiple Range Test; * No significant differences

Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated to quantify the relationships between winter wheat yield and the examined factors (genotype, fertilizer level, and preceding crop). The results revealed a strong positive correlation between yield and fertilizer level ($r = 0.622^{**}$), and a moderate positive correlation between yield and preceding crop ($r = 0.526^{**}$).

These values confirm that both nitrogen fertilization and pre-crop selection play a significant role in yield determination. In contrast, the correlation between genotype and yield was very weak ($r = -0.066$), indicating that under the given experimental conditions, varietal differences had a negligible impact on productivity.

Table 3

Relationships between yield and major agronomic factors of winter wheat based on Pearson's correlation analysis.

	Genotype	Nitrogen fertilization	Pre-crop
Yield	-0,066 (ns)	0,622 (**)	0,526 (**)

NB: Significance levels: $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), (ns) – not significant

Nitrogen use efficiency and environmental implications

Beyond yield, the study also revealed differences in nitrogen utilization efficiency. Wheat after sweet corn and sunflower showed higher apparent N recovery efficiency compared with maize. Excess nitrogen ($> 120 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) did not further improve yield, implying diminishing returns and potential environmental losses through nitrate leaching or gaseous emissions. Similar results were reported by Govindasamy et al. (2023), who stressed that matching nitrogen supply to crop demand is essential to balance productivity and sustainability. Consequently, adopting appropriate pre-crops can reduce required N input by 20–30% while maintaining comparable yields — a crucial aspect of sustainable cereal production systems (Al-Musawi et al., 2025).

CONCLUSIONS

The study confirmed that both the preceding crop and nitrogen fertilization level

are major determinants of winter wheat yield. Among the tested pre-crops, sweet corn proved the most favorable, enabling a reduction in fertilizer application without yield loss. The optimal yield was achieved at $120 \text{ kg N} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1}$, beyond which no significant improvement occurred. These findings demonstrate that appropriate crop rotation can enhance nitrogen use efficiency and contribute to more sustainable wheat production systems.

The results highlight the predominance of agronomic factors—particularly pre-crop and fertilizer management—over genotypic variation under the given environmental and management conditions. This conclusion is consistent with earlier findings by Liu et al. (2023) and Xu et al. (2024), who emphasized that optimizing nutrient inputs and rotation design plays a more decisive role in yield formation than cultivar selection under well-managed field conditions.

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STUDY ON THE DIVERSITY OF WEED FLORA IN AGRICULTURAL CROPS IN TELECHIU AREA (BIHOR COUNTY)

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The study was conducted in the locality of Telechiu in Bihor County, aiming to identify weeds in agricultural crops. For the study, 11 sample plots were established in corn, winter wheat, bean, sweet corn and sunflower fields. Weeds are unwanted plants in agricultural crops, foreign to the cultivated variety or hybrid, which cause damage by consuming water, soil nutrients, and other growth factors, leading to a decrease in both the quality and quantity of the harvested crop. When establishing control strategies, the following aspects must be considered: identifying the weeds and the methods to combat them. To develop and implement a comprehensive set of measures and methods for controlling weeds in agricultural crops, a thorough study of their life cycles and behavior under different climatic conditions is necessary, especially since weeds have biological characteristics that differ from those of cultivated plants. Despite the progress made in agriculture in recent years, weeds continue to be present in cultivated fields. The floristic composition of agricultural land, in terms of arable flora, has been systematically modified through soil tillage, fertilization, and the application of herbicide treatments. Effective control of weeds in agricultural crops requires a solid understanding of the weeds themselves, the pedoclimatic conditions in which they grow, and the effectiveness of the control treatments applied.

Keywords: weeds, agricultural crop, floristic composition, ecological indices
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INTRODUCTION

The study of the segetal flora was conducted on agricultural lands located in the village of Telechiu, Bihor County. In terms of the composition of the segetal flora, 11 crops were analyzed, including maize, sweet corn, winter wheat, sunflower and beans. Telechiu village is situated in the central-eastern part of Bihor County (figure 1), approximately 30 km from the city of Oradea, with the nearest town being Aleșd, located only 3 km away. Regarding neighboring areas, to the south is Vârciorog locality, to the east is Aștileu locality, to the north is Lugașu de Jos locality, and to the west is Tileagd locality.

Within these boundaries, Telechiu village covers an area of 51.2 km², representing 0.67% of the total area of the county. Climatically, due to its geographical position, the studied area falls under the influence of maritime air masses, present throughout the year, with a higher frequency in summer.

Additionally, the arrangement of the two marginal hilly/mountain units and the presence

of the Crișul Repede river play an important role in the local climate.

Figure 1 Location of the study in Bihor County (processing after - <https://ro.wikipedia.org>)

The average air temperature is 9°C-10°C. Regarding average monthly temperatures, the highest occurs in July at 19°C, and the lowest in January at 1.7°C. Annual precipitation ranges around 700-800 mm. Its distribution over the year shows a main summer maximum in June with 102.2 mm and a secondary maximum in December with approximately 60 mm. Although the territory of Telechiu village is extensive, with an agricultural area of 4064 ha, representing 79.4% of the area, it is composed of 2663 ha of arable land, 1149 ha of pastures, 204 ha of hayfields, 16 ha of orchards and nurseries, and 32 ha of vineyards. The land is suitable for agriculture, cultivating: cereals on 1693 ha (63.4% of arable land), potatoes on 200 ha, sunflowers on 71 ha, vegetables on 50 ha, with the remainder occupied by other crops.

For the study of the crop flora in the area, several specialized works were consulted: Anghel, 1972; Bujorean et al., 1962; Bujorean & Grigore, 1967; Chirilă, 2001; Grigore et al., 1979; Grigore et al., 1981; Ionescu-Șișești, 1955; Soran, 1962.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The synopsis and analysis of the weed flora in the studied agricultural crops were

carried out based on original field research conducted in 2025.

Species identification was done using specialized identification guides, "Segetal flora of Romania" by Ciocârlan et al. (2004).

The information obtained was organized in a systematic table, in which species were grouped by families according to a current plant classification system. For each species, its classification is indicated based on the number of seed embryo cotyledons, along with ecological indices for moisture (U), temperature (T), and soil chemical reaction (R).

The ecological index values were determined according to synthesis works by Soó (1964-1980), Májovsky & Murin (1987), Sanda et al. (1983), Pop (1977), Ellenberg, 1979, Cristea (1993), Ciocârlan et al. (2004) and Cristea et al. (2004).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For the study of segetal flora, a total of 11 physical plots were considered, encompassing 5 types of crops (corn, sweet corn, winter wheat, beans, sunflower) (table 1), where the weeds present both inside and at the edges of the plots were identified and described.

Table 1

Weed species identified in agricultural crops in the Telechiu area (Bihar County)																						
U	T	R	Cot.	Sample surface no. (type of culture)	GPS coordinates	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11						
						N	E	N	E	N	E	N	E	N	E	N	E	N	E			
						05607	04362	04313	05592	03850	05526	04103	04162	03693	05182	04562						
						22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22						
						25696	26172	26090	26766	26489	26017	27417	26010	26382	26920	25583						
						0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	
Weed species identified within the crops																						
3-3.5	3-3.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
2-2.5	0	0	D	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>		.	x	.	x	.	x	x	x	x
3-3.5	0	0	D	<i>Chenopodium album</i>		x	x	x	x
3-3.5	0	4-4.5	D	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>		.	.	x	x
3-3.5	2-2.5	3-3.5	D	<i>Oxalis stricta</i>		x	x	x	.
2-2.5	2-2.5	3-3.5	D	<i>Polygonum convolvulus</i>		x	x	x	x	.	.	x	.	.	.	x	x	.
2-2.5	3-3.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Papaver rhoeas</i>		.	.	x	x	x	x
2-2.5	4-4.5	5-5.5	D	<i>Lathyrus tuberosum</i>		x	x	.	.	.	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
3-3.5	0	0	D	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>		x
3-3.5	2-2.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Mentha arvensis</i>		x
2-2.5	2-2.5	5-5.5	D	<i>Aristolochia clematidis</i>		x
3-3.5	0	4-4.5	D	<i>Matricaria inodora</i>		.	.	.	x	x	.	.	x	x	.	x	x
5-5.5	2-2.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Calystegia sepium</i>		x
2-2.5	0	5-5.5	D	<i>Consolida regalis</i>		.	.	x	x	x	x
3-3.5	0	0	M	<i>Agropyron repens</i>		x	x	x	x	.	.	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
4-4.5	0	0	D	<i>Polygonum lapathifolium</i>		x
2-2.5	4-4.5	0	D	<i>Bifora radians</i>		.	.	x
4-4.5	4-4.5	0	D	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>		x	x	x
2-2.5	3-3.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Fumaria schleicheri</i>		.	.	x	x	x
3-3.5	2-2.5	0	D	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>		x

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
3-3.5	0	4-4.5	D	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	x	x
3-3.5	4-4.5	0	D	<i>Hibiscus trionum</i>	.	x	.	x
2-2.5	0	4-4.5	M	<i>Avena fatua</i>	x	x
3-3.5	2-2.5	0	-	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	x	x	x	.	.
3-3.5	3-3.5	2-2.5	M	<i>Apera spica-venti</i>	.	.	x	x	x	x
2-2.5	4-4.5	0	D	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x
2-2.5	4-4.5	0	D	<i>Ambrosia trifida</i>	x
2-2.5	2-2.5	5-5.5	D	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	x
3-3.5	0	5-5.5	D	<i>Atriplex patula</i>	.	x
2-2.5	4-4.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Anthemis arvensis</i>	.	.	.	x	x
3-3.5	0	4-4.5	M	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	x	.	.	.	x
4-4.5	2-2.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Symphytum officinale</i>	x	x
2-2.5	4-4.5	4-4.5	M	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	x	.	x	.	.	.
2-2.5	4-4.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Cardaria draba</i>	x
3-3.5	0	0	D	<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i>	x	x	.	.
2-2.5	0	4-4.5	D	<i>Thlasi arvense</i>	x
Weed species identified at the edge of the crops															
3-3.5	2-2.5	5-5.5	D	<i>Rubus caesius</i>	x	x	x	x	.	x	.
3-3.5	2-2.5	5-5.5	D	<i>Rubus sulcatus</i>	x
2-2.5	2-2.5	5-5.5	D	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	.	x	x
3-3.5	2-2.5	0	D	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>	x	.	x	x
2-2.5	4-4.5	0	D	<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	.	x	x
3-3.5	0	4-4.5	D	<i>Veronica hederifolia</i>	x	.	.	.	x	x
2-2.5	2-2.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	x
3-3.5	0	0	D	<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i>	.	.	.	x
2-2.5	2-2.5	3-3.5	D	<i>Conium maculatum</i>	x	.	x	.	x	x
3-3.5	0	4-4.5	D	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	x
3-3.5	0	0	D	<i>Stellaria media</i>	.	.	.	x	x	.	.
3-3.5	0	0	M	<i>Agropyron repens</i>	x
4-4.5	0	3-3.5	M	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	.	x	x	x	x	.	.
4-4.5	2-2.5	0	D	<i>Galium aparine</i>	x	.	.	.	x	.	x
4-4.5	2-2.5	4-4.5	D	<i>Symphytum officinale</i>	x
3-3.5	0	5-5.5	D	<i>Atriplex patula</i>	x	.	x	x	.	.
3-3.5	0	4-4.5	M	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	x	.	x	x	x	x	x
2-2.5	0	0	D	<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	x	x	x	x	.
2-2.5	0	0	D	<i>Erigeron canadensis</i>	x	x	.	x	.
3-3.5	0	4-4.5	M	<i>Lamium amplexicaule</i>	x	x	x	.	.
2-2.5	4-4.5	4-4.5	M	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	.	x	.	x	x
2-2.5	4-4.5	4-4.5	M	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	.	.	.	x	.	.	.	x	.	.	.
2-2.5	4-4.5	0	D	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	x

where: U-humidity; T-temperature; R-chemical reaction of the soil ; Cot - No. of cotyledons at the level of the embryo; M - monocotyledonous; D - dicotyledonous; 1 - Bergold bean crop (*Phaseolus vulgaris*); 2 - Bergold bean crop (*Phaseolus vulgaris*); 3 - Anapurna wheat crop (*Triticum aestivum*); 4 - Anapurna wheat crop (*Triticum aestivum*); 5 - Anapurna wheat crop (*Triticum aestivum*); 6 - Anapurna wheat crop (*Triticum aestivum*); 7 - Pioneer P9241 corn crop (*Zea mays*); 8 - Pioneer P9241 corn crop (*Zea mays*); 9 - Pioneer P9241 corn crop (*Zea mays*); 10 - Golden Bantam sweet corn crop (*Zea mays* ssp. *saccharata*); 11 - Pioneer P64LP170 Lumisena sunflower crop (*Helianthus annuus*).

The weed flora is characterized by a relatively high diversity of species, as a consequence of the diversity of the studied agricultural crops. Investigations carried out in the agricultural crops studied during the year 2025 highlighted a total of 51 weed species

belonging to 45 genus and 23 families. The analysis of ecological indices (table 2) for field crops highlights the specific characteristics of agricultural cultures in this area, viewed through the lens of the local pedoclimatic factors.

Table 2

The proportion of ecological categories in the studied crop field flora								
Ecological indices	Categories	1-1.5	2-2.5	3-3.5	4-4.5	5	6	0
U	%	-	45.10	43.14	9.80	1.96	-	-
	No. of species	-	23	22	5	1	-	-
T	%	-	1.96	33.34	23.53	-	-	41.17
	No. of species	-	1	17	12	-	-	21
R	%	-	1.96	7.84	39.22	13.73	-	37.25
	No. of species	-	1	4	20	7	-	19

Figure 2 The spectrum of ecological indices depending on humidity (U)

Analyzing the grouping of weed species according to their water requirements, it is observed that the majority belong to the xeromesophilous category ($U_{2-2.5}=45.10\%$) and mesophilous category ($U_{3-3.5}=43.14\%$) (figure 2).

Figure 3 The spectrum of ecological indices according to temperature (T)

Under the report on the behavior of the studied plants in relation to temperature, the abundance in the weed flora of euritherms is noted ($T_0=41.17\%$), followed by micromesotherms ($T_{3-3.5}=33.34\%$) and moderately thermophilic species ($T_{4-4.5}=23.53\%$) (figure 3).

CONCLUSIONS

The floristic study reveals the presence of 51 weed species, which are taxonomically classified into 45 genus and 23 families.

Analyzing the identified species in terms of ecological indices (humidity, temperature,

Figure 4 The spectrum of ecological indicators depending on the soil chemical reaction (R)

In terms of soil reaction preferences, most plants belong to the weak acid-neutral category ($R_{4-4.5}=39.22\%$), followed by the euryionic ones ($R_0=37.25\%$) (figure 4).

Figure 5 The distribution of the identified species based on the number of cotyledons in the embryo (where: D - dicotyledonous; M - monocotyledonous; P - pteridophytes)

Depending on the number of cotyledons in the seed embryo, the identified weed plant species are predominantly dicotyledonous (42 species), with a low number of monocotyledonous species (8 species) (figure 5).

and soil chemical reaction), we highlight the large presence of xeromesophilic species (45.10%), mesophilic species (43.14%), eurithermic species (41.17%), micromesothermic species (33.34%), moderately thermophilic species (23.53%),

weakly acidic neutrophilic species (39.22%), and euryionnic species (37.25%).

In terms of seed morphology, dicotyledonous weeds are dominant (42 species), followed by monocotyledonous weeds (8 species).

Among the weed species with the highest presence within the studied agricultural crops are: *Convolvulus arvensis* (bindweed), *Amaranthus retroflexus* (redroot pigweed), *Cirsium arvense* (creeping thistle), and *Agropyron repens* (quackgrass).

We observed a higher presence of xeromesophilic species, such as *Consolida regalis*, *Polygonum convolvulus*, *Papaver rhoeas*, *Fumaria schleicheri*, *Bifora radians*, *Anthemis arvensis* and *Avena fatua*, in wheat crops.

In corn, bean, and sunflower crops, mesophilic weeds, namely *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Chenopodium album*, *Agropyron repens*, *Hibiscus trionum*, *Setaria pumila* and *Equisetum arvense*, are predominantly found.

Understanding weeds is essential in agriculture as they directly affect crop productivity, soil health, and resource use efficiency. Knowing them is crucial for identifying the most effective control methods.

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EVOLUTION OF CLIMATIC PARAMETERS OVER THE LAST FIVE DECADES (1974–2023) AND THEIR ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT IN THE INEU ADMINISTRATIVE UNIT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The paper examines the dynamics of the principal climatic parameters recorded over the last five decades (1974–2023), focusing on the annual mean temperature and the total annual amount of precipitation, which are considered essential indicators of the thermal and pluviometry regimes. The meteorological data were processed based on records from the Oradea station, which shares a similar geographical and climatic context with the Ineu Administrative-Territorial Unit (ATU), thereby facilitating the extrapolation of results to the local level. Preliminary results reveal an upward trend in temperatures and a pronounced variability in the fluviometric regime, marked by periods of accentuated water deficit over the last two decades. For an integrated perspective, the study utilizes GIS and remote sensing technologies, generating spatial maps through the NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) and NDMI (Normalized Difference Moisture Index). These tools offer a supplementary analysis of vegetation evolution and soil moisture fluctuations within the Ineu ATU. The integration of meteorological data with spatial analysis allows for a comprehensive assessment of climate and environmental change, highlighting general trends and areas vulnerable to climatic stress and ecosystem alterations.

Keywords: annual mean temperature, annual precipitation, climatic parameters, GIS, NDVI, NDMI, remote sensing, water deficit
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INTRODUCTION

The Oradea Meteorological Station possesses an extensive climatic series, spanning the period 1974–2023, which facilitates a detailed analysis of the long-term evolution of atmospheric conditions characteristic of the western region of Romania. Temperatures and precipitation are established as essential climatic indicators, enabling the identification of trends and consequences of climate variability at both the regional and local scales.

By processing this data, the study reveals a clear picture of the transformations within the thermal and pluviometry regimes, serving as a foundation for understanding climatic warming processes and their effects on the local ecosystem.

The Ineu Administrative-Territorial Unit (ATU), situated in the proximity of the municipality of Oradea, benefits from a similar geographical and climatic context, which validates the extrapolation of the results obtained. This

spatial correspondence provides the research with an applicative character, with direct implications for territorial planning strategies and adaptation to climate change in the Ineu area.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The analysis was conducted in two principal phases: the temporal processing of meteorological data (Babak, Hossein, Rajmund, & Aleksandra, 2025) and the spatial integration through GIS (Juntao, Chuntian, & Shen, 2024) and remote sensing technologies.

Meteorological Data Processing

To highlight the evolution of annual mean temperatures and the average precipitation level (Monica & Nagavciuc, 2021) a graph was created in Excel (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The evolution of annual mean temperatures and the annual mean precipitation during the 1974–2023 period.

The meteorological data, sourced from the Oradea station and covering the 1974–2023 interval, include monthly values for the mean temperature and total precipitation (Giovenale, Chloe, Jan, & Rachel, 2025). Processing was performed in the Python programming language (version 3.12), utilizing specialized libraries such as Pandas (for data management) and Matplotlib (for graphical visualizations of temporal evolution).

The annual mean temperature was calculated as the arithmetic mean of the monthly values:

$$T_{\text{annual}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} T_i}{12}$$

and the mean annual amount of precipitation was determined using the following relation:

$$P_{\text{annual}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} P_i}{12}$$

where T (annual) represents the mean monthly temperature, and P (annual) represents the monthly precipitation (mm). The data were checked for integrity by excluding incomplete values (e.g., "-999") and rounding the results to one decimal place for consistency.

The statistical analysis included the determination of the overall mean for the entire period, the identification of extremes (minimums and maximums), and the evaluation of temporal trends through simple linear regression. To evaluate the relationship between the annual mean temperature and the total annual amount of precipitation, an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) linear regression was applied to the Oradea climatic series for the 1974–2023 interval. The mean monthly temperatures and monthly precipitation were aggregated annually, and the functional relationship was expressed as:

where:
 P = annual precipitation (mm)

T = annual mean temperature (°C)

β_0, β_1 = model coefficients

ϵ = residual term

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T + \epsilon$$

The analysis was performed in Python, utilizing the Pandas and Stats models libraries, including verification of statistical significance (test t) and model quality (coefficient of determination R^2). The significance of the correlation level was evaluated at $p < 0,05$.

Figure 2. OLS Regression: Precipitation vs. Annual Mean Temperature, Oradea 1974–2023

Parameter	Value
Temperature Coefficient	-41.58 mm / °C
Intercept	1071.70 mm
R ²	0.119
P - value	0.014 statistically significant
Observations	50 years

Interpretation:

- For every 1°C increase in the annual mean temperature, precipitation decreases by approximately 41.6 mm/an.
- The relationship is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$)
- $R^2 = 0.119 \rightarrow$ Temperature explains approximately 12% of the variability in precipitation (which is typical for multiannual climatic studies, as climate is multivariate)

The results of the simple linear regression (OLS) for the 1974–2023 period indicate a negative relationship between the annual mean temperature and the total annual amount of precipitation in the Oradea area, thus confirming the climatic tendency towards a warmer and drier climate. For every 1°C increase in the annual mean temperature, the mean precipitation amount decreases by approximately 41,6 mm/an.

The relationship is statistically significant ($p = 0.014$), suggesting a robust long-term climatic correlation. This analysis supports contextual observations regarding the intensification of drought phenomena and pluviometry variability, with direct implications for water resource management, agriculture, and adaptive planning (Linsenmeier, 2024).

Spatial Analysis using GIS and Remote Sensing

For the spatial component, the QGIS software (version 3.34) (Subhajit, Kundan , & Preet, 2025) was utilized, which facilitated the processing of satellite imagery and the elaboration of thematic maps for the UAT Ineu.

To provide a suggestive visualization of the difference in vegetation status and density as well as soil moisture and hydric stress-resulting from the effects of climate change and the climatic tendency toward a warmer and drier climate-a comparative analysis was performed for the last 10 years, referencing August 2015 and August 2025 (Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4).

The imagery sources included the Copernicus Browser-Sentinel 2 archives (Antonio , et al., 2024) with a 20 m resolution, spanning the 2015–2025 interval, accessed through open platforms such as Esri Maps - Environmental System Research Institute, ensuring transparency and open access to data.

The indicators evaluated are the **NDVI** - Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (Ana-Maria, Catalin , Bogdan, & Florin, 2024) and the **NDMI** - Normalized Difference Moisture Index (Berca & Roxana, 2022)

To ensure spectral and temporal consistency, atmospheric corrections (DOS and

6S algorithms), cloud filtering (QA band mask), and normalization of spectral values were applied.

Data Integration: The climatic parameters (temperature and precipitation) were spatially correlated with the NDVI and NDMI indices through overlay operations in QGIS, analyzing relationships such as the impact of reduced precipitation on NDMI (hydric deficit) and the influence of increased temperatures on NDVI (thermal stress on vegetation)

The NDVI Index was utilized for the evaluation of vegetation status and density, calculated according to the formula:

$$NDVI = (NIR - Red) / (NIR + Red)$$

where NIR represents the Near-Infrared band and Red represents the Red band. NDVI values

were determined for seasonal periods (summer, autumn) in order to identify temporal changes in vegetation cover.

The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index is a simple yet efficient index for quantifying green vegetation. It serves as a measure of vegetation health, based on how plants reflect light at specific wavelengths. The value range for NDVI is from -1 to 1. Negative NDVI values (approaching -1) correspond to water. Values close to zero (-0,1 till 0,1) generally correspond to bare areas of rock, sand, or snow. Small positive values represent shrubs and grasslands (approximately 0,2 till 0,4), while high values indicate tropical and temperate forests (values approaching 1).

Figure 1. Vegetation Status and Density Assessment (NDVI 2015)

Figure 2. Vegetation Status and Density Assessment (NDVI 2025)

From the captured imagery, a decrease in vegetation density can be observed in 2025 compared to 2015, which is objectified by extensive areas highlighted in the yellow color (Figure 1, Figure 2).

The NDMI Index was applied for the analysis of soil and vegetation moisture, according to the following relation:

$$NDMI = (NIR - SWIR) / (NIR + SWIR)$$

where SWIR designates the Shortwave Infrared band. NDMI values were calculated and cartographically represented across the UAT Ineu (approx. 10 km² - total analyzed area), highlighting zones exposed to moisture deficit or thermal stress.

The NDMI Index can be utilized for detecting hydric stress and for monitoring irrigation and/or soil moisture. For all index values greater than 0, knowing the type of land use and cover, it is possible to determine whether irrigation has occurred or whether soil moisture is optimal. Furthermore, by knowing the crop type (e.g., citrus crops), one can identify the efficiency of irrigation during the critical summer growing season and highlight areas of the farm that are sub- or over-irrigated.

The comparative imagery objectifies the decrease in soil moisture and the associated hydric stress, colored in yellow to reddish tones, characteristic of 2025 compared to 2015 (Figure 3, Figure 4).

Figure 3. Soil and Vegetation Moisture Status Assessment (NDMI 2015)

Figure 4. Soil and Vegetation Moisture Status Assessment (NDMI 2025)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of the climatic parameter evolution for the 1974–2023 interval clearly highlights modification trends in the thermal and pluviometry regimes within the analyzed area. The annual mean temperature demonstrates a constant long-term increase, with a visible intensification over the last two decades. The linear regression results indicate an average annual rate of temperature increase, which confirms the regional warming trend, consistent with climatic observations at the national and European levels. In parallel, precipitation variability is pronounced, featuring episodes of severe hydric deficit, particularly after the year 2000, alternating with isolated wetter years. This indicates an increasingly unstable and hard-to-anticipate climate.

From a spatial perspective, the mean NDVI values processed for the vegetative seasons indicate a slight decrease in vegetation vigor across certain portions of the Ineu ATU, particularly in intensively utilized agricultural areas and near lands experiencing high anthropogenic pressure. This tendency can be correlated with the reduction in water resource availability and the increased thermal stress on local ecosystems. The NDMI values support this conclusion by highlighting a higher frequency of zones with soil moisture deficit, especially during consecutive dry years, which can affect agricultural productivity and the resilience of natural vegetation.

The linear regression results emphasize a statistically significant negative relationship between the annual mean temperature and the total annual amount of precipitation. The model demonstrates that, over the 50 analyzed years, the rise in mean temperatures was associated with a decline in precipitation:

These results indicate that a 1° increase in the annual mean temperature is associated with a reduction of approximately 41,6 mm in annual precipitation. The R^2 value suggests that approximately ~12% of the precipitation variability is explained by temperature - a typical level for multifactorial climatic systems.

The observed trend confirms the shift towards a warmer and drier regional climate, with direct relevance for local agriculture, water resources, and biodiversity. These findings are congruent with recent literature concerning the climatology of Central and Eastern Europe, which reports similar scenarios of increasing temperatures and heightened hydric pressure.

The integration of climatic results with remote sensing analysis underscores the importance of adaptation to climate change for the sustainable management of natural resources. The identified trends are relevant in the context of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 13 – "Climate Action", SDG 15 – "Life on Land", and also SDG 6 – "Clean Water and Sanitation", given the increasing pressure on water resources. The precipitation variability, correlated with the decline in spectral-ecological indices in some areas, indicates potential risks for ecosystem stability and the necessity for agricultural practices adapted to hydric stress

phenomena, in accordance with the principles of sustainable land management and the strategic national provisions (e.g., The National Strategy for Sustainable Development, 2030).

These results also align with the objectives of SDG 11 – "Sustainable Cities and Communities", through the need for local interventions aimed at increasing the resilience of rural and urban communities to the effects of climate change, as well as improving green infrastructure and protecting agricultural lands.

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrates that during the 1974–2023 interval, the analyzed territory is subject to gradual climatic warming, accompanied by an increase in the variability of the pluviometry regime and increasingly frequent episodes of hydric deficit. These transformations directly influence the dynamics of vegetation and the capacity of ecosystems to respond to climatic stress, an aspect confirmed by the analysis of the NDVI and NDMI indices. High-vulnerability areas require continuous monitoring and the implementation of adaptive measures, particularly in the agricultural sector, where water use efficiency, crop diversification, and soil conservation techniques become essential.

The statistical analysis confirms the existence of a significant inverse relationship between the annual mean temperature and the total annual precipitation for the 1974–2023 period at the Oradea station. The results support the hypothesis of the intensification of the regional thermal regime and the reduction of pluviometry resources, thus arguing for the necessity of local climate adaptation strategies.

In the context of sustainable development, the results support the need to consolidate local strategies oriented towards the protection of natural resources and the adaptation of communities to climate change. The contribution of this research falls in line with promoting responsible environmental management, aligned with SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land), highlighting the importance of GIS and remote sensing tools as technical support for monitoring and decision-making.

Therefore, the integration of statistical climatic modeling with spatial analysis (NDVI/NDMI) contributes to a deeper understanding of local ecosystem vulnerabilities

and supports the foundation of measures for climate change mitigation and adaptation.

In the medium and long term, it is recommended to continue regional climatic studies, correlate them with pedological and economic information, and integrate the results into local land-use planning and sustainable agriculture schemes. This approach will contribute to increased resilience against future climatic challenges.

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THE ALLELOPATHIC EFFECT PRODUCED BY SYNTHETICALLY AND NATURALLY ALLYL ISOTHIOCYANATE ON SEEDLING GROWTH TO TRITICOSECALE AND TRITICUM AESTIVUM FALADO VARIETY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper study the effects of microemulsions (0,02% ; 0,01% ; 0,005%; 0,002% and 0,001%) of synthetically Sigma-Aldrich allyl isothiocyanate and of the solutions naturally obtaining (20%, 10%, 5%, 2% and 1%) from horseradish roots. The allyl isothiocyanate is the main bioactive compound in aqueous extracts from metamorphosed horseradish roots. The effect produced on caryopses germination ability and seedling growth of *Triticosecale* and *Triticum aestivum* L. var. Falado was followed. The germination capacity of cereal caryopses - compared to the control - was not modified by any concentrations of synthetically allyl isothiocyanate microemulsion used (0,02%, 0,01%, 0,005%, 0,002% and 0,001%). Only the 20% aqueous extract from horseradish roots caused a decrease in germination of wheat caryopses to 48%. In *Triticosecale* and *Triticum aestivum* variety Falado the 0,02% concentration of microemulsion determined significant inhibitions of seedling growth; 0,01% and 0,005% concentrations caused influences statistically insignificant. The 0,002% and 0,001% concentrations caused significant stimulation of roots and coleoptiles growth. The growth in length of vegetative organs of cereal seedlings was significantly inhibited by aqueous extracts of horseradish roots at 20% and 10% concentrations. In triticale the 5% concentration caused significant stimulations but in wheat this concentration determined significant inhibitions in the growth of seedlings. In the last two variants of aqueous horseradish root extracts 2% and 1% the growth in length of triticale seedlings was significantly stimulated. In wheat Falado variety the influences were insignificant for roots but coleoptile was significantly stimulated of aqueous horseradish extracts 2%.

Keywords: allyl isothiocyanate, *Triticosecale*, *Triticum aestivum* var. Falado, allelopathy

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INTRODUCTION

Allelopathy is an important mechanism that plays a semnificative role in natural as well as cultivated ecosystems. Allelochemicals are released by a variety of mechanisms (volatilization, decomposition of residues and root exudation). The plants release secondary metabolites (allelochemicals) that influence positive or negative the growth and development of neighboring plants (Cachiță et Corbu, 2010; Hiero et Callaway, 2021, Zang et al., 2020). More recently, a distinction is made between "true allelopathy" (direct release of active compounds) and "functional allelopathy" (compounds transformed by soil microorganisms) (Scavo et al., 2018).

The allyl glucosinolate called sinigrin exists in significant amounts in metamorphosed

horseradish roots and releases allyl isothiocyanate through myrosinase hydrolysis (Stoin et al., 2007, 2008). This volatile, pungent compound is an allelochemical (Corbu et al., 2007).

This study examined the effects of naturally allyl isothiocyanate from aqueous extracts of horseradish root and synthetic isothiocyanate Sigma – Aldrich on the growth of seedlings of two cereals *Triticosecale* and *Triticum aestivum* var. Falado. In fact, all allelochemicals, depending on their concentration, have inhibitory or stimulating effects on plants growth. The boundary between the stimulatory and inhibitory concentrations for each species and variety should be precisely determined (Bandici et al., 2017; Bortîș et Șipoș, 2018; Șipoș et al., 2012;).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The certified materials used in our experiments were represented by cereals caryopses without chemicals treatment from Territorial Inspectorate for Quality of Seeds and Implanting Material Bihor. The germination ability was determined at *Triticum aestivum* var. Falado (95%-100%) and *Triticosecale* (98-100%).

The synthetic oil of allyl isothiocyanate (Sigma-Aldrich) was dispersed in water by ultrasonication using an Emmi device-4D with the frequency 40 kHz. In an Erlenmeyer flask with a glass cork 0,2 ml of synthetic allyl isothiocyanate and 100 ml of distilled water were introduced. 0,2% microemulsions of allyl isothiocyanate was obtained after ultrasonication for 30 minutes at 30°C. Using the graduated cylinders dilutions 0,02% (I₁), 0,01% (I₂), 0,005% (I₃), 0,002% (I₄), 0,001% (I₅) were performed.

The naturally allyl isothiocyanate solution was produced by scraping tuberous roots of horseradish (*Amaracia rusticana* L.) harvested in the fall. 200 g of scraped material was placed in 1000 ml distilled water. The mixture was left to macerate for 24 hours at

room temperature (20 - 21°C). The aqueous horseradish extract was strained and filtered obtaining a 20% concentration solution (H₁). The following dilutions were prepared: 10% (H₂), 5% (H₃), 2% (H₄), 1% (H₅).

The germination of caryopses in sterile colorless plastic casseroles was performed. The bottom of casseroles with filter paper moisted with 25 ml of different dilution or distilled water (for control) were covered. 50 caryopses were placed in each casserole for all experimental variants and control lots. The germination ability was determined in two replicates. The casseroles were then placed in a germination cabinet at 21-23°C in the dark. The germination ability and seedling growth after 5 days of germination was determinate. The embryonic and adventitious root length and coleoptile height (cm) of 50 plantlet were measured for all experimental variants and control lots. Individual data were statistically processed with the Sigma Plot 2001 software. Statistical analysis included arithmetic media and Student's test. Values of the procentual differences in raport with control (100%) were determined. The significance level of this difference was P>0,05 insignificant P<0,05 significant or P<0,001 strongly significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The germination capacity of *Triticosecale* and *Triticum aestivum* var. Falado caryopses - compared to the control - was not modified by any concentrations of synthetically allyl isothiocyanate microemulsions used (0,02%, 0,01%, 0,005%, 0,002% and 0,001%). Only the 20% allyl isothiocyanate aqueous extract from horseradish roots caused a decrease in germination of wheat caryopses to 48% (Table 1).

The microemulsion of allyl isothiocyanate at a concentration of 0,02% (I₁) caused insignificant inhibitions of the growth in length of the vegetative organs of triticale plantlets. For triticale the inhibitions were - 10,3% for embryonic roots, -7,9% for adventitious roots and -8,02% for coleoptiles. The wheat variety Falado proved to be more sensitive because the growth of the seedlings was significantly inhibited (-24.49%; -19.55%, respectively -32.61%) (p<0.001).

Table 1.
The germination ability of the caryopses of the *Triticosecale* and *Triticum* var. Falado in control groups (C) and various dilutions of synthetically ($I_1 - I_5$) and naturally ($H_1 - H_5$) obtaining allyl isothiocyanate.

Treatment	Variants	Germination ability	
		<i>Triticosecale</i>	<i>Triticum Falado</i>
Allyl isothiocyanate Sigma Aldrich	Control	100%	100%
	I_1 (0,02%)	100%	96%
	I_2 (0,01%)	98%	98%
	I_3 (0,005%)	100%	100%
	I_4 (0,002%)	100%	98%
	I_5 (0,001%)	98%	100%
Allyl isothiocyanate in aqueous horseradish extract	Control	99%	95%
	H_1 (20%)	92%	48%
	H_2 (10%)	96%	100%
	H_3 (5%)	98%	98%
	H_4 (2%)	98%	100%
	H_5 (1%)	98%	100%

The following two concentrations of synthetic allyl isothiocyanate microemulsions 0,01% (I_2) and 0,005% (I_3) determined in triticale and wheat (Falado) stimulations of the growth in length of the vegetative organs of the seedlings (embryonic roots, adventitious roots, coleoptiles), but influences were statistically insignificant. The concentrations of 0,002% (I_4) and 0,001% (I_5) caused significant stimulation of rootlets and coleoptiles growth (Table 2).

Previous results show that the growth of wheat Cubus and Dropia variety seedlings was significantly inhibited at concentrations of allyl isothiocyanate (0,02%; 0,01%). In the case of experimental concentrations (0,002%; 0,001%) inhibitions were insignificant or growth was stimulated (Bortiş and Şipoş, 2018). In the Lukulus wheat variety seedling growth at the 0,001% concentration allyl isothiocyanate was stimulated. The seedlings growth of Tristan variety triticale evolved in optimum conditions using the concentration of 0,001% allyl isothiocyanate (Şipoş et al., 2016). The concentrations 0,02% and 0,01% allyl isothiocyanate significantly inhibited seedling growth of Marco Polo wheat variety. Instead, the 0,002% and 0,001% concentrations ensured their optimal growth. The Trublion wheat variety was less sensitive to the action of the allelopathic substance allyl isothiocyanate. Only the 0,02% concentration caused significant inhibitions of seedling growth. The other concentrations taken in the study (0,01; 0,005; 0,002 and 0,001%) significantly stimulated the growth in the length of the vegetative organs (Şipoş et al., 2023).

The growth of vegetative organs (embryonic roots, adventitious roots,

coleoptiles) of triticale and wheat (Falado) seedlings was significantly inhibited ($p < 0,001$) by aqueous horseradish extracts H_1 (20%) and H_2 (10%). Thus, in *Triticosecale*, the inhibitions were -90,35% (H_1) and -78,55% (H_2), in terms of embryonic roots; -93,6% (H_1) and -84,9% (H_2) for adventitious roots; -84,2% (H_1) and -77,1% (H_2) for coleoptiles. In wheat (Falado) inhibitions were recorded -90% (H_1) and -87,7% (H_2) for embryonic roots; -86,5% (H_1) and -86,1% (H_2) for adventitious roots and -75,2% (H_1) and -67,5% (H_2) for coleoptiles (Table 2).

In *Triticum aestivum* Falado variety the concentration of 5% (H_3) of aqueous horseradish extracts caused significant inhibitions ($p < 0,001$) of the growth in length of the vegetative organs: embryonic roots (-37,2%); adventitious roots (-29,4%) and coleoptiles (-26,1%). In triticale, the concentration of 5% (H_3) caused significant stimulations ($p < 0,05$) of the growth of the studied vegetative organs.

In the last two variants of aqueous horseradish root extracts 2% (H_4) and 1% (H_5) the growth in length of embryonic, adventitious and coleoptile roots of triticale seedlings was significantly stimulated. In wheat var. Falado the influences were insignificant for roots but coleoptile was significantly stimulated of aqueous horseradish extracts 2% (Table 2).

Our previous research provided similar results regarding the action of aqueous extracts from horseradish roots on the growth of Marco Polo and Trublion wheat seedlings. In the Marco Polo and Trublion wheat variety the concentration 20% from the aqueous extract of horseradish determined significant inhibition in the seedling growth. At Marco Polo the other dilutions 10%, 5% and 2% significantly inhibited the growth of rootlets and coleoptiles showed statistically insignificant stimulations. Only the 1% concentration caused insignificant inhibitions in root length growth and significant stimulations in coleoptile growth. The Trublion wheat variety was also shown to be more resistant to the action of aqueous horseradish extracts. The dilutions 10% and 5% determined significant inhibitions in the roots growth but coleoptiles were significantly stimulated. The 2% concentration caused insignificant inhibitions in roots length growth and significant stimulations in coleoptiles growth. The last dilution of horseradish root aqueous extract 1% were found to be beneficial because significant stimulated the growth of the plantlets (Şipoş et al., 2023).

Table 2.

Values of the procentual differences (%) in raport with control (100%) of arithmetic media of embryonic and adventitious root length and coleoptile height (cm) and significance level (a-strongly significant $P < 0,001$; b-significant $P < 0,05$; c-insignificant $P > 0,05$)

Treatment	Dilutions	Biotest species					
		<i>Triticosecale</i>			<i>Triticum Falado</i>		
		Embryonic root length	Adventitious root length	Coleoptile height	Embryonic root length	Adventitious root length	Coleoptile height
Allyl isothiocyanate	I ₁ - 0,02%	-10,31%c	-7,91%c	-8,02%c	-24,49%a	-19,55%a	-32,61%a
	I ₂ - 0,01%	+5,68%c	+6,66%c	+14,8%b	-2,4%c	+1,01%c	+6,6%c
	I ₃ - 0,005%	+10,3%c	+8,14%c	+9,54%c	+7,19%c	+9,13%c	+1,46%c
	I ₄ - 0,002%	+19,5%a	+15,5%a	+27,1%a	+26,2%a	+23,6%a	+15,01%b
	I ₅ - 0,001%	+33,7%a	+23,7%a	+27,3%a	+20,2%a	+13,45%b	+17,58%b
Aqueous horse-radish extract	H ₁ - 20%	-90,35%a	-93,6%a	-84,24%a	-90 %a	-86,53%a	-75,29%a
	H ₂ - 10%	-78,55%a	-84,98%a	-77,18%a	-87,73%a	-86,1 %a	-67,53%a
	H ₃ - 5%	+19,1%b	+19,7%b	+22,4%b	-37,28%a	-29,46%a	-26,15%a
	H ₄ - 2%	+29,1%a	+15,7%b	+31,9a	-2,58%c	+8,9%c	+16,66%b
	H ₅ - 1%	+18 %b	+15,7%b	+16,2%b	-5 %c	+3,42%c	-0,29%c

CONCLUSIONS

1. The germination capacity of triticale and wheat Falado caryopses was not modified - compared to the control - by any of allyl isothiocyanate concentrations of the microemulsions used: 0,02%, 0,01%, 0,005%, 0,002% and 0,001%. Only the 20% aqueous extract from horseradish roots caused a decrease in germination to 48% at *Triticum aestivum* Falado variety.

2. In *Triticosecale* and *Triticum aestivum* variety Falado the 0,02% concentration of the synthetic allyl isothiocyanate microemulsions caused significant inhibitions of the growth in length of embryonic, adventitious roots and coleoptiles. The 0,01% and 0,005% concentrations caused stimulations or inhibitions of the growth in length of vegetative organs but all influences were statistically insignificant. In contrast, the 0,002% and 0,001% concentration caused significant stimulation of roots and coleoptiles growth.

3. The growth in length of vegetative organs of cereal seedlings was significantly inhibited by aqueous extracts of horseradish roots at 20% and 10% concentrations. In triticale the 5% concentration caused significant stimulations but in wheat this concentration determined significant inhibitions in the growth of seedlings. In the last two variants of aqueous horseradish root extracts 2% and 1% the growth in length of triticale seedlings was significantly stimulated. In wheat Falado variety the influences were insignifiant for roots but coleoptile was significantly stimulated of aqueous horseradish extracts 2%.

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THE INFLUENCE OF SOWING TIME ON THE YIELD OF SWEET CORN UNDER THE NATURAL CONDITIONS OF THE BLACK CRIȘUL MEADOW IN 2025

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The research aimed to assess the influence of sowing time and fertilization regime on the yield performance of the sweet corn hybrid Dessert R78 under the specific pedoclimatic conditions of the Black Criș Meadow in 2025. The experiment was organized in a two-factor design, including four fertilization variants (control, organic compost, NPK complex, and NPK + microelements) and two sowing times. Results revealed that early sowing favored higher yields, while delayed sowing caused a slight reduction in production. The NPK + microelements treatment achieved the maximum yield of 22.79 t/ha, exceeding the control by 128.8%. Statistical analysis indicated a highly significant influence of fertilization and a moderate effect of sowing time, demonstrating the hybrid's adaptability and high productive potential in local environmental conditions.

Keywords: sweet corn, sowing time, fertilization, production, Black Crișul Meadow.

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INTRODUCTION

Sweet corn (*Zea mays* convar. *saccharata*) is one of the most valuable vegetable species cultivated in temperate regions, appreciated both for its sweet taste and distinctive aroma, as well as for its high nutritional value (Gavrić & Omerbegović, 2021). Due to its rich content of simple sugars, vitamins, and minerals, sweet corn is a crop of significant economic and dietary interest, intended for consumption either fresh or in processed form (Jung et al., 2014).

The yield and quality of sweet corn production are influenced by a range of technological and environmental factors, among which the sowing time plays a crucial role (Uğur & Maden, 2015). Choosing the optimal sowing moment determines the rate of germination, the dynamics of plant growth, and, consequently, the level of production. Soil temperature at the time of sowing has a direct influence on germination and early plant development, and deviations from the optimal range can lead to reduced plant density, shifts in growth stages, and decreased final yields (Rajablarjani et al., 2014).

In addition to sowing time, the fertilization regime significantly contributes to

the physiological and productive performance of sweet corn (Soare et al., 2019). The interaction between fertilization and sowing time can have complex effects on growth dynamics, directly influencing final yield and crop quality (Sofyan et al., 2019).

The aim of this study is to analyze the influence of sowing time on sweet corn production under the specific conditions of the Black Crișul Meadow in 2025, in correlation with four applied fertilization variants. The experiment included a total of eight experimental plots, resulting from the combination of four fertilization variants — (1) control with no fertilization, (2) organic fertilization with compost, (3) fertilization with a complex fertilizer, and (4) fertilization with a complex fertilizer enriched with micronutrients — with two distinct sowing times:

Sowing Time I – at the attainment of the optimal sowing temperature

Sowing Time II – 14 days after the optimal sowing temperature is reached

Through the comparative analysis of yields obtained according to sowing time and fertilization variant, the study aims to identify the optimal period for sowing sweet corn under the pedoclimatic conditions of the Black Crișul Meadow and to formulate recommendations to help maximize crop yield.

The research results can provide useful information for both agricultural producers and agronomy specialists, supporting the adoption of technological strategies adapted to current climatic conditions and the principles of sustainable agriculture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the Black Crișul Meadow, an area characterized by fertile soils and a moderately temperate-continental

climate. Precipitation patterns and the average temperature during the sweet corn growing period were monitored to assess the influence of climatic conditions on the experimental results.

For precise localization of the experimental field, Figure 1 presents a satellite image of the experimental site.

Figure 1 Satellite image of the experimental field

The research was conducted on Gleyic Alluviosol soils, ranging from slightly silty to moderately silty, located in Căpâlna, Bihor County. These soils developed on fluvial deposits and exhibit a characteristic profile up to 105 cm deep, with morphological features specific to floodplain environments. The soil texture is predominantly silty, with a significant content of fine sand and clay, which results in a

moderate capacity to retain water and essential nutrients for agricultural crops.

To assess the influence of climatic conditions on the development of the sweet corn crop, precipitation and average air temperature during the growing period were monitored. Table 1. presents the monthly average temperatures, while Table 2 illustrates the monthly average precipitation values recorded in 2025.

Table 1.

Average air temperature

Month	Average air temperature
January	3.4
February	1.0
March	8.9
April	12.6
May	14.0
June	23.3
July	23.4

The analysis of the monthly average temperatures in the Black Crișul Meadow during the period January–July 2025 highlights a thermal regime characterized by a pattern typical for the climatic conditions of the lowland area, with a gradual increase in average values from the beginning of the year to the summer months.

The winter months were relatively mild, with an average temperature of 3.4°C in January and 1.0°C in February, slightly above the long-

term regional average, indicating a less severe winter. In March (8.9°C) and April (12.6°C), a progressive warming was observed, favorable for soil preparation and the onset of the optimal sowing period for spring crops.

In June (23.3°C) and July (23.4°C), high temperatures were recorded, typical for the period of intensive vegetative growth, conducive to the development of green biomass and sugar accumulation in the cobs, provided that the water regime is adequate.

Table .2

Amount of precipitation (l/m²)

Month	Amount of precipitation (l/m ²)
January	28.2
February	12.2
March	84.0
April	9.1
May	35.3
June	9.0
July	42.4

The analysis of the average precipitation recorded in the Black Crișul Meadow during the period January–July 2025 shows an uneven distribution of rainfall, with alternation between months with abundant precipitation and months with deficits.

The winter months received a moderate amount of rainfall, with 28.2 mm in January and 12.2 mm in February, values that allowed a slight recharge of soil water reserves but remained below the long-term average for this period. In March (84.0 mm), a significant peak

in precipitation was recorded, contributing to the restoration of soil moisture before the sowing campaign and creating favorable conditions for seed germination.

In contrast, April (9.1 mm) and June (9.0 mm) were dry months, with a pronounced precipitation deficit. May (35.3 mm) brought a slight improvement in the water regime, while July (42.4 mm) partially compensated for the lack of water in the preceding months.

Overall, 2025 was characterized by a deficient and uneven rainfall regime, with periods of drought alternating with episodes of heavy rainfall. This uneven distribution of precipitation played an important role in differentiating yields according to sowing time, affecting both germination and the vegetative growth dynamics of sweet corn.

The study used the sweet corn hybrid Dessert R78, a semi-early variety notable for a growing period approximately 8 days longer than the Dessert R70 hybrid, which it replaces in the recommended crop portfolio. The hybrid is suitable for sowing from mid-April to early June and is adapted to the climatic conditions of the lowland area.

Figure 1. Dessert R78

The plants are semi-tall, morphologically well-balanced, with cobs approximately 21 cm long, positioned at medium height on the stem, and with 16–18 rows of kernels. The kernels are deep, intensely golden-yellow, with a high sugar content, giving the hybrid superior taste quality.

Dessert R78 exhibits genetic resistance to the Maize Dwarf Mosaic Virus (MDMV), a trait that contributes to production stability under biotic stress. Due to its adaptability and high yield potential, the hybrid is recommended both for fresh consumption and for industrial processing.

The experiments were conducted on a field organized into 8 plots, each covering 1 a (5 m width × 20 m length). To evaluate the effect of different fertilization strategies on the crop, four fertilization variants were applied, sown in two different periods as follows:

V1 (Control) – unfertilized crop, used as a reference for evaluating the effect of applied treatments.

V2 (Organic fertilization) – application of compost before sowing at a rate of 30 t/ha, to improve soil structure and increase nutrient availability.

V3 (Complex mineral fertilization) – application of NPK fertilizer at 300 kg/ha, providing essential macroelements for plant development.

V4 (Complex mineral fertilization with micronutrients) – application of NPK fertilizer at 300 kg/ha, supplemented with micronutrients (Zn, B, Fe, Mn) at 30 kg/ha, aimed at optimizing nutrient uptake, supporting plant physiological processes, increasing yield potential, and improving crop quality.

The crop was sown in two distinct periods to assess the influence of sowing time on the development and yield of sweet corn:

First sowing period – performed when the soil reached the optimal sowing temperature, serving as the reference condition for normal and uniform crop development.

Second sowing period – performed 14 days after the soil reached the optimal temperature, to analyze the effects of delayed sowing on growth, development, and productivity.

By combining the two sowing periods with the four fertilization variants, the experiment included a total of 8 experimental plots, each monitored for growth, development, and yield characteristics.

The experiment was organized using the Latin rectangle method, ensuring that each variant was applied in a manner that controlled for spatial variability of soil and environmental conditions. This experimental design allowed for a rigorous evaluation of the treatments' effects on crop performance.

For field preparation, standard agrotechnical practices specific to the area were applied. The land was plowed in autumn, followed by two discing operations in spring. Before sowing, a harrowing operation was performed to create a uniform, well-leveled seedbed, favorable for rapid and uniform plant emergence.

Sowing was carried out at a density of 55,000 seeds/ha, considered optimal for semi-early sweet corn hybrids. Fertilization was applied manually according to the experimental variant, as described above (control, organic, complex mineral, complex mineral with micronutrients).

Sweet corn harvesting was performed manually when the plants reached the milk-

dough stage, corresponding to the optimal stage for cob utilization. Cobs from each experimental plot were harvested and weighed, and the data were compiled to calculate the average yield per hectare (t/ha).

The results were statistically processed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the significance of differences between the variants.

Table.3

Calculation of the mean, differences, and percentage variation

Variant	Sowing time I	Sowing time II	Average (kg/ha)	Difference from control
V1	10490	9430	9960	-
V2	17520	16620	17070	71,3%
V3	21040	20100	20570	106,5%
V4	23200	22380	22790	128,8%

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that the effect of fertilization on sweet corn yield was highly statistically significant ($F = 144.29$; $p < 0.001$). The interaction between sowing time and fertilization was not significant. The highest yields were obtained in variant V4 (NPK + micronutrients), with 22.79 t/ha, followed by V3 (NPK) – 20.57 t/ha. The results confirm the importance of balanced fertilization and the selection of the optimal sowing time for maximizing the yield of the Dessert R78 hybrid under the conditions of the Black Crişul Meadow.

CONCLUSION

The sweet corn hybrid Dessert R78 stood out for its high yield potential, demonstrating good adaptability to the pedoclimatic conditions of the Black Crişul Meadow area.

The sowing time had a significant influence on yield, with the highest values obtained from early sowing (Sowing Time I), while delayed sowing (Sowing Time II) resulted in an average reduction of 4–6%.

Fertilization had a decisive effect on yield, with the differences between variants being highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The V4 variant (NPK + micronutrients) recorded the highest yield, 22.79 t/ha, exceeding the control (V1) by 128.8%, followed by V3 (NPK) with 20.57 t/ha.

The interaction between sowing time and fertilization variant was not significant, indicating the stability of the Dessert R78

hybrid's yield in relation to variations in sowing time.

The results confirm that for the Dessert R78 hybrid, the optimal sowing time is when the soil temperature reaches 12°C, and the application of a complex NPK fertilization supplemented with micronutrients ensures the maximum utilization of the hybrid's biological potential.

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VEGETATIVE RESPONSE OF *AMELANCHIER ALNIFOLIA* TO SPRING PRUNING UNDER TEMPERATE CONDITIONS: HORTICULTURAL IMPLICATIONS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study investigates the vegetative response of *Amelanchier alnifolia* Nutt. to spring pruning under temperate continental conditions in western Romania. Sixty mature plants (15 years old) were monitored during the 2025 growing season following uniform renewal pruning aimed at removing senescent and poorly positioned shoots. The experimental design focused on key vegetative parameters: shoot density, basal diameter, shoot length, and emission zone. Measurements were performed using precision horticultural tools, and data were analyzed statistically in Python using descriptive indicators and Pearson correlation coefficients.

Results revealed a strong regenerative capacity, with an average of 7.8 shoots per plant (range: 3–12; SD = 2.21) and mean shoot length of 46.1 cm (range: 21.4–63.7 cm; SD = 9.54). These findings indicate efficient activation of latent buds and redistribution of assimilates toward renewal shoots. Correlation analysis ($r = 0.62$, $p < 0.01$) demonstrated a positive relationship between shoot number and elongation vigor, confirming a coordinated regenerative mechanism. This trend aligns with previous reports on vegetative plasticity in Rosaceae species and highlights the adaptability of *A. alnifolia* to managed horticultural systems.

The integration of pruning practices and row orientation emerges as a critical strategy for optimizing canopy architecture, light interception, and fruit quality in sustainable orchards. Compared to other fruit-bearing shrubs, *A. alnifolia* exhibits a balanced ratio between regeneration and productivity, making it suitable for low-input systems. Overall, the study provides a robust scientific basis for refining canopy management and yield optimization strategies in emerging *Amelanchier alnifolia* plantations across temperate Europe.

Keywords: *Amelanchier alnifolia*, pruning, vegetative vigor, shoot performance, horticulture
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INTRODUCTION

The diversification of perennial fruit crops in Europe has generated an increased interest in species capable of combining agronomic performance, ecological adaptability and high-value fruit production. Among them, *Amelanchier alnifolia* Nutt. (Saskatoon berry) stands out for its low temperature tolerance, drought resistance, and nutraceutical properties of the fruit (Mihovilović et al., 2020; Rop et al., 2012; Pluta, 2015).

Native to the Canadian prairie provinces, this species has considerable potential for integration into multifunctional agroforestry systems, contributing to increasing biodiversity and promoting agricultural sustainability (Budău et al., 2023; Musselman et al., 2014). Belonging to the Rosaceae family, *A. alnifolia* has a shrub habit, and fruiting is predominantly carried out on shoots of one year or older. In North America, the crop is well established commercially, and in Europe it is considered emerging for horticulture (Bieniek et al., 2019).

Fruits are rich in phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and anthocyanins, giving them antioxidant properties and health benefits (Rop et al., 2013; Gunawardana et al., 2016; Budău et al., 2022). In Romania, adaptation studies have shown high survival rates and vigorous vegetative development in the establishment phase (Budău, 2017), and yield research has confirmed productive performance under local pedoclimatic conditions (Budău & Enescu, 2022).

In addition to the agronomic benefits, *Amelanchier alnifolia* has significant economic and nutritional relevance. Its fruits are appreciated in the food industry for their high antioxidant content and potential for use in functional products, which responds to the growing demand for healthy food in Europe. The integration of this species into agroforestry systems contributes to reducing climate risks and diversifying farmers' incomes, which are essential for the transition to sustainable agriculture. Another feature is suitability to varied soils and tolerance to water stress, which recommends it for areas with limited water

resources, strengthening its role in agricultural resilience strategies.

Vegetative growth in *A. alnifolia* determines the architecture of the canopy, the efficiency of light interception and the potential for long-term fruiting. Pruning interventions influence vegetative renewal by eliminating apical dominance, activating dormant buds, and redistributing assimilated buds (Zayan et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2010). Excessive vegetative vigor can compromise fruit quality and ripening uniformity, while insufficient renewal accelerates canopy senescence.

Despite the growing interest in this species, information on the behavior of shoots after pruning under European conditions is limited. The present study aims to quantify the growth parameters of vegetative shoots after spring pruning and interpret their implications for sustainable canopy management.

Beyond the agronomic and ecological benefits, *Amelanchier alnifolia* holds significant potential for economic diversification and functional food production. The species' adaptability to the temperate continental climate and its resilience to abiotic stressors positions it as a valuable element in climate-smart agriculture strategies. Its integration into agroforestry systems not only increases biodiversity but also contributes to carbon sequestration and improved soil health, in line with the European Union's sustainability objectives. Additionally, the growing consumer demand for antioxidant-rich fruits highlights the importance of developing effective canopy management practices for this species. These considerations establish a solid basis for investigating the dynamics of vegetative growth under felling regimes, as a foundation for optimizing orchard performance and ensuring long-term viability in European horticulture.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research was conducted in the experimental plantation of *Amelanchier alnifolia* located at Bărzani Farm, Arad County, western Romania. The geographical coordinates are 46°29'12.6"N, 22°08'22.9"E (Plot 1, 0.11 ha) and 46°28'56.6"N, 22°07'04.1"E (Plot 2, 0.63 ha), at an altitude of approximately 180 m (Budău & Enescu, 2022). The area is characterized by a temperate continental climate, with an average annual temperature of 10.3 °C, mean precipitation of 560–580 mm, and clay-illuvial chernozem soils with a pH of 6.4–

6.8. The plantation was established using a spacing scheme of 3 m between rows × 1 m between plants, totaling 367 individuals in Plot 1 and 2,467 in Plot 2.

The choice of the experimental location was based on the pedoclimatic representativeness for western Romania, an area characterized by thermal variability and periods of water deficit. These conditions allow the assessment of the vegetative plasticity of the species in scenarios similar to those encountered in European commercial orchards. The instruments used were selected for the accuracy of the measurements, and the statistical analysis in Python ensures the reproducibility and transparency of data processing, according to international horticultural research standards.

Figure 1. Measurements made with horticultural tape

During the 2025 growing season, 60 mature plants (15 years old) were selected from Plot 1. In spring 2025, a uniform renewal pruning was applied, removing senescent shoots and those with inadequate positioning. The plantation was not irrigated. For each plant, the following parameters were recorded:

- Total number of new shoots per plant.
- Basal diameter (mm).
- Shoot length (cm).
- Emission zone (%).

Measurements were performed using a horticultural tape (precision ± 0.5 mm) and a Mitutoyo CD-6' ASX digital caliper (Figure 1).

Statistical analyses were conducted in Python 3.12 using the packages pandas, scipy, matplotlib, and seaborn. Descriptive indicators were calculated (mean, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, coefficient of variation – CV%). Correlations among parameters were determined using Pearson's coefficient (r), with significance levels at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$ (Table 1).

Table 1.
Descriptive statistics of vegetative parameters in *Amelanchier alnifolia* (2025)

Parameter	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	CV (%)
Shoots per plant	7.8	8	3	12	2.21	28.3
Shoot length (cm)	46.1	45.0	21.4	63.7	9.54	20.7

The choice of experimental methodology was based on the need to obtain reproducible and internationally comparable data. The use of high-precision measuring instruments, such as the digital shaker and horticultural tape recorder, ensures the accuracy of the vegetative parameters analyzed.

In addition, the integration of statistical analysis into the Python environment provides transparency and flexibility in data processing, complying with modern horticultural research standards.

This approach allows not only the correct interpretation of biological variability, but also the development of predictive models applicable in orchard management.

By combining experimental rigor with advanced digital tools, the study creates the premises for expanding research towards assessing the impact of agroecological practices on vegetative performance and fruit quality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of the results highlights the significant impact of spring pruning on the vegetative dynamics of *Amelanchier alnifolia*. This section presents the interpretation of the measured parameters, statistical correlations,

and horticultural implications of observed regenerative behavior.

Understanding these mechanisms is essential for optimizing canopy architecture and developing sustainable orchard management strategies.

The results are discussed in relation to literature, to highlight the convergences and differences with other species of the Rosaceae family, as well as their relevance in the context of European horticulture.

The vegetative response of *Amelanchier alnifolia* demonstrated a strong regenerative capacity following spring pruning. The mean shoot density was 7.8 shoots per plant (SD = 2.21), with a range of 3–12 shoots per plant, confirming the activation of both latent axillary and adventitious buds.

Comparable compensatory dynamics have been reported in other perennial mixed-fruit shrubs, where pruning modifies resource allocation and hormonal gradients.

Shoot elongation exhibited considerable variability, ranging from 21.4 cm to 63.7 cm, with an average of 46.1 cm (SD = 9.54). This vigorous growth suggests efficient mobilization of assimilates toward renewal shoots, consistent with patterns described in the Saskatoon Berry Production Manual (2013), which attributes this behavior to the release of apical dominance and improved light penetration within the canopy.

Correlation analysis ($r = 0.62$, $p < 0.01$) revealed a positive association between shoot number and maximum shoot length (Figure 2), indicating that plants with a higher shoot density tend to exhibit greater elongation vigor.

This trend reflects a coordinated regenerative mechanism through which *A. alnifolia* redistributes assimilates among multiple growth axes while maintaining shoot vigor.

Similar correlations have been documented in other Rosaceae species, where balanced pruning promotes both shoot density and elongation potential (Pluta, 2015). These findings emphasize the physiological plasticity of *A. alnifolia*, supporting its adaptability to managed horticultural systems.

Looking ahead, future research should explore the combined impact of organic pruning and fertilization on vegetative dynamics and fruit quality, as well as the adaptation of mechanized harvesting technologies for this species. Also, the integration of phenological data into predictive models can support

management decisions in the context of climate change, strengthening the position of *Amelanchier alnifolia* as a strategic species for European horticulture.

Figure 2. **Correlation between the number of shoots and the maximum shoot height**

The scatter plot (Figure 2) illustrates the relationship between the number of shoots per plant and their maximum height (cm) following the spring pruning (2025). The observed positive trend indicates an efficient internal allocation of resources within the canopy and confirms the regenerative plasticity of the species under the temperate continental climate of western Romania.

The obtained shoot density aligns with horticultural objectives aiming to maintain open canopy structures, which are favorable for light interception and fruit set.

Excessive shoot density in fruit-bearing shrubs can inhibit flowering through shade-induced suppression, while moderate densities support renewal and reproductive balance. These findings are consistent with previous acclimatization trials conducted in Romania, where *A. alnifolia* demonstrated sustained vigor both during establishment and in mature production phases (Budău, 2017; Budău & Enescu, 2022).

Overall, the results support the hypothesis that spring pruning facilitates efficient vegetative renewal in *A. alnifolia*, and that the species' high regenerative plasticity enables adaptive canopy management strategies that promote long-term horticultural performance in European temperate environments.

These findings not only confirm the regenerative plasticity of *Amelanchier alnifolia* but also underline its strategic role in sustainable orchard management. Maintaining moderate shoot density and balanced elongation vigor ensures optimal canopy architecture, improving light interception and air circulation—key factors for fruit quality and disease prevention. From a practical perspective, these results provide actionable guidelines for growers aiming to integrate *A. alnifolia* into low-input systems while preserving productivity and ecological resilience. Future research should expand on these observations by assessing the combined effects of pruning intensity, organic fertilization, and mechanization on both vegetative dynamics and fruit yield. Additionally, incorporating phenological data into predictive models will enhance decision-making under climate variability, reinforcing the species' potential as a cornerstone for climate-smart horticulture in temperate Europe.

CONCLUSIONS

Integrating experimental findings with existing literature, it can be concluded that spring pruning facilitates balanced vegetative renewal without compromising the plant's reproductive potential, providing an adaptive management model for emerging *Amelanchier alnifolia* orchards in continental Europe (Bieniek et al., 2019; Kuzmina & Toropova, 2020). This integrated approach reinforces the need to calibrate pruning practices and row orientation to maximize light interception and natural ventilation, thereby improving fruit quality—critical parameters for ecological and sustainable berry production systems (Reinhart et al., 2006).

Amelanchier alnifolia demonstrates strong regenerative capacity following spring pruning, characterized by moderate shoot density and vigorous elongation, consistent with previous findings on the species' vegetative plasticity (Mihovilović et al., 2020; Budău & Enescu, 2022). Positive correlations between shoot number, maximum height, and basal diameter confirm a coordinated regenerative mechanism, where internal resource redistribution is stimulated by pruning.

Compared to other fruit-bearing shrubs, *A. alnifolia* exhibits a balanced ratio between

regeneration and productivity, making it suitable for low-input sustainable orchards (Musselman et al., 2014; Kumar et al., 2024). The integration of regular pruning and proper row orientation optimizes microclimatic conditions and fruit quality while reducing the incidence of fungal diseases (Gonzales et al., 2023).

Overall, these findings consolidate *Amelanchier alnifolia* as a promising horticultural species for temperate Europe, providing a solid scientific basis for refining canopy management and yield optimization strategies.

The results obtained confirm not only the vegetative plasticity of the *Amelanchier alnifolia* species, but also its strategic potential for the development of sustainable orchards in the temperate zones of Europe. The implementation of spring pruning, correlated with the optimal orientation of the rows, contributes to the improvement of the microclimate, the reduction of disease pressure and the increase of fruit quality. Beyond horticultural aspects, these findings have economic and ecological implications, supporting the integration of the species into multifunctional agroforestry systems. Future research should explore the interaction between cutting regimes, organic fertilization and adaptation of mechanized harvesting technologies, as well as the use of predictive models based on phenological data to optimize management decisions. Thus, *Amelanchier alnifolia* is emerging as a promising crop, capable of responding to climatic challenges and market requirements for functional food products.

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PHYTOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIOXIDANT POTENTIAL OF *VACCINIUM MYRTILLUS L.* A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LEAVES AND FRUITS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Bilberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus L.*) is a medicinally valuable shrub whose leaves (*Myrtilli folium*) and fruits (*Myrtilli fructus*) are rich sources of bioactive compounds. This study aimed to comparatively evaluate the phytochemical composition and antioxidant potential of ethanolic extracts obtained from leaves and fruits. Plant material was collected from spontaneous flora in Bihor County, Romania, and subjected to Soxhlet extraction. Total phenolic and flavonoid contents were quantified using the Folin–Ciocalteu and aluminum chloride colorimetric methods, respectively, while antioxidant activity was assessed via DPPH radical scavenging assay. The results indicated that leaf extracts contained a significantly higher total phenolic content (119.64 ± 1.014 mg GAE/g) and total flavonoid content (19.89 ± 0.195 mg QE/g) compared to fruit extracts (34.12 ± 0.895 mg GAE/g and 11.76 ± 0.180 mg QE/g, respectively). Correspondingly, DPPH radical scavenging activity was higher in leaves ($76.56 \pm 0.505\%$) than in fruits ($61.74 \pm 0.391\%$). These findings align with literature data and underscore the superior bioactive potential of leaves. The observed differences between organs reflect organ-specific metabolic allocation, with leaves likely accumulating phenolics for protection against environmental stress, while fruits prioritize compounds associated with reproductive functions. The study highlights *Vaccinium myrtillus* leaves as a promising source of natural antioxidants, with potential applications in nutraceuticals, functional foods, and therapeutic interventions targeting oxidative stress-related disorders.

Keywords: bilberry, ethanolic extract, polyphenol content, flavonoids, DPPH radical scavenging

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INTRODUCTION

Vaccinium myrtillus L. (*Ericaceae*), commonly known as bilberry, is a subfruticose shrub widely distributed in the mountainous regions of Europe, from the lower limits of coniferous forests up to alpine zones, where it forms dense clusters called bilberry patches. Both the leaves (*Myrtilli folium*) and the fruits (*Myrtilli fructus*) have been traditionally valued for their medicinal properties, including antidiabetic, hypolipidemic, antibacterial, antiviral, anticancer, and anti-inflammatory effects (Brasanac-Vukanovic et al., 2018; Chan and Tomlinson, 2020; Pires et al., 2020).

Previous studies have shown that the bioactivity of bilberry extracts is largely attributed to their polyphenolic content. In leaves, phenolic acids such as chlorogenic acid, caffeic and quinic acid derivatives, and feruloylquinic acid predominate, whereas fruits are especially rich in flavonoids, particularly anthocyanins, responsible for their red, blue, and violet pigmentation (Popović et al., 2016; Scalzo et al., 2015).

The antioxidant potential of bilberry extracts has been closely correlated with their phytochemical profile, with leaf extracts often demonstrating higher radical-scavenging activity than fruit extracts from the same species. This activity has been linked to protective effects against oxidative stress-related disorders, improvement of lipid profiles, and vascular health through endothelial stabilization and enhanced collagen and mucopolysaccharide biosynthesis in capillaries (Bljajić et al., 2017; Faleva et al., 2024).

The present study aims to comparatively evaluate the antioxidant potential of leaf and fruit extracts of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.*, using total phenolic and flavonoid content as key indicators of bioactivity, thereby providing a comprehensive insight into their functional relevance and therapeutic potential.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

PLANT MATERIAL

Specimens of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* were collected from natural habitats in Ponoară village, Bratca commune, Bihor County,

Romania (46.891488, 22.682169), an unpolluted area. Leaves were harvested during dry weather in May 2022 using scissors, selecting only healthy, non-flowering branches, while fully ripened fruits were collected manually in July 2022. Only healthy and clean plant material was retained. A pressed voucher specimen is preserved in the Herbarium of the Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutical Botany (code UOP 05.710).

REAGENTS AND EQUIPMENT

Analytical grade reagents were employed throughout the study, including ethanol (Chimreactiv, Romania), distilled water, gallic acid (Silver Chemicals, Romania), quercetin (Silver Chemicals, Romania), DPPH (2, 2 - diphenyl - 1 - picrylhydrazyl, Merck, Germany), Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (Merck, Germany), sodium carbonate (Chimreactiv, Romania), sodium nitrite (Chimreactiv, Romania), aluminum chloride (Merck, Germany), and sodium hydroxide (Chimreactiv, Romania). Extraction and concentration procedures were performed using a rotary evaporator Hei-VAP Advantage (Heidolph, Germany), and absorbance measurements were conducted with a UV-VIS spectrophotometer PG Instruments T70+ (UK).

METHODS

Microscopy: Samples of stem, leaf, and fruit from *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* were examined using an optical microscope (Optika B-380 Series, Italy) with 10× and 40× objectives. Observations focused on the structural characteristics of each organ to document diagnostic features relevant for identification and comparative analysis.

Extraction: Dried leaf and fruit samples of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* were finely ground to enhance the efficiency of bioactive compound extraction. Ten grams of *Myrtilli folium* were subjected to Soxhlet extraction with ethanol for 4 hours (10 cycles), while an equal amount of *Myrtilli fructus* underwent extraction for 3 hours (11 cycles). The resulting extracts were concentrated using a Hei-VAP Advantage rotary evaporator (Heidolph, Germany) at 40°C, 80 rpm, and 200 atm until a minimal residue remained. Each concentrated extract was subsequently reconstituted in 10 mL of ethanol for further analyses.

Total Phenolic Content: The total phenolic content of ethanolic extracts was measured using the Folin-Ciocalteu method.

Extracts (0.3 mL) were mixed with 1.2 mL distilled water and 0.45 mL Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, left in the dark for 10 minutes, then 1.5 mL 20% sodium carbonate was added. After 60 minutes at room temperature, absorbance was recorded at 765 nm (Elferjane et al., 2024). A blank was prepared with ethanol, and all determinations were performed in triplicate. Quantification was based on a gallic acid calibration curve (10–50 mg/mL).

Total Flavonoid Content: Flavonoid content was assessed using the aluminum chloride colorimetric method. A volume of 1 mL extract was mixed with 4 mL distilled water and 0.3 mL 5% NaNO₂, allowed to react in the dark for 5 minutes, followed by the addition of 0.3 mL 10% AlCl₃ for 6 minutes. Subsequently, 2 mL 1 M NaOH was added, and the final volume adjusted to 10 mL with distilled water. Absorbance was recorded at 510 nm against a blank containing ethanol. Measurements were carried out in triplicate, and quercetin (2–10 mg/mL) was used for calibration (Altiok et al., 2022).

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay: Antioxidant activity was assessed using a 0.1 mM DPPH solution. Extracts (0.5 mL) were mixed with 3 mL DPPH solution and incubated in the dark for 30 minutes. A blank containing ethanol instead of extract was used. Absorbance was recorded at 517 nm, and the percentage of radical scavenging was calculated. All determinations were performed in triplicate (Ciulca et al., 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Microscopic analysis of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* stem sections reveals the organization of protective, vascular, and mechanical tissues, as illustrated in Figure 1. The stem is composed of the epidermis, cortical parenchyma, and central cylinder. The epidermis consists of a single layer of small, living cells with tightly appressed, slightly convex, cutinized walls. Beneath it, the cortical parenchyma comprises 5–6 layers of thin-walled cells, some containing chloroplasts. The central cylinder, or stele, includes the pericycle, collateral vascular bundles, and medullary parenchyma. Vascular bundles are closed and collateral, with xylem oriented inward and phloem outward, facilitating the transport of sap. Medullary parenchyma occupies the central region and consists of large, thin-walled cells arranged in a rosette.

Figure 1. Transverse section of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* stem.

A – 1-epidermis, 2-cortex, 3-parenchymatous tissue, 4-collateral vascular bundles accompanied by collenchyma arcs, 5-medullary parenchyma (10X); B– rib with collenchymatous tissue (40X)

Microscopic analysis of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* leaves revealed a unistratified adaxial and abaxial epidermis and a bifacial mesophyll composed of palisade and spongy parenchyma. The palisade parenchyma contains tightly packed, chloroplast-rich cells, while the

spongy parenchyma has loosely arranged cells with large intercellular spaces connected to substomatal chambers. The main vein includes a collateral vascular bundle surrounded by collenchyma, providing mechanical support and transport.

Figure 2. Transverse section of *Vaccinium myrtillus leaf*:

A – 1: adaxial (upper) epidermis, 2: palisade parenchyma, 3: spongy parenchyma, 4: abaxial (lower) epidermis (10×); B – collateral vascular bundle (40×)

Examination of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* fruit sections highlights the diagnostic features of the pericarp and seed coat. The exocarp contains scattered sclereids with thick, lignified

walls, contributing to the fruit's firm texture, while parenchyma cells are present to store water and nutrients. These anatomical details are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Microscopic examination of *Vaccinium myrtillus L.* fruits

The total phenolic content (TPC) of ethanolic extracts obtained from *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. leaves and fruits was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu spectrophotometric method. The calibration curve for gallic acid showed excellent linearity across the tested concentration range, described by the regression equation $Y = 0.007X + 0.0671$ ($R^2 = 0.9918$). As presented in Table 1, the ethanolic extract of *Myrtilli folium* exhibited a mean total phenolic concentration of 119.64 ± 1.01 mg

GAE/g dry extract, whereas the extract obtained from *Myrtilli fructus* recorded a mean value of 34.12 ± 0.89 mg GAE/g dry extract. When compared to literature data, the obtained results are in good agreement with previously reported ranges for *Vaccinium myrtillus* species, which indicate values between 107.79 and 173.12 mg GAE/g for leaf extracts and 20.79 to 41.32 mg GAE/g for fruit extract (Bujor et al, 2016; Ștefănescu et al, 2020; Tian et al, 2018).

Table 1

Total phenolic content in ethanolic extracts of *Myrtilli folium* and *fructus*

Sample	Sample absorbance measured at 765 nm	Sample concentration (mg GAE/g dry extract)	Mean concentration (mg GAE/g dry extract) \pm SD
Ethanolic extract of <i>Myrtilli folium</i>	0,906	119,84	119,64 \pm 1,014
	0,897	118,55	
	0,911	120,55	
Ethanolic extract of <i>Myrtilli fructus</i>	0,308	34,41	34,12 \pm 0,895
	0,299	33,12	
	0,311	34,84	

Quantification of total flavonoids in the ethanolic extracts of *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. was achieved using the aluminum chloride colorimetric assay. The calibration curve for quercetin demonstrated good linearity within the tested range, expressed by the regression equation $Y = 0.033X + 0.1418$ ($R^2 = 0.9873$). According to the results summarized in Table 2, the leaf extract (*Myrtilli folium*) exhibited a

mean flavonoid content of 19.89 ± 0.20 mg QE/g dry extract, while the fruit extract (*Myrtilli fructus*) contained 11.76 ± 0.18 mg QE/g dry extract. These values align with previously reported data for *Vaccinium myrtillus*, which indicate a concentration range of 12.05–25.92 mg QE/g for leaves and 3.88–14.64 mg QE/g for fruits (Neamtu et al., 2020; Ziemiańska et al., 2021).

Table 2

Total flavonoid content in ethanolic extracts of *Myrtilli folium* and *fructus*

Sample	Sample absorbance measured at 765 nm	Sample concentration (mg QE/1 g dry extract)	Mean concentration (mg QE/g dry extract) \pm SD
Ethanolic extract of <i>Myrtilli folium</i>	0,798	19,88	19,89 \pm 0,195
	0,805	20,09	
	0,792	19,70	
Ethanolic extract of <i>Myrtilli fructus</i>	0,530	11,76	11,76 \pm 0,180
	0,524	11,58	
	0,536	11,94	

The DPPH radical scavenging activity of ethanolic extracts of *Myrtilli folium* and *Myrtilli fructus* was assessed, and the mean inhibition percentages are presented in Table 3. The ethanolic extract of *Myrtilli folium* demonstrated a high DPPH radical scavenging activity ($76.56 \pm 0.51\%$), consistent with

previously reported ranges of 73.11–91.80% for leaf extracts. The fruit extract exhibited moderate activity ($61.74 \pm 0.39\%$), which aligns with literature values for bilberry fruits, ranging between 50.87–78.03% (Routray and Orsat, 2014).

Table 3

DPPH radical scavenging activity of ethanolic extracts of *Myrtilli folium* and *fructus*

Sample	Blank absorbance	Sample absorbance	Inhibition %	Mean inhibition % \pm SD
Ethanolic extract of <i>Myrtilli folium</i>	0,895	0,210	76,53	76,56 \pm 0,505
		0,205	77,09	
		0,214	76,08	
Ethanolic extract of <i>Myrtilli fructus</i>	0,895	0,346	61,34	61,74 \pm 0,391
		0,339	62,12	
		0,342	61,78	

CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation of ethanolic extracts from *Myrtilli folium* and *Myrtilli fructus* demonstrates that both plant organs possess significant bioactive potential, with leaves exhibiting markedly higher concentrations of phenolic and flavonoid compounds, as well as superior antioxidant activity. Specifically, *Myrtilli folium*

displayed a total phenolic content of 119.64 ± 1.014 mg GAE/g dry plant material, a total flavonoid content of 19.89 ± 0.195 mg QE/g dry plant material, and DPPH radical scavenging activity of $76.56 \pm 0.505\%$, all consistent with previously reported ranges in the literature. In contrast, *Myrtilli fructus* presented lower but nonetheless appreciable values: 34.12 ± 0.895 mg GAE/g total phenolics, 11.76 ± 0.180 mg QE/g total flavonoids, and $61.74 \pm 0.391\%$ DPPH inhibition, in line with prior studies.

Comparative analysis indicated that the leaf extract contained 71.48% more phenolics and 40.87% more flavonoids than the fruit extract, corresponding to a 19.5% higher antioxidant capacity. These results underscore the prominent potential of bilberry leaves as a rich source of natural antioxidants, supporting their prospective application in nutraceutical and functional food development, as well as in pharmacological interventions targeting oxidative stress-associated conditions.

Overall, the differential accumulation of bioactive compounds between leaves and fruits highlights the organ-specific metabolic allocation and ecological adaptation of *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. The elevated phenolic content in leaves likely reflects a protective strategy against environmental stressors, including ultraviolet radiation and pathogen attack, whereas the phytochemical profile of fruits primarily supports reproductive functions.

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INFLUENCE OF CULTIVAR, GRAFTING, AND FERTILIZATION REGIME ON THE BIOACTIVE COMPOUND PROFILE OF EGGPLANT FRUITS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

*Eggplant represents an important vegetable crop from a nutritional point of view, mainly due to its elevated antioxidant potential associated with a high phenolic content. In this research, it was investigated how two commercial cultivars, Mirval F1 and Black Pearl F1, together with grafting practice and fertilization strategy, shape the accumulation of bioactive compounds and the antioxidant behavior of the fruits. A factorial field experiment was established using ungrafted plants or plants grafted onto the commercial rootstock Rezistar F1 and the wild species *Solanum sisymbriifolium*, under four fertilization variants, unfertilized control, Micoseed® biofertilizer, organic fertilizer and conventional chemical fertilizer. Fruit samples were analyzed for total polyphenols, chlorophyll a and b, lycopene, tannins and antioxidant activity by ABTS and DPPH methods. The results indicated that Mirval F1 accumulated significantly higher concentrations of polyphenols and lycopene compared to Black Pearl F1. Ungrafted plants showed the highest pigment contents, while grafting onto *S. sisymbriifolium* clearly improved the antioxidant capacity. Fertilization did not significantly modify total polyphenol content, but both chemical fertilization and the lack of fertilization stimulated chlorophyll and lycopene accumulation more than the biofertilizer. The strongest DPPH activity was observed in unfertilized plants, suggesting that a moderate stress condition may activate antioxidant defenses. Overall, Mirval F1 combined with vigorous rootstocks and balanced nutrition generated fruits with the most pronounced antioxidant profile. These data highlight the combined impact of genotype, grafting and fertilization on eggplant quality and offer practical directions for producing biofortified fruits with enhanced functional value.*

Keywords: eggplant, grafting, fertilization, bioactive compounds, antioxidant activity

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INTRODUCTION

Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) is a widely consumed vegetable appreciated for its nutritional value and its high content of antioxidant compounds, mainly phenolics (Mady et al., 2025), substances that give eggplant functional food properties through their capacity to reduce oxidative stress. Strong differences exist among cultivars, as dark purple or black skinned fruits usually contain higher levels of phenolics and show stronger antioxidant activity than white types. Recent comparative studies confirm that the genetic background largely determines the concentration of phenolics, flavonoids and anthocyanins, and therefore the overall antioxidant potential of the fruit (Kim et al., 2025; Gozel et al., 2025; Josef et al., 2025).

Beyond varietal choice, grafting has become an important horticultural tool for improving both plant performance and fruit quality. Grafting onto vigorous or disease resistant rootstocks, such as *Solanum torvum* or *S. sisymbriifolium*, enhances tolerance to stress and often increases yield. Several studies also report higher fruit phenolic content in grafted plants (Lal et al., 2025; Ashraf et al., 2025). For example, Gisbert et al. observed about a 31 percent increase in phenolics after grafting, while other authors confirmed similar trends depending on the rootstock used (Gisbert et al., 2011). Still, grafting effects are not always consistent, since some combinations may reduce phenolic accumulation, showing that careful rootstock selection is essential for improving fruit quality and not only yield.

Nutrient management is a major factor controlling the phytochemical profile of

eggplant. As a crop with high nutrient demand, eggplant reacts strongly to fertilization type, whether mineral, organic or biological. Moderate nutrient limitation or organic inputs can stimulate phenolic synthesis as part of a defense response, while excessive fertilization often favors growth at the expense of antioxidant compounds (Thingujam et al., 2020). Studies on tomato and other vegetables have shown higher phenolic levels under reduced nitrogen or organic fertilization, supporting this concept (González et al., 2022; Benard et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2024). In contrast, abundant mineral nutrition tends to dilute secondary metabolites (Tang et al., 2024). Biostimulants and microbial inoculants are also of interest, since they can improve nutrient uptake and trigger mild stress responses that influence antioxidant accumulation, though results are not always uniform.

Still, only limited information is available on how cultivar, grafting and fertilization together shape eggplant fruit quality. In this context, all three factors, and their interaction, strongly affect phenolics, pigments and tannins, and therefore antioxidant capacity. Vigorous hybrids such as Mirval F1 may accumulate more bioactive compounds than darker but less productive types like Black Pearl F1, while grafting and sustainable fertilization could further modify this response. The present study was designed to evaluate these combined effects and to identify cultivar, rootstock and fertilizer combinations able to produce fruits with higher functional value, which is not always simple in practice.

MATERIALS AND METHODES

The study was carried out during one vegetation season at the V. Adamachi Experimental Farm of the University of Life Sciences in Iași, Romania, on a typical chernozem soil. Two commercial eggplant hybrids, Mirval F1 and Black Pearl F1, were selected as scion material because of their contrasting fruit traits and high relevance for current production systems. Seedlings were produced under greenhouse conditions, and when they reached the stage of 4–5 true leaves, part of the plants from each cultivar was subjected to grafting. Three propagation variants were considered: ungrafted plants used as self rooted controls, plants grafted onto the commercial tomato rootstock Rezistar F1, known for its strong vigor and disease tolerance, and plants grafted onto the wild

species *Solanum sisymbriifolium*, recognized for its resistance to soil borne pathogens such as Verticillium and bacterial wilt, as well as for its potential to enhance plant performance. Grafting was performed using the splice grafting technique, and the grafted seedlings were maintained under high humidity conditions for 7 to 10 days to allow proper healing of the graft union.

After the grafts were fully established, both grafted and ungrafted plants were transplanted to the open field in late spring, around mid May, using a planting distance of 70 cm between plants and 80 cm between rows. The experiment was organized following a split plot factorial design with three experimental factors, cultivar, grafting or rootstock type, and fertilization regime. Each combination of treatments was replicated three times, with individual plots consisting of 15 to 20 plants. Throughout the growing period, standard agrotechnical practices specific for eggplant were applied, and pest control was conducted according to integrated pest management recommendations, so that additional uncontrolled stress was kept as low as possible.

Fertilization Treatments

Four distinct fertilization strategies were implemented at sub plot level. The unfertilized control received no nutrient input or soil amendment and was used as a reference variant, reflecting a condition of moderate nutritional limitation. The biological fertilization treatment consisted of the commercial mycorrhizal product Micoseed® MB, which contains arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi from the genus *Glomus*, together with other beneficial microorganisms such as *Beauveria*, *Metarhizium* and *Trichoderma*. This treatment was intended to stimulate nutrient uptake through natural symbiosis and to enhance soil biological processes. Micoseed was incorporated into the soil at planting at a rate of about 30 kg per hectare and reapplied at the beginning of fruit set, using the same dose, in accordance with the producer recommendations, so that root colonization could be ensured.

The organic fertilization program was based on a composted organic fertilizer combined with a microbial biostimulant, Nutryaction®. The organic product was applied twice during mid season, reaching a cumulative rate close to 800 kg per hectare, and it was supplemented through fertigation with the biostimulant

solution in order to activate rhizosphere microbial activity. These organic inputs provided nutrients in a gradual release form and supported soil biological balance, which is in line with principles of sustainable agriculture. The chemical fertilization variant followed a conventional high input mineral regime based on balanced NPK fertilizers from the Nutrispore® range. A total dose of approximately 800 kg per hectare of compound fertilizer was divided into three applications, half before planting, followed by two additional applications at early fruiting and mid fruit set. The formulations supplied both macroelements such as nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and magnesium, as well as microelements including boron, iron, manganese and zinc, all in readily available forms. This variant was designed to represent an intensive nutrition strategy aimed mainly at maximizing vegetative growth and yield, even if sometimes quality traits can be affected.

Data Collection and Chemical Analyses

Fruits were harvested at commercial maturity from each experimental plot during the main harvest period. For every treatment, a mixed sample of five to six fruits per replicate was collected and immediately transported to the laboratory. All biochemical analyses were performed on fresh material. After homogenizing the whole fruit pulp including the peel, several chemical determinations were carried out.

Total polyphenols were quantified using the Folin Ciocalteu method, with methanolic extracts measured at 725 nm and results expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents per 100 g fresh weight (Perez et al., 2023). Tannins were evaluated by a spectrophotometric method and expressed as mg tannic acid equivalents per 100 g fresh weight, mainly to follow treatment induced variation since eggplant is normally low in tannins. Chlorophyll a and b were extracted in acetone and measured at 645 and 663 nm, while lycopene was extracted with hexane acetone and read at 503 nm. All pigment contents were expressed as mg per 100 g fresh weight.

Antioxidant activity was assessed using ABTS and DPPH assays. Sample extracts were reacted with the respective radicals and absorbance decrease was recorded at 734 nm for ABTS and 517 nm for DPPH. Trolox served as reference standard and results were expressed as Trolox equivalents or relative scavenging activity.

These tests provided an integrated estimation of antioxidant potential linked mainly to phenolics and pigments.

Statistical Analysis

The experimental results were processed by analysis of variance adapted to the factorial experimental structure. A three factor ANOVA was applied in order to test the individual effects of cultivar, rootstock and fertilization, together with their combined interactions, on all analyzed parameters, namely total polyphenols, chlorophyll a and b, lycopene, tannins and antioxidant activity measured by ABTS and DPPH. Whenever significant interaction effects were detected, the data were further examined through simple effect analyses, by separating the influence of each factor for a clearer biological interpretation. The comparison of treatment means was performed using Tukey HSD test at a probability threshold of $p < 0.05$. Results are expressed as mean values \pm standard error, and different letters shown in the tables indicate statistically significant differences among variants. All statistical procedures was carried out using the SPSS software package version 21.0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Results on Antioxidant Activity (DPPH and ABTS), Total Polyphenol Content (TPC), and Tannin Content in Eggplant Fruits

The chemical composition of eggplant fruits obtained during the experiment, focusing on total polyphenols, tannins, chlorophyll a and b and lycopene as shown in Table 1, reflects key aspects of nutritional and functional quality. These compounds are directly linked to antioxidant activity, pigmentation and sensory traits. Evaluating how cultivar, rootstock and fertilization influence these parameters offers useful guidance for selecting cultivation variants that improve fruit quality, even if some responses were not perfectly uniform.

Table 1.
Chemical Composition of Eggplant Fruits in Relation to Cultivar, Rootstock, and Fertilization Regime

Cultivar	1	2	3	4	5
Mirval F1	2.97 ± 0.01	3.44 ± 0.07	4.74 ± 0.18	1.58 ± 0.05	0.11 ± 0.00
Black Pearl F1	2.15 ± 0.05	2.19 ± 0.02	2.82 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.00
Significance	*	*	*	*	*
Rootstock					
Ungrafted	2.70 ± 0.04 a	3.63 ± 0.04 a	4.97 ± 0.08 a	1.67 ± 0.02 a	0.11 ± 0.00 a
Rezistar	2.51 ± 0.05 b	2.10 ± 0.02 c	2.66 ± 0.01 c	0.89 ± 0.01 c	0.11 ± 0.00 a
S. sisymbriifolium	2.52 ± 0.01 b	2.86 ± 0.05 b	3.92 ± 0.14 b	1.29 ± 0.05 b	0.10 ± 0.00 b
Significance	*	*	*	*	*
Fertilization					
Unfertilized	2.60 ± 0.02	3.30 ± 0.03 a	4.44 ± 0.08 a	1.47 ± 0.02 a	0.11 ± 0.00 a
Mycoseed	2.58 ± 0.03	2.46 ± 0.01 d	3.23 ± 0.01 c	1.03 ± 0.02 d	0.10 ± 0.00 b
Organic	2.54 ± 0.05	2.65 ± 0.03 c	3.63 ± 0.09 b	1.25 ± 0.00 c	0.10 ± 0.00 b
Chemical	2.59 ± 0.01	3.04 ± 0.01 b	4.10 ± 0.11 a	1.37 ± 0.03 b	0.10 ± 0.00 b
Significance	ns	*	*	*	*

*1. Total polyphenols (mg/100 g); 2. Chlorophyll A (mg/100 g); 3. Chlorophyll B (mg/100 g); 4. Lycopene (mg/100 g); 5. Tannins (mg/100 g)

**Legend: Values represent the mean ± standard error. Values followed by different letters within the same column indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

ns = non-significant differences; * = significant differences.

Cultivar Influence

The two cultivars showed clear differences in bioactive accumulation, with Mirval F1 consistently outperforming Black Pearl F1. Mirval F1 registered higher total polyphenols and lycopene, indicating a stronger genetic capacity for synthesizing antioxidant compounds. This advantage is likely linked to its more intense pigmentation and a more active secondary metabolism. Although Black Pearl F1 also contained relevant bioactives, its values were systematically lower. These results suggest that Mirval F1 is better suited for obtaining fruits with higher nutritional quality under the studied conditions.

Rootstock Influence

Rootstock choice significantly affected fruit composition. Ungrafted plants showed the highest levels of most compounds, including polyphenols, chlorophylls and lycopene, possibly because grafting related vigor did not interfere with metabolite accumulation. Among grafted variants, S. sisymbriifolium performed better than Rezistar, leading to higher chlorophyll and lycopene contents. Tannins remained almost unchanged across treatments. Rezistar generally showed the lowest pigment values, suggesting a dilution effect under high vigor. In contrast, S. sisymbriifolium represented a better balance between grafting

benefits and fruit biochemical quality, even if not all responses was perfectly uniform.

Influence of Fertilization

Fertilization had little effect on total polyphenols, which remained relatively constant across treatments, indicating a strong genetic control. In contrast, chlorophylls and lycopene responded clearly to nutrition, with the highest values in the control and chemical variants, and the lowest under Micoseed, while organic fertilization showed intermediate effects. This suggests that both mild stress and high nutrient availability can favor pigment accumulation through different mechanisms. Tannins decreased slightly under fertilized conditions, likely due to reduced stress in well nourished plants.

Antioxidant activity measured by ABTS and DPPH showed only minor differences between cultivars, with Mirval F1 being slightly higher, especially in DPPH, in line with its greater phenolic and lycopene content. Still, both hybrids displayed comparable overall antioxidant capacity, probably due to compensation by other compounds in Black Pearl, which seems plausible.

Rootstock influence was much stronger. Ungrafted plants had the lowest antioxidant values, whereas grafting, especially on S. sisymbriifolium, significantly increased both ABTS and DPPH. Rezistar showed intermediate effects. This indicates that the wild rootstock stimulated antioxidant metabolism, likely by improved uptake or mild induced stress.

Fertilization modified antioxidant activity in an assay dependent manner. Micoseed gave the highest ABTS values, while the control showed the highest DPPH response, supporting the idea that nutrient limitation can stimulate lipophilic antioxidant synthesis. Organic and chemical treatments maintained high activity, but did not surpass the control in DPPH, which is quite interesting.

Overall, Mirval F1 remained superior for antioxidant traits, S. sisymbriifolium proved the most effective rootstock for enhancing activity, and low input conditions activated stress related phenolic metabolism. Together, cultivar, grafting and fertilization clearly act in combination to shape the functional quality of eggplant fruits.

Figure 1. Antioxidant capacity of eggplant fruits determined by ABTS and DPPH assays in relation to cultivar, rootstock, and fertilization regime

2. Combined Influence of Cultivar × Rootstock on the Content of Bioactive Compounds in Eggplant Fruits

To clarify how cultivar and grafting jointly shape fruit quality, the combined effects of scion and rootstock were evaluated on key biochemical traits. Table 2 summarizes changes in polyphenols, chlorophylls, lycopene, and tannins across each cultivar–rootstock combination. This comparison shows that fruit composition depends not only on genotype but also on the chosen rootstock, and sometimes this interaction is more important than expected. These results are directly relevant for nutritional and functional quality, offering growers practical guidance for selecting cultivar and rootstock pairs that maximize fruit value.

Table 2. Influence of Cultivar × Rootstock Interaction on Polyphenol Content, Photosynthetic Pigments, Lycopene, and Tannins in Eggplant Fruits

Experimental factor	1	2	3	4	5
Mirval F1 × Ungrafted	2.96 ± 0.02 a	4.70 ± 0.17 a	6.65 ± 0.34 a	2.24 ± 0.09 a	0.11 ± 0.00 a
Mirval F1 × Rezistar	2.92 ± 0.02 a	2.05 ± 0.03 d	2.42 ± 0.03 d	0.80 ± 0.02 d	0.11 ± 0.00 ab
Mirval F1 × <i>S. sisymbriifolium</i>	3.03 ± 0.01 a	3.57 ± 0.06 b	5.15 ± 0.22 b	1.71 ± 0.07 b	0.09 ± 0.00 c
Black Pearl F1 × Ungrafted	2.45 ± 0.06 b	2.56 ± 0.09 c	3.29 ± 0.18 c	1.10 ± 0.06 c	0.10 ± 0.00 abc
Black Pearl F1 × Rezistar	2.10 ± 0.07 c	2.15 ± 0.02 cd	2.90 ± 0.02 cd	0.97 ± 0.01 cd	0.10 ± 0.00 abc
Black Pearl F1 × <i>S. sisymbriifolium</i>	2.01 ± 0.00 c	2.15 ± 0.04 d	2.69 ± 0.06 cd	0.87 ± 0.02 cd	0.10 ± 0.00 bc
Significance	*	*	*	*	*

*1. Total polyphenols (mg/100 g); 2. Chlorophyll A (mg/100 g); 3. Chlorophyll B (mg/100 g); 4. Lycopene (mg/100 g); 5. Tannins (mg/100 g)

Total Polyphenols (TPC)

The highest polyphenol concentrations were consistently observed in Mirval F1 combinations, with the maximum recorded in Mirval grafted onto *S. sisymbriifolium* (3.03

mg/100 g), followed closely by the ungrafted and Rezistar-grafted Mirval variants. All Mirval treatments clearly exceeded Black Pearl values, which remained below 2.5 mg/100 g in all cases. This confirms the strong genetic control of phenolic accumulation in Mirval. Grafting slightly enhanced TPC only when Mirval was combined with *S. sisymbriifolium*, while Black Pearl showed small declines after grafting. Thus, cultivar effect was dominant, while rootstock acted only as a secondary modifier.

Photosynthetic Pigments

The highest chlorophyll contents were recorded in ungrafted Mirval fruits, indicating superior pigment retention under own-root growth. Mirval grafted on *S. sisymbriifolium* maintained intermediate values, whereas grafting on Rezistar caused a marked pigment reduction. Black Pearl showed consistently lower chlorophyll levels, especially after grafting. These results suggest that grafting, particularly onto vigorous rootstocks, may accelerate fruit maturation and reduce chlorophyll persistence, and this effect appear stronger in Black Pearl.

Lycopene

Lycopene followed a pattern similar to chlorophyll. Ungrafted Mirval showed the highest values (2.24 mg/100 g), while Mirval grafted on *S. sisymbriifolium* ranked second. Rezistar markedly reduced lycopene, especially in Mirval, where values dropped below those of Black Pearl. This indicates a strong negative rootstock effect on carotenoid formation, likely linked to altered ripening physiology. Overall, Mirval expressed a much higher inherent carotenoid potential, while *S. sisymbriifolium* proved the most suitable rootstock for preserving this trait.

Tannins

Tannin levels varied only slightly among treatments, remaining within the generally low range typical for eggplant. The highest values were observed in ungrafted Mirval and Mirval grafted on Rezistar, both close to 0.11 mg/100 g, while Mirval on *S. sisymbriifolium* showed the lowest value at about 0.09 mg/100 g. Most Black Pearl variants remained around 0.10 mg/100 g and were little affected by rootstock choice. This indicates that grafting Mirval on the wild rootstock slightly reduced tannin accumulation, which may improve taste by lowering bitterness. In contrast, Black Pearl showed little response. The significant

interaction suggests that tannin expression depend on both cultivar and rootstock, and the lower tannins in Mirval on *S. sisymbriifolium* may reflect a shift toward other non tannin phenolics.

Data from Table 2 confirm that Mirval F1, particularly when ungrafted or grafted on *S. sisymbriifolium*, produced fruits richer in bioactive compounds than Black Pearl F1. The grafting effect depended strongly on rootstock. Mirval on *S. sisymbriifolium* combined high polyphenols with well preserved pigments, while Mirval on Rezistar maintained high polyphenols but showed lower pigment values. Black Pearl had consistently lower phytochemical content, and grafting did not improve its profile, in some cases it even decline. This confirms that scion genotype remains the main driver of fruit nutritional quality, while rootstock only fine tunes the response.

Antioxidant results from Figure 2 followed the same pattern. Ungrafted plants had the lowest ABTS and DPPH values in both cultivars. Grafted Mirval variants showed the highest activities, with Mirval on Rezistar leading DPPH and Mirval on *S. sisymbriifolium* leading ABTS. This suggests that grafting amplified Mirval natural antioxidant potential, likely through modified nutrition and stress signaling. In Black Pearl, grafting caused only moderate improvements and values stayed below those of Mirval.

DPPH separated the treatments more clearly than ABTS, indicating a stronger role of lipophilic antioxidants. Although ungrafted Mirval had the highest pigments, its antioxidant activity was lower than in grafted plants, showing that pigments alone are not sufficient. Overall, Mirval F1 combined with appropriate rootstocks proved most efficient for antioxidant enhancement. *S. sisymbriifolium* offered the most balanced improvement in polyphenols, pigments and antioxidant capacity, while ungrafted Mirval remained superior for chlorophyll and lycopene. These results confirm that grafting can steer biochemical quality when genotype compatibility is correctly selected.

Figure 2. Antioxidant capacity (ABTS and DPPH assays) of eggplant fruits in relation to cultivar × rootstock combination

3. Effect of Cultivar × Fertilization Interaction on Bioactive Compounds in Eggplant Fruits

At the same time, Was evaluated how different fertilization strategies affected the accumulation of major bioactive compounds in the two eggplant cultivars, including polyphenols, chlorophylls, lycopene and tannins. By examining the interaction between cultivar and fertilization, cultivar specific nutritional responses to nutrient supply can be identified and better management options for improving fruit quality can be outlined (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of Fertilization Regime on Polyphenol Content, Photosynthetic Pigments, Lycopene, and Tannins in Two Eggplant Cultivars

Cultivar	1	2	3	4	5
Mirval F1 × Control	2.76 ± 0.01 b	3.21 ± 0.01 b	4.18 ± 0.08 b	1.39 ± 0.03 bc	0.11 ± 0.00 bc
Mirval F1 × Micoseed	3.01 ± 0.02 a	3.19 ± 0.07 b	4.19 ± 0.12 b	1.33 ± 0.06 c	0.10 ± 0.00 cd
Mirval F1 × Organic	3.00 ± 0.04 a	3.14 ± 0.12 b	4.49 ± 0.22 b	1.57 ± 0.02 b	0.11 ± 0.00 bc
Mirval F1 × Chemical	3.11 ± 0.05 a	4.22 ± 0.07 a	6.11 ± 0.29 a	2.04 ± 0.07 a	0.11 ± 0.00 b
Black Pearl F1 × Control	2.44 ± 0.02 c	3.39 ± 0.05 b	4.71 ± 0.08 b	1.56 ± 0.01 b	0.12 ± 0.00 a
Black Pearl F1 × Micoseed	2.15 ± 0.03 d	1.74 ± 0.05 d	2.27 ± 0.11 c	0.74 ± 0.02 e	0.11 ± 0.00 bc
Black Pearl F1 × Organic	2.09 ± 0.06 d	2.16 ± 0.05 c	2.76 ± 0.04 c	0.93 ± 0.02 d	0.10 ± 0.00 d
Black Pearl F1 × Chemical	2.07 ± 0.06 d	1.85 ± 0.05 cd	2.09 ± 0.07 c	0.69 ± 0.02 e	0.09 ± 0.00 e
Significance	*	*	*	*	*

*1. Total polyphenols (mg/100 g); 2. Chlorophyll A (mg/100 g); 3. Chlorophyll B (mg/100 g); 4. Lycopene (mg/100 g); 5. Tannins (mg/100 g)

Polyphenols

Mirval F1 showed consistently higher polyphenol levels than Black Pearl F1 under all fertilization regimes. In Mirval, fertilization slightly increased TPC, with chemical and biofertilizer treatments giving the highest

values, while the control remained only slightly lower. In contrast, Black Pearl reached its maximum polyphenols under the unfertilized control and showed reduced values after fertilization. This confirms a clear genotype dependent response, where Mirval benefits from nutrient input, while Black Pearl seems to express higher phenolics under mild stress, and extra nutrients do not help, maybe even depress it.

Chlorophylls

Fertilization strongly modified pigment content in a cultivar specific manner. Chemical fertilization greatly enhanced chlorophyll a and b in Mirval fruits, showing the highest pigment retention under this treatment. Black Pearl behaved oppositely, as its control plants had the highest chlorophyll while fertilization, especially chemical and Micoseed, caused sharp pigment losses. This suggest that Mirval maintains greenness under strong nutrition, while Black Pearl matures faster and loses pigments when well fed.

Lycopene

Mirval again outperformed Black Pearl across all treatments. The highest lycopene was recorded in Mirval under chemical fertilization, while even its lowest value remained above the best Black Pearl treatment. In Black Pearl, fertilization sharply reduced lycopene, with the minimum under chemical input. This indicates that Mirval converts nutrients efficiently into carotenoids, while Black Pearl responds better to low input or mild stress, and high fertility suppresses carotenoid buildup.

Tannins

Tannin levels varied only slightly but showed contrasting behavior. Black Pearl had the highest tannins in the unfertilized control and the lowest under chemical fertilization, indicating stress related accumulation. Mirval maintained nearly stable tannin values across all treatments, with only a minor decrease under Micoseed. Although statistically significant, these differences are likely minor in sensory perception.

The cultivar by fertilization interaction indicates that Mirval F1 shows a higher nutritional adaptability. It efficiently converts added nutrients, especially under chemical fertilization, into increased polyphenols, pigments and lycopene, resulting in fruits with superior quality. In contrast, Black Pearl F1

reached its best biochemical values mainly in the control and biofertilizer treatments, while high fertilization often lowered its quality traits. This suggest that Black Pearl is better suited for low input systems, whereas Mirval performs best under optimized nutrition. Accordingly, the Mirval F1 with chemical fertilization proved to be the most productive combination overall.

Figure 3 confirms these patterns through antioxidant assays. The highest ABTS values were observed in Black Pearl under control and Micoseed, indicating strong antioxidant activity under minimal or biological input. Mirval achieved similar ABTS levels mainly under organic fertilization, while its chemical and biofertilizer treatments were slightly lower. These data show that Black Pearl expresses hydrophilic antioxidant activity mostly under natural nutrient supply, while Mirval responds more positively to balanced or organic fertilization, although not all responses are identical between genotypes.

Figure 3. Antioxidant capacity (ABTS and DPPH assays) of eggplant fruits in relation to cultivar × fertilization interaction

In the DPPH assay, which reflects mainly lipophilic antioxidants, a different ranking was observed. The highest values occurred in Black Pearl F1 under control conditions and in Mirval F1 under chemical fertilization, showing two contrasting physiological responses. In Black Pearl, the strongest activity appeared without fertilization, suggesting that mild nutrient stress stimulated antioxidant accumulation. In Mirval, the top DPPH value was linked to full nutrient supply, indicating that this hybrid uses added resources to intensify antioxidant synthesis. Organic and Micoseed treatments in Mirval also produced high DPPH values, only slightly below the chemical variant, showing that this genotype remains highly responsive even under non mineral inputs. By contrast, fertilized Black Pearl variants displayed clearly lower DPPH

activity, confirming a weaker positive response to nutrient addition.

These responses indicate that antioxidant fractions measured by ABTS and DPPH do not react uniformly to fertilization. Black Pearl appears to rely more on stress activated compounds, while Mirval benefits from nutrient driven metabolic activation. The consistently high DPPH value of Mirval under chemical fertilization supports the idea that its antioxidant pathways are strongly nutrient sensitive. In turn, Black Pearl achieved its maximum antioxidant potential mainly under nutrient limitation, suggesting that additional inputs tend to shift its metabolism toward growth rather than defense.

Taken together, the data confirm that antioxidant behavior depends strongly on the cultivar–fertilization interaction. Black Pearl performs best under low input or biostimulant based systems, while Mirval expresses higher and more stable antioxidant capacity under organic and chemical fertilization. This emphasize that fertilization strategies should be adapted to the genetic background if functional quality is the main production goal.

4. Combined Impact of Rootstock × Fertilization on the Content of Bioactive Compounds in Eggplant Fruits

The interaction between rootstock type and fertilization regime was further evaluated to assess how combined propagation and nutrient strategies influence the bioactive profile of eggplant fruits. By analyzing this interaction in Table 4, it becomes possible to identify whether specific rootstocks respond more favorably to particular fertilization approaches in terms of improving fruit phytochemical content. This integrated perspective allows a clearer understanding of how paired technological inputs can optimize nutritional quality, even if responses are not always uniform.

Table 4.
Polyphenol, Chlorophyll a and b, Lycopene, and Tannin Content of Eggplant Fruits in Relation to Rootstock × Fertilization Interaction (mean ± standard error)

Factor	1	2	3	4	5
Ungrafted × Control	2.35 ± 0.03 e	4.41 ± 0.02 a	5.94 ± 0.01 a	1.96 ± 0.00 a	0.11 ± 0.00 bcd
Ungrafted × Microseed	2.61 ± 0.03 cde	2.48 ± 0.04 f	3.37 ± 0.06 de	1.13 ± 0.03 cd	0.09 ± 0.00 de
Ungrafted × Organic	2.98 ± 0.11 ab	4.15 ± 0.05 b	6.01 ± 0.14 a	2.08 ± 0.01 a	0.12 ± 0.01 a
Ungrafted × Chemical	2.88 ± 0.02 abc	3.49 ± 0.06 c	4.57 ± 0.13 b	1.51 ± 0.04 b	0.11 ± 0.00 abc
Rezistar × Control	2.34 ± 0.03 e	3.24 ± 0.03 d	4.47 ± 0.14 bc	1.49 ± 0.03 b	0.12 ± 0.00 ab
Rezistar × Microseed	2.38 ± 0.10 e	2.04 ± 0.07 g	2.40 ± 0.12 fg	0.78 ± 0.05 e	0.10 ± 0.00 bcd
Rezistar × Organic	2.74 ± 0.08 bcd	1.47 ± 0.00 h	1.80 ± 0.02 g	0.62 ± 0.01 e	0.10 ± 0.00 cd
Rezistar × Chemical	2.57 ± 0.03 de	1.65 ± 0.04 h	1.96 ± 0.07 g	0.65 ± 0.02 e	0.10 ± 0.00 cd
S. sisymbriifolium × Control	3.11 ± 0.06 a	2.26 ± 0.05 fg	2.92 ± 0.10 ef	0.98 ± 0.02 d	0.11 ± 0.00 abc
S. sisymbriifolium × Microseed	2.74 ± 0.05 bcd	2.87 ± 0.08 e	3.92 ± 0.09 cd	1.18 ± 0.09 c	0.11 ± 0.00 abc
S. sisymbriifolium × Organic	1.92 ± 0.04 f	2.33 ± 0.05 f	3.06 ± 0.11 e	1.05 ± 0.02 cd	0.08 ± 0.00 e

*1. Total polyphenols (mg/100 g); 2. Chlorophyll A (mg/100 g); 3. Chlorophyll B (mg/100 g); 4. Lycopene (mg/100 g); 5. Tannins (mg/100 g)

Polyphenols

Polyphenol levels differed strongly with the rootstock and fertilization pairing. The highest value occurred in *S. sisymbriifolium* × Control (3.11 mg/100 g), suggesting that this wild rootstock favors phenolic accumulation under low input conditions, likely through mild physiological stress. Ungrafted plants supplied with organic or chemical fertilizer also showed high values, whereas Rezistar combinations were consistently lower, indicating a possible dilution effect linked to excessive vegetative vigor. Notably, *S. sisymbriifolium* × Organic showed the lowest value (1.92 mg/100 g), implying that high nutrient availability suppressed phenolic synthesis in this pairing.

Chlorophylls

The highest chlorophyll a and b contents were recorded in Ungrafted × Control and Ungrafted × Organic treatments, showing that self rooted plants retained more green pigments, probably due to slower ripening. High values were also observed in *S. sisymbriifolium* × Chemical, while

Rezistar under organic or chemical fertilization showed the lowest pigment levels. This indicates that vigorous growth induced by Rezistar combined with high nutrients accelerated chlorophyll loss in fruits.

Lycopene

Lycopene accumulation was greatest in Ungrafted × Organic, Ungrafted × Control, and *S. sisymbriifolium* × Chemical, all near 2.0 mg/100 g. These results suggest that both natural nutrition and wild rootstock under high nutrient supply can favor carotenoid synthesis. In contrast, Rezistar under organic or chemical fertilization produced the lowest lycopene values, below 0.7 mg/100 g, showing a strong negative interaction between this rootstock and high nutrient input for carotenoid accumulation.

Tannins

Tannin levels remained low overall, yet small differences were observed. The highest values appeared in Ungrafted × Organic and Rezistar × Control (0.12 mg/100 g), while the lowest occurred in *S. sisymbriifolium* × Organic and *S. sisymbriifolium* × Chemical (0.08 mg/100 g). This suggests that the wild rootstock under good nutrition reduced bitterness related compounds, which could be favorable for fruit palatability.

Overall, ungrafted plants under organic or low input conditions and wild rootstock under chemical fertilization emerged as the most favorable systems for maximizing pigments, lycopene, and polyphenols, while Rezistar combined with strong fertilization often depressed these quality traits.

The synthesis of Table 4 confirms that both grafting and fertilization strongly regulate the biochemical profile of eggplant fruits through clear interactive effects. Ungrafted plants, especially under organic or chemical fertilization, showed the highest chlorophyll and lycopene levels, reflecting intense pigment metabolism. In contrast, the Rezistar rootstock consistently produced the weakest responses for most quality traits, indicating that its vigor favors yield rather than phytochemical enrichment. The *S. sisymbriifolium* rootstock stimulated the highest polyphenol accumulation under control conditions, suggesting that this

wild rootstock induces a beneficial stress or improves nutrient scavenging. Under heavy fertilization, however, the same rootstock shifted metabolism toward pigments rather than phenolics or tannins. Overall, ungrafted plants and *S. sisymbriifolium* under moderate nutrition appear most suitable for achieving broad nutritional quality, while Rezistar under rich nutrition tends to dilute fruit value.

Antioxidant activity further clarified these trends. The highest ABTS values were observed in Rezistar × Micoseed and *S. sisymbriifolium* × Control, showing that both microbial input and wild rootstock under low nutrients can strongly enhance hydrophilic antioxidants. In the DPPH assay, the best performance was recorded for *S. sisymbriifolium* × Control and *S. sisymbriifolium* × Chemical, indicating that this rootstock ensures consistently strong lipophilic antioxidant activity across fertilization levels. In contrast, Rezistar × Control and Rezistar × Chemical ranked among the lowest in both assays. These results highlight that *S. sisymbriifolium* provides the most stable antioxidant performance across conditions, while Rezistar requires specific interventions like Micoseed to partially compensate. Taken together, the data show that rootstock selection is as critical as fertilization strategy for maximizing functional quality. Wild rootstocks paired with balanced nutrition clearly offer the most reliable route for enhancing antioxidant value, while mismatched combinations may still give high yields but poor nutraceutical quality.

Figure .4. Antioxidant activity (ABTS and DPPH assays) of eggplant fruits in relation to grafting × fertilization interaction

CONCLUSIONS

The present investigation demonstrates that the biochemical quality of eggplant fruits is governed by a close interaction between genetic background, grafting strategy and fertilization regime rather than by any isolated factor alone. When considered together, the data indicate that decisions taken at each of these three levels, cultivar, rootstock and nutrition, are able to shift the balance between vegetative vigor aimed at yield and the accumulation of health related bioactive compounds.

First of all, cultivar choice proved to be the most stable and influential determinant of fruit quality. Across all tested variants, Mirval F1 accumulated consistently higher levels of total polyphenols, chlorophylls and lycopene, and, in parallel, exhibited slightly stronger antioxidant activity than Black Pearl F1. This superiority was maintained across different grafting and fertilization treatments, confirming that a favorable phytochemical profile is primarily genetically controlled. From a practical standpoint, Mirval F1 clearly represents a more suitable candidate for production systems targeting functional or nutraceutical quality, while Black Pearl F1 appears less adapted to such objectives, particularly under intensive fertilization, even if its agronomic behavior may still be acceptable.

Second, grafting acted not as a simple switch that turns quality on or off, but rather as a fine regulatory instrument whose effects depended strongly on the scion–rootstock interaction. Ungrafted plants generally produced fruits with the highest pigment contents, especially in terms of chlorophylls and lycopene, yet the antioxidant assays revealed that grafting, particularly onto *S. sisymbriifolium*, can markedly enhance radical scavenging activity. The wild rootstock provided a well balanced profile, combining high or very high antioxidant capacity with satisfactory levels of phenolics and pigments. In contrast, the commercial rootstock Rezistar frequently led to lower concentrations of key bioactive compounds, and only in a few specific cases, such as Mirval F1 × Rezistar for DPPH or Rezistar × Micoseed for ABTS, did it partially compensate through improved antioxidant response. Overall, *S. sisymbriifolium* appears to be the more appropriate rootstock when fruit quality is a core target, whereas Rezistar seems better

suitable for production systems where vigor and yield dominate over nutritional density.

Third, fertilization exerted a more nuanced and differentiated influence, affecting pigments and antioxidant activity more strongly than total polyphenol content. Total phenolics remained relatively stable across the fertilization treatments, but both pigment accumulation and antioxidant behavior showed clear responsiveness. Unfertilized control plants often exhibited elevated antioxidant capacity, particularly in DPPH, indicating that moderate nutritional stress can activate endogenous defense mechanisms and stimulate phenolic metabolism. Chemical fertilization, on the other hand, strongly promoted chlorophyll and lycopene accumulation in Mirval F1 and in certain grafted combinations, for example *S. sisymbriifolium* × Chemical, showing that well nourished high vigor plants are also able to develop very rich pigment profiles. Organic fertilization generally produced intermediate responses, often close to control, and appeared to offer a compromise between productivity and functional quality. The Micoseed biofertilizer induced more contrasting effects, tending to reduce pigment accumulation but, in some combinations, Rezistar × Micoseed, Black Pearl × Micoseed, coinciding with high ABTS values which suggests a shift in antioxidant composition rather than a simple overall decline.

From a technological perspective, the most favorable combinations for obtaining high quality fruits appear to be the following, (i) Mirval F1 grown ungrafted or grafted onto *S. sisymbriifolium* under moderate to high fertilization, organic or chemical, when the emphasis is placed on pigments and total antioxidant potential, and (ii) *S. sisymbriifolium* rootstock under either unfertilized or balanced mineral fertilization when the goal is to maximize antioxidant activity across diverse production contexts. Black Pearl F1, in contrast, expressed its highest antioxidant potential under low input conditions, control, Micoseed, yet even in these situations it did not reach the absolute bioactive levels observed in Mirval. These observations indicate that in quality oriented eggplant chains, cultivar and rootstock should be selected first based on functional targets, and fertilization should afterwards be adjusted to fine tune stress intensity rather than simply to maximize biomass.

In conclusion, the present study confirms that the bioactive compound profile of eggplant

fruits is highly plastic and can be deliberately steered through informed combinations of cultivar selection, grafting and fertilization. Mirval F1, especially when associated with *S. sisymbriifolium* or with carefully managed nutrition, is capable of producing fruits with superior phenolic, pigment and antioxidant profiles. Grafting, particularly onto wild rootstocks, should therefore be viewed not only as a tool for disease resistance and stress tolerance, but also as a powerful lever for improving nutritional and functional value. Integrating these strategies into commercial practice may support the development of eggplant production systems that ensure both agronomic performance and added value for consumer health, fully aligned with the broader principles of sustainable and health oriented horticulture.

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INTEGRATIVE REVIEW ON TECHNOLOGICAL MEASURES AFFECTING THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND NUTRITIONAL QUALITY OF EGGPLANTS

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

*Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) is among the most widely cultivated vegetable crops worldwide, and interest has increasingly shifted from yield alone toward fruit quality attributes, including dry matter content, mineral composition, and antioxidant capacity. This review compiles recent evidence on how cultivation practices modulate the physicochemical and nutritional profile of eggplant fruits. Water regime emerges as one of the dominant drivers of quality formation. Excess irrigation generally leads to dilution of soluble solids and minerals, whereas moderate water restriction favors dry matter accumulation, improves flavor intensity, and enhances antioxidant potential. Fertilization strategy exerts a similarly pronounced influence. Balanced macro- and micronutrient supply, including foliar NPK applications enriched with iron, zinc, and boron, consistently increases fruit mineral concentrations, in some cases by twenty to thirty percent. Organic systems based on green manures and biofertilizers further enhance nutrient density when compared with unfertilized controls. In contrast, lycopene content remains minimal in eggplant and appears to be largely genotype-dependent, with limited responsiveness to agronomic management. The antioxidant profile, including phenolics, anthocyanins, and vitamin C, is particularly sensitive to cultivation conditions. Mild abiotic stress induced by regulated deficit irrigation or alternative water sources often stimulates antioxidant activity by twenty to fifty percent, while organic amendments have been associated with marked increases in radical scavenging capacity. Fine-tuning irrigation and fertilization represents a powerful approach for improving eggplant fruit quality. Through moderate water stress and targeted nutrient management, growers can obtain fruits with enhanced nutritional value, firmer texture, and superior antioxidant properties without compromising yield.*

Keywords: eggplant, irrigation, fertilization, antioxidant capacity, fruit quality

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INTRODUCTION

Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) is one of the most widely consumed vegetable crops worldwide, cultivated on about 1.8 million hectares and producing over 54 million tonnes annually, with Asia as the dominant producer (Bana et al., 2022). Beyond its well known culinary versatility and characteristic purple pigmentation, eggplant is increasingly appreciated for its nutritional and functional value (Diaz-Perez, 2015). Although the fruit contains large amounts of water, it also provides dietary fiber, phenolic compounds such as chlorogenic acid and anthocyanin pigments like nasunin, all linked to health related benefits (Mekky et al., 2025). However, many essential vitamins and minerals are present only at moderate levels, therefore

improving fruit quality remains an important goal in both research and production, and sometimes is difficult to be achieved.

Modern consumers demand vegetables with better flavor and higher nutritional value, which has increased the importance of agronomic practices as tools for regulating fruit quality. Unlike breeding, which requires long time periods, cultivation measures such as irrigation control, fertilization, plant density and organic amendments can be adjusted within one season. In eggplant, the major challenge is to obtain fruits that combine good yield with high dry matter, improved mineral content and elevated levels of bioactive compounds with health value.

Previous studies clearly indicate that fruit quality in eggplant is highly dependent on environmental and technological conditions

(Abbas et al., 2025; Islam et al., 2024; Amami et al., 2025). Excessive irrigation leads to diluted fruits with weak flavor, while moderate water stress tends to favor sugar and phenolic accumulation (Li et al., 2024). Similarly, excess nitrogen may raise yield but often reduces quality, whereas balanced fertilization and micronutrient supplementation improve nutrient density (Nisar et al., 2025). Organic fertilizers and biofertilizers also enhance vitamin and mineral content through improved soil function and mild stress responses. Even so, the combined action of these factors on specific quality traits is still not completely understood. This review is grounded on the assumption that a well balanced optimization of cultivation practices can improve eggplant fruit quality without causing yield reduction. It critically evaluates the influence of major agronomic factors such as irrigation management, fertilization approach, planting density and related field practices on dry matter accumulation, mineral profile, lycopene level, antioxidant capacity and other relevant biochemical traits. By integrating results from a wide range of experimental studies, the analysis aims to deliver practically useful guidance for the production of eggplants with enhanced nutritional quality and increased consumer value, which is today more and more expected.

MATERIALS AND METHODES

This study was conducted as an integrative literature review, aiming to collect and synthesize a wide range of scientific evidence related to eggplant cultivation and fruit quality. A structured search was carried out in major scientific databases, including Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed, and Google Scholar. Priority was given to peer reviewed papers published mainly within the last two decades, roughly between 2000 and 2025, that investigated the influence of agronomic or technological practices on eggplant fruit composition. The search strategy involved combining the terms “eggplant” or “*Solanum melongena*” with expressions such as irrigation regime, deficit irrigation quality, fertilization eggplant nutrients, foliar feeding eggplant, organic manure eggplant quality, spacing yield quality, wastewater irrigation eggplant, and postharvest eggplant composition. In addition, the reference lists of key articles were examined in order to capture further relevant studies that may not have appeared directly in the database queries.

Inclusion Criteria

Only studies that reported quantitative or qualitative data for at least one physicochemical or nutritional attribute of eggplant fruits in response to a clearly defined cultivation practice were included. Both open field and greenhouse experiments were considered, covering factors such as irrigation level and method, water quality including saline or wastewater use, fertilizer type and dose comprising mineral fertilization, micronutrient supplementation, organic manures and biofertilizers, as well as planting density, harvest timing and certain postharvest treatments. Research conducted under both conventional and organic or sustainable management systems was taken into consideration. Preference was given to experiments with sound methodological design such as replicated trials and randomized layouts. Studies evaluating fruit quality attributes including dry matter and soluble solids content, mineral element concentrations, antioxidant compounds such as phenolics, anthocyanins and vitamins, together with indices of antioxidant activity, were prioritized in the selection process.

Data Extraction and Synthesis

From each selected paper, information regarding the applied technological measure and the resulting changes in eggplant fruit quality parameters was extracted. Whenever available, numerical values such as mean concentrations or percentage variations were recorded for comparative purposes. Due to the considerable diversity of experimental designs, methodologies and reporting units among the studies, results were synthesized primarily in a narrative format. This interpretation was supported by summary tables that compile and normalize the most important data. Tables 1 to 5 were included in the paper to compare findings from multiple sources concerning specific quality traits, including dry matter, mineral composition, lycopene content, antioxidant indicators and other biochemical characteristics. A formal meta analysis was not performed because the heterogeneity of experimental conditions did not allow for reliable statistical aggregation. Instead, general patterns, consistencies and also contradictions among studies were interpreted using physiological principles.

All information presented in this review is derived exclusively from previously

published research and each source is cited accordingly. In several instances, minor unit conversions were applied to improve comparability among studies, for example transforming mineral concentrations to a common dry weight basis, and these adjustments were noted where relevant. The present review is therefore qualitative in nature and aims to integrate existing knowledge in order to draw broader conclusions about how technological cultivation practices may be applied to enhance eggplant fruit quality. By examining a wide body of independent research, this integrative approach offers a more comprehensive understanding that may support future agronomic decision making and guide further investigations in eggplant and related vegetable crops.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The quality of eggplant fruits was shown to be strongly affected by cultivation practices. The paper examines how the principal technological measures influence several key quality attributes, namely dry matter content, mineral composition including both macro and microelements, lycopene concentration, total antioxidant capacity, and other biochemical traits such as sugars, proteins, vitamins, and glycoalkaloids. Within each category, findings from multiple studies are compared and interpreted in order to build an integrated view of how agronomic management shapes eggplant fruit quality, and how these effects sometimes differ between experimental conditions.

Effect of Technological Measures on Dry Matter Content

Dry matter content is a key indicator of eggplant fruit quality because it reflects the balance between solid constituents and water, directly influencing firmness, taste intensity and processing suitability (Zipelevish et al., 2000). Evidence from the literature clearly indicates that irrigation management strongly controls this trait, through an obvious inverse relationship between water supply and dry matter concentration (Arrobas et al., 2021). Excessive watering, especially during fruit filling, promotes water accumulation in the tissues and leads to a clear dilution of solids. Field and greenhouse studies consistently confirm that high irrigation rates reduce fruit dry weight and soluble solids, producing larger but more watery fruits with only about six to seven percent dry matter (Li et al., 2024; Tezcan

et al., 2025; Abrham, 2024). In contrast, plants subjected to moderate irrigation develop fruits with a higher proportion of solids (Khapte, et al., 2025; Kiran et al., 2025). Conversely, a mild and well regulated water deficit stimulates dry matter accumulation through adaptive physiological responses such as stomatal regulation and osmotic adjustment, which limit excessive water inflow into the fruit. As a result, fruits become slightly smaller but richer in sugars and other solutes. This principle, known as deficit irrigation, has proven to be an effective tool for improving eggplant fruit quality without causing serious yield losses, if applied carefully (Lipovac et al., 2025).

Moderate irrigation regimes, supplying roughly 70 – 80% of the full water requirement or based on partial scheduling, have been shown to increase dry matter and soluble solids in eggplant fruits while limiting total water consumption (Thomas et al., 2025). Under such mild water stress, fruits contained about 15 – 20% percent more soluble solids than those grown under full irrigation, leading to better flavor and firmer texture, although values varied by season and genotype. By restricting excess water, plants produced fruits that were less watery and richer in structural compounds. For this reason, controlled deficit irrigation is increasingly used as both a water saving and quality enhancing strategy, even if in practice it remains difficult to apply precisely (Ali et al., 2025).

Fertilization also plays an important role in dry matter accumulation. Adequate nutrient supply supports carbohydrate synthesis and the formation of fruit solids, with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium being central regulators of this process. However, excessive nitrogen promotes vegetative growth and delays ripening, which can reduce dry matter through continued water accumulation (Li et al., 2025). Balanced fertilization is therefore essential. Studies show that fertilizers including sulfur and micronutrients such as boron can consistently improve dry matter levels. In a tropical field experiment, the use of NPSB fertilizer increased dry matter to about 10.21 percent, compared to only 8.13 percent in unfertilized plants. This difference is agronomically relevant and reflects improved metabolic activity and cell wall formation in well nourished plants, whereas nutrient limited crops remained visibly inferior in fruit quality (Choudhary et al., 2025; Dawar et al., 2025; Balaout et al., 2025).

Plant density also interferes with dry matter formation in eggplant, although in a more indirect manner. Wider spacing reduces competition for light, water and nutrients, allowing each plant to develop a stronger canopy and to fill fruits more evenly. In the Ethiopian field study, the optimal balance between yield and quality was observed at 40 cm between plants under proper fertilization. At 50 cm spacing, fruit dry matter reached about 9.6 percent, while at 30 cm it dropped to nearly 8.4 percent (Abrham et Shumbulo, 2025). This suggests that reduced competition and slightly higher exposure under wide spacing favored solid accumulation, whereas dense crops created humid conditions and stronger resource sharing, leading to more watery fruits. Although spacing is usually adjusted mainly for yield, its effect on quality is real and often underestimated. Water quality also affected dry matter levels. Treated wastewater irrigation generally resulted in higher dry matter than clean freshwater. In one experiment, fruits from wastewater plots reached up to 7.8 percent dry matter, compared to about 5.7 percent under freshwater. This effect is linked to mild osmotic stress caused by salts and to the additional nutrients present in reclaimed water, which together limit water dilution and support solid build up. Even if the absolute values seem small, the relative increase was enough to improve texture and flavor. (Abrham et Shumbulo, 2025).

Table 1.
Influence of Selected Technological Measures on the Dry Matter Content of Eggplant Fruits

Technological Measure	Dry Matter Content (%)
Intensive irrigation (high water, semi-arid conditions)	6.5
Moderate irrigation (controlled deficit regime)	8.2
NPSB fertilization (200 kg/ha blend)	10.21
Unfertilized control (no fertilization)	8.13
Wider plant spacing (50 cm between plants)	9.65
Closer plant spacing (30 cm between plants)	8.4
Irrigation with clean water (freshwater)	5.77
Irrigation with treated wastewater	7.8

The accumulated evidence confirms that proper control of both irrigation and fertilization can markedly increase dry matter in eggplant fruits. When excess water is avoided and only moderate supply is applied, fruits become denser and richer in flavor. Likewise, a well balanced nutrient input supports the formation and retention of solid compounds. These changes lead to firmer fruits with better

sensory and nutritional quality, which is increasingly demanded by the market. Importantly, this improvement does not always reduce yield. Several deficit irrigation approaches show that quality can rise while production remains stable. Thus, dry matter is shaped by the combined effect of water, nutrients and spacing, and by adjusting these factors, growers can intentionally improve fruit quality, even if field conditions are never perfect.

Effect of Technological Measures on Macro- and Microelement Content

Beyond water effects, the mineral profile of eggplant is a major component of its nutritional value. Fruits supply relevant amounts of potassium, magnesium, calcium and phosphorus, along with smaller but important levels of iron and zinc (Chatzistathis et al., 2025). These concentrations are shaped not only by genotype and soil, but very clearly by fertilization and soil management. The reviewed data show that targeted fertilization can significantly increase mineral density, effectively turning eggplant into a biofortified food crop.

A particularly effective approach is the use of combined macro and micronutrient fertilization, especially through foliar feeding. In field trials, foliar application of NPK enriched with iron, zinc and boron led to notable increases in fruit mineral content, with iron rising by about 26 percent and zinc by more than 30 percent (El-Motaium, 2025). Such gains are nutritionally meaningful over time. Foliar delivery bypasses soil limitations and directly supports fruit formation. Importantly, these improvements were not obtained at the expense of yield, which in some cases even increased. This confirms that multi nutrient foliar fertilization can enhance both productivity and nutritional quality, although in practice it requires careful timing and management.

Agroecological and organic soil management can markedly improve mineral uptake in eggplant. In a recent Armenian study, the combination of green manure, especially soybean, with nitrogen fixing and phosphorus solubilizing biofertilizers led to very high mineral accumulation in fruits. Compared with the unfertilized control, iron, potassium, calcium, phosphorus and magnesium increased by large margins (Martirosyan, 2023). These results show that soil improving practices can

substantially enrich the mineral profile of eggplant, sometimes even beyond levels reported for standard chemical fertilization.

This response is linked to improved soil structure, higher organic matter and sustained nutrient release from decomposing green manures, together with the direct action of beneficial microbes in the rhizosphere. Nitrogen was supplied gradually and insoluble phosphorus became more available, leading to a more balanced nutrition across the growing period. In practice, these green technologies proved capable of matching, and sometimes exceeding, the mineral enrichment achieved with NPK alone, which is not always expected.

Table 2.

Macro- and Microelement Content of Eggplant Fruits Under Different Fertilization Practices

Technological Measure	Fe*	Zn*	Ca*	K*	P*	Mg*
Foliar fertilization (NPK + micronutrients)	55.7	48.2	379	1750	–	–
Control (no foliar fertilization)	44.1	36	325	1650	–	–
Green manure (soybean) + biofertilizer (soil applied)	59.2	42.3	393	1908	25.5	160.5
Control (unfertilized, conventional soil)	44.2	30.1	335.5	1555	18.5	132.5

*(mg/kg)

The data show that well adjusted fertilization can strongly enhance the mineral content of eggplant fruits. Foliar feeding mainly increased the elements applied directly, while green manure and biofertilizers improved a broader range of minerals through better soil functioning. Control treatments reflect nutrient limited conditions, whereas enriched variants confirm the real potential for agronomic biofortification. An iron level close to 59 mg kg⁻¹ dry weight is rather high for a vegetable and indicates that eggplant may become a relevant source of dietary iron under such management. Importantly, organic based treatments improved mineral ratios in a balanced way, since calcium and magnesium increased together with potassium, and not being suppressed as it sometimes happens under heavy chemical inputs.

From a wider perspective, integrating organic amendments, biological inputs and targeted micronutrient supply allows farmers to obtain fruits that are not only larger but also

more nutritious, which fits well with the idea of functional food production at farm level. This is especially meaningful in regions where eggplant is consumed daily, and even small nutrient increases can matter for public health. At the same time, these systems support soil quality and reduce dependence on synthetic fertilizers, which is long term beneficial.

Eggplant mineral composition is highly responsive to fertilization strategy. Basic NPK remains necessary for yield, but micronutrient supplementation and organic soil management clearly enhance fruit micronutrient density. When nutrients are supplied in balance and not in excess, together with biofertilizers, a more stable and favorable mineral profile can be achieved, and this is not always easy to manage in practice.

Effect of Technological Measures on Lycopene Content

Lycopene, a carotenoid responsible for the red color of tomato and watermelon, is present in eggplant only in trace amounts or is sometimes not detectable at all. The pigmentation of eggplant is instead dominated by anthocyanins, mainly nasunin, which give the characteristic purple skin (Panda et al., 2025). Because the biosynthetic pathway for lycopene is weakly expressed in this species, its concentration remains extremely low and is controlled almost entirely by genetic factors, not by cultivation practices. Changes in irrigation or fertilization therefore have very limited capacity to influence lycopene formation.

Analytical data confirm this pattern. Reported values in eggplant generally range between about 1.5 and 6.8 µg g⁻¹ dry weight, which is nearly two orders of magnitude lower than in tomato, where lycopene commonly reaches 50 to 120 µg g⁻¹ (Mukhtar et al., 2025). In most commercial purple cultivars, lycopene is close to the detection limit, and only a few reddish eggplant types accumulate slightly higher levels. Even in those cases, eggplant remains a very weak dietary source of lycopene, and this fact is often underestimated.

For this reason, agronomic measures do not produce measurable changes in eggplant lycopene content. Field experiments consistently show that water regime, nutrient supply or spacing fail to modify this pigment in any relevant way. In the studies reviewed here, lycopene stayed at similarly minimal levels across all treatments, often below 0.0005

percent of dry weight. Even increased potassium, which stimulates lycopene in tomato, had no effect in eggplant, confirming that this trait is rigid and mainly genetically fixed.

From a theoretical point of view, strong light exposure could stimulate carotenoid formation, since irradiance regulates pigment metabolism in many crops (Quián-Ulloa and Stange, 2021). In eggplant, fruits exposed directly to sunlight receive stronger light signals than shaded ones, and for this reason a slight stimulation of carotenoids has been speculated. However, solid experimental evidence for a real effect on lycopene is missing. If any response does exist, it is extremely weak. Most dark purple cultivars show no detectable lycopene regardless of sun exposure, because their metabolism is genetically directed toward anthocyanin production, and this basic pattern do not change under normal field conditions.

Postharvest handling appears to influence carotenoids more than cultivation. Thermal processing was shown to reduce the already very low carotenoid and lycopene levels in eggplant, together with vitamin C. Frying was the most damaging treatment, likely due to high temperature and solubility of carotenoids in oil, while baking also caused noticeable losses. In contrast, steaming or brief sautéing preserved a larger fraction of these compounds. Even so, lycopene remains nutritionally irrelevant in eggplant, since its initial concentration is far too low for cooking methods to make a meaningful difference.

Table 3.
Lycopene Content of Eggplant Fruits vs. Tomato (for comparison)

Cultivar / Genotype	Lycopene ($\mu\text{g/g}$ dry weight)
Eggplant – typical dark-purple cultivar (Nigeria)	1.5 – 2.1 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Eggplant – white-purple striped cultivar (Turkey)	2.8 – 4.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Eggplant – orange-pigmented cultivar (<i>Solanum aethiopicum</i>)	5.3 – 6.8 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Ripe Tomato (red cultivar)	50 – 120 $\mu\text{g/g}$

Lycopene occurs in eggplant only at trace levels, and neither cultivar choice nor cultivation practices lead to any relevant increase. For this reason, lycopene is not a meaningful quality marker for eggplant production. Breeding programs do not target this trait, and agronomic interventions offer little practical potential to modify it, since the species has a very limited biological capacity to synthesize this carotenoid. In practice, lycopene remains consistently low

and only weakly influenced by postharvest handling. From a nutritional view, consumers seeking lycopene should prefer red fruits such as tomato, while eggplant should be valued for fiber, anthocyanins and mineral content.

Effect of Technological Measures on Antioxidant Potential

Eggplant fruits are appreciated not only for taste and nutrients, but also for their strong antioxidant potential, which is mainly derived from phenolic acids such as chlorogenic acid, anthocyanins concentrated in the peel, especially nasunin, and vitamin C. Together, these compounds confer a high capacity to neutralize reactive oxygen species, as shown by common assays such as DPPH or ABTS (Jarerat et al., 2022). This antioxidant function is an important component of the fruit's functional quality and is linked with protective effects against oxidative stress and inflammation. Antioxidant accumulation in eggplant is closely connected to plant stress physiology. Moderate water or nutritional stress usually stimulates the synthesis of secondary metabolites, while very favorable conditions tend to reduce it.

Irrigation and Water Stress

Water regime strongly controls the antioxidant profile of eggplant mainly through its effect on plant stress physiology. Polat et al. (2024) reported that irrigation with treated wastewater led to a clear increase in total phenolic content and antioxidant activity compared with clean water. The mild salinity and trace elements in reclaimed water likely induced a low level of osmotic stress that stimulated phenolic synthesis. In contrast, plants supplied with abundant clean water showed the lowest phenolic levels, probably due to dilution and the lack of any stress signal. Thus, higher water availability was linked with lower antioxidant accumulation, while limited or lower quality water promoted enrichment. Still, wastewater use must be strictly controlled for safety, even if it improves functional quality, otherwise the risk may not be worth it.

Combined Water and Nutrient Management

The joint regulation of water and nitrogen strongly influences the antioxidant quality of eggplant fruits. Zhou et al. (2021) showed that moderate water restriction together with balanced nitrogen supply produced the highest vitamin C, soluble sugars and soluble proteins. Under about seventy five

percent irrigation and medium nitrogen, vitamin C reached roughly 63 to 69 mg per kg fresh weight, around forty percent higher than under excessive water and nitrogen, where values fell near 41 to 46 mg per kg. Although heavy inputs increased yield, fruits became biochemically diluted. Mild water stress stimulated sugar and antioxidant accumulation, while adequate nitrogen supported enzyme activity without promoting excessive vegetative growth. In contrast, surplus nitrogen under ample water delayed fruit maturation and reduced phenolic and vitamin C levels.

Organic and Biological Fertilization

Organic and biological fertilization clearly enhances the antioxidant potential of eggplant fruits. Compost, manure and green cover crops promote secondary metabolite synthesis due to slow nutrient release and higher soil microbial activity. Many studies report higher phenolic content and stronger antioxidant activity in organic fruits, even if yield is sometimes slightly lower. In the Armenian study by Martirosyan et al. (2023), green manure combined with biofertilizers nearly doubled ABTS activity, reaching about 692 μmol Trolox per g dry weight compared with 365 μmol in the control. The same treatment also showed the highest vitamin C and increased B vitamins. These results indicate that ecological fertilization can even outperform conventional systems in functional quality.

Anthocyanin Enhancement

Anthocyanins are a key contributor to the antioxidant capacity of eggplant, as these

pigments act as strong free radical scavengers. Therefore, practices that influence anthocyanin formation also affect fruit antioxidant potential. Light exposure is especially important, since fruits receiving more direct radiation usually develop darker skins and higher pigment levels, when the genotype allows this. Simple canopy adjustments, such as partial leaf removal near the fruits or reflective mulches, can enhance coloration and indirectly raise antioxidant content. Potassium nutrition may also support pigment synthesis through its role in carbohydrate transport and metabolism, although in eggplant the evidence is still limited. A sufficient K supply appears beneficial, but excessive doses does not seem to bring extra gains (Colak et al., 2022).

Niño Medina et al. (2014) reported a native Philippine eggplant genotype with very dark skin that showed extremely high anthocyanin content, about 161 mg per 100 g fresh weight, together with outstanding antioxidant activity, reaching over 92% DPPH inhibition and an ORAC value near 539 μmol Trolox per gram. These levels are exceptional for a vegetable and confirm the dominant role of anthocyanins in shaping antioxidant capacity. Although this variation is largely genetic, agronomic conditions such as full light exposure, balanced potassium nutrition and moderate stress can further enhance pigment expression. Even in common purple cultivars, fruits with deeper coloration usually show stronger antioxidant responses than pale ones, which is often clear in practice.

Table 4.

Effect of Technological Measures on the Antioxidant Potential of Eggplant Fruits

Applied Measure	Antioxidant Parameter	Observed Effect or Value
Wastewater irrigation (vs. clean water)	Total phenolic content	~20–30% increase compared to clean-water
Wastewater irrigation (vs. clean water)	Overall antioxidant activity	Higher antioxidant capacity under wastewater (saline stress) than under freshwater
Moderate water deficit + moderate N fertilization	Vitamin C (ascorbic acid)	63–69 mg/kg (fresh weight) in fruit – about 40–50% higher than in over-irrigated, high-N conditions (~41–46 mg/kg)
Moderate water deficit + moderate N fertilization	Soluble solids & proteins	Elevated levels (both higher than in either water-excess or nitrogen-excess scenarios) indicating more accumulated metabolites
Organic fertilization (green manure + biofertilizers)	ABTS radical scavenging capacity	692 μmol Trolox/g (d.w.) in organically fertilized fruits vs. ~365 μmol /g in unfertilized control (nearly 2 \times higher)
Organic farming system (vs. conventional)	General antioxidant activity	Significantly higher in organic (due to greater phenolics, etc.) – e.g., DPPH scavenging and FRAP values often superior in organic eggplants
Intensely purple cultivar (high anthocyanins)	Total anthocyanins (in skin)	~161 mg/100 g fresh weight (very high pigment content)
Intensely purple cultivar (high anthocyanins)	DPPH free radical inhibition	92.5% inhibition (strong antioxidant effect)
Intensely purple cultivar (high anthocyanins)	ORAC (Oxygen Radical Absorbance)	538.9 μmol Trolox equiv./g (exceptionally high antioxidant capacity)

Overall, available evidence shows that several agronomic practices can effectively enhance the antioxidant potential of eggplant fruits. Mild stress conditions, such as regulated deficit irrigation or the use of slightly saline irrigation water, stimulate phenolic synthesis, while balanced fertilization ensures the metabolic support needed for antioxidant production. Organic amendments appear particularly beneficial, since they promote slow nutrient release, better micronutrient availability and a moderate physiological stress that favors secondary metabolism. Cultivar choice remains decisive, as dark skinned types naturally express higher antioxidant capacity, especially when grown under full light and appropriate nutrition.

It must be acknowledged that increased antioxidants may involve small sensory compromises, because very high phenolic levels can introduce slight bitterness. However, most studies report that the increases remain within acceptable sensory limits, and compounds like chlorogenic acid often contribute positively after cooking. Only extreme pigment accumulation in some breeding materials might alter texture or taste, which is less relevant for standard cropping systems.

In conclusion, antioxidant capacity in eggplant is a flexible trait that can be shaped through cultivation strategies. Controlled water stress, organic fertilization, foliar micronutrients and careful variety selection all contribute to higher levels of phenolics, vitamins and anthocyanins. Many of these practices also support sustainability by saving water and improving soil quality, which makes their application both practical and desirable, even if field conditions are not always perfect.

Effect of Technological Measures on Other Biochemical Characteristics

Beyond dry matter and antioxidants, eggplant fruits also contain other biochemical components that shape both nutritional value and sensory quality, including sugars, organic acids, small amounts of proteins and amino acids, B group vitamins and glycoalkaloids responsible for bitterness. Most of these traits can be modified by cultivation practices and often respond in parallel with the physiological mechanisms already described.

Eggplant is a low sugar vegetable, yet even small variations in sugar level clearly affect taste perception. Glucose and fructose dominate at maturity, while total soluble solids

reflect the overall pool of soluble compounds. Available evidence shows that irrigation and nitrogen supply play a central role in sugar accumulation. In the study of Li et al. (2023), the highest sugar content occurred under limited irrigation of about seventy five to eighty percent of full water demand combined with optimal nitrogen, where sugars were roughly fifteen to thirty six percent higher than under excess water or nitrogen. Thus, a fruit with around three degrees Brix under high input could reach about four under moderate stress, a change that is clearly perceived by consumers.

Within the same water regime, moderate nitrogen further increased sugars, while excessive nitrogen consistently reduced them. This is likely because high nitrogen promotes vegetative growth and delays fruit maturation, producing larger but more watery fruits. Over irrigation had a similar dilution effect. For this reason, avoiding surplus water and nitrogen, especially late in fruiting, appears essential for flavor optimization. A mild, well controlled stress favors sugar accumulation as an osmotic response and improves overall taste, which was also reflected by higher total soluble solids in optimally managed plants.

Proteins and Amino Acids

Eggplant fruits contain very low amounts of protein, usually below two percent fresh weight, so they are not a major protein source. Still, changes in protein concentration can indicate differences in fruit quality. Soluble proteins and free amino acids contribute to umami taste and nutritional value, especially amino acids such as arginine and tryptophan. Nitrogen availability is the main driver of protein accumulation in the fruit. Evidence shows that moderate nitrogen supply supports higher protein levels, whereas both nitrogen shortage and excess reduce protein content. Fruits grown under optimal water and nitrogen conditions had about forty five percent more soluble protein than low input plants, and up to sixty seven percent more than under unfavorable regimes (Chawla et al., 2025). In contrast, the extreme combination of strong water stress and excessive nitrogen caused a sharp protein decline and produced small, shriveled fruits with weak flavor. This likely reflects a metabolic imbalance, with reduced sugars and amino acids and increased stress compounds.

B-Complex Vitamins

Eggplant fruits contain modest but detectable amounts of several B-complex vitamins. Mukhtar et al. (2023) reported wide differences among cultivars, with thiamine values ranging from about 11 to 95.6 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry weight and niacin from 83 to 265 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$. These variations were mainly attributed to genotype and growing environment, since Nigerian samples generally showed higher levels than Turkish ones, probably due to cultivar and soil effects.

Direct evidence on how cultivation practices modify B-vitamin content in eggplant is still scarce. However, from a physiological point of view, these vitamins are linked to primary metabolism and may respond to nutrient status and soil microbial activity. Organic amendments such as compost or manure could indirectly enhance vitamin accumulation, because some microorganisms synthesize B vitamins that plants can absorb. Thus, the assumption that organic fertilizers may support higher B-vitamin levels in eggplant fruits is biologically realistic, even if exact values are still missing. Such practices do not seem to reduce vitamin content, while severe stresses, like long drought, could negatively affect more sensitive compounds.

Glycoalkaloids and Bitterness

Eggplant fruits contain defensive glycoalkaloids, mainly solasonine and solamargine, which are responsible for their slight bitterness and, at very high levels, potential toxicity. In commercial cultivars these compounds are usually present at low and safe concentrations, giving only a mild bitter taste that is often reduced by culinary practices such

as salting. One of the main factors affecting glycoalkaloid content is fruit maturity. Overripe fruits, recognized by dull skin, hardened seeds and yellowing, tend to accumulate higher levels, which explains their stronger bitterness (Contreras-Angulo et al., 2022).

Severe environmental stress, including drought or pest attack, may further stimulate glycoalkaloid synthesis, but under normal farming conditions the dominant controls remain cultivar choice and harvest timing (Merino et al., 2023). Many modern varieties were bred for low inherent bitterness, keeping glycoalkaloids minimal under most conditions. Importantly, quality improving practices such as moderate water stress generally do not raise these compounds to harmful levels. When bitterness is still noticeable, traditional methods like salting sliced fruits remain effective in lowering glycoalkaloids before consumption.

Organic Acids and Acidity

Eggplant pulp contains only limited amounts of organic acids, mainly malic and citric acid, which explains its generally low titratable acidity and the absence of a distinctly sour taste (Zhou et al., 2023). Most studies report acidity values between 0.1 and 0.4 percent on a fresh weight basis, while only few higher values around 1.5 percent were occasionally noted, but these likely reflect dry matter calculations or very specific growing conditions (Kanval et al., 2025; Gaccionne et al., 2025; Blumenthal et al., 2024). In practical sensory terms, however, such variations remain minor, and acidity rarely plays a dominant role in eggplant flavor, which is instead shaped mostly by texture, mild bitterness and seasoning.

Table 5.

Influence of Technological Measures on Additional Biochemical Characteristics of Eggplant Fruits

Applied Measure	Biochemical Parameter	Effect on Parameter
Moderate water deficit + moderate N fertilization	Soluble sugars (SSC)	Increases by ~15–36% compared to no stress (control)
	Total soluble solids (TSS)	~+15% vs. fully irrigated control (more concentrated juices)
	Soluble proteins	~+45–67% vs. other treatments (highest under optimal water+N)
Excessive nitrogen fertilization (high N, ample water)	Soluble sugars, TSS	Decrease by ~30–36% (dilution and delayed ripening effect)
	Soluble proteins	Among lowest values (excess N leads to poor fruit compositional quality)
Severe water stress + excess N (extreme W_1N_3 scenario)	Soluble proteins	Strong decrease (40–67% drop) – fruit developmental issues under stress
	Palatability (taste)	Noticeably worsened (fruits small, less sweet, potentially more bitter)
Organic fertilizer inputs (compost, green manure)	B-vitamin content	Likely increases (not explicitly quantified, but improved soil microbiome could raise B levels)
	Soil microbial activity	Enhanced (improved nutrient cycling and possibly vitamin synthesis in soil)
Delayed harvest (overripe fruits)	Glycoalkaloids (solasonine, etc.)	Slight increase in content (more bitter compounds accumulate)
	Sensory bitterness	Slightly higher (overripe or stressed fruits taste more bitter)
High temperature regime + balanced nutrition	Titratable acidity (malic acid)	~1.5–1.6 g per 100 g (malic acid equiv.) – somewhat higher acidity observed under these conditions

The available data indicate that excessive inputs, especially water and nitrogen, generally reduce both flavor intensity and nutritional quality through dilution of sugars and proteins. By contrast, moderate and balanced resource supply consistently supports better fruit quality. Cultivar remains a major determinant of vitamin content, since genetic and geographic factors strongly condition this trait and cannot be fully corrected through agronomy alone, although varietal choice is still a key management decision. Organic fertilization appears to have indirect positive effects on vitamin levels as well, even if specific evidence for eggplant is still rather scarce and further studies are needed.

From a practical perspective, growers aiming for tastier eggplants with higher sugar and slightly improved protein should avoid over irrigation during fruit growth and refrain from excessive nitrogen supply. Instead, balanced nutrition combined with mild water limitation favors denser and more palatable fruits. Harvest timing is also essential, because fruits picked at proper maturity maintain low glycoalkaloid levels so that moderate stress does not translate into excessive bitterness. Overall, sugars, acids, proteins and minor vitamins are shaped by cultivation practices in parallel with major quality traits, and a controlled supply of water and nutrients generally provides the best compromise between sensory quality and nutritional value.

CONCLUSIONS

The research purpose was to demonstrate that the physicochemical and nutritional profile of eggplant fruits is highly sensitive to agricultural management. Core technological interventions such as irrigation control, fertilization regime and general cultivation practices exert strong influences on fruit composition, in many cases comparable to or even exceeding the effects of genetic variability among commercial hybrids. Through careful adjustment of these factors, growers can obtain eggplants with superior firmness, improved sensory quality and enhanced nutritional value, responding directly to the increasing consumer demand for foods with recognized health benefits.

Among all factors, water management proved to be one of the most decisive. Moderate water limitation repeatedly promoted higher dry matter, soluble sugars and antioxidant concentration, whereas excessive irrigation

resulted in dilution of these compounds. Controlled water supply leads to firmer and more flavorful fruits while maintaining acceptable yields. From a practical perspective, strategies such as regulated deficit irrigation or the cautious use of slightly saline reclaimed water can stimulate beneficial stress responses that intensify phenolic accumulation and soluble solids. However, these approaches must be applied carefully so that irreversible physiological damage not occurs. In contrast, excessive irrigation, often practiced to maximize fruit size, generally produces watery fruit with weak flavor and reduced nutritional density. These findings argue for a reorientation from yield maximization alone toward water use efficiency directed at quality improvement.

Nutrient management and soil practices are equally important. A balanced fertilization program, particularly when supported by micronutrient supplementation or organic inputs, was shown to significantly enrich eggplant fruits with essential minerals and vitamins. Foliar application of micronutrient containing fertilizers sharply increased fruit iron, zinc and related trace elements, directly enhancing dietary value. Likewise, organic amendments such as compost and green manure, together with beneficial soil microorganisms, improved both mineral uptake and antioxidant potential, in some cases nearly doubling antioxidant activity and markedly raising mineral content. These outcomes illustrate that sustainable soil management can elevate nutritional quality while simultaneously strengthening soil health. Still, the review also highlights the risks of over fertilization. Excess nitrogen favors vegetative growth but often suppresses fruit quality by lowering sugar levels and diluting mineral concentrations. Thus, the optimal strategy remains a balanced nutrient supply that supports productivity without disturbing the plant's metabolic equilibrium.

With respect to individual quality traits, the review confirms that several are highly responsive to agronomic manipulation, whereas others remain largely fixed by genetic programming. Antioxidant compounds, including phenolics, anthocyanins and vitamin C, belong to the first category, showing consistent increases under moderate stress and organic management. This offers practical opportunities for producing eggplant as a functional food through already accessible cultivation techniques. In contrast, lycopene

content appeared essentially unresponsive to field management, which helps focus future efforts on enhancing those compounds that can realistically be modified.

The interaction between yield and quality also deserves careful attention. In many evaluated studies, treatments producing maximum yields were not those generating the highest fruit quality. Often, intermediate input levels delivered fruits with clearly superior nutritional and sensory attributes at only a minor cost to yield. This reinforces a central horticultural principle that optimal production is a balance between quantity and quality. Practically, eggplant producers dispose of a broad set of agronomic tools capable of substantially upgrading crop value. By adjusting irrigation carefully, refining fertilization through integration of micronutrients and organic matter, avoiding nitrogen excess and selecting appropriate cultivars and harvest timing, it is possible to increase dry matter, enrich fruits in minerals and antioxidants and stabilize desirable flavor traits. These improvements benefit consumers through higher dietary quality and may also strengthen farm profitability through improved market appeal.

Overall, the review emphasizes the need for continued research at the interface between crop management and food quality. Future work should focus on understanding the physiological and molecular mechanisms behind stress induced phenolic accumulation, as well as the specific roles of different biofertilizers in nutrient and vitamin metabolism. Breeding efforts may further exploit these insights by selecting genotypes that respond efficiently to quality oriented cultivation systems. By integrating agronomy with nutritional science, modern agriculture can contribute not only to higher productivity but also to improved public health and environmental sustainability. In short, the goal is not simply to grow more eggplants, but to grow better ones, a direction that aligns well with the priorities of contemporary food systems.

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THE INFLUENCE OF ACTIVATED SLUDGE ON GERMINATION, GROWTH DEVELOPMENT AND BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF TOMATO SEEDLINGS (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.)

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study evaluated the effects of activated sludge on germination, early growth, photosynthetic pigments, and antioxidant capacity in *Lycopersicon esculentum*. Four treatments were applied: Control, LC, MC, and HC. Activated sludge markedly enhanced the germination index, with the strongest response in the HC group, likely due to its nutrient-rich composition and microbial activity. Biometric measurements showed improved plant height, root length, and leaf number in MC and HC treatments, indicating stimulated early growth. In contrast, chlorophyll a and b concentrations decreased with increasing sludge levels, suggesting a potential stress response or treatment-specific factors affecting pigment synthesis. Antioxidant assessments revealed substantial increases in total phenolic content and DPPH radical-scavenging activity in MC and HC groups, reflecting an enhanced antioxidant defense. The activated sludge shows promise as a sustainable organic amendment that improves germination and stress-related antioxidant capacity. Further research is needed to clarify the mechanisms underlying pigment reduction and to optimize application rates for agricultural use.

Keywords: active sludge, sustainability, sustainable agriculture

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INTRODUCTION

Lycopersicon esculentum (tomato) is one of the most important horticultural plants worldwide, with significant economic importance due to its extensive use in food consumption and the food processing industry. Tomatoes are widely cultivated in various regions globally and are valued for their rich content of vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants, such as lycopene.

The economic significance of tomatoes stems from the constant global demand, both for fresh consumption and for processed products such as sauces, tomato paste, and canned goods.

In the current context, agriculture faces multiple challenges, including climate change and drought. In this framework, the use of alternative resources, such as activated sludge derived from wastewater treatment, represents an innovative solution for improving seed germination and plant growth. Activated sludge is a byproduct of the wastewater treatment process and contains essential elements, including nutrients and beneficial microorganisms, which can stimulate plant growth and enhance soil fertility. Compared to regular water, activated sludge provides

additional advantages, such as a high content of organic matter and macro- and micronutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, etc.).

Previous studies have highlighted the beneficial effects of dried sludge on plant growth, but limited research has explored the use of liquid activated sludge. For example, a study conducted by Garcia, (2021) demonstrated that applying dried sludge to soil improved wheat seed germination and plant vigour by enriching the soil with essential nutrients. However, applying liquid activated sludge may offer additional advantages, such as faster nutrient absorption and increased activity of beneficial microorganisms in the soil (Seleiman et al., 2024).

This study makes a significant contribution to the scientific literature by investigating the effects of liquid activated sludge on tomato seed germination and growth, a relatively unexplored area. The use of liquid activated sludge presents an innovative approach that could provide viable solutions for farmers facing soil fertility issues and limited water availability.

The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the effects of activated sludge on germination and germination indicators in

tomato plants (*Lycopersicon esculentum*). Specifically, this research aims to determine:

- *Germination rate*: comparing the percentage of germinated seeds under activated sludge treatment versus regular water conditions.
- *Germination speed*: analysing the germination rate in both treatment conditions.
- *Plant vigour*: assessing plant vigour through growth measurements (plant height, biomass) and overall plant health.

This topic was chosen to highlight the potential benefits that activated sludge can bring to plant growth and productivity. The motivation for research arises from the need to find sustainable agricultural solutions, particularly in the context of drought and limited water availability. Additionally, this study contributes to expanding existing knowledge by offering new insights into the use of activated sludge in agriculture, contrasting with previous research that has primarily focused on dried sludge.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Plant Material

This study used tomato seeds (*Lycopersicon esculentum*), purchased from a local supermarket (Auchan). The seeds were selected to ensure uniformity and quality for germination and growth experiments.

2. Experimental Design

The experiment consisted of four treatment groups:

- Control (C): seeds were watered with regular water for 14 days.
- Low Concentration (LC): seeds were treated with a 2.5% activated sludge solution (2.5 ml sludge in 100 ml water).
- Medium Concentration (MC): seeds were treated with a 5% activated sludge solution (5 ml sludge in 100 ml water).
- High Concentration (HC): seeds were treated with a 10% activated sludge solution (10 ml sludge in 100 ml water).

The seeds were placed in four trays (15 x 10 cm) lined with cotton and filter paper. Each tray contained 24 selected seeds and was kept at room temperature (19-20°C) under natural light.

The experiment lasted 14 days. At the end of the experiment, the following analyses were performed:

- Germination analysis: germination rate and speed were recorded daily.
- Biometric measurements: plant height and biomass were assessed to evaluate plant vigour.
- Post-experimental processing: after measurements, plants were dried at 40°C for 9 hours, and prepared for further biochemical analyses:
- Chlorophyll and carotenoid content analysis
- DPPH assay: Antioxidant capacity evaluation using the DPPH method (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl).
- Total polyphenolic content by Folin-Ciocalteu assay

BIOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS

To evaluate plant growth and development, biometric measurements were conducted at the end of the 14-day period. The recorded parameters included:

- Plant height: Measured from the base of the stem to the tip of the highest leaf using a metric ruler.
- Root length: Measured from the root-stem junction to the longest root tip, assessing root system development.
- Stem length: The segment between the root insertion point and the first major branching or fully developed leaf.
- Leaf count per plant: The number of fully developed leaves, serving as an indicator of photosynthetic activity and plant health.

All measurements were taken under consistent conditions to minimize variability. The same operator conducted all assessments to ensure methodological accuracy.

PHOTOSYNTHETIC DETERMINATION

PIGMENT

Dried plant samples were ground, and 0.1 g of the powdered material was extracted with 3 ml of 70% ethanol. The mixture was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes, and the supernatant was analysed to

determine chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total carotenoid content. Spectrophotometric measurements were performed using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (UV mini-1240, Shimadzu) following the protocol described by Nayek S. et al., 2014.

DETERMINATION OF TOTAL PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS - FOLIN CIOCALTEU METHOD

The total phenolic content was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method, with slight modifications based on Singleton et al., 1999 and Vicas et al., 2019. The calibration curve was established using gallic acid standards in the range of 0.05-0.25 mg/ml, and results were expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/g of dry weight (dw). The calibration curve followed the regression equation $y = 2.2793x + 0.0862$ ($R^2 = 0.3584$).

DETERMINATION OF ANTIOXIDANT CAPACITY BY THE DPPH METHOD

The antioxidant capacity of the extracts was determined using the DPPH radical scavenging assay, following the protocol described by Miliauskas et al., 2003. For each sample, 0.1 mL of extract was mixed with 2.9 mL of 80 μ M DPPH solution and incubated in darkness for 30 minutes. Absorbance was measured at 517 nm using a Shimadzu UV-mini-1240 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The calibration curve was established using Trolox as a standard, and results were expressed as the

percentage of DPPH radical inhibition, calculated using the formula: Percent of inhibition of DPPH(%) = $\frac{(A_0 - A_s) \times 100}{A_0}$

Where:

- A_0 = absorbance at 517 nm for the blank sample
- A_s = absorbance at 517 nm for the extract samples.

The regression equation for the calibration curve was: $y = 0.218x + 97.125$ and $R^2 = 0.2043$ and the results were expressed as mol Trolox Equivalents (TE)/g dw.

RESULTS

1. Germination Index

Figure 1 shows the Germination Index (GI) for the four experimental groups, an indicator reflecting both the proportion of germinated seeds and the speed of germination. All treatments with activated sludge (LC, MC, and HC) resulted in significantly higher GI values compared with the control ($p < 0.05$). The HC group exhibited the highest GI, statistically exceeding both LC and MC, while the latter two did not differ significantly from each other. The control group recorded the lowest GI, indicating reduced germination performance relative to all treated groups. These results demonstrate a clear, concentration-dependent increase in the Germination Index across the activated-sludge treatments.

Figure 1 Germination Index (GI) of *Lycopersicon esculentum* seeds across the four experimental groups: Control, LC, MC, and HC. Bars represent mean \pm standard deviation.

2. Photosynthetic Pigment Analysis

Figure 2 shows the concentrations of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and carotenoids across the four treatment groups. Chlorophyll a levels were highest in the control group (6.81 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and progressively decreased with increasing sludge concentration, reaching the lowest value in the HC group (5.79 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). A similar pattern was observed for chlorophyll b: the control group displayed the highest concentration (7.00 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), while the HC treatment recorded the lowest (6.32 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Carotenoid content showed a slightly different trend. The highest carotenoid concentration occurred in the MC group (0.87 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), followed by HC

(0.81 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), whereas the control and LC groups exhibited comparable values (0.78–0.79 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Overall, these results demonstrate that activated sludge treatments modified the pigment profile of *Lycopersicon esculentum* seedlings. Increasing sludge concentration was associated with a gradual reduction in chlorophyll a and b levels, while carotenoid content showed a moderate increase at intermediate and high treatments.

Figure 2 Concentrations of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and carotenoids in *Lycopersicon esculentum* seedlings subjected to Control, LC, MC, and HC treatments. Values are presented as mean \pm standard deviation

3. Determination of total phenolic compounds - Folin Ciocalteu Method

Figure 3 presents the total phenolic content (TPC) of *Lycopersicon esculentum* seedlings across the four treatment groups. The MC group exhibited the highest TPC value (5.32 mg GAE/g dw), followed by the HC group (3.28 mg GAE/g dw). In contrast, the Control and LC groups showed

markedly lower and comparable TPC values (1.07 and 1.11 mg GAE/g dw, respectively). These results indicate that medium and high concentrations of activated sludge led to a pronounced increase in phenolic compound accumulation, whereas low-concentration treatment produced no substantial change relative to the untreated control.

Figure 3 Total phenolic content (TPC) of *Lycopersicon esculentum* seedlings subjected to Control, LC, MC, and HC treatments. Values are expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents/gram dry weight (mg GAE/g dw) and presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

4. Determination of antioxidant capacity using the DPPH method

Figure 4 shows the antioxidant capacity of *Lycopersicon esculentum* seedlings, expressed as DPPH radical-scavenging activity. The lowest antioxidant activity was observed in the LC group (0.95 mol/g dw), followed by the Control group (2.40 mol/g dw). In contrast, the MC

treatment produced a marked increase in antioxidant capacity (4.97 mol/g dw), and the highest value was recorded in the HC group (6.59 mol/g dw). These results indicate a clear dose-dependent enhancement of antioxidant activity, with medium and high sludge concentrations substantially increasing the plant's radical-scavenging potential.

Figure 4 Antioxidant capacity of *Lycopersicon esculentum* seedlings determined by the DPPH radical-scavenging assay across the Control, LC, MC, and HC treatments. Values are expressed as mol DPPH scavenged per gram dry weight (mol/g dw) and presented as mean \pm SD.

DISCUSSIONS

Germination Analysis

The results of this study show that activated sludge treatments significantly enhanced the germination index of *Lycopersicon esculentum* seeds, with the most pronounced effect observed in the HC treatment. This stimulation contrasts with some previous findings, where organic

amendments such as compost teas or wastewater by-products either had no significant influence or negatively affected germination due to phytotoxic compounds (Coria et al., 2022; Smith, 2020). The discrepancy may be attributed to differences in the physicochemical properties of the organic materials used. Activated sludge contains elevated levels of

nitrogen, micronutrients, and beneficial microbial communities that may accelerate enzymatic processes linked to early germination and radicle emergence (Seleiman et al., 2019).

Furthermore, sludge-derived microorganisms may contribute to the breakdown of inhibitory seed coat components or support early root development, resulting in improved germination performance compared with the control. These findings highlight the importance of sludge composition, stabilization process, and application rate in determining its biological impact on seed germination.

Photosynthetic Pigment Determination

Unlike several previous studies reporting increases in chlorophyll a and b following the application of organic fertilizers or compost extracts (Mthiyane et al., 2024; Carrascosa et al., 2023), the present study revealed a reduction in chlorophyll content as sludge concentration increased. This decline may indicate a mild stress response, potentially linked to salinity, heavy metal traces, or an imbalance in nutrient availability commonly associated with certain types of wastewater-derived amendments (Irin et al., 2024).

Chlorophyll reduction is a well-documented physiological marker of plant stress, often associated with disruptions in chlorophyll biosynthesis, enhanced degradation, or impaired nutrient uptake (Li et al., 2015). It is possible that exceeding a threshold concentration of particularly in MC and HC treatments—resulted in conditions unfavorable for pigment stability and photosynthetic efficiency.

These results emphasize the need to optimize sludge dosage to balance its fertilizing benefits with potential physiological constraints on photosynthetic machinery.

Antioxidant Capacity Determination

The antioxidant assays demonstrated a strong dose-dependent increase in radical-scavenging activity, with

the HC treatment showing the highest DPPH values. This pattern differs from some previous reports where organic amendments triggered neutral or reduced antioxidant responses (Rusli et al., 2022). However, increased antioxidant activity under sludge treatment is consistent with studies indicating that moderate abiotic stress caused by organic residues, salinity, or micronutrient accumulation, can stimulate the biosynthesis of phenolic compounds as part of the plant's protective mechanism (Kaczur et al., 2025; Ray et al., 2024).

The elevated total phenolic content observed in MC and HC groups supports this interpretation, suggesting that activated sludge induced a metabolic adjustment aimed at counteracting oxidative stress. Phenolics and related secondary metabolites function as radical scavengers, metal chelators, and modulators of stress signaling, which together contribute to the increased DPPH capacity recorded in this study. Differences from earlier findings likely stem from variations in sludge composition, extraction solvents, and antioxidant assessment methods, all of which are known to influence phenolic quantification and radical scavenging results.

CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated the effects of activated sludge on germination, early vegetative development, photosynthetic pigments, and antioxidant capacity in *Lycopersicon esculentum*. The results highlight the potential of activated sludge as a sustainable organic amendment with measurable benefits for plant performance. Activated sludge markedly enhanced seed germination, with the highest concentration producing the greatest improvement. This stimulatory effect is likely associated with its enriched nutrient profile and beneficial microbial communities, contrasting with reports in the literature where organic treatments have shown neutral or inhibitory effects. Biometric parameters including plant height, root length, and leaf

number, also increased in response to sludge application, particularly at medium and high concentrations, indicating a positive influence on early plant growth.

In terms of physiological traits, a decline in chlorophyll a and b levels was observed as sludge concentration increased. This finding diverges from previous studies reporting enhanced pigment synthesis following organic amendments and may reflect treatment-specific differences in sludge composition or associated stress factors.

Conversely, antioxidant capacity increased substantially under sludge treatments, with the highest values recorded at higher concentrations. The elevated DPPH radical-scavenging activity and the corresponding rise in total phenolic content suggest that activated sludge may induce protective metabolic responses that strengthen plant resilience to oxidative stress.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that activated sludge has promising applications as an organic soil amendment capable of improving seed germination, growth, and antioxidant potential in tomato plants. Nonetheless, further investigations are needed to elucidate the underlying biochemical mechanisms, assess long-term soil and plant impacts, and determine optimal application rates to ensure safe and effective use in agricultural systems.

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ANTIOXIDANT CAPACITY OF BLACKBERRIES AND BLUEBERRIES: CORRELATION WITH POLYPHENOLS AND IMPACT OF GROWING CONDITIONS

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

Since ancient times, the relationship between man and nature has been one of coexistence, nature providing vital resources for survival. Although, at first, man only intuited the importance of this connection, the evolution of knowledge has highlighted the need for a correct and conscious attitude towards the environment, considered an essential source for achieving human happiness and prosperity.

With scientific advances, people are actively searching nature for untapped natural remedies to their full potential, aware of the benefits they can provide. Particular interest is given to polyphenols, the main constituents of plant products. These compounds are found in abundance in medicinal plants, which are a major source of new pharmaceuticals.

The antioxidant properties of plant constituents are the basis of their role in disease prevention and control, being associated in particular with the wide range of polyphenolic compounds (including phytochemicals, pro-vitamins and nutraceuticals).

The aim of this paper was to analyze published scientific articles to evaluate and compare data on: total polyphenol content, total flavonoid content and antioxidant capacity of extracts obtained from berries (wild or cultivated) harvested from various geographical areas globally.

Keywords: natural remedies, polyphenols, flavonoids, medicinal plants, berries

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INTRODUCTION

Polyphenols are natural phytochemical compounds found in plants, fruits, vegetables, whole grains, vegetables, tea, coffee, wine, cocoa and medicinal plants, with more than 8000 polyphenolic compounds being identified, including phenolic acids, flavonoids, stilbenes, lignans and polymeric lignans in plant foods (Pandey & Rizvi, 2009).

Polyphenols are secondary metabolites of plants that act as a barrier against ultraviolet radiation, oxidants and pathogens (Beckman, 2000). Based on these possible therapeutic properties, in recent years numerous researchers have been involved to find new

sources of polyphenols that can have applications in the food industry and the pharmaceutical industry. Studies have estimated that the dietary intake of polyphenols is about 1 g of polyphenols/day (Khoddami et al., 2013). The bioavailability of these bioactive compounds depends on the preparation process of plant products containing polyphenols, the process of gastrointestinal digestion, their absorption and metabolism (Scalbert & Williamson, 2000). During absorption, dietary polyphenols must be hydrolyzed by intestinal enzymes or microflora in the colon and then conjugated in intestinal cells and subsequently in the liver by methylation, sulfation or glucuronidation (Scalbert et al., 2002). So, polyphenols reach and accumulate in the target

tissue and induce biological properties, and polyphenol derivatives are mainly eliminated through bile and urine.

Various studies in the literature have shown that some of the polyphenolic compounds (procyanidins, quercetin, procyanidins, flavanols) have a rapid absorption in plasma, having maximum plasma concentrations 2-3 hours after ingestion (Manach et al., 2004). There are studies attesting to the biological activities and beneficial properties of these compounds, including: antioxidant, antiallergic, anti-inflammatory, antiviral and antimicrobial, anti-proliferative, anti-mutagenic, anti-carcinogenic, free radical blocking, regulation of cell cycle stopping, apoptosis and induction of antioxidant enzymes. Free radicals can damage cells and play an important role in heart disease, cancer, and other diseases. Studies suggest that a rich intake of antioxidants is associated with a lower risk of cancer, cardiovascular disease, Parkinson's disease, and Alzheimer's (Sharma et al., 2013).

1. DEFINITION, CHEMICAL STRUCTURE

Polyphenols are a large and varied group of aromatic benzene ring compounds with one or more hydroxyl groups, produced by plants mainly for protection against oxidative stress, synthesized during plant development (Harborne et al., 1982) or in response to certain adverse conditions (UV radiation, etc.) (Shahidi, 2004).

Over time, polyphenols have been classified into several categories based on the number of phenolic rings and the structural elements that connect these rings to each other (Pietta et al., 2003), this class includes simple phenols, phenolic acids, coumarins, flavonoids, stilbenes, hydrolyzable and condensed tannins, lignans, and lignins.

Phenolic acids comprise two main branches: derivatives of hydroxybenzoic acid (protocatechic acid, gallic acid, p-hydroxybenzoic acid) and derivatives of hydroxycinnamic acid (caffeic acid, chlorogenic acid, coumaric acid, ferulic acid, synapic acid). Caffeic, p-coumaric, vanilla, ferulic and protocatechic acids are acids present in almost all plants.

Flavonoids are the most abundant polyphenols in the human diet and more than 4000 types have been identified. These compounds have at least two phenol subunits, and compounds that possess three or more

phenol subunits are called tannins (hydrolyzable and non-hydrolyzable). Flavonoids are planar molecules, ubiquitous in plants, consisting of the aromatic amino acid, phenylalanine, tyrosine and malonate (Harborne et al., 1986). The basic flavonoid structure is the flavan nucleus, which consists of 15 carbon atoms arranged in three rings (C6-C3-C6). There are six subclasses of flavonoids including anthocyanins, flavonols, flavanols, flavanones, flavones, and isoflavones; Anthocyanins (cyanidin, pelargonidin, delphinidin, malvidine) which are found in the family of berries, red wine, red cabbage, cherry, black grapes and strawberries. Flavonols, including quercetin, campferol, and myricetin, have been detected in onions, leeks, broccoli, and blueberries. Isoflavones are the most important dietary flavonoids that include daidzein, genistein, and glycitain. Stilbenes occur in the human diet in small quantities; Resveratrol, one of the well-studied compounds in these groups, is largely detected in grapes and red wine (Pandey & Rizvi, 2009).

2. CLASSIFICATION OF POLYPHENOLS

Polyphenols in food can be classified according to the number of phenolic rings and the structural elements to which the phenolic nucleus attaches, into four broad categories:

- **Phenolic acids** - found in abundance in food and are divided into two subclasses: benzoic acid derivatives and cinnamic acid derivatives. The content of hydroxybenzoic acids in edible plants is generally low. Exceptions are certain red fruits, black radish and onions, where they can have concentrations of several tens of mg/kg of fresh product. Hydroxycinnamic acids are more common than hydroxybenzoic acids and consist mainly of p-coumaric, caffeic, ferulic and synapic acids.

- **Flavonoids** are the most studied group of polyphenols. Flavonoids have a common basic structure consisting of two aromatic rings that are linked together by three carbon atoms that form a heterocycle with oxygen. More than 4,000 types of flavonoids have been identified, many of which are responsible for the attractive colors of flowers, fruits, and leaves. The classification by the heterocycle involved, divides flavonoids into six subclasses: flavonols (kaempferol, quercetin, myricetin), flavones (apigenin, luteolin), flavanones (naringenin, ariodictiol, hisperidine), flavanols (quercetin, catechin/epicatechin, gallo catechin, tannins or proanthocyanidins,

procyanidins, prodelfinidins, etc.), anthocyanins (pelargonidin, cyanidin, delphinidin, petunidin, malvidin) and isoflavones (glycein, formononetin, genistein). Quercetin, myricetin, catechins, etc., are some of the most common flavonoids.

- **Stilbene** – contain two linked phenyl through a methylene bridge. The occurrence of stilbenes in the human diet is quite low. Most plant stilbenes act as antifungal phytoalexins, compounds that are only synthesized in response to infection or injury. One of the best-studied, naturally occurring polyphenol stilbene is resveratrol (3, 4', 5-trihydroxystilbene), which is mostly found in grapes, in red wine.

- **Lignins/lignans** - are diphenolic compounds containing a 2,3-dibenzylbutane structure that is formed by the dimerization of two cinnamic acid residues. Several lignans (secoisolariciresinol), are considered phytoestrogens. The richest dietary source is flaxseed, which contains secoisolariciresinol (up to 3.7 g/kg dry product) and small amounts of matairesinol (Pietta, Gardana & 2003).

3. EXTRACTION, ESTIMATION AND QUANTIFICATION OF PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS

3.1. Extraction of phenolic compounds

Phenolic compounds are very important components for plants and for human health, so it is very useful to know their concentration and their biological activity, which may indicate a potential use of them as therapeutic agents (Benedec et al., 2013).

In general, the extraction of phenolic compounds from the plant product is influenced by their chemical nature, sample size, extraction time and storage conditions, as well as the presence of interfering substances. The most widely used method of extracting polyphenolic compounds from plants is the one that uses solvents, being an easy, efficient method that can be applied on a very large scale. Chemical extraction depends on the type of solvent being used, the polarity of the solvent used, the extraction time and temperature, as well as the chemical composition and physical characteristics of the samples being analyzed.

Among the most used solvents we can mention: water, acetone, methanol, ethanol, N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF) or their mixtures with water, the mixtures being more efficient at extraction, because the solvents are of different polarities and thus, they can solubilize several components of plant products (Rajbhar et al.,

2015)]. Hydrophilic polyphenols, including aglycones, glycosides and oligomers, are extracted using water, polar organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile and acetone, or their mixture with water. Liquid extracts are sometimes divided with solvents such as ethyl acetate, depending on the solubility of the target polyphenols. Polyphenols are more stable at a low pH because the acidic environment helps polyphenols remain neutral, so they can be easily extracted into organic solvents (Khoddami, Wilkes & 2013). The use of an alcoholic solution ensures a satisfactory extraction. Methanol, acetone, and water are inefficient solvents for the total extraction of phenols from plants in powder form, as polyphenols are associated with other biomolecules such as proteins, polysaccharides, terpenes, chlorophyll, lipids, and inorganic compounds. However, methanol extracts have been shown to be better for extracting catechins, epicatechin, and epigallocatechin (Koffi et al., 2013). Aqueous acetone mixtures are good solvents for polar polyphenols, but unwanted residues remain in the extracts. The low solubility of polyphenols in absolute organic solvents is due to the strength of the hydrogen bonds between polyphenols and proteins. The increase in solubility by adding water to organic solvents is due to the weakening of hydrogen bonds in aqueous solutions.

3.2. Estimation and quantification of phenolic compounds

For the estimation and quantification of phenolic compounds, the Folin-Ciocalteu test is used. The test is a method of quantifying the total polyphenol content using different solvents (e.g. methanol) to demonstrate their extraction efficiency. The test uses the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, a reagent containing molybdenum in a superior state of oxidation (+6), which has a yellow color. Polyphenolic compounds lead to the reduction of Mo6+ from a higher oxidation state to one of the lower oxidation states (Mo4+, Mo5+) which have a blue color and can be monitored at a wavelength of 765 nm (Folin & Ciocalteu, 1927).

Polyphenol estimation can be done by different techniques, for example: nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, near-infrared reflection spectroscopy, high-performance thin-layer chromatography (HPTLC), liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectroscopy (LC-MS), high-performance capillary electrophoresis (HPCE) and high-

performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). In addition to organic solvent extraction, qualitative and quantitative analysis techniques can be applied, as well as isolation and purification procedures for more specific results. Chromatographic techniques such as thin-layer chromatography (TLC), high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC) and subsequently capillary electrophoresis (CE), column chromatography (CC) over Sephadex LH-20 are used for final purification, due to the clear solutions that are obtained, without residues (Rajbhar, Dawda & 2015).

3.3. Total flavonoid estimation

The results reported in the literature for the total flavonoid content were obtained using the $AlCl_3$ colorimetric method. The principle on which the colorimetric method is based is that $AlCl_3$ forms stable complexes with the carbonyl groups (keto-C-4 and/or with the hydroxyl C-3 or C-5 group) of flavones and flavonols. Such complexes also form $AlCl_3$ with the ortho-dihydroxyl groups in the A or B ring of flavonoids, whose absorbance can be measured with the help of a spectrophotometer at an appropriate wavelength.

3.4. Evaluation of antioxidant capacity

There is a growing demand to evaluate the antioxidant properties of plant extracts, and in recent years, attention has focused on antioxidant products from natural sources (De Judicibus, 2011).

Much research is focused on antioxidant activity, flavonoid content of medicinal plants, and total polyphenol content, but for other medicinal plants there is no data on their antioxidant action (Nikolova et al., 2013).

The methods used to determine total antioxidant capacity can be divided into two major groups: methods based on electron transfer (SET-single electron transfer) and hydrogen atom transfer reaction (HAT). SET methods include ABTS/TEAC analysis (Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity), FRAP (iron reduction ability), CUPRAC (copper reduction) test, and DPPH (2,2-diphenylpyrylhydrazil radical capture capacity); HAPX test. The hydrogen atom transfer reaction (HAT) method includes ORAC (oxygen radical absorption capacity) and TRAP (total radical-trapping antioxidant parameter) analysis. These tests are frequently used to measure the total antioxidant capacity of extracts, but a single test will not reflect all the antioxidants present in the system (De Judicibus, 2011).

Using the data provided by the literature, we will list the most common tests to check the antioxidant capacity of extracts.

3.5. DPPH Test

DPPH test is a simple, fast, inexpensive analysis that determines antioxidant capacity *in vitro* and is based on the evaluation of the free radical scavenging activity of plant extracts using a radical reagent of 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazil. DPPH is an intense purple color that, after being reduced by an antioxidant (the flavonoids in the plant extract), turns into a pale yellow or colorless product. It measures the ability of compounds extracted from different plant products to fight free radicals or compounds that can release hydrogen ions. The turn can be seen with the naked eye (Güzel et al., 2019).

The absorbance after the neutralization reaction of the DPPH reagent by the flavonoids contained in the plant extract can be read with the help of a UV-VIS spectrophotometer at the wavelength of 515 nm.

3.6. FRAP Test

The FRAP test is a method by which the antioxidant capacity of compounds from plant extracts can be evaluated by evaluating the reduction power of the Fe^{3+} ion to Fe^{2+} , which is chelated by TPTZ to form the Fe^{2+} - TPTZ complex, with a maximum absorption at 593 nm, using a spectrophotometer to measure the absorbance of the colored product (Benzie & Strain, 1996).

III.7. CUPRAC test – reduction of Cu^{2+} ions

The FRAP test is based on the evaluation of the capacity to reduce copper ions (Cu^{2+}) evidenced by changing the color from light blue to yellow-orange of a complex: $Cu(II)$ -neocuproine (2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline) (Benzie & Strain, 1996).

III.8. Oxygen Radical Absorbing Activity (ORAC)

By this method, the activity of peroxy radical absorption is measured using 6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid (Trolox) as standard (Huang et al., 2002).

III.9. ABTS Radical Cation Discoloration Test

The ABTS analysis is based on the ability of an ABTS radical cation capture sample (ABTS+), a green-blue chromophore that absorbs at 734 nm, the method being compared to the Trolox standard (Arnao et al., 2001).

1. TOTAL DETERMINATION OF POLYPHENOLS, FLAVONOIDS AND ANTIOXIDANT CAPACITY OF BERRIES

In one study, three varieties of blackberries were analyzed: prickly, thorny and sweet tomatoes, harvested at three different stages of maturity, maturity appreciated by their color. The study found that red blackberries have the highest polyphenol content (104 ± 1 , 31 ± 1 , 20.0 ± 0.5 mg GAE/g DW), followed by blackberries (93 ± 1 , 25.3 ± 0.2 , 17.6 ± 0.1 mg GAE/g DW) and then sweet blackberries (83 ± 2 , 20.3 ± 0.2 , 13.5 ± 0.3 mg GAE/g DW).

The ORAC test (expressed as mmol Trolox equivalent/g dry mass, *mmol TE/g DW*), showed that antioxidant activity decreases from green, pink, and ripe fruits from prickly berries (2805 ± 25 , 1543 ± 71 , 994 ± 9 mmol TE/g DW), to prickly berries (2131 ± 15 , 1230 ± 12 , 767 ± 5 mmol TE/g DW) and then to sweet blackberries (1781 ± 28 , 866 ± 14 , 551 ± 10 mmol TE/g DW). The results are similar to the total polyphenol content found in the first Folin-Ciocalteu method. As for the anthocyanin content determined on the three types of blackberries, reported as mg cyanidin-3-glucoside equivalent/g dry sample, increased as the fruit ripened, in order: prickly blackberries (1.38 ± 0.06 , 3.3 ± 0.2 , 15.4 ± 0.3 mg cyanidin-3-glycoside equivalent), prickly blackberries (0.92 ± 0.01 , 2.37 ± 0.06 , 11.3 ± 0.1 mg cyanidin-3-glycoside equivalent), blackberry (0.71 ± 0.05 , 2.02 ± 0.06 , 9.0 ± 0.4 mg cyanidin-3-glycoside equivalent) (Van de Velde et al., 2019).

In another study carried out on blueberry (*Vaccinium myrtillus*) and sea buckthorn (*Hippophaë rhamnoides*) fruits, from Romania, it was observed that the total polyphenol content determined with the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent of the freeze-dried extract of blueberry fruits (343.93 ± 0.01 mg GAE/100g DW) is lower compared to that of the alcoholic extract of the same fruit (812.13 ± 0.02 mg GAE/100g DW). For sea buckthorn fruits, higher content of total polyphenols was found in the freeze-dried extract (251.47 ± 0.02 mg GAE/100g DW), compared to the alcoholic extract (211.91 ± 0.02 mg GAE/100g DW). The total flavonoid content for blueberry fruits was higher for the alcoholic extract (125.82 ± 8.91 mg QE/100 g DW) than for the freeze-dried extract (72.80 ± 7.61 mg QE/100g DW), and for sea buckthorn fruits, the flavonoid content was higher for the freeze-dried extract (145.44 ± 8.72 mg QE/100g DW) compared to the alcoholic extract (43.14 ± 2.42 mg QE/100g DW).

The antioxidant capacity of the two extracts was carried out by three established methods: DPPH, ABTS and FRAP, and the results obtained for the blueberry fruits were:

- in the case of lyophilized extract - DPPH 8.51 ± 1.11 %, ABTS 326.95 ± 5.98 $\mu\text{mol TE/g DW}$, FRAP 73.05 ± 0.00 $\mu\text{mol TE/g DW}$,
- in the case of alcoholic extract - DPPH 34.02 ± 2.01 %, ABTS 280.91 ± 1.12 $\mu\text{mol TE/g DW}$, FRAP 201.91 ± 0.05 $\mu\text{mol TE/g DW}$. For sea buckthorn fruits, the results were:
- for freeze-dried extract - DPPH 4.12 ± 0.11 %, ABTS 48.67 ± 0.31 $\mu\text{mol TE/g DW}$, FRAP 44.41 ± 0.01 $\mu\text{mol TE/g DW}$,
- for alcoholic extract - DPPH 47.41 ± 3.22 %, ABTS 56.85 ± 3.25 $\mu\text{mol TE/g DW}$, FRAP 52.78 ± 0.01 $\mu\text{mol TE/g DW}$ (Jurca, Vicas, et al., 2016).

Another plant product analyzed was the blueberry fruit, *Myrtillum vaccinum* (blueberry), collected from Bihor County, Apuseni Mountains. The harvested blueberries (a1) were analyzed compared to four other types of samples: (a2) - blueberry tea, (a3) - blueberry tincture, (a4) - blueberry capsules, (a5) - cranberry alcoholic extract, on the Romanian market.

After harvesting, the cranberry fruits were dried, and ground to obtain a powder, samples A2 and A4 were extracted with 70% ethanol solution (1:10 g/v) using a magnetic mixer for 20 min and then sonicated for 5 minutes, and samples A5 and A3 were centrifuged and supernatants were evaporated in vacuum and then frozen and freeze-dried.

The comparative data on bioactive compounds such as total polyphenols, total flavonoids and antioxidant capacity of the five blueberry preparations are different.

- Total polyphenol content, expressed in mg GAE/100 g DW, was: a1- 343.90 ± 7.32 , a2 - 344.60 ± 4.96 , a3 - 811.26 ± 14.53 , a4 - 341.51 ± 9.11 , a5 - 813.42 ± 15.55 .
- Total flavonoid content, expressed in mg QE/100 g DW, was: a1- 1182.95 ± 6.46 , a2 - 1180.55 ± 6.47 , a3 - 1426.00 ± 1.80 , a4 - 1179.19 ± 7.90 , a5 - 1425.44 ± 1.94 .
- The antioxidant capacity of the five The samples analyzed were carried out with the help of three methods, and the results obtained were:
 - ✓ DPPH (a1- 82.38 ± 17.56 , a2 - 86.36 ± 13.67 , a3 - 3.12 ± 0.33 , a4 - 78.50 ± 16.85 , a5 - 3.24 ± 0.40 %);
 - ✓ ABTS (a1- 326.36 ± 3.88 , a2 -

327.63±3.42, a3 - 275.55±21.10, a4 - 324.66±7.41, a5 - 283.51±19.59 µmol TE/g DW);

✓ FRAP (a1- 73.16±1.86, a2 - 74.78±4.86, a3 - 3.39±0.16, a4 - 69.12±3.19, a5 - 3.46±0.22 µmol TE/g) (Jurca, Vicaş, et al., 2016).

The objectives of another study were to investigate and compare the nutritional substances and antioxidant potential of three blackberry species (*Rubus ellipticus*, *Rubus niveus*, *Rubus ulmifolius*) that are the most consumed by Himalayan communities. Fresh and ripe fruits were collected from different localities in the Himalayan Mountains, Pakistan. In addition to the antioxidant effect, they also analyzed the content of fats, saccharides, proteins, fibers and essential minerals: Ca, P, Mg, K, Na, Cl, S, Mn, Zn, Fe, Cu, Se, Co, Ni.

The fruits were air-dried at a temperature of 65°C for 48 hours. To analyze the antioxidant capacity, the dried fruits are ground and extracted with methanol. Methanol extracts of fruits of *Rubus* species were tested with the DPPH test, using an extract with a concentration of 1 mg crude extract/mL. The extracts show a high antioxidant capacity (>50%).

The DPPH analysis performed for the three types of blackberry (*Rubus ellipticus*, *Rubus niveus*, *Rubus ulmifolius*), of four concentrations showed different results: at 50 µg/mL - *R. ulmifolius* (80.28%) > *R. niveus* (68.30%) > *R. Ellipticus* (45.97%), at 100 µg/mL - *R. ulmifolius* (87.62%) > *R. niveus* (74.54%) > *R. ellipticus* (54.82%), at 200 µg/mL - *R. ulmifolius* (94.46%) > *R. niveus* (80.38%) > *R. Ellipticus* (72.23%), at 400 µg/mL - *R. ulmifolius* (98.89%) > *R. niveus* (91.64%) > *R. Ellipticus* (84.00%). It was also observed that with the increase in the concentration of the extract used, the antioxidant capacity increased. The authors' conclusion was that due to the nutritional content of *Rubus* fruits, they may constitute an alternative source of edible wild fruits (Ahmad et al., 2015).

Another study looked at fresh blackberries, blueberries, black raspberries, and red raspberries purchased from a local market in Texas. To obtain the extracts, the fresh fruits were frozen and ground, then 95% ethanol (1: 4 w/v) was added over them, at room temperature for 2 days, then centrifuged at 3500 revolutions/minute for 20 minutes. The supernatants were filtered and stored at -20 °C.

The total determination of polyphenols (expressed in mg GAE/g FW), flavonoids (expressed in mg QE/g FW) and proanthocyanidins (mg GAE/g FW) led to various results:

- blueberries: 443.6, 151.7, 1589.6;
- Blackberry: 269.5, 56.7, 763.2;
- black raspberry: 965.4, 186.4, 2677.0;
- Red raspberries: 434.3, 114.5, 946.9.

The highest concentration of polyphenols, flavonoids and proanthocyanidins was found in black raspberries, followed by blueberries, red raspberries, blackberries.

Determination of antioxidant capacity using the FRAP method (expressed in mmol Fe²⁺/kg FW, showed a variation in the order: red raspberries > blackberries > black raspberries and blueberries. The *in vitro* antioxidant capacity in fruit extracts was determined with the DPPH and ABTS assays/methods. For blueberry, black raspberry and red extracts, very high values were obtained, which increased with increasing extract concentration (20–100 µg/mL): blueberries 38.5% to 87.9%, black raspberries 64.2% to 89%, blackberries 40.5% to 77.8% and red raspberries 37.6% to 87%. Comparing fruit extracts of the highest concentration, the descending order of antioxidant capacity is: black raspberries > blueberries > blackberries > red raspberries. The ABTS analysis to determine the antioxidant capacity led to the obtaining of different values, values that increased with the increase in the concentration of the extracts: for blueberries 11.1-23.1%, for blackberries 18.2-25.3%, for black raspberries 20.1-21.3% and for red raspberries 20.9-31.1% (Basu & Maier, 2016).

In order to compare the quality characteristics, as well as the content of polyphenols and anthocyanins and antioxidant activity, six fruits were analyzed, including black currant (*A. Melanocarpa*), blueberry (*Vaccinium ugliedinosum*), cherries, cranberries (*Vaccinium macrocarpom*), raspberries and strawberries. These fruits have been evaluated for potential use in the development of functional drinks. The fruit comes from the store and has been frozen. For the preparation of the samples, 5 g of frozen fruit was ground and then mixed with 45 mL ethanol of 94.5% concentration. The mixtures were stirred for 24 hours, at a temperature of 24°C, at 100 revolutions/minute, then centrifuged at 4°C, for 20 minutes at 8000 revolutions/minute and then filtered.

The highest total polyphenol content was determined in black squirrels (6001.3 mg GAE/100 g FW), followed by blueberries (2322.3 mg GAE/100 g FW), cranberries (1561.0 mg GAE/100 g FW), raspberries (1225.5 mg GAE/100 g FW), strawberries (1082.0 mg GAE/100 g FW) and cherries (693.3 mg GAE/100 g FW).

The anthocyanin content of the fruits analyzed in the study ranged from 0.27 to 1.74 mg anthocyanin/g FW: cranberries (1.74), raspberries (1.50), black carrots (1.04), followed by blueberries (0.80), cherries (0.27) and strawberries (0.13).

The antioxidant capacity of these fruits was determined by using the DPPH test and showed that cranberries have the highest antioxidant capacity (52.4%), followed by raspberries (39.8%), black scabs (35.9%), blueberries (33.5%), cherries (18.5%) (Kim et al., 2018).

CONCLUSIONS

This review shows that blackberries and blueberries are outstanding natural sources of antioxidants (polyphenols and anthocyanins), their antioxidant capacity being closely correlated with these components. It is observed that wild varieties are generally superior to those grown in terms of antioxidant content, and blackberries demonstrate a higher antioxidant capacity than blueberries. The study shows that in blackberries, the green ripening phase contains the highest concentration of polyphenols and has the highest antioxidant activity, while anthocyanins increase as the fruit ripens. Extraction is most effective using 95% ethanol, and most of the antioxidants in blueberries are found in the skin of the fruit. This data is valuable for both researchers looking for new sources of antioxidants and growers targeting strains with increased health benefits.

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ANALYSIS OF IMPORTANT FACTORS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE SALONTA AREA, BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This article aims to analyse the main factors that can contribute to economic growth in the area bordering Salonta municipality in Biho rcounty, Romania, with the intention of transforming this area into a centre of polarisation in the economic and investment fields for the localities bordering Salonta municipality: Avram-Iancu, Ciumeghiu, Batăr, Tulca, and Mădăras. In this context, the existing development resources in these communes are analysed, respectively the analysis of human resources and soil resources. The research results provide valuable information that can support the development of efficient solutions and programs for administrative and political decision-makers. Thus, the research can contribute to the identification of best practices and measures for the consolidation and valorisation of the potential of these communities, ensuring a balance between economic, social development and environmental protection in the sustainable context in the area bordering Salonta municipality – the communes of Avram-Iancu, Ciumeghiu, Batăr, Tulca, and Mădăras.

Keywords: human resources, soil resources, agriculture, economic development.

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INTRODUCTION

To ensure a sustainable and equitable development of the rural area bordering Salonta municipality, it is essential to consider the use of available resources and labour force, which is why we have taken into account the analysis of available resources and existing labour resources in the bordering area of this locality. The studies conducted allow the identification of effective means for increasing the attractiveness and interest of the factors involved in promoting the development directions of rural communities. (Cristina et al, 2015; Mateoc -Sîrb et al, 2024).

The results of the research obtained can support the development of solutions and programs useful to administrative and political decision-makers, facilitating the design of a clear strategy for the promotion of rural communities. Thus, these efforts can contribute

to strengthening the role of rural communities as essential elements of sustainable development policy, promoting the balance between economic growth, environmental protection, and social cohesion in rural areas. (Man et al, 2007; Mateoc -Sîrb et al, 2013).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The analysis of the main factors of economic growth in the research area, namely, population dynamics and the evolution of land as a source of agricultural development can contribute to economic growth in this area.

The study was conducted based on data published by official data sources (INS), and the main methods used consist in quantitative and qualitative analysis, analysis based on the system of statistical indicators (multicriteria analysis), and field research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Population growth, combined with efficient management and modernisation of the

land fund, can generate a favourable environment for the sustainable development of agriculture and, implicitly, for economic growth in the research area. These factors need to be supported by appropriate policies, investments, and innovation to maximize the benefits for the entire area.

Changes in the demographic structure (e.g. urbanisation, rural-urban migration) can affect the availability of labour and may require adaptations in production methods (Mateoc-Sîrb *et al.*, 2018). Population, as the available labour resource, represents one of the main

factors that can significantly influence the development of areas. Therefore, we considered it essential to analyse the evolution of the population at the level of the communes in our study, because the availability of human resources directly contributes to their involvement in the implementation of investments and activities in the area. This analysis allows to better understand of the development potential and identify any opportunities or challenges related to the available labour force in each commune.

Table 1.

Population dynamics in the neighbouring communes of Salonta municipality			
Locality	Number of people		2022 / 1992
	1992	2022	%
Avram Iancu	3 441	3 375	-1,92
Batâr	5 560	5 655	+1,70
Ciumeghiu	4 571	4 614	+0,94
Mădăras	3 033	2 854	-5,90
Tulca	3 059	2 704	-11,60
Municipiul Salonta	21 075	18 319	-13,08
Total	40 739	37 521	-7,90

Source: Own processing based on INS, Tempo online, Population by residence, 2023.

According to the statistical data in the Table 1 regarding the evolution of the population in the localities under study, we found that, during the analysed period, there was a decrease in the population of 3,218 people, which represents a share of -7.90%, from **40,739** people registered in 1992 to

37,521 people registered in 2022. The largest population decreases during the period 1992-2022 were recorded in **Salonta -13.08%**, **Tulca -11.60%**, **Mădăras -5.90%**, and **Avram Iancu -1.92%**. Population increases were recorded in the communes of **Batâr +1.70%** and **Ciumeghiu +0.94%** respectively.

Table 2.

Population in Salonta municipality by age category		
Age	Number of people	[%]
0- 14 years	2 101	11,47
15-24 years	2 022	10,66
25-64 years	10 846	59,20
65+ years	3 419	18,67
TOTAL	18 319	100,0

Source: Own processing based on INS, Tempo online

According to the population analysis of **Salonta** municipality, (Table 2) people aged 65+ represent 18.67% of the total population, pointing to a significant share of the elderly. At the same time, the age category 0-14 years has a share of 11.47%, suggesting a lower proportion of children and adolescents compared to the elderly population. These data highlight an aging trend of the local population which may have implications for social, health, and urban planning policies.

Table 3.

Population in Avram Iancu commune by age category		
Age	Number of people	[%]
0- 14 years	650	19,26
15-24 years	454	13,45
25-64 years	1 826	54,10
65+ years	445	13,19
TOTAL	3 375	100,00

Source: Own processing based on INS, Tempo online

In **Avram Iancu** commune, located in the immediate vicinity of Salonta municipality, the analysis by age group highlights that the population aged 65+ accounts for 13.19%, while the population in the 0-14 age range accounts for 19.2% (Table 3).

Table 4.

Population in Batăr commune by age category		
Age	Number of people	[%]
0- 14 years	1 211	21,41
15-24 years	899	15,90
25-64 years	2 868	50,72
65+ years	677	11,97
TOTAL	5 655	100,00

Source: Own processing based on INS, Tempo online, 2025

The population analysis of **Batăr** commune, (Table 4) shows that 11.97% of the inhabitants are aged 65+, while 21.41% belong to the 0-14 age range. This points to a relatively balanced distribution between young and elderly people, suggesting that there is a sufficiently young people to support the commune's active workforce in the future. This demographic structure can be considered favourable for local development, as young people represent the potential for economic growth and long-term sustainability.

Table 5.

Population in Ciumeghiu commune by age category		
Age	Number of people	[%]
0- 14 years	985	21,35
15-24 years	633	13,62
25-64 years	2385	51,79
65+ years	611	13,24
TOTAL	5 655	100,00

Source: Own processing based on INS, Tempo online, 2025

In Ciumeghiu commune, the population analysis by age groups highlights that the population aged 65 and over 65 occupies a share of 13.24% while the population in the 0-14 age category holds a share of 21.35%. This fact indicates that in Ciumeghiu commune there is a young population capable of replacing the active labor force of the commune (Table 5).

Table 6.

Population in Mădăras commune by age category		
Age	Number of people	[%]
0- 14 years	480	16,82
15-24 years	340	11,91
25-64 years	1 569	54,97
65+ years	465	16,30
TOTAL	2 854	100,00

Source: Own processing based on INS, Tempo online, 2025

The analysis of the population of **Mădăras** commune by age groups reveals a relatively balanced distribution between the population aged 0-14 (16.82%) and the

population aged 65+ (16.30%). This distribution suggests a possible continuity in the labour force and human resources of the locality, given that the young population is large enough to replace the active labour force, which represents 16.30% of the total population. Although, in 2022, the population of the commune decreased by 179 people, which represents a reduction of 5.90% compared to the 1992 level (Table 1), the demographic situation points to a certain stability in the structure by age groups, which may have positive implications for the sustainability of the locality in the long term, (Table 6).

Table 7.

Population in Tulca commune by age category		
Age	Number of people	[%]
0- 14 years	450	16,64
15-24 years	353	13,05
25-64 years	1 475	54,55
65+ years	426	15,76
TOTAL	2 704	100,00

Source: Own processing based on INS, Tempo online, 2025

The analysis of the population of **Tulca** commune by age groups highlights a relatively balanced structure between the young and the elderly population. Thus, the percentage of the population aged 65+ represents 15.76%, while the population in the 0-14 age category has a share of 16.64%, (Table 7). This distribution suggests a relatively balanced distribution of the population by age categories, which may point to a potential for the replacement of the active labour force by the young population.

However, we need to also take into account the demographic context: in 2022, the population of the commune registered a significant decrease of 355 people, which represents a decrease of approximately 11.60% compared to the level in 1992. This considerable decrease may have long-term implications on the labour force, social services, and sustainability of the local population. In conclusion, although the age structure currently appears balanced, the population decline in recent years points to a need for policies and measures to counteract demographic decline and ensure a sustainable balance in the long term.

The analysis of land resources, both agricultural and non-agricultural land reserves, is an essential element for assessing the development potential of the agricultural sectors, namely the crop and livestock sectors,

in each locality of the area delimited for research. Comparing the structure of the land fund in 1992 with that of 2014, we can notice the evolution and trends of change in land use, as well as the potential for expansion or limitation of agricultural activities.

This analysis has the following main objectives:

Identifying available resources

Determining the proportion of agricultural and non-agricultural land in the land fund structure for each commune and highlighting the basic resources for the development of the crop and livestock sectors.

Assessing change trends

Comparing data from 1992 and 2014 to identify the increase or decrease in agricultural and non-agricultural areas, as well as possible land transfers between these categories.

Supporting the development strategy planning

Guiding the decisions of local authorities and factors involved in the sustainable development of the area based on the information thus obtained to use land resources efficiently.

For a full interpretation, detailed analysis of data specific to each locality is necessary, as well as the identification of factors that have influenced changes over time. Thus, a clear picture can be built on the potential for agricultural and zootechnical development, in accordance with the available resources and the evolution trends of the land fund.

Figure 1. Land dynamics in Salonta municipality

Figure 2 Structure of land use categories, Salonta

According to statistical data provided by the INS, the municipality of Salonta has a total area of 17,004 ha. In 1992, the agricultural area was 15,439 ha, but this decreased by 425 ha, reaching 15,014 ha in 2014. This means that agricultural land represents approximately 86.8% of the total area of the municipality. Of the agricultural land, over 60.16% is arable land, and 39.65% is pasture and hayfields. In addition, the areas of vineyards and orchards share a very small proportion of the total agricultural land (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 3. Land dynamics in Avram Iancu commune

Figure 4 Structure of land use categories, Avram Iancu commune

According to statistical data provided by the INS, the commune of Avram Iancu has a total area of 8,217 ha. In 1992, the agricultural area of the commune was 6,871 ha, a figure that remained constant until 2014, representing a share of 83.61% of the total area of the commune. Of this agricultural area, over 88.61% is arable land, and 11.13% is pastures and hayfields (Figure 3 and 4).

Figure 6 Structure of land use categories, Batâr commune

The commune of Batâr has a total area of 12,649 ha. In 1992, the agricultural area was 11,447 ha, a value that remained unchanged in 2014, thus representing 90.50% of the total area of the commune. Of this agricultural area, 85.72% is arable land, 14.24% are pastures and hayfields, while the areas of vineyards and orchards share an insignificant proportion. This distribution points to a predominance of arable land dedicated to plant cultivation (Figure 5 and 6).

Figure 5 Land dynamics in Batâr commune

Figure 7. Land dynamics in Ciameghiu commune

Ciameghiu commune has a total area of 11,028 ha. In 1992, its agricultural area was 9,861 ha, and this area increased by 35 ha, reaching 9,896 ha in 2014. Currently, agricultural land represents approximately 89.74% of the total area of the commune, which points to a predominance of agricultural land in the local landscape. Of the available agricultural land, 87.17% is mainly intended for arable land, while 12.79% is pastures and hayfields. The areas occupied by vineyards and orchards are negligible, while, in 2014, the areas of orchards have completely disappeared, pointing to a decrease or abandonment of these crops in recent years (Figure 7 and 8).

Figure 8 Structure of land use categories, Ciameghiu commune

Mădăras commune has a total area of 9,275 ha. In 1992, its agricultural area was 8,189 ha, but this decreased by 7 ha, reaching 8,181 ha in 2014. Currently, agricultural land represents approximately 88.20% of the total area of the commune. Of this agricultural land, 74.43% is arable land, while 25.48% is pasture and hayfields. The area intended for vineyards and orchards has an insignificant share, and in 2014, the vineyard areas were completely removed. This availability of arable land, pastures, and hayfields highlights a significant potential for the development of agriculture in the commune of Mădăras, either for growing plants or for raising animals.

Figure 9. Land dynamics in Mădăras commune

Figure 10 Structure of land use categories, Ciameghiu commune

Tulca commune has a total area of 5862 ha, of which 5495 ha are dedicated to agricultural land, representing a very large share of 93.16% of the commune's total area (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 11. Land dynamics in Tulca commune

Figure 12 Structure of land use categories, Tulca commune

Of its agricultural land, 81.96% is arable land, pointing to a significant availability for agricultural crops, while 18.04% are pastures and hayfields, offering a potential for animal husbandry and fodder production. It is worth noting that the areas of vineyards and orchards have completely disappeared, Tulca commune not having a tradition in the cultivation of vines or fruit trees.

However, the high availability of arable land, combined with the significant proportion of pastures and hayfields, highlights a considerable potential for the development of agriculture, both through plant cultivation and animal husbandry. These aspects can constitute solid bases for agricultural and tourism development strategies in the commune.

CONCLUSIONS

To increase the economy and quality of life, rural communities must take into account the use of available resources when establishing their development plans. In this sense, a development plan, respectively a development strategy for the areas, should include:

- Capitalizing on local agricultural resources by promoting traditional and organic products, participating in fairs, and creating a brand identity.
- Supporting local resource processing activities, such as the manufacture of handicrafts, conservation, and processing.
- Exploiting the tourism potential of the area by developing tourist infrastructure, promoting cultural and natural heritage, and creating attractive tourist packages.

To create employment, the following actions are necessary:

- Creating vocational training programs adapted to the current needs of the labour market, in areas such as modernized agriculture, processing of agricultural products, rural tourism and agrotourism, and traditional crafts and technology.
- Developing initiatives to stimulate local entrepreneurship, including microenterprises and cooperatives, through facilitated access to financing and consultancy to generate stable income.

In addition to these measures to grow the economy and the life quality of residents in rural areas, *investments in infrastructure* are also needed: roads, water supply, sewage, renewable energy, and digitalization to facilitate access and improve living conditions; the development of social and educational services to increase literacy levels and provide opportunities for young people and families; and the promotion of cooperation projects between the community, authorities, and the private sector to attract investments and stimulate innovation.

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INFLUENCE OF PRUNING SYSTEMS ON TREE YIELD IN 'GOLDEN DELICIOUS' APPLE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Pruning is a critical orchard management practice that directly influences vegetative growth, light interception, fruiting behavior, and ultimately yield in apple trees. The cultivar 'Golden Delicious' is widely grown due to its high productivity and fruit quality; however, its yield potential is strongly affected by the pruning system adopted. This article reviews the influence of different pruning systems on tree yield in 'Golden Delicious' apple, focusing on canopy structure, light distribution, flower bud formation, fruit set, and yield efficiency. The findings highlight that appropriate pruning systems enhance productivity by balancing vegetative and reproductive growth, improving light penetration, and maintaining long-term orchard performance.

Keywords: Apple, Golden Delicious, pruning systems, yield, canopy management

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INTRODUCTION

Apple (*Malus × domestica* Borkh.) continues to be one of the most economically important temperate fruit crops worldwide, with global production systems evolving rapidly due to labor shortages, mechanization, and the need for higher productivity per unit area. Pruning and canopy management are recognized as essential cultural practices that shape tree architecture, optimize light distribution, regulate vegetative–reproductive balance, and thereby influence not only fruit quality but also total yield (Win et al., 2025). The cultivar 'Golden Delicious' is widely cultivated due to its broad adaptability and market demand, but like many high-yielding cultivars, its productivity and fruit quality are strongly dependent on efficient pruning systems that manage canopy vigor and light interception.

Pruning practices have traditionally been labor-intensive and require skilled labor, prompting increased research interest in mechanized and hybrid pruning approaches. Recent work has demonstrated that mechanical pruning, while reducing labor input, may alter canopy structure in ways that can limit light penetration deeper into the tree and negatively affect fruit size and coloration unless

supplemented with manual follow-up pruning (Win et al., 2025). In 'Arisoo' apple trees, for example, mechanical pruning alone reduced light penetration within the canopy and produced smaller, less well-colored fruits compared to trees receiving manual or combined mechanical + manual pruning, although yields were comparable; combined pruning significantly reduced pruning time while maintaining yield and quality parameters (Win et al., 2025).

In addition to winter pruning strategies, summer pruning has gained renewed attention as a cultural technique that influences tree physiology directly during the growing season. Summer pruning — including shoot thinning, bending, and ring wounding — has been shown to promote flower bud differentiation, improve ventilation and light conditions within the canopy, and reduce the incidence of pests and diseases, which together contribute to better fruit quality and potentially improved yield when applied at appropriate growth stages (Qiu et al., 2025). However, excessive summer pruning can weaken trees and negatively impact yield if not tailored to growth vigor and orchard context.

Effective pruning fundamentally alters canopy light interception and distribution, which influences photosynthetic efficiency — a

main driver of assimilate production and overall yield. Research on canopy structure underscores that pruning methods that promote open, well-distributed foliage can enhance light availability to fruiting zones, thereby improving flower bud formation and crop load distribution (Park et al., 2025). Shading caused by dense canopy layers is known to reduce chlorophyll content and lower photosynthetic rates, ultimately diminishing both vegetative vigor and reproductive success in poorly pruned orchards.

Integrated pruning strategies that combine winter and summer approaches, along with modern robotic and precision pruning technologies, are emerging as promising solutions to labor constraints and orchard sustainability challenges. New developments in robotic pruning, precision canopy sensing, and machine learning-based management tools aim to optimize pruning decisions based on tree structure and light models, enabling more consistent yield outcomes across diverse orchard conditions.

Despite growing research interest, there remain significant gaps in understanding how different pruning systems specifically affect tree yield and fruit quality in cultivars like 'Golden Delicious' across varying climates and planting densities. Given the cultivar's susceptibility to dense canopy formation, biennial bearing, and quality variations under suboptimal light conditions, a comprehensive assessment of pruning practices is essential to guide orchard management decisions that maximize yield while maintaining fruit quality and orchard longevity.

Pruning is a fundamental orchard management practice that serves multiple physiological and horticultural functions in apple production. By selectively removing shoots and branches, pruning regulates vegetative growth and controls tree size, thereby maintaining an optimal canopy structure suited to the planting density and rootstock vigor (Robinson et al., 2021). Proper pruning improves light penetration and distribution within the canopy, which is a key factor influencing photosynthetic efficiency, spur productivity, and fruit development (Corelli Grappadelli et al., 2020).

Light availability within the canopy directly affects flower bud differentiation and fruiting potential. Well-pruned apple trees exhibit higher flower bud density due to improved exposure of shoots and spurs to sunlight during

the critical period of bud initiation (Qiu et al., 2024). Pruning also helps maintain a balance between vegetative growth and reproductive activity, preventing excessive shoot growth that can compete with developing fruits for assimilates (Zhou et al., 2023).

In addition to its effects on yield formation, pruning enhances fruit size, color, and overall quality by improving canopy microclimate, air circulation, and light interception around fruiting zones (Park et al., 2025). Open canopies also reduce humidity and shading, thereby lowering the incidence of pests and diseases and improving spray penetration and orchard sanitation (Sun et al., 2021).

In the cultivar 'Golden Delicious', which is moderately vigorous and prone to dense canopy formation, pruning plays a particularly critical role. Without systematic pruning, trees may develop excessive shading, poor spur renewal, and irregular bearing, ultimately leading to reduced yield consistency. Therefore, appropriate pruning strategies are essential for sustaining high and regular yields in 'Golden Delicious' apple orchards.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experiment was conducted during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons in the northwestern part of Romania, at an experimental apple orchard located in Bihor County. The site is situated at approximately 300–400 m above mean sea level and is characterized by a temperate continental climate with moderate influences from Western Europe.

The region experiences cold winters and mild to warm summers, with an average annual rainfall of 600–700 mm, most of which occurs during spring and early summer. Mean annual temperature is approximately 9–10 °C, with summer temperatures ranging between 18 and 28 °C. The soil of the experimental orchard is classified as loam to clay loam, well-drained, with good fertility and uniform physical characteristics across the site. The study was conducted on uniform, healthy 'Golden Delicious' apple (*Malus × domestica* Borkh.) trees grafted on M.26 rootstock, which is commonly used in Romanian apple orchards due to its moderate vigor and adaptability. The trees were 8 years old at the beginning of the experiment and planted at a spacing of 4.0 m × 2.5 m, corresponding to a semi-intensive orchard system.

Standard orchard management practices, including irrigation, fertilization, weed control, and plant protection measures, were uniformly applied to all trees throughout the experimental period in accordance with regional recommendations.

The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with five pruning treatments and four replications. Each replication consisted of three adjacent trees, and to minimize border effects, all observations and measurements were recorded on the central tree of each experimental unit. The pruning treatments evaluated included the central leader system (T_1), modified central leader system (T_2), open center or vase system (T_3), minimal pruning (T_4), and renewal pruning (T_5).

Pruning was carried out during the dormant season (late February to early March) in both years of study, prior to bud break. All pruning operations were performed manually using sterilized pruning tools to ensure precision and to prevent disease transmission.

In the central leader system, a dominant vertical axis was maintained with well-spaced lateral branches arranged in a conical shape. The modified central leader system involved limiting tree height and encouraging lateral branching to improve canopy openness. In the open center (vase) system, the central leader was removed to create an open canopy structure with three to four main scaffold branches. Vegetative growth was evaluated by recording annual shoot extension growth (cm) on selected current-season shoots and by calculating the trunk cross-sectional area (TCSA, cm^2) from trunk diameter measurements taken at 30 cm above the graft union. Flowering intensity was assessed at full bloom by counting the number of flower clusters per tree, while fruit set (%) was calculated as the ratio of the number of fruits retained after natural fruit drop to the initial number of flowers, expressed as a percentage.

Fruits were harvested at commercial maturity in September, and yield parameters were recorded, including yield per tree (kg), number of fruits per tree, average fruit weight (g), and yield efficiency, expressed as kg cm^{-2} TCSA. For fruit quality assessment, a random sample of 20 fruits per tree was collected and analyzed for fruit diameter (mm) and fruit weight (g). Fruit skin color was evaluated visually using a standard color chart, while total soluble solids (TSS, °Brix) were determined

using a digital refractometer. Titratable acidity (%) was measured by titration with sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and fruit firmness (kg cm^{-2}) was assessed using a penetrometer.

The collected data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using R statistical software. Treatment means were compared using Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test at a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$. Percentage data were arcsine transformed prior to statistical analysis where necessary to meet assumptions of normality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Pruning systems significantly influenced vegetative growth parameters of 'Golden Delicious' apple trees. Annual shoot extension growth varied markedly among treatments, with the minimal pruning (T_4) treatment exhibiting the highest shoot growth, reflecting reduced control of vegetative vigor. In contrast, trees subjected to renewal pruning (T_5) and the open center system (T_3) showed moderate shoot extension, while the central leader (T_1) and modified central leader (T_2) systems maintained balanced vegetative growth.

Trunk cross-sectional area (TCSA) increased progressively over the study period in all treatments; however, trees under minimal pruning (T_4) recorded the largest TCSA, indicating excessive vegetative development. The central leader (T_1) and modified central leader (T_2) systems exhibited moderate increases in TCSA, suggesting a better balance between vegetative growth and reproductive activity.

Table 1.

Effect of pruning systems on vegetative growth of 'Golden Delicious' apple trees

Pruning system	Annual shoot extension growth (cm)	Trunk cross-sectional area (cm^2)
Central leader	38.6 ± 1.4 b	68.3 ± 2.1 b
Modified central leader	40.2 ± 1.6 b	70.1 ± 2.4 b
Open center (vase)	42.8 ± 1.8 b	72.5 ± 2.6 b
Minimal pruning	52.4 ± 2.0 a	80.9 ± 3.1 a
Renewal pruning	44.1 ± 1.7 b	73.8 ± 2.8 b

Flowering intensity was significantly affected by pruning systems. The central leader (T_1) and modified central leader (T_2) systems produced the highest number of flower clusters per tree, indicating improved flower bud differentiation. Trees under minimal pruning (T_4) showed comparatively lower flowering intensity, likely due to increased canopy shading and reduced light penetration.

Fruit set (%) followed a similar trend, with the highest fruit set observed in the central leader and modified central leader systems, while the open center system (T_3) recorded moderate fruit set. Renewal pruning (T_5) resulted in improved fruit set compared to minimal pruning, reflecting the positive effect of renewed fruiting wood on reproductive performance.

Table 2

Effect of pruning systems on flowering and fruit set of 'Golden Delicious' apple trees

Pruning system	Flower clusters per tree	Fruit set (%)
Central leader	185 ± 6 a	62.4 ± 1.9 a
Modified central leader	178 ± 5 a	60.7 ± 2.1 a
Open center (vase)	160 ± 6 b	56.2 ± 2.0 b
Minimal pruning	142 ± 7 c	49.8 ± 1.8 c
Renewal pruning	168 ± 6 b	57.9 ± 2.2 b

Yield per tree differed significantly among pruning treatments. The central leader system (T_1) recorded the highest yield per tree, followed closely by the modified central leader system (T_2). These systems also produced a greater number of fruits per tree, indicating superior yield potential. The open center system (T_3) resulted in moderate yields, while minimal pruning (T_4) produced lower and more variable yields despite high vegetative growth.

Pruning systems had a significant effect on fruit quality characteristics. Fruits harvested from trees trained under the open center (T_3) and central leader (T_1) systems exhibited larger fruit size and better skin coloration, attributed to enhanced light exposure within the canopy. The modified central leader (T_2) system

produced fruits of comparable size and acceptable coloration.

Total soluble solids (TSS) content was generally higher in fruits from well-illuminated canopies, particularly under the open center and central leader systems, whereas fruits from minimally pruned trees recorded lower TSS values. Titratable acidity showed minor variation among treatments, while fruit firmness was slightly higher in fruits from moderately pruned trees, indicating improved texture and storage potential.

Table 3

Effect of pruning systems on yield and yield efficiency of 'Golden Delicious' apple trees

Pruning system	Yield per tree (kg)	Fruits per tree	Average fruit weight (g)	Yield efficiency (kg cm ⁻² TCSA)
Central leader	45.6 ± 1.8 a	265 ± 10 a	172 ± 5 a	0.67 ± 0.03 a
Modified central leader	43.8 ± 1.7 a	258 ± 9 a	170 ± 6 a	0.63 ± 0.02 a
Open center (vase)	38.2 ± 1.6 b	228 ± 8 b	168 ± 5 ab	0.53 ± 0.02 b
Minimal pruning	32.5 ± 1.5 c	210 ± 9 c	155 ± 6 b	0.40 ± 0.02 c
Renewal pruning	36.9 ± 1.6 b	235 ± 8 b	165 ± 5 ab	0.50 ± 0.02 b

Yield efficiency (kg cm⁻² TCSA) was significantly higher in the central leader and modified central leader systems, reflecting more efficient conversion of vegetative growth into fruit production. Minimal pruning showed the lowest yield efficiency, whereas renewal pruning (T_5) improved yield efficiency compared to minimal pruning by stimulating productive new shoots.

pruning	1.3 ab	0.3 ab	0.02	
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Table 4

Effect of pruning systems on fruit quality attributes of 'Golden Delicious' apple

Pruning system	Fruit diameter (mm)	TSS (°Brix)	Titrateable acidity (%)	Fruit firmness (kg cm ⁻²)
Central leader	72.8 ± 1.2 a	13.6 ± 0.3 a	0.41 ± 0.02	7.8 ± 0.2 a
Modified central leader	71.9 ± 1.3 a	13.4 ± 0.3 a	0.42 ± 0.02	7.6 ± 0.2 a
Open center (vase)	73.5 ± 1.1 a	13.8 ± 0.4 a	0.40 ± 0.02	7.7 ± 0.3 a
Minimal pruning	69.2 ± 1.4 b	12.6 ± 0.3 b	0.44 ± 0.03	7.1 ± 0.2 b
Renewal	71.0 ±	13.1 ±	0.42 ±	7.4 ± 0.2 ab

Overall, the results indicate that central leader (T₁) and modified central leader (T₂) pruning systems provided the most favorable balance between vegetative growth, flowering, yield, and fruit quality in 'Golden Delicious' apple. Minimal pruning (T₄) promoted excessive vegetative growth at the expense of yield efficiency and fruit quality, while renewal pruning (T₅) improved productivity compared to minimal pruning but remained inferior to structured pruning systems. The open center system (T₃) enhanced fruit quality but resulted in moderately lower yields.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study demonstrated that pruning systems exert a significant influence on vegetative growth, flowering, yield, and fruit quality of 'Golden Delicious' apple trees grown under the climatic conditions of northwestern Romania. Pruning was shown to be an essential canopy management practice for regulating tree vigor, improving light distribution within the canopy, and sustaining productive fruiting over successive seasons.

Among the evaluated pruning systems, the central leader and modified central leader systems proved to be the most effective in achieving a balanced relationship between vegetative growth and reproductive performance. Trees trained under these systems exhibited moderate vegetative growth, higher flowering intensity, improved fruit set, and superior yield efficiency compared with other treatments. These systems also produced consistently higher yields per tree while maintaining desirable fruit size, coloration, and internal quality attributes.

The open center (vase) system enhanced fruit quality due to improved light penetration and canopy openness; however, it resulted in comparatively lower yields, likely due to

reduced canopy volume and leaf area. Minimal pruning promoted excessive vegetative growth, which negatively affected flowering, yield efficiency, and fruit quality, highlighting the long-term disadvantages of insufficient canopy regulation. In contrast, renewal pruning improved productivity relative to minimal pruning by stimulating new fruiting wood, although its performance remained inferior to structured leader-based systems.

Overall, the findings indicate that adopting well-defined pruning systems, particularly central and modified central leader systems, is essential for maximizing yield, improving fruit quality, and ensuring long-term orchard productivity in 'Golden Delicious' apple. These pruning strategies can be recommended for semi-intensive apple orchards in northwestern Romania and similar temperate regions. Further research integrating pruning systems with high-density plantings, mechanized pruning techniques, and precision orchard management tools may help further optimize apple production under evolving climatic and economic conditions.

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NORMATIVE AND INSTITUTIONAL ANALYSIS OF THE REORGANIZATION PROCESS OF THE NATIONAL FORESTRY ADMINISTRATION – ROMSILVA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper analyzes the reorganization process of the National Forest Administration – Romsilva, as provided in the draft Government Decision and the related Explanatory Memorandum (Nota de fundamentare). The reorganization is part of the implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Component C2 – "Forest and biodiversity protection," Reform 1 – "Reform of the forest management and governance system." The study examines the legal basis of this reform, the proposed institutional modus operandi, as well as the anticipated administrative, economic, and ecological effects. The analysis demonstrates that the reorganization aims to modernize forest governance through digitalization, the streamlining of territorial structures, and the consolidation of transparency, with the final goal of ensuring the sustainable management of state public-owned forests and aligning the national forest administration with European standards of sustainability and control.

Keywords: legislation, reorganization, administration

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INTRODUCTION

The reorganization of the National Forest Administration – Romsilva, proposed through the draft **Government Decision approving the organizational, operational, and reorganization measures for Romsilva**, represents one of the most significant administrative reforms in the forestry sector in the last 15 years. This legislative initiative is grounded in **Law no. 331/2024 concerning the Forestry Code**, published in the *Official Gazette of Romania*, Part I, no. 21 of January 12, 2025, and derives from the obligations assumed by Romania through **Regulation (EU) 2021/241** of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The materials used in writing this paper are composed of legislation, web sites and specialized law courses. The methods used are legal, namely the formal method, the comparative method, the logical and sociological method, the analytical method. The use of these methods has the role of performing a systematic analysis of the information from the studied sources in order to elaborate the points of view and the conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

According to the **Explanatory Memorandum**, the draft decision addresses the requirements of **Milestone 24** of the *National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)*, Component C2 – *Forest and biodiversity protection*, Reform 1 – *Reform of the forest management and governance system*, through which the Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests is obliged to adopt and bring into force a coherent set of legislative acts to rationalize the legal framework, combat illegal logging, and improve forest management: "Entry into force of the following legislative acts, which aim to rationalize the legal framework, combat illegal logging and improve forest management: (i) The New Forestry Code [...] (iv) Other governmental decisions for combating illegal logging and improving forest management, including amendments to Government Decision no. 229/2009 regarding Romsilva." (Explanatory Memorandum, Section 2.1)

The purpose of the reorganization, formulated in Art. 4 para. (1) of the draft Decision, is "the administration of the state's public and private national forest estate for the sustainable management of forests, the consolidation of their resilience, and the increase of their contribution to limiting the effects of climate change." This formulation expresses the orientation of the new forestry

policy toward an integrated environmental vision, where the forest is treated as a strategic ecological infrastructure.

Chapter 1. Motivation for the Reorganization of the National Forest Administration - Romsilva

The necessity for the reorganization of Romsilva derives from legal, political, and administrative factors. The reform aims to align the agency's mode of governance with the requirements of the NRRP, the Forestry Code (Law no. 331/2024), and the principles of corporate governance regulated by Government Emergency Ordinance no. 109/2011, published in the Official Gazette of Romania, Part I, no. 883 of December 14, 2011, approved by Law no. 111/2016 (Official Gazette, Part I, no. 409 of May 30, 2016). According to the Explanatory Memorandum (Section 2.1), the draft Government Decision is elaborated "pursuant to Art. 108 of the Constitution of Romania and Art. 32 para. (2) of Law no. 331/2024," which stipulates that Romsilva's reorganization is approved by a Government Decision. The document also invokes the Government Program 2025-2028, which provides for: "Romsilva reform that should include the reduction of the number of forest directorates, the separation of activities based on their efficiency, and the provision of supplementary control over timber transports to reduce fiscal evasion."

In Section 3.1 of the Explanatory Memorandum, it is shown that the act "takes into account the creation of an efficient, flexible, and responsible forest administration [...] by establishing competencies for each structure and its head within Romsilva." The reform introduces a **performance-based management system**, correlated with economic objectives and measurable indicators. *In Section 3.4.1*, it is mentioned that the reorganization "will lead to a decrease in permanent expenditure by reducing the number of Romsilva units and subunits," contributing to the observance of budget deficit conditions.

From an ecological perspective, Sections 3.6 and 3.8 affirm that the decision "creates the premises for the sustainable management of the state public-owned national forest estate," consolidating the institutional capacity of the agency to apply the National Forest Strategy - 2030 (Government Decision no. 1227/2022, *Official Gazette*, Part I, no. 1240/23.12.2022).

Summary: The reform responds to the problems of territorial fragmentation, managerial inefficiency, and lack of transparency, transforming Romsilva into a modern instrument of **forestry governance**.

Chapter 2. Modality of the Reorganization of the National Forest Administration - Romsilva

The reorganization provides for a three-level structure (Government Decision, Art. 2):

- the central structure - management, coordination, and control
- units without legal personality - regional forest directorates and the "Silva" Complex
- units with legal personality - park administrations, the Equine Directorate, the Posada Museum

Romsilva's own patrimony is **459,376,512 lei** (Government Decision, Art. 3), and the assets and liabilities of the reorganized units are taken over in full by the new structures.

The reorganization reduces the number of county-level **forest directorates** to **12 regional directorates** (Annex no. 1), consolidating territorial competencies and control over exploitation.

Corporate Governance and Contractual Management

The application of **Government Emergency Ordinance no. 109/2011** (Official Gazette no. 883/2011, effective January 1, 2012) and **Law no. 111/2016** (Official Gazette no. 409/30.05.2016) to Romsilva aligns the agency with European principles of public governance.

The Board of Administration (Government Decision, Art. 26–27) and the General Director (Government Decision, Art. 29) are appointed through competition and a mandate contract, based on **EC Recommendation 2005/162/EC** and the **OECD Principles 2015**.

Performance evaluation is carried out based on the indicators provided in **Annex no. 3**, covering economic efficiency, professional training, forest control, and adherence to ethics.

Subunits and Digitalization

Pursuant to the Government Decision, Art. 15–18, each directorate may establish subunits (forest districts, sections, centers), with activity permitted only "under conditions of economic efficiency."

Article 36 mandates the Board of Administration to elaborate, within 120 days, a **digitalization and debureaucratization plan**, an **ethics regulation**, and a **plan for the efficientization of forestry tourism**.

These provisions indicate a transition toward data-based, transparent, and integrated governance.

Summary

The reorganization of Romsilva involves:

- **Structural consolidation** – reduction of directorates and centralization of support;
- **Managerial professionalization** – mandate contracts and performance indicators;
- **Transparency and ethics** – salary publicity and code of conduct;
- **Ecological responsibility** – correlation with the National Forest Strategy 2030.

Through these instruments, Romsilva becomes a modern public forest management institution, compliant with European standards.

Chapter 3. Anticipated Effects and Implications of the Reorganization Administrative

According to the Explanatory Memorandum, Section 3.1, the reform creates an "efficient, flexible, and responsible" forest administration.

Mandate contracts and digitalization (Government Decision, Art. 36) professionalize leadership and reduce bureaucracy.

Economic

The Explanatory Memorandum, Section 3.4.1 shows that the reform "will determine a decrease in permanent expenditure," and the Government Decision, Art. 31, mandates the transmission of the revenue and expenditure budget for Government approval, pursuant to Government Ordinance no. 26/2013 (Official Gazette no. 549/29.08.2013).

Result: Financial efficiency, autonomy, and reduction of budgetary pressure.

Social

The Explanatory Memorandum, Section 3.2 mentions the integral takeover of the personnel.

Through the Government Decision, Art. 35, annual evaluation and professional training (minimum 18 hours/year, Annex no. 3) introduce a meritocratic and transparent culture.

Ecological

The Explanatory Memorandum, Sections 3.6 and 3.8, and the Government Decision, Art. 4 para. (1), establish the purpose of "sustainable forest management."

The reform aligns with the **EU Forest Strategy 2030** and the **European Green Deal (COM(2019) 640 final)**, contributing to biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation.

Chapter 4. General Conclusions

The reorganization of Romsilva has a **triple dimension**: legal, administrative, and ecological.

On the legal plane, it is based on **Law no. 331/2024 (The Forestry Code)** and **Government Emergency Ordinance no. 109/2011**, integrating the standards of **EC Recommendation 2005/162/EC** and the **OECD Principles (2015)** regarding corporate governance.

Administratively, it introduces contractual governance, measurable performance, and decisional transparency.

Economically, it rationalizes expenditure and stimulates internal efficiency. Socially, it maintains personnel but mandates professionalism and continuous training.

Ecologically, it aligns Romania with European policies regarding climate neutrality and sustainable forest management.

CONCLUSIONS

The success of the reorganization will depend on the effective application of the reform, the quality of the leadership, and the capacity of the Ministry of Environment to ensure real and objective control.

If these conditions are met, the reform can become a **model of sustainable public governance**, demonstrating that environmental protection and economic efficiency can coexist in a modern forest administration.

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ANALYSIS AND SIMULATION OF THREE-PHASE ASYNCHRONOUS MOTOR CONTROL WITH SWITCHING DEVICES FOR FORESTRY APPLICATIONS IN SIMULINK

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study analyses the start-up performance of a 5 kW, 400 V, 50 Hz three-phase induction motor driving circular steel saw blades of 300 mm, 600 mm, and 1200 mm diameters. A MATLAB Simulink model with a star-delta starter was developed to assess how blade inertia affects motor dynamics while limiting inrush current. Each blade was modelled as a thin steel ring, and its inertia was added to the motor rotor inertia. Simulations were conducted under no-load conditions to isolate inertial effects on current, torque, and acceleration.

Keywords: Three-phase asynchronous motor, Simulink simulation, Timber cutting start-up, Forestry machinery, Switching devices

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INTRODUCTION

In modern forestry machinery, electric drive systems must operate reliably under harsh environmental and mechanical conditions. Three-phase asynchronous (induction) motors are widely used in this field due to their robustness, simplicity, and cost-effectiveness. However, direct-on-line (DOL) starting can produce extremely high inrush currents and torque peaks, leading to mechanical stress, voltage drops, and reduced overall system efficiency (Deesor, et al., 2022).

The star-delta starting method offers a practical and economical solution to these issues. By initially connecting the stator windings in a star configuration and then switching to delta once the motor reaches a certain speed, this method effectively reduces starting current and mechanical stress. Despite its simplicity, the switching period can introduce transient effects that influence performance, especially under variable load conditions typical in forestry applications (Goh, H.H., Looi, M.S. & Kok, B.C., 2009).

This study presents a simulation-based analysis of a three-phase asynchronous motor controlled through a star-delta scheme using MATLAB/Simulink. The model focuses on capturing the dynamic behavior during the switching process and evaluating key parameters such as torque, speed, and current. The results provide valuable insights for

optimizing start-up performance and improving the reliability and efficiency of electric drives used in forestry equipment.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study used a 5 kW, 400 V, 50 Hz, three-phase induction motor with a rated torque of approximately 32.9 N·m at 1500 rpm. A star-delta starter was included in the simulation to reduce inrush current during start-up. For the purpose of this study, the same motor was used for all blade sizes. This approach allows a clear understanding of how blade inertia affects start-up dynamics while maintaining consistent electrical and mechanical motor parameters. Three steel circular blades were analysed with diameters of 300 mm, 600 mm, and 1200 mm. Each blade was approximated as a thin steel ring, and its moment of inertia was calculated using:

$$I = m \cdot R^2$$

where m is the mass and R is the radius of the blade. The blade inertia was added to the motor rotor inertia in the simulation. Start-up simulations considered no mechanical load, meaning the motor only accelerated the rotor and attached blade. Required torque for acceleration was determined by:

$$T_{\text{start-up}} = I_{\text{total}} \cdot \alpha$$

Where:

$$I_{\text{total}} = I_{\text{motor}} + I_{\text{blade}}$$

and α is the angular acceleration needed to reach rated speed (~ 1500 rpm). Mechanical power during start-up was calculated as:

$$P_{\text{start-up}} = T_{\text{start-up}} \cdot \omega$$

with ω as the angular velocity in rad/s. Using the same motor allows clear observation of how blade inertia influences start-up behaviour without confounding factors.

Start-up torque requirements and motor capabilities for each blade size are summarized in Table 1. Results confirm that the 5-kW motor can start all blades unloaded, although larger blades accelerate more slowly due to higher inertia.

Table 1.

Saw Blade Start-up based on diameter

Blade Diameter	Blade Inertia (kg·m ²)	Startup Torque (N·m)	Motor Rated Torque (N·m)
300 mm	0.0015	3.4	32.9
600 mm	0.0117	9.7	
1200 mm	0.094	30.5	

The motor start-up control system was modelled and simulated using MATLAB Simulink, as seen in Figure 1, to implement a

star-delta starter based on the saw blade diameter. The schematic consists of motor winding configurations for both star (Y) and delta (Δ) connections, represented by dedicated subsystems for each mode. Input signals corresponding to three-phase voltages are processed through RMS measurement blocks to monitor the current and voltage values accurately.

A user-selectable parameter for saw blade diameter (300 mm, 600 mm, and 1200 mm) was integrated into the model to adjust the motor start-up parameters accordingly. The transition from star to delta connection is controlled by logic blocks that analyse the measured RMS values and apply timing delays to ensure smooth switching, minimizing mechanical stress and electrical surge.

The motor is modelled with its electrical characteristics, and the torque output is monitored to evaluate performance during the start-up sequence. The model includes continuous mode operation, enabling sustained motor running post start-up.

Figure 1 Motor start-up control syst

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 shows the RMS current profiles during start-up for the three blade sizes. At initial energization ($t \approx 0$ s), the motor draws a peak inrush current of approximately 35–40 A, which quickly settles to around 17–18 A during

the star connection period. Around $t = 1.0$ s, the star-delta transition occurs, resulting in a transient spike of similar magnitude before the current gradually decreases as the motor reaches steady-state operation.

The decay rate of the current differs noticeably across blade sizes. The 300 mm

blade settles to its steady-state current (~ 9 A) by $t \approx 1.45$ s, while the 600 mm and 1200 mm blades reach the same condition around $t \approx 1.55$ s and $t \approx 1.7$ s, respectively. This demonstrates that increased inertia prolongs the current draw period, as the motor requires more time to accelerate heavier blades. The star-delta configuration effectively limits current magnitude throughout the process, preventing excessive inrush and ensuring safe operation.

The speed characteristics shown in Figure 3 further illustrate the influence of inertia on acceleration. All three blades follow a similar speed trajectory during the star connection phase, achieving roughly 250–300 rpm by $t = 1$ s. Once switched to the delta connection, acceleration increases sharply until rated speed is achieved. The 300 mm blade reaches 1500 rpm at approximately 1.45 s, the 600 mm blade at 1.55 s, and the 1200 mm blade at 1.7 s. Although all blades ultimately attain synchronous speed, larger diameters require

longer acceleration times due to higher moments of inertia. At energization, the torque exhibits oscillations with peak magnitudes of approximately ± 25 N·m, stabilizing near 5–8 N·m during steady-state star operation. A strong transient is visible at $t = 1$ s, corresponding to the star-delta switching instant. The 1200 mm blade shows the highest post-transition torque peak of about 40 N·m, whereas the 300 mm blade peaks near 30 N·m before settling smoothly. These transients are characteristic of mechanical and electromagnetic coupling effects during reconfiguration of the supply voltage. After approximately $t = 1.6$ – 1.8 s, torque for all configurations stabilizes around the rated value of 32.9 N·m, confirming that the motor achieves normal operating conditions. The higher torque oscillations observed with the 1200 mm blade are attributed to its higher inertia, which demands greater torque to maintain equivalent angular acceleration.

Figure 2 RMS current profiles during start-up for the three blade sizes

Figure 3 Speed characteristics current profiles during start-up for the three blade size

CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the start-up performance of a 5 kW, 400 V, 50 Hz three-phase induction motor driving circular steel saw blades of different diameters using MATLAB Simulink. The model employed a star-delta starter, one of the most practical and widely used reduced-voltage methods in industrial and forestry machinery, to evaluate its ability to minimize inrush current and torque transients. The simulation results confirmed that the star-delta configuration effectively limits starting current while maintaining sufficient torque for acceleration, consistent with earlier analyses comparing DOL, star-delta, and autotransformer starting methods (Deesor et al., 2022; Goh et al., 2009).

Three blades, 300 mm, 600 mm, and 1200 mm—were analyzed to evaluate the effect of load inertia on motor start-up. Greater inertia resulted in longer acceleration times and higher transient torque. The 300 mm blade ($0.0015 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$) reached rated speed (1500 rpm) in 1.45 s, while the 600 mm ($0.0117 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$) and 1200 mm ($0.094 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$) blades required approximately 1.55 s and 1.70 s, respectively. Peak inrush currents ranged between 35–40 A, and torque peaks reached 40 N·m before stabilizing near 32.9 N·m. These findings confirm that the star-delta method provides a reliable and economical solution for high-inertia loads typical of sawmill and forestry applications. The study further emphasizes the importance of electrical contact behavior and switching transients in determining overall motor reliability. Variations in contact resistance can alter efficiency and lifetime performance (Stasac et al., 2019), while mechanical vibration and fluctuating temperatures influence contact wear and mechanical stability (Labelle et al., 2019). Investigations into the thermal and vibrational effects on electrical contacts (Hoble et al., 2017) demonstrate that improved contact materials and protective configurations are essential for motors operating in demanding forestry environments. These insights suggest that a combination of mechanical robustness and precise control is required to ensure optimal performance.

Although the present work is simulation-based, it provides a strong foundation for future experimental validation. Laboratory studies focusing on switching

currents, contact heating, and vibration impacts could verify the predicted torque and current responses under real operating conditions. In such investigations, the methodologies proposed by Stasac and Hoble (2021) and the broader framework for sustainable and efficient drive systems outlined by Šušnjar et al. (2022) and Wasilewski et al. (2023) may serve as valuable references. Overall, the results contribute to improving the design, reliability, and sustainability of electric drive systems in forestry machinery and align with the sector's transition toward hybrid, intelligent, and energy-efficient technologies.

Continued integration of simulation and experimental research will be key to advancing robust, adaptable, and environmentally responsible electric drives for next-generation forestry applications.

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KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS FOR THE CONTROL ACTIVITIES OF THE SUCEAVA FOREST GUARD: RESULTS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

This article examines the methodological framework for quantifying the control activities conducted by the Forest Guard through the use of performance indicators. By analysing these indicators in correlation with statutory obligations and institutional objectives, the study seeks to determine their relevance and analytical value. Furthermore, the article proposes the introduction of new indicators aligned with European and international requirements, designed to capture both institutional capacity and the substantive effects generated within the forestry sector through regulatory control activities.

Keywords: forest guard, key performance indicators, forest control, forestry, forest legislation

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INTRODUCTION

In 1992, Romania adopted the Statement of Forest Principles during the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, a document stipulating that "Forest resources and forest lands should be sustainably managed to meet the social, economic, ecological, cultural and spiritual human needs of present and future generations." Thus, Romania committed itself to ensuring a sustainable management of forests, enabling the long-term fulfilment of all their functions. According to Prins et al. (2023), sustainable forest management informs and guides the decisions of forest owners and managers and of those who make policy and law with regard to forests, and thus influences the condition of forests and the goods and services they provide to society and the planet.

Within a legislative framework intended to fulfil the desideratum of sustainable forest management, one of the necessary conditions is that the State authority possesses the capacity to ensure the enforcement and implementation of this legislation. The first territorial control structures of the central public authority responsible for forestry were established on the basis of Government Emergency Ordinance No. 96/1998 regarding the regulation of the forest regime and the administration of the national forest fund. These structures underwent numerous organisational and territorial adjustments until 2005. Subsequently, although

the territorial distribution of the control structures remained unchanged and their competences largely the same, the management of these institutions relied exclusively on statutory powers, without a clear definition of institutional mission, objectives and, implicitly, indicators for assessing the achievement of these objectives.

Following a broad consultation process with public officials within these institutions, conducted in 2016, the mission and objectives of the Forest Guards, including those of the Suceava Forest Guard, were defined. In the context of sustainable forest management, the mission of the Suceava Forest Guard is to ensure the enforcement of the law with a view to the sustainable development of forest and game resources, while contributing to the improvement of the regulatory framework in the public interest (<https://gfsuceava.gov.ro/gfsv/misiune/>).

The general objective of the institution is the guarantee of compliance with the forest and game regime and with the legality of timber circulation. Subordinate to this general objective, ten specific objectives have been identified. The indicators analysed in this paper focus on the achievement of the following specific objectives:

- Integrity, quality and diversity of forest and game resources
- Prevention and reduction of illegal tree felling and ensuring the integrity and development of the forest fund

- Ensuring the guarding of the national forest and game fund
- Ensuring the legality of placing forest products on the market

The specialised literature demonstrates that the performance of institutions responsible for forest governance can only be assessed through measurable indicators that reflect both the efficiency and the impact of control activities. Consequently, for the Suceava Forest Guard, the definition and use of indicators relating to control activities (e.g. number of inspections, value and number of sanctions, value of damages, level of compliance) are essential for measuring progress against the specific objectives and for grounding management decisions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The analysis of the indicators used in evaluating the activities carried out by the Suceava Forest Guard was conducted in two stages: first, a descriptive stage concerning the control activities that generate the indicators employed, and second, the actual analytical stage, involving their comparison with various other parameters (e.g. surface area inspected, number of sanctions, etc.).

The description of the principal control activities undertaken by the Forest Guard was carried out from the perspective of the following elements:

- Definition/purpose
- Legal basis (entitlement or obligation), standardised control form
- Frequency, duration and timeframe for execution.

1. Comprehensive/partial forest inspection

- Definition/purpose

The comprehensive forest inspection is a control activity aimed at verifying the manner in which the forest ranger fulfils guarding duties within a forest district (canton). According to the provisions of the Regulation on guarding the forest fund, approved by Government Decision No. 1076/2009, the comprehensive forest inspection encompasses:

- verification of the boundaries of the forest fund to determine any potential encroachments;
- verification of boundary markers and management unit limits;
- identification of trees, seedlings or shoots that have been cut, broken or uprooted

without authorisation, by surveying the entire area, as well as the evaluation of damages and calculation of losses;

- verification of the delineation in the field of zones and routes authorised for grazing, watering and sheltering, as applicable;
- verification of the management of entrusted assets; (...)

- Legal basis (entitlement or obligation)

The authority to conduct this type of inspection is provided by Article 11(a) of Government Decision No. 1076/2009, as well as by Article 14 of the Regulation on guarding the forest fund approved by the same act, Article 11(1) and (2), Article 132(1)(a) of Law No. 331/2024 – the 2024 Forest Code, and Article 6(1)(a), (j), and Article 19(1)(k) of Order No. 2185/2024.

The performance of a comprehensive or partial inspection constitutes a right of the Forest Guards, becoming an obligation under the following circumstances: complaints, requests from the Public Prosecutor's Office, police or other institutions, or instructions from superior authorities. The standard control form is set out in Annex 4 of the Regulation on guarding the forest fund approved by Government Decision No. 1076/2009.

- Frequency, duration and timeframe for execution

As this type of control is primarily a right of the institution, no specific duration or fixed interval for its execution is defined. The annual control plan establishes the scheduling of such inspections, generally specifying the number of actions and occasionally their location. When the inspection becomes an obligation, the deadline for execution is a maximum of 30 days or the timeframe indicated in the referring document (e.g. the prosecutor's order, instruction issued by a higher authority, etc.). Regardless of the circumstances, the duration of a comprehensive inspection is inherently conditioned by several factors: the surface area to be covered and the nature of the terrain, season, climatic conditions, number of cutting sites in operation, number of silvicultural works, issues identified, and the number of personnel involved. On average, a comprehensive inspection lasts between 4 and 12 days, though documented cases exist in which, due to identified irregularities, such an inspection extended to as long as 90 days.

2. Inspection of compliance with timber harvesting rules

- Definition/purpose

The inspection of compliance with timber harvesting rules is a control activity aimed at verifying the manner in which an authorised economic operator fulfils the obligations incumbent upon it within a harvesting plot. According to Article 19(1) of the 2011 Instructions regarding the deadlines, methods and periods for collecting, removing and transporting timber, approved by Order No. 1540/2011, such inspections aim to verify compliance with the provisions of these Instructions, with the purpose of preventing and limiting the damages that may be caused to the national forest fund through timber harvesting activities.

b) Legal basis (entitlement or obligation)

The authority to conduct this type of inspection is provided by Article 19(2) of the 2011 Instructions, Article 11(1) and (2), Article 132(1)(a) of Law No. 331/2024 – the 2024 Forest Code, and Article 6(1)(a), (j), and Article 19(1)(k) of Order No. 2185/2024.

The performance of this inspection constitutes a right of the Forest Guards, becoming an obligation under the following circumstances: complaints, requests from the Public Prosecutor's Office, police, other institutions, or instructions from higher authorities. The standardised control form is set out in Annex 5 of the 2011 Instructions approved by Order No. 1540/2011.

c) Frequency, duration and timeframe for execution

As this type of control is primarily a right of the institution, no specific duration or interval for execution is defined. The annual control plan establishes the scheduling of such inspections, generally indicating the number of actions and, at times, their location. When the inspection becomes an obligation, the timeframe is a maximum of 30 days or as stipulated by the referring document. The duration is conditioned by factors such as terrain, climatic conditions, issues detected, and the number of personnel involved. On average, the inspection lasts one day, although in cases of severe irregularities (illegal felling, suspected unauthorised use of the marking hammer, use of falsified devices, damage to regeneration, etc.), this duration may be significantly extended.

3. Inspection of timber transport legality

a) Definition/purpose

The inspection of timber transport legality is a control activity aimed at verifying

the legality of timber transports, the lawfulness of timber provenance, and the legality of placing such timber on the market.

b) Legal basis (entitlement or obligation)

The authority to conduct this type of control derives from Article 4(5)(a) of the 2020 Norms regarding the provenance, circulation and commercialisation of timber materials, the regime of timber storage facilities and roundwood processing installations, and provisions implementing Regulation (EU) No. 995/2010 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 October 2010, approved by Government Decision No. 923/2020; Article 24(1)(a) of Law No. 171/2010 on the establishment and sanctioning of forestry contraventions; Article 132(1)(c) of Law No. 331/2024 – the 2024 Forest Code; and Article 6(1)(e), Article 19(1)(w), (x), (y) of Order No. 2185/2024.

The performance of this control is a right of the Forest Guards, becoming an obligation when triggered by complaints, requests from the Public Prosecutor's Office, police or other institutions, or instructions from superior authorities. Since the applicable legislation does not provide a standard form for this control, the Suceava Forest Guard developed its own template.

c) Frequency, duration and timeframe for execution

As with other control types, no fixed timeframe is defined. Scheduling is done through the annual control plan. If the control becomes obligatory, the relevant document stipulates the deadline. Duration depends on factors such as route, season, climatic conditions, number of vehicles inspected, irregularities identified, and the size of the inspection team. On average, such inspections last one day, although severe irregularities (illegal transports, cubage difficulties, lack of handling equipment, etc.) may prolong the activity significantly.

4. Inspection of timber depots/processing installations

a) Definition/purpose

The inspection of timber depots and roundwood processing installations concerns the legality of timber provenance, processing activities, and the placing of timber products on the market.

b) Legal basis (entitlement or obligation)

The authority to conduct these inspections is established by Article 4(5)(a) of the 2020 Norms, Article 24(1)(a) of Law No.

171/2010, Article 132(1)(c) of Law No. 331/2024 – the 2024 Forest Code, and Article 6(1)(e), Article 19(1)(w), (x), (y) of Order No. 2185/2024.

This inspection is a right of the Forest Guards, becoming an obligation under the same conditions as above. As the legislation contains no standardised form, a template was created at institutional level.

c) Frequency, duration and timeframe for execution

The general rules on scheduling, obligations and duration apply similarly to this type of control. Duration is influenced by route, season, climatic conditions, number of vehicles checked, irregularities found, and staff involved. On average, the inspection lasts one day, though severe non-compliance issues may extend this significantly.

Outside these inspection categories, the Forest Guard also conducts other inspections based on statutory responsibilities.

Results of the activities conducted, structured by type of control, are reflected in quantitative indicators within the periodic reporting document entitled the guarding memorandum, drawn up quarterly by each Forest Guard and centralised at the National Forest Guard. These indicators were initially structured by forest ownership category, type of inspection, and nature of irregularities.

To analyse this reporting system, the SWOT method was used. In public and non-profit administration, Bryson (2018) recommends SWOT as an analytical instrument within a strategic cycle, contributing to clarifying the current position, challenges and development directions.

Table 1

SWOT Analysis of the Forest Guard Surveillance Report, Applied to Operational Data of the Suceava Forest Guard

<p>Puncte Forte (Strengths)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Detailed structure by counties, forest districts, ownership types and control types ✓ Easy to complete in Excel ✓ Possibility for manual consolidation ✓ Long-term use (at least 10 years), allowing comparative analyses over time ✓ Prevents additional information requests from the central public authority 	<p>Puncte Slabe (Weaknesses)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Absence of qualitative parameters within control activity ✗ Requires manual centralisation for numerous forest districts (88 districts) ✗ High risk of erroneous data entry due to the large number of fields – 412 ✗ Overlapping data between control types (e.g. illegal felling detected through comprehensive, partial, exploitation or stand-reconstruction inspections; possible association with illegal use of marking hammers)
<p>Oportunități (Opportunities)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Potential to develop a centralised digital platform (e.g. Google Forms) → Introduction of qualitative and performance indicators (aligned with National Forest Strategy 2030 – DSA 13 OECD, Forest Code) → Automation of reporting with automated flagging of potential irregularities → Integration with other forestry databases (SILV 1, SUMAL 2.0) 	<p>Amenințări (Threats)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⚠ Risk of errors and duplication in reporting ⚠ High manual workload → staff demotivation ⚠ Lack of standardisation of national datasets ⚠ Risk of misinterpretation and reduced transparency

Analysis of the evolution of control indicators at the Suceava Forest Guard (2016–2024)

Based on the guarding memorandum, correlated with the share of activities carried out and with the accuracy of data enabling correlation, the following indicators were identified as relevant, with their corresponding

position in the memorandum shown in parentheses:

- Forest inspections (comprehensive, partial, integrity checks, grazing inspections, fire prevention) – number of actions (13)
- Illegal timber volume (m³) (19)
- Timber transport inspections – number of actions (56)

- Contraventions recorded during timber transport inspections – number (57)
 - Timber confiscated during transport inspections (m^3) (60)
 - Inspections of processing installations, depots etc. – number of actions (65)
 - Offences identified during inspections of processing installations, depots etc. – number (66)
 - Contraventions identified during inspections of processing installations, depots etc. – number (67)
 - Timber confiscated during inspections of processing installations, depots etc. (m^3) (70+75)
 - Exploitation inspections – number of actions (79)
 - Contraventions identified during exploitation inspections – number (80)

Comprehensive/partial inspections and associated indicators (number of inspections, volume detected as illegally harvested)

The number of forest inspections corresponding to Chapter 1, point 13 of the guarding memorandum provides an aggregate view of inspections conducted in the forest fund, combining comprehensive/partial inspections with those aimed at forest integrity, grazing and fire prevention. Given the importance and weight of these inspections, the parameter that must be considered and correlated with other indicators is the number of comprehensive/ partial inspections. In the absence of a breakdown by distinct inspection types, it is not possible to present the temporal fluctuation of their numbers.

For a qualitative assessment, it would have been necessary to report the area surveyed during comprehensive/partial inspections relative to the total forest fund area. Unfortunately, this parameter is not quantified, although it would have been relevant for assessing the proportion of forest area effectively inspected.

From the processing of available data, the following aspects emerged:

- Incorrect reporting in 2016, likely due to a transcription error or the summation of values inconsistent with reality, indirectly confirming one of the weaknesses highlighted in the SWOT analysis.
 - The average number of inspections per employee is 6.5, indicating that—contrary to the importance of this inspection type—the actual activity is relatively limited.

- In the absence of data on the inspected area, the proportion of inspected forest relative to the total forest fund cannot be assessed.

Within comprehensive/partial inspections, the principal indicator monitored is the volume of illegally harvested timber. In assessing the intensity of the phenomenon, it is relevant to relate the volume detected as illegally harvested to the total forest fund area. According to Bouriaud (2005), “A Romanian official acknowledged that, in fact, nobody knows how much timber is harvested from private forests, estimating approximately 4 million m^3 of black-market timber, meaning 30% to 40% more than the officially recorded volumes.” Regarding the Suceava Forest Guard’s area of competence, the same author notes that in northern Romania, private owners acknowledged that in the absence of a forest management plan, they harvest 3–4 m^3 /ha/year instead of the legal quota of 2 m^3 /ha/year.

In this context, the most relevant indicator remains the volume of illegally harvested timber.

Figure 1 Illegal volume harvested per forest area

Both the effectiveness of inspections and the intensity of the illegal harvesting phenomenon can be calculated by reporting the volume detected as illegally harvested to the number of inspections conducted (noting that the calculation is based on the parameter in the guarding memorandum and not strictly on comprehensive/partial inspections):

Figure 2 Evolution of the ratio between illegal volume and forest control actions

Both qualitative indicators highlight a significant decline in illegal timber harvesting, at least at levels detectable through comprehensive/partial inspections.

Exploitation control and associated indicators

As in the case of comprehensive/partial inspections, the absence of data regarding either the inspected surface area or the timber volume associated with harvesting plots prevents the calculation of ratios such as inspected area vs. total forest area, or inspected timber volume vs. total harvested timber volume.

In this situation, the analysis of efficiency was limited to the ratio between the number of contraventions applied and the number of exploitation inspections conducted.

Figure 3 Evolution of the sanction-to-exploitation control ratio

The analysis of the data indicates a significant increase in exploitation inspections that resulted in sanctions, eventually reaching a ratio of approximately one sanction for every two inspections carried out.

Control of timber circulation and associated indicators (confiscated volume, number and value of contraventions, number of offences)

The activity of controlling the circulation of timber is one largely carried out in cooperation with the police authorities, due to the fact that the competence to stop vehicles on public roads lies exclusively with them. Another defining feature of these actions is that, through the "SUMAL 2.0 system - Inspectorul pădurii", any interested natural or legal person may report suspected irregularities related to timber transport.

The qualitative assessment of this type of control focused on two aspects:

1. territorial coverage (number of inspections per 1,000 ha), and
2. average number of sanctions imposed per inspection, together with timber volume confiscated per inspection.

Figure 4 Evolution of the ratio between forest area and number of wood-transport controls

Figure 5 Evolution of the sanction-to-wood-transport control ratio

Figure 6 Evolution of the ratio between confiscated volume and wood-transport controls

Efficiency could also be measured by relating the number of verified transport authorisations to the number of authorisations issued (according to SUMAL 2.0) within a given period and region. Since there is no central recording of the number of vehicles or authorisations actually verified, this correlation cannot currently be made.

Correlating the data on timber-transport inspections shows a downward trend in the number of inspections, combined with an increase in the number of sanctions applied per inspection, as well as an increase in the volume confiscated per inspection.

An important parameter relevant to the efficiency of timber-transport control is the number of offences, particularly because, starting in 2020, under Law No. 197/2020, the transport of quantities exceeding 10 m³ without proof of legal provenance constitutes a criminal offence. Moreover, the current Forest Code has lowered this threshold to 5 m³. Since these actions are conducted jointly with the police, and the legal measures (e.g. confiscation of the transport vehicle and initiation of criminal proceedings) are applied by the police, this parameter is not included in the guarding memorandum, although it would be relevant for assessing enforcement effectiveness.

Control of timber depots/processing installations and associated indicators

(number of inspections, confiscated volume, number of sanctions)

The control of timber depots and processing installations represents a significant share of enforcement activities. In terms of results (number and value of sanctions, volume of confiscated timber), this is the type of control that has generated the highest revenues for the State budget.

Our analysis examined:

1. the evolution over time of the number of inspections and of detected offences, and
2. the efficiency of these inspections, expressed as the ratio of sanctions applied and confiscated timber volume relative to the number of inspections.

Figure 7 Variation over time in the number of sawmill deposit controls

Figure 8 Time variation of detected offences at sawmill deposit controls

Figure 9 Evolution of the sanction-to-sawmill control ratio

Figure 10 Dynamics of confiscated wood mass over time

The data clearly indicate an increase in enforcement efficiency and a targeted focus on high-risk entities. This improvement is attributable to:

- The use of SUMAL 2.0, which provides access to information (timber volumes, suppliers, historical stock evolution, and protected data-integrity mechanisms) that, when cross-referenced, yields valuable insights for enforcement;
- Inter-institutional cooperation with other relevant authorities (forest administrators, police, gendarmerie);
- Public access to transport data in SUMAL, enabling the reporting of irregularities not only by State authorities but also by citizens.

According to Bouriaud et al. (2014), “Illegal logging is connected to forest-related activities such as timber harvesting, processing, transport and commercialisation in violation of the law.”

An interesting aspect concerning illegal harvesting volumes is the correlation between:

- the volume detected during comprehensive inspections,
- the volume identified as illegal in transport controls, and
- the volume identified in depot/processing-installation inspections.

The graph below compares these three indicators:

Figure 11 Time dynamics of illegal harvested volume vs. confiscated volume

This graphic representation indicates that although the volume identified as illegally harvested shows a continuous decline, the volumes confiscated during transport and depot/processing inspections remain at very high levels.

This apparent anomaly may have several causes, which may act simultaneously to varying degrees.

Possible causes:

1. The reorientation of enforcement efforts, with an emphasis on timber transport and processing installations at the expense of forest-fund inspections;
2. Confiscation of timber not originating from illegal harvesting, when loss of traceability arises from procedural breaches rather than actual illegal felling;
3. Confiscation of timber that may have resulted from illegal activities in previous years;
4. Illegal harvesting carried out through alteration of dendrometric data in valuation documents or through unauthorised use of marking devices.

For causes 1 and 4, analyses may be conducted and methods developed to evaluate enforcement outcomes by:

- Analysing the distribution of enforcement activities and correlating them directly with their respective outcomes;
- Including, in the reporting of volumes detected as illegally harvested (from the guarding memorandum), the quantities detected during stand reconstruction or cases involving illegal use of marking devices.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The present article highlights the necessity for major changes in the approach to evaluating control activities and in the way these activities are reported.

With regard to the indicators of control activity, for a realistic and objective measurement of performance, we consider it appropriate to shift from exclusively quantitative indicators to qualitative indicators. These new indicators are intended to reflect the efficiency of control activities from multiple perspectives:

- the degree of coverage of the forest sector by inspections (e.g. area inspected through comprehensive control/total forest fund area; number of verified transports/total number of transports; number of economic operators inspected/total number of authorised operators, etc.);
- institutional effort (e.g. number of inspections of a certain type/number of staff with enforcement duties; total value of sanctions applied and recovered/annual institutional budget);
- the intensity and frequency of legal violations (e.g. number of sanctions applied/number of inspections conducted; confiscated volume/number of inspections; confiscated volume/illegally harvested volume, etc.).

Regarding the reporting methodology, we consider that the following actions would be beneficial and would produce immediate effects:

- automation of data centralisation in the guarding memorandum;
- clarification and completion of terminology used in the memorandum;
- introduction of qualitative indicators that can be derived from the existing data in the current reporting template.

Rethinking the method for evaluating control activities will implicitly generate greater efficiency and a more outcome-focused orientation of enforcement actions.

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TECHNICAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE TRENDS IN TIMBER HARVESTING IN ROMANIA AND ACROSS EUROPE

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

The paper analyzes the technical and administrative developments in timber harvesting in Romania and Europe, highlighting the transformations driven by machinery modernization, process digitalization, and the adoption of forest policies oriented toward sustainability. The study shows that developed European countries have reached a high level of mechanization, particularly through the use of cut-to-length systems and digital monitoring technologies, while Romania is undergoing a gradual alignment process influenced by mountainous terrain, limited forest infrastructure, and fragmented ownership. At the administrative level, the new Forest Code (Law No. 331/2024), the implementation of the SUMAL 2.0 system, and the shift toward the valorization of processed timber represent important steps toward increasing transparency and professionalization within the sector. A comparison of European management models—public, private, associative, and corporate—highlights the need to strengthen institutional capacity and increase the degree of mechanization in Romania. The conclusions emphasize the necessity of an integrated approach that combines technical modernization, administrative reform, and responsibility toward forest resources in the context of climate change and European legislative requirements.

Keywords: mechanization, governance, sustainability, digitalization, biodiversity, regulation

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INTRODUCTION

Timber harvesting is undergoing profound transformation both in Romania and across Europe, driven by technological progress, pressures generated by climate change, and increasingly stringent environmental protection requirements (Forest Europe, 2020; FAO, 2020). Over the past two decades, the demands of sustainable forest management, the digitalization of administrative processes, and the implementation of complex European policies have significantly reshaped the way timber harvesting is organized. In this context, professional standards, traceability, and low-impact technologies have become central pillars of modern forest operations.

As highlighted by Horodnic (2014) in his work on forest operations engineering, the current direction of development aims at adapting technologies to ecological principles, marking the emergence of a new field: "forest operations ecology." This approach seeks to reduce negative effects on soil, water, biodiversity, and the atmosphere through energy-efficient technologies, spatially optimized extraction systems, and interventions

adapted to natural conditions (Horodnic, 2014; Proto et al., 2018).

At the European level, timber harvesting has rapidly evolved toward full mechanization, particularly through cut-to-length (CTL) systems based on harvesters and forwarders. This process has been facilitated by the high density of forest infrastructure, advanced environmental policies, and European regulations concerning traceability and supply-chain responsibility. The adoption of Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 on deforestation-free products (EUDR) marks a defining moment, imposing strict due-diligence and geospatial traceability obligations on operators (European Commission, 2023).

In Romania, the evolution of the sector is distinct and strongly influenced by natural conditions, particularly by the mountainous terrain and the less developed forest road network (Abrudan, 2012; Popa & Bann, 2012). These realities maintain the predominance of semi-mechanized systems—especially articulated forest tractors (TAFs), skidders, and cable yarding systems—and lead to the widespread application of the tree-length method, characterized by the extraction of long logs and by extended skidding distances (Borz

et al., 2016). Studies conducted in the Carpathians show that skidding distances frequently range between 250 and 1,000 meters, depending on accessibility, which significantly affects productivity and operational costs (Borz et al., 2013; Kaakkurivaara et al., 2022).

At the legislative level, Romania is gradually narrowing the gap with Central European countries through the adoption of the new Forest Code—Law No. 331/2024, published in the Official Gazette No. 7/2025. This law strengthens the principles of sustainable forest management, redefines administrative structures (including the National Forest Guard), and uniformly regulates the system for timber evaluation, harvesting, and transport, in close correlation with the requirements of the SUMAL 2.0 digital system. The digitalization of traceability flows, transport verification, and stock monitoring in depots enables closer alignment with European standards (MMAP, n.d.).

Traditionally associated with manual or semi-mechanized activities, the timber harvesting sector is thus entering a phase of profound modernization. This process is amplified by the broader European context, in which the need to comply with climate objectives, adapt to extreme events (storms, fires, windthrow), and increase the social responsibility of operators requires high-performance technologies, efficient administration, and full transparency throughout the timber supply chain (FAO & UNEP, 2020; EFI, 2019).

In Romania, major challenges include insufficient infrastructure, fragmented ownership, limited financial resources for many owners and companies, and a public perception that is often critical of timber harvesting (Halalisan et al., 2014). However, the introduction of modern harvesting technologies, the expansion of digital monitoring systems, and the improvement of the legal framework indicate a positive shift toward professionalization and efficiency (Nicolescu et al., 2018).

Against this backdrop, analyzing technical and administrative trends is essential for understanding how Romania's forest sector adapts to current and future requirements. This study offers a comprehensive synthesis of developments in Romania and other European states, highlighting modernization directions, emerging tools, and their impact on timber

harvesting, with the aim of supporting a coherent and sustainable approach to forest resource management.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study focuses on the technical and administrative trends that characterize timber harvesting in Romania and Europe. Although the two dimensions are addressed separately for conceptual clarity, they do not function independently: mechanization, infrastructure, and harvesting methods directly influence administrative structures, while organization and regulation determine the technical possibilities of forest operations. Thus, the study follows a complementary approach, highlighting the permanent interdependence between technology and administration in the process of sustainable forest management.

TECHNICAL TRENDS IN TIMBER HARVESTING

The technical trends in timber harvesting in Romania and Europe reflect an accelerated modernization of harvesting methods, a continuous increase in mechanization levels, and an adaptation of forestry practices to climatic challenges, socio-economic pressures, and European legislative requirements. In the developed countries of Europe, modern technologies have been systematically integrated over the past decades, leading to higher efficiency and reduced environmental impact. In Romania, the process follows the same direction, but the pace is shaped by terrain characteristics, existing infrastructure, and the economic performance of sector operators.

In most European countries with accessible forests, timber harvesting has evolved toward the fully mechanized cut-to-length (CTL) system, in which the harvester-forwarder pair performs all felling, processing, and primary extraction operations (Table 1). This system has become dominant in Scandinavia, where over 95% of the annual volume is harvested using CTL. Its adoption is explained by high efficiency, operational flexibility, standardized assortments, and integration with digital planning tools. Research conducted in Central Europe and Scandinavia shows that CTL technology enables the optimization of timber flow and a significant reduction in soil pressure—important aspects in the context of climate change and sustainability requirements (Mederski, 2022; Labelle & Lemmer, 2019).

Table 1
Level of Forest Mechanization in Different European Regions

Region	Mechanization level	Dominant harvesting system	Observations
Romania	Medium	Semi-mechanized (TAF)	Mountainous terrain, few forest roads
Central Europe	High	CTL + modern cable yarding systems	Good accessibility
Scandinavia	Very high	95–100% CTL	Excellent infrastructure
Southeast Europe	Low–Medium	Chainsaw + tractors	Fragmented ownership

In contrast with these developments, countries with predominantly mountainous terrain—such as Romania, Slovakia, Bulgaria, and partly Austria or Italy—still retain a significant share of semi-mechanized harvesting systems. In Romania, the dominant harvesting method continues to rely on manual felling and bucking using chainsaws, followed by timber extraction with articulated forest tractors (TAF) or skidders (table 2).

This situation is influenced by the low density of forest roads, property fragmentation, and the limited accessibility of certain forested areas. Studies by Borz et al. (2016) and Kaakkurivaara et al. (2022) show that, under such conditions, extraction distances often exceed 300–600 m and, in difficult terrain, may reach up to 1,000 m, which significantly affects productivity, fuel consumption, and operational costs.

Table 2
Characteristics of the main harvesting systems

Characteristic	CTL System (cut-to-length)	Tree-length system (semi-mechanized)
Type of equipment	Harvester + forwarder	Chainsaw + TAF / skidder
Soil impact	Low	Medium–high
Terrain suitability	Ideal in accessible terrain	Suitable for mountainous areas
Productivity	High	Variable
Infrastructure requirements	High	Medium
Investment cost	Very high	Medium

Figure 1 Comparison of CTL vs. tree-length performance

A distinctive element of forest operations in Romania is the traditional and still necessary use of cable yarding systems, which are essential on steep terrain. These cable systems allow timber to be harvested safely and with reduced soil impact, avoiding the need to build forest roads in sensitive areas. Popa and Borz (2019) highlight that the yarders used in the Carpathians can operate over distances of 150–500 m, while recent European research shows that modern cable yarders can exceed 600 m, using computerized winches and automated carriages, which reduce downtime and increase work safety (Spinelli et al., 2020; Stampfer, 2015). Although high initial costs and the need for a specialized crew limit their large-scale application, cable yarders remain the optimal technical solution in mountainous conditions.

The differences between Romania and the Nordic countries become even more evident when analyzing forest infrastructure. Countries such as Sweden or Finland benefit from dense forest road networks, which allow timber extraction over average distances of 50–150 m. This infrastructure supports full mechanization, reduces logistical costs, and minimizes equipment wear. In Romania, the significantly lower forest road density results in much larger extraction distances, leading to higher energy consumption and lower productivity. Romanian research in this field emphasizes that the optimal extraction distance for TAF operations should remain below 400–500 m, a threshold beyond which costs increase considerably (Borz et al., 2013; Borz et al., 2016).

The technological flows of primary transport and handling in Romania are organized around primary landings, located at the edge of harvesting sites, and intermediate depots situated along public roads. These points serve for sorting, weighing, and loading timber

for final transport. This structure is compatible with the requirements of the SUMAL 2.0 system, which mandates full traceability of timber and strict control over each logistical stage, in accordance with the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 (EUDR). In other European countries, intermediate depots are often equipped with automatic measurement systems, high-performance loading machinery, and integrated digital technologies, which optimize operational times and reduce losses (EFI, 2019).

In Western Europe and Scandinavia, recent trends include the use of winch-assist technologies, whereby harvesters are supported by winches anchored at the upper part of the slope, enabling safe mechanization on gradients exceeding 35–45%. There is also a marked shift toward electric or hybrid machinery, reduced soil pressure through wide contact-area tracks, the use of sensors and drones for route planning and stand monitoring, as well as the integration of LIDAR models in operational analyses. Romania has begun to adopt these technologies gradually, particularly through projects financed by the NRDP or the NRRP, but the overall level of mechanization remains lower than in Western countries.

Regarding the structure of the sector, Romania is characterized by a very large number of small and medium-sized enterprises, most of which have limited financial capacity, making the acquisition of CTL equipment or modern cable yarders difficult (table 3). In contrast, Nordic countries operate through strong cooperatives and integrated corporations that own extensive fleets of modern machinery and can invest consistently in advanced technologies (Moskalik et al., 2017). This difference in capitalization partially explains the mechanization gap between Romania and Western Europe.

Table 3
Synthetic parameters for forestry harvesting companies (CAEN 0220), Romania (2022)

Indicator	Value (2022)
Number of active companies	2,295
Number of employees	11,267
Total turnover (RON)	4,284,911,798
Total net profit (RON)	579,197,496

Sources: RisCo – Top Companies 2022, CAEN code 0220 “Logging”.

Overall, European technical trends indicate a quick shift toward full mechanization,

digitalization, and the use of technologies with reduced impact on soil and biodiversity. Romania follows the same directions, but at a pace influenced by terrain characteristics, existing infrastructure, and the economic structure of the sector. Strategic directions for the future include the modernization of machinery, the diversification of technologies used on steep terrain, investments in forest infrastructure, and the strengthening of the operational capacity of harvesting companies.

ADMINISTRATIVE TRENDS IN TIMBER HARVESTING

Administrative trends in the Romanian and European forestry sector reflect a profound reorganization of institutions, valorization processes, control instruments, and the responsibilities of economic operators, in line with new environmental policies and the need for sustainable resource management (table 4). Forest administration can no longer be viewed solely as a technical activity, but as a complex system integrating economic, social, ecological, and legislative requirements. Differences among European countries arise from property structures, forest management traditions, levels of economic development, and institutional heritage, yet the overarching directions are largely convergent.

Table 4
Administrative models of forest management in Europe

Administrative model	Representative countries	Share in Europe (approx.)	Main characteristics
State public	Romania, France, Finland	~35–45%	Continuity, long-term planning
Individual private	Germany, Sweden, Austria	~45–50%	High investment, full mechanization
Community / communal	Austria, Switzerland	~10%	Local decision-making, strong tradition
Cooperative	Sweden (Södra), Finland	~5%	Economic efficiency, advanced mechanization

In Romania, the new Forest Code – Law no. 331/2024, published in the Official Gazette no. 7/2025 – represents the central element of current regulation. It redefines the framework for forest management, establishes the principles of sustainable administration,

strengthens the role of the National Forest Guard, and updates the mechanisms for timber appraisal, harvesting, and circulation. The Code emphasizes management continuity, the responsibility of forest administrators, as well as the need for digitalization, transparency, and alignment with European legislation. The introduction of stricter sanctions, the explicit regulation of forestry services for private owners, and the formalization of stringent procedures for timber harvesting, transport, and sale provide a more robust administrative framework designed to reduce illegal activities and increase the level of professionalization in the sector.

At the level of public administration, forests in the public ownership of the state are managed by the National Forest Administration – Romsilva, an institution that administers approximately 48% of Romania’s national forest fund. This model is similar to that of France, where the National Forest Office (ONF) manages both state and communal forests, or to Finland, where Metsähallitus administers state-owned forest lands, integrating them into a coherent national strategy (table 5). In these public models, ecological, social, and economic objectives are addressed simultaneously, with long-term planning at their core. The advantage lies in management continuity and high administrative capacity, while risks include bureaucratic rigidity and reduced ability to rapidly adapt to market changes.

Table 5

Examples of state forest administrators in Europe

Country	Organization	Managed area (million ha)	Notes
Romania	Romsilva	3.13	State-owned public forests
France	ONF	≈11	Public forests (state and local authorities)
Finland	Metsähallitus	≈9	State lands (including forests)
Latvia	Latvijas valsts meži (LVM)	≈1.4	State forests
Austria	ÖBf	≈0.51	State-managed forests

Sources: Romsilva, ONF, Metsähallitus, LVM, ÖBf – official reports. Values are approximate.

Private forest management plays an important role in most European countries, where individual owners, companies,

foundations, or industrial corporations manage large forest areas. In Sweden and Finland, cooperatives such as Södra or corporations such as Stora Enso and UPM-Kymmene administer extensive forest holdings, using integrated digital systems, full mechanization, and intensive production planning. Romania finds itself in a different situation: although roughly half of its forests are privately owned, they are highly fragmented, with many plots being small or very small. Under these conditions, management is ensured by private or public forest districts, which contributes to the standardization of practices but limits the ability of owners to invest in modern technologies. Studies by Abrudan (2012) and Halalisan et al. (2014) show that although the diversity of ownership forms can be an advantage, the lack of financial resources and technical expertise poses major challenges for small owners.

Community and communal ownership forms play a particularly important role. These structures—traditional in Romania (traditional community forest associations and joint ownership forest associations) and well developed in Switzerland, Austria, or Germany—allow community involvement in decision-making, and revenues from timber harvesting are reinvested locally. However, their technical and financial capacity is limited, and management often depends on forest districts. In Romania, these entities administer significant areas in mountainous regions where harvesting is difficult, making their success dependent on collaboration with professional forest managers.

Timber valorization in Romania is carried out through three main modalities: standing timber sales, processed (roadside) timber sales, and contracting harvesting services. The current strategic direction, supported by the new Forest Code and national policy, is to reduce the volume sold as standing timber and increase the share of processed timber delivered at forest roads or depots (table 6). This model, already dominant in Central and Northern Europe, provides superior control over work quality, allows accurate monitoring of volumes, and reduces the risk of overharvesting. In countries such as Germany, Austria, or Sweden, standing timber is sold only in small proportions, while most timber is processed and sorted in modern depots managed by administrations or cooperatives.

Table 6
The stages of the wood supply chain in Romania

Stage	Description	Involved actors
Primary landing	Wood is collected from the harvesting site	Logger / harvesting company
Intermediate depot	Sorting, weighing, SUMAL 2.0 documentation	Forest district / company
Final depot	Industrial reception, document verification	Industry / local authority (UAT)
Transport	Transport monitored through SUMAL 2.0	Transport operator

Digitalization of forest administration is one of the most important recent trends. In Romania, the SUMAL 2.0 system serves as the central digital infrastructure for recording timber volumes, issuing and verifying transport documents, and monitoring stocks. The public interface “*Forest Inspector*” enables real-time verification of timber transports, increasing transparency and reducing the potential for fraud.

Environmental organizations’ assessments have shown that the implementation of SUMAL 2.0 has led to a decrease in unjustified transports and improved identification of vulnerable areas. At the European level, the EUTR and EUDR regulations impose strict due diligence obligations on operators, including geospatial identification of origin parcels, risk assessment, and maintaining chain-of-custody systems. This requires forest administrations and economic operators to adopt complex IT systems capable of managing parcel-level data.

Across Europe, forest administration is becoming increasingly transparent and better integrated into environmental policies. Countries such as Finland and Norway publish detailed data on harvesting, planning, silvicultural works, and environmental impacts, and their national GIS systems are interoperable with European platforms. Romania is advancing in the same direction, but at a gradual pace, marked by the consolidation of the legal framework and the expansion of digital tools—yet limited by the financial capacity of local administrations and the level of staff training.

Timber valorization by local administrative units (UATs) and communal forests follows specific procedures: local councils annually approve the volumes according to the management plan, while auctions for timber sales are organized by forest

districts, based on clear transparency criteria. This model ensures a certain procedural uniformity, but efficiency depends on the administrative capacity of each UAT. In practice, differences are significant, and some local administrations face difficulties in applying legislation or in ensuring transparent management of the process.

Overall, European administrative trends converge toward a model characterized by advanced digitalization, increased transparency, professionalization, strengthening of the public role of forest administrations, and greater accountability for economic operators. Romania is gradually aligning with these directions, and the evolution of the legislative and technological framework demonstrates a clear intention to modernize the sector. The development of institutional capacity, the expansion of control systems, and the support for associative forms of forest management will play a key role in accelerating this transition.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Wood harvesting in Romania and across Europe is undergoing a broad process of transformation, driven by climate challenges, socio-economic pressures, sustainability requirements, and the rapid evolution of forestry technologies. A comparative analysis of technical and administrative trends highlights both shared directions and the specific features of each national context. Although development models and investment capacities differ significantly between Northern Europe and Central-Southern Europe, the objectives converge toward the sustainable, efficient, and transparent management of forest resources.

On the technical side, the evolution of the European sector is dominated by full mechanization and the adoption of modern harvesting systems such as CTL (cut-to-length), supported by the development of forest infrastructure and the use of advanced digital technologies for planning and monitoring operations. Romania is gradually aligning with these trends, albeit at a moderate pace, influenced by the challenges posed by mountainous terrain, the low density of forest roads, and fragmented ownership. The use of skidders (TAF), semi-mechanized systems, and cable yarders remains characteristic of inaccessible areas; however, the gradual introduction of harvesters, forwarders, winch-assist systems, and monitoring tools based on

drones and GIS marks the beginning of a consistent modernization.

On the administrative side, the changes are equally profound. The new Forest Code – Law no. 331/2024 – has strengthened a modern legislative framework oriented toward responsibility, efficiency, and environmental protection, integrating the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 on deforestation-free products (EUDR). Digitalization, through SUMAL 2.0, has become the central tool for monitoring timber, ensuring transparency of flows, and reinforcing the fight against illegal logging. At the same time, the reform of timber valuation procedures, the shift toward selling processed (cut-to-length) timber, and the professionalization of the management of private and community-owned forests contribute to improved forest governance.

At the European level, forest administrations—whether public, private, associative, or corporate—have developed a management model that is adaptable and integrated with climate and biodiversity conservation policies. Romania is in a process of converging with these standards, benefiting

from a modern legal framework, strong digital tools, and a professional community increasingly connected to international trends. However, significant challenges remain, such as infrastructure modernization, strengthening the administrative capacity of local authorities (UATs), increasing the level of mechanization, and developing forest cooperatives that would allow small forest owners to access professional services and modern technologies.

Overall, both technically and administratively, the direction of evolution is clear: advanced mechanization, digitalization, transparency, responsibility, and sustainability. Romania has considerable potential, and through strategic investments, institutional strengthening, and the adoption of European best practices, the forestry sector can reach a high level of efficiency, competitiveness, and compliance with international standards. The modernization of wood harvesting is not only a technical necessity but also an administrative, economic, and social one, and harmonizing these components is essential for the sustainable management of forests

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OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN FORESTRY: CONTEXT AND CHALLENGES

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

Occupational safety in forestry and logging operations represents a complex challenge shaped by the interaction between the natural environment, human factors, and technology. Although the forestry sector has benefited from technological progress, it remains one of the most hazardous industries, with persistently high rates of severe and fatal accidents. The determining factors include unpredictable natural conditions—terrain configuration, vegetation density, unstable soils, and meteorological variability—alongside workers' experience and behavior, as well as technical equipment that is often inadequate or poorly maintained. Accidents arise from a combination of these elements, and a simplistic approach that attributes incidents solely to human error proves insufficient. Safety culture, which reflects the way employees perceive and manage risks, plays a central role in prevention. Its development requires continuous training, active managerial involvement, and open communication at all organizational levels. Preventive measures encompass on-site risk assessments, the use of personal protective equipment, adherence to standardized work procedures, and the integration of modern technologies.

Keywords: safety culture, forestry work, risk factors, forest harvesting, forestry sector

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INTRODUCTION

Forestry and forest harvesting rank among the most complex and hazardous professional activities, both due to the nature of the environments in which they take place and the dynamic character of the operations involved. In the global context of recent decades—marked by increasing pressure on natural resources and a steadily rising demand for wood products—the forestry sector must reconcile its economic objectives with the responsibility to ensure safe working conditions for its workforce. International organizations such as the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the International Labour Organization (ILO) emphasize that, despite substantial technological advancements, forestry remains one of the most dangerous industries worldwide, displaying a disproportionately high rate of serious and fatal accidents (Poschen, 2011). This situation underscores the necessity for an in-depth examination of occupational risks, the determinants of accidents, and the ways in which safety culture can transform the sector into one that is both sustainable and prevention-oriented.

The significance of such an analysis derives not only from the imperative to protect workers' health and lives, but also from the fact that occupational safety is directly linked to the sector's economic efficiency. A severe accident can produce far-reaching operational consequences, including delays, substantial financial losses, legal liabilities, and a deterioration of worker morale. Over the long term, the absence of a strong safety culture affects the reputation of forestry organizations, their ability to attract qualified personnel, and, consequently, the stability of the market. Therefore, a thorough assessment of risks and the formulation of appropriate preventive measures become not only necessary actions but also essential strategic components for the long-term development of the forestry sector (Garland et al., 2020).

Beyond its economic and ecological significance, the forestry sector constitutes a domain of major interest for interdisciplinary research, positioned at the intersection of environmental sciences, occupational health and safety, engineering, and the social sciences. The forestry work environment combines natural uncertainty with complex interactions between human factors and technology, making

it particularly relevant for the analysis of systemic risk and for the development of adaptive safety strategies. In this context, occupational risks cannot be understood solely as isolated events, but rather as outcomes of dynamic and interdependent processes.

Despite the existence of well-established legislative frameworks and international guidelines, accident rates in forestry remain high in many regions, indicating a substantial gap between formal regulations and their implementation under real working conditions. This discrepancy highlights the need to move beyond strictly normative approaches and toward analytical models capable of capturing the context-specific nature of risk. Examining how safety measures are implemented, adapted, or disregarded in practice becomes essential for identifying the limitations of conventional prevention systems (Garland et al., 2020).

From a scientific perspective, research on occupational safety in the forestry sector has traditionally focused on individual risk factors or technical failures. However, recent developments in occupational risk theory emphasize the importance of integrated approaches that account for cumulative exposure, behavioral adaptation, and organizational learning processes. In this regard, forestry activities provide a relevant framework for analyzing how risk is negotiated on a daily basis within environments characterized by high variability and limited control.

This study integrates theoretical foundations and internationally established guidelines to provide a comprehensive perspective on the complexity of the forest environment as both a professional setting and a zone of inherent risk. Its objective is to highlight how the interaction between natural, human, and technological factors generates a challenging occupational landscape, while also demonstrating the central role that safety culture plays in mitigating risks and fostering a sustainable long-term working environment.

FOREST: WORKPLACE AND RISK

The forest, by definition, represents a living, dynamic, and fundamentally unpredictable ecosystem. In contrast to industries that operate in controlled environments, forestry operations take place in a context where every natural element can influence the level of risk (FAO, 1993). Variable

terrain, soil composition, vegetation density, weather conditions, and the presence of biological factors constitute essential components of an environment that is difficult to standardize. Forestry workers must perform their tasks on steep slopes, unstable areas, wet or frozen soils, amid exposed roots, dense vegetation, and natural obstacles that may impede movement and equipment handling. Unlike other professions, in which risks can be consistently anticipated, forestry work requires repeated assessments, constant adaptation, and a high capacity for rapid decision-making under stressful conditions (FAO, 1993).

Weather conditions represent another major factor affecting worker safety. Strong winds, sudden precipitation, extreme temperatures, or microclimatic variations can radically alter tree stability and the safety level of workers (Garland et al., 2020). For instance, a tree that appears stable under calm conditions can become extremely hazardous during gusty winds. Simultaneously, the presence of soil moisture, combined with leaf litter or snow cover, reduces the traction of work footwear and increases the risk of slips.

A distinct aspect of forestry work is isolation. In many cases, worksites are located at considerable distances from populated areas, limiting rapid access to medical care and emergency teams. In the absence of effective communication systems, even minor accidents can become fatal. Consequently, isolation significantly amplifies worker vulnerability and underscores the importance of well-structured preventive measures, first-aid training, and detailed operational planning.

The human factor plays a central role in risk dynamics. The experience of forestry workers, their ability to assess hazards, their interpretation of natural signals, and their proficiency in handling technical equipment directly contribute to accident prevention. Research indicates that workers at the beginning of their careers are exposed to significantly higher risks, particularly due to lack of experience and practical skills (Poschen, 2011). In many countries, young or seasonal workers are employed without adequate training, which considerably increases the number of severe accidents.

Technology in the forestry sector is constantly evolving. While modern equipment reduces direct exposure to hazards, it introduces new risks, particularly associated with the operation of heavy machinery. Vehicle

overturns, hydraulic system failures, mechanical blockages, or limited visibility can trigger serious accidents (Poschen, 2011). In economically constrained regions, equipment is often outdated, improvised, or inadequately adapted, which significantly intensifies operational hazards.

FACTORS INFLUENCING OCCUPATIONAL ACCIDENTS IN THE FORESTRY SECTOR

Accidents in forestry operations arise from a complex interplay of interdependent factors. FAO analyses emphasize that the majority of severe incidents are not the result of a single element, but rather a combination of factors such as inadequate training, human errors, technical malfunctions, adverse weather conditions, and the absence of proper supervision (FAO, 1993). This reality necessitates a systemic approach to safety, one that goes beyond the simplistic perspective attributing accidents solely to worker mistakes.

Human factors constitute the primary category of accident determinants. Inattention, fatigue, lack of experience, overestimation of personal abilities, and productivity pressures frequently lead to risky decisions. A worker who fells trees without correctly assessing their direction of fall or who operates a chainsaw from an unstable position exposes themselves to immediate hazards. Simultaneously, workers compensated on a piece-rate or quota basis are prone to bypass safety steps in an attempt to increase productivity, a practice that is highly dangerous (Garland et al., 2020).

Faulty or inappropriate technical equipment represents another significant determinant of accidents. Older machinery, lack of regular maintenance, mechanical improvisations, and the absence of specialized equipment are acute problems in many developing countries. Conversely, even modern equipment can become hazardous when operated by untrained personnel.

Organizational and managerial conditions decisively influence the level of risk. Lack of direct supervision, absence or non-enforcement of procedures, economic pressures, and poor communication are factors that increase the likelihood of accidents. In many cases, forestry organizations lack formal risk monitoring systems or do not encourage incident reporting, which limits their capacity for learning and continuous improvement.

An additional factor influencing the occurrence of occupational accidents in the forestry sector is the organization of working time and the management of chronic fatigue. Forestry activities involve intense physical exertion, prolonged periods of concentration, and continuous muscular strain. Extended working hours, insufficient rest breaks, or the absence of task rotation lead to a reduced capacity for reaction and judgment. Accumulated fatigue adversely affects coordination, attention, and risk assessment, thereby increasing the likelihood of errors that, in the forestry environment, may result in severe or fatal consequences.

Another distinct element concerns the contractual structure of the workforce, particularly the frequent use of subcontracting and temporary employment. Workers engaged on short-term contracts or through intermediaries are often insufficiently integrated into organizational occupational health and safety systems, with limited access to information, training, or supervision. This fragmentation of responsibilities undermines the consistent application of safety procedures and creates areas of ambiguity in accountability for accident prevention (Poschen, 2011).

The quality of information flow and operational planning constitutes another significant determinant of risk. Incomplete or delayed communication regarding changes in field conditions, work sequencing, or the presence of other teams can generate hazardous situations, including interactions between workers and machinery. The absence of clearly structured work plans, regularly adjusted to actual site conditions, increases uncertainty and exposure to uncontrolled risks (Garland, 2018).

In the current context, climate change has emerged as a factor that directly influences occupational safety in the forestry sector. The increasing frequency of extreme events—such as storms, strong winds, intense precipitation, or prolonged droughts—affects tree stability and the predictability of tree behavior during harvesting operations (Odenthal-Kahabka, 2005). Trees subjected to hydric stress, diseases, or pest infestations often exhibit unpredictable fracture patterns, complicating risk assessment and necessitating the continuous adaptation of operational procedures.

VULNERABLE GROUPS IN THE

FORESTRY SECTOR

In numerous countries, children and adolescents are involved in forestry activities, particularly in rural communities that depend on natural resources (Garland et al., 2020). This involvement is extremely hazardous, as they often lack the physical strength, attention, cognitive maturity, and experience required to identify and avoid hazards. Activities may include the collection of non-timber forest products, work in nurseries, tree planting, or plantation maintenance. In many cases, they may also be exposed to chemicals or physical tasks that exceed age-appropriate limits.

Child labor is closely linked to poverty and social inequalities and can have negative consequences on education, health, and physical and psychological development (FAO, 2015). Individuals under 18 years of age should not engage in hazardous tasks, and light work must be strictly regulated and supervised. The use of children in dangerous activities violates fundamental child rights and represents a significant occupational safety and health concern (ILO, 2017). Protecting children and youth in the forestry sector requires prohibiting hazardous work, regulating light activities, ensuring adequate supervision, complying with national legislation, and implementing social measures for families economically dependent on child labor.

Women constitute another particularly vulnerable group in the forestry sector, engaging in activities such as collecting non-timber forest products, working in nurseries, planting and maintaining plantations, or operating light machinery (Poschen, 2011). Personal protective equipment is often designed for male anatomy, reducing effectiveness and increasing ergonomic risks (Garland et al., 2020). Additionally, physically demanding tasks, heavy material handling, and exposure to chemicals can lead to musculoskeletal disorders, reproductive system impairments, and other health problems. Studies indicate that women generally have lower work capacity than men and face weight limits for lifting that are often exceeded, increasing the likelihood of accidents and health issues (Poschen, 2011).

Socially and organizationally, women face limited access to professional training, technical information, and decision-making participation, frequently being involved in the informal economy or underrepresented in professional

organizations and unions. The work environment may be hostile, including harassment or gender discrimination, which affects safety behaviors and increases accident risks. Additional family responsibilities contribute to work-family conflicts and stress.

To mitigate these vulnerabilities, it is essential to provide tailored professional and safety training, appropriate personal protective equipment, and active involvement of women in safety-related decision-making. Integrating gender perspectives into occupational health and safety policies aims to create a fair and safe working environment for all employees, rather than offering special treatment.

BUILDING A SAFETY CULTURE IN FORESTRY

Safety culture constitutes a fundamental element in preventing accidents and promoting occupational health within the forestry sector, a field characterized by high levels of risk and exposure to multiple hazards. It goes beyond mere compliance with formal regulations and reflects the way employees perceive risks, adhere to protective procedures, and assume responsibility for their own safety as well as that of their colleagues (Garland et al., 2020). Developing a robust safety culture is a gradual process that requires the ongoing commitment of all organizational levels and the facilitation of open dialogue between management and workers, enabling the identification and reporting of hazardous situations without constraints and with the aim of implementing effective solutions (Cooper, 2016).

Leadership plays a decisive role in reinforcing this culture. When managers and supervisors rigorously adhere to safety standards, actively participate in prevention programs, and consistently identify and mitigate risks, employee behavior naturally aligns with safety norms (Ek et al., 2014; Tobisch et al., 2005). In this context, continuous training and practical instruction are fundamental components. Employees must be consistently informed about the specific risks associated with forestry activities, receive detailed guidance on the use of personal protective equipment, and participate in practical exercises that develop emergency response skills. This training not only enhances individual competencies but also strengthens team cohesion and collective responsibility for maintaining a safe working environment (McLean & Rickards, 1998).

Decision-making regarding risk acceptance or mitigation in the forestry sector is influenced by a range of psychosocial and organizational factors, including professional experience, task familiarity, perception of potential consequences, and behaviors modeled by colleagues or supervisors. Productivity pressures, economic incentives, and confidence in equipment can increase vulnerability to accidents, which is why safety programs must integrate these dimensions, promoting a preventive approach and awareness of human factors.

Active employee involvement in all stages of implementing safety policies represents another essential element. Participation in hazard identification, priority setting, procedure development, and outcome monitoring fosters a genuine sense of responsibility and strengthens preventive behaviors. Even in small organizations, where responsibility may fall on the manager or owner, employees must be trained to recognize hazards and act knowledgeably, thereby contributing to the establishment of a sustainable and participatory organizational culture.

International experiences demonstrate that a mature safety culture is not an obstacle to productivity but is a crucial factor for sustainable sector development. Documented examples, such as those from Chile and South Africa, show that investments in employee professionalization, equipment modernization, continuous training, and the implementation of effective reporting and monitoring systems simultaneously reduce accidents and enhance organizational performance (Garland et al., 2020).

Under these conditions, safety culture in the forestry sector represents a complex system requiring responsible leadership, ongoing training, active employee involvement, careful assessment of risk tolerance, and the adaptation of procedures to real working conditions (Fennell, 2015). Only through an integrated and sustained approach can values regarding occupational safety and health be transformed into concrete practices, ensuring a protected, responsible, and accident-preventive working environment.

RISK MANAGEMENT AND PREVENTION

Risk management in the forestry sector involves the identification, assessment, and

mitigation of hazards before they materialize. A critical stage in this process is the on-site risk assessment, during which supervisors analyze the terrain, weather conditions, vegetation type, tree stability, and the availability of resources (Sarri, 2011). Based on this evaluation, clear operational strategies can be developed, restricted zones can be established, and strict procedures for movement, tree felling, and equipment handling can be implemented.

Personal protective equipment (PPE) constitutes a vital component of prevention. Helmets, face shields, hearing protection, cut-resistant trousers, gloves, and boots with slip-resistant soles significantly reduce the severity of accidents. However, PPE cannot replace technical and organizational measures—it functions as the last line of defense rather than as a primary solution.

Worker training represents another critical element. Training programs must integrate both theoretical components (legislation, procedures, organizational aspects) and practical elements, such as simulations, demonstrations, and applied exercises. These activities are designed to reinforce correct tree-felling techniques, proper machinery operation, effective communication in the field, and emergency response protocols.

A complementary component of risk management consists of the use of prospective assessments aimed at anticipating hazardous situations that may arise as working conditions change. The analysis of potential scenarios, including atypical or rare events, enables the identification of latent risks that are not always evident during routine operations. This approach enhances organizational preventive capacity and reduces vulnerability to unforeseen events.

At the same time, the effectiveness of preventive measures depends significantly on the integration of risk management into daily decision-making processes. When operational planning, resource allocation, and production targets are established without explicit consideration of acceptable risk levels, safety measures tend to become reactive. By embedding safety criteria into decision-making at all organizational levels, accident prevention becomes a continuous and proactive process adapted to field realities (Luria et al., 2008).

The use of modern technologies significantly contributes to accident prevention. Stability sensors, telemetry systems, protective cabins, and automatic shutdown devices are

tools that can substantially reduce operational risks. Their effectiveness, however, depends on proper personnel training and rigorous maintenance.

CONCLUSIONS

Occupational safety in the forestry sector represents a multidimensional challenge that requires systemic interventions, continuous training, and a mature organizational culture. Analyses based on FAO documents highlight the complexity of interactions between the natural environment, human factors, and technology (FAO, 2013; FAO, 2015). In the absence of an integrated approach, the specific risks associated with forestry activities inevitably manifest, keeping accident rates at a high level.

Through the implementation of a robust safety culture, technological modernization, appropriate training, and the development of effective risk management systems, the forestry sector can progress toward a sustainable and safe model. International evidence demonstrates that change is feasible, with benefits that are both human and economic. The future of forest operations depends on the ability of organizations to embed safety as a core value and to create a working environment in which the life of the worker is the highest priority.

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THE ROLE OF AGROFORESTRY IN CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION: A REVIEW OF CURRENT PRACTICES AND FUTURE OPPORTUNITIES

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Agroforestry, a land-use practice that combines trees with agricultural crops and/or livestock, has been recognized as a potential strategy for mitigating climate change. This review article synthesizes the current state of knowledge on the role of agroforestry in climate change mitigation, highlighting its benefits, challenges, and future opportunities. We discuss the various agroforestry practices, their carbon sequestration potential, and the factors influencing their adoption. Our review suggests that agroforestry can play a significant role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting sustainable agriculture, but its implementation requires careful consideration of local contexts, farmer needs, and policy support. This article explores the role of agroforestry in climate change mitigation, highlighting current practices and future opportunities. Agroforestry systems, which integrate trees into agricultural landscapes, provide multiple environmental benefits, including carbon sequestration, soil conservation, and enhanced biodiversity. The article also examines various agroforestry techniques—such as alley cropping, silvopasture, and forest farming—and their potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions while improving farm productivity and resilience to climate change. Despite these benefits, challenges like land tenure issues, knowledge gaps, and economic constraints hinder broader adoption. The article concludes by identifying key opportunities for scaling up agroforestry practices, including policy support, financial incentives, and further research on species selection and carbon accounting methodologies.

Keywords: Agroforestry, crops, livestock, climate change, mitigation carbon sequestration, greenhouse gas, sustainable agriculture

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INTRODUCTION

Agroforestry, the practice of integrating trees and shrubs into agricultural landscapes, has gained recognition as a crucial strategy for climate change mitigation and environmental sustainability. By combining crops, livestock, and forestry, agroforestry enhances biodiversity, improves soil health, and sequesters carbon, addressing key challenges posed by climate change

(<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/ecology-and-evolution/articles/10.3389/fevo.2021.630151/full>; <https://environmentalevidencejournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13750-022-00260-4>].

Its multifunctional approach not only contributes to carbon dioxide reduction and greenhouse gas emissions offset but also fosters resilience in agricultural systems, making it a

significant area of interest for policymakers, environmentalists, and farmers alike (<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/forests-and-global-change/articles/10.3389/ffgc.2025.1473355/full>; <http://www.climatehubs.usda.gov/hubs/northeast/topic/how-can-agroforestry-support-climate-change-mitigation-northeast>].

Current agroforestry practices encompass a variety of systems such as alley cropping, silvopasture, and forest farming, each offering unique benefits. For instance, alley cropping reduces soil erosion while promoting nutrient cycling, whereas silvopasture enhances animal welfare and carbon storage. Despite these advantages, the adoption of agroforestry faces barriers, including economic constraints, lack of knowledge, and insecure land tenure, which hinder its potential to be a widespread solution for climate issues. (<https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/cli2.70018>) [<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877343513001449>];

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/21683565.2025.2524733?src=>

Notably, agroforestry's role in enhancing biodiversity is increasingly important as ecosystems face the pressures of climate change. By creating diverse habitats that support various species, agroforestry contributes to ecosystem resilience, which is critical for food security and agricultural productivity.

(<https://www.pur.co/news-stories/4-key-benefits-agroforestry/>;<https://www.developmentaid.org/news-stream/post/198468/advantages-and-limitations-of-agroforestry>)

Moreover, the incorporation of native tree species is particularly beneficial for local ecosystems, enhancing pest resistance and adaptation to changing conditions

(<https://journaljeai.com/index.php/IEAI/article/view/2849>)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

DATA COLLECTION

Current Practices

Agroforestry has emerged as a vital strategy for addressing climate change and enhancing environmental sustainability through the integration of trees, crops, and livestock. Current practices in agroforestry encompass a range of methods that contribute to carbon sequestration, soil health, and biodiversity enhancement, thereby mitigating the impacts of climate change.

Types of Agroforestry Systems

Agroforestry systems can be classified into several categories based on their structure and purpose. Common practices include alley cropping, silvopasture, and forest farming. Alley cropping involves planting crops between rows of trees, which provides multiple benefits such as reduced soil erosion and improved nutrient cycling.

(<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/ecology-and-evolution/articles/10.3389/fevo.2021.630151/full>)

Silvopasture integrates trees into pasturelands, allowing for improved animal welfare and increased carbon storage in tree biomass and soil [

While the benefits of agroforestry are clear, addressing the challenges associated with its implementation is essential for maximizing its impact on climate change mitigation. Strategies such as innovative financing, enhanced education and training for farmers, and supportive policy frameworks can promote wider adoption of agroforestry practices. Ultimately, as the global community seeks sustainable solutions to climate challenges, agroforestry presents a promising pathway for integrating ecological and economic objectives. (<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/forests-and-global-change/articles/10.3389/ffgc.2025.1616451/full>);

(<https://www.fs.usda.gov/nac/topics/soil-health.php>)

(<https://environmentalevidencejournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13750-022-00260-4>).

Forest farming utilizes the forest understory to cultivate specialty crops, thus promoting biodiversity while enhancing farmers' income (<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/ecology-and-evolution/articles/10.3389/fevo.2021.630151/full>).

Benefits of Agroforestry Practices

The multifunctional nature of agroforestry systems provides numerous ecological benefits. By improving soil structure and fertility, these systems help maintain agricultural productivity even under climate stress

(<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/forests-and-global-change/articles/10.3389/ffgc.2025.1473355/full>).

Moreover, agroforestry enhances biodiversity by creating diverse habitats that support a variety of species (<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/forests-and-global-change/articles/10.3389/ffgc.2025.1473355/full>);

(<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/ecology-and->

[evolution/articles/10.3389/fevo.2021.630151/full](https://environmentalevidencejournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13750-022-00260-4)].

The incorporation of native tree species is particularly beneficial, as they offer structural complexity and resilience against pests and diseases while being well-adapted to local conditions

(<https://environmentalevidencejournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13750-022-00260-4>].

Agroforestry practices also contribute significantly to carbon sequestration. For example, studies have shown that hedgerows and shelterbelts can sequester substantial amounts of carbon in both biomass and soil, playing a crucial role in climate change mitigation efforts (

<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/forests-and-global-change/articles/10.3389/ffgc.2025.1473355/full>;

<https://environmentalevidencejournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13750-022-00260-4>].

Furthermore, the integration of trees into agricultural landscapes can lead to improved microclimatic conditions, reducing the risk of crop failure during extreme weather events

(<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/forests-and-global-change/articles/10.3389/ffgc.2025.1473355/full>].

Implementation Challenges

Despite the evident benefits, the adoption of agroforestry practices faces challenges. Farmers often require education and training to understand the best management practices for integrating trees into their existing systems effectively

(<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/ecology-and-evolution/articles/10.3389/fevo.2021.630151/full>].

Additionally, there may be initial financial barriers and longer-term investment considerations, as the benefits of agroforestry can take time to materialize (<https://environmentalevidencejournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13750-022-00260-4>].

Addressing these challenges is essential to promote wider adoption and maximize the

potential of agroforestry in mitigating climate change.

Benefits of Agroforestry in Climate Change Mitigation

Agroforestry, the integration of trees and shrubs into agricultural landscapes, offers a multitude of benefits that contribute significantly to climate change mitigation. These benefits stem from its ability to enhance biodiversity, improve soil health, and sequester carbon, among other ecological advantages.

Carbon Sequestration and Greenhouse Gas Emissions Reduction

Agroforestry contributes to climate change mitigation primarily through carbon sequestration in both biomass and soils. By integrating trees into agricultural systems, these practices significantly increase the amount of carbon dioxide absorbed from the atmosphere, thereby helping to offset greenhouse gas emissions.(

[<http://www.climatehubs.usda.gov/hubs/northeast/topic/how-can-agroforestry-support-climate-change-mitigation-northeast>]

Furthermore, agroforestry systems are designed to reduce emissions associated with agricultural practices, contributing to a decrease in overall greenhouse gases released into the environment

[<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877343513001449>].

Enhancing Biodiversity

One of the notable ecological benefits of agroforestry is its capacity to enhance biodiversity. The incorporation of various plant species—including trees, shrubs, and herbaceous plants—creates diverse habitats that support a wide range of wildlife, including pollinators and other beneficial organisms [<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/21683565.2025.2524733?src=;https://www.pur.co/news-stories/4-key-benefits-agroforestry/>].

This increase in biodiversity not only aids in ecosystem resilience but also contributes to the stability and productivity of agricultural systems, thereby supporting food security in the face of climate change [<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877343513001449>].

Soil Health Improvement

Agroforestry practices significantly enhance soil health, which is critical for sustainable agriculture and climate resilience. These systems improve soil fertility, structure, and moisture retention, leading to reduced soil erosion and enhanced water management [<https://www.developmentaid.org/news-stream/post/198468/advantages-and-limitations-of-agroforestry>] [<https://journaljeai.com/index.php/IEAI/article/view/2849>].

Healthier soils are more capable of supporting crops and storing carbon, thereby playing a crucial role in combating climate change impacts [<https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/cli2.70018>], [<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/forests-and-global-change/articles/10.3389/ffgc.2025.1616451/full>].

The integration of trees into agricultural systems also aids in nutrient cycling and promotes biological activity in the soil, which further contributes to soil health and productivity [<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/ecology-and-evolution/articles/10.3389/fevo.2021.630151/full>]; [<https://www.fs.usda.gov/nac/topics/soil-health.php>].

Resilience to Climate Change

Agroforestry systems increase the resilience of agricultural landscapes to climate variability. By improving soil quality and biodiversity, these systems can better withstand extreme weather events such as droughts and floods [<https://www.hilarispublisher.com/open-access/economic-and-ecological-benefits-of-agroforestry-systems.pdf>]; [<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0167880920300840>].

The presence of trees also helps in moderating microclimates, reducing temperature fluctuations, and improving water retention in soils, all of which are vital in adapting to changing climatic conditions [<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/21683565.2025.2524733?src=>

<https://www.frontierspartnerships.org/journal/s/spanish-journal-of-soil-science/articles/10.3389/sjss.2022.10457/full>]

Social and Economic Benefits

In addition to environmental advantages, agroforestry projects often provide significant social and economic benefits to local communities. Successful initiatives frequently focus on community engagement and empowerment, offering secure employment opportunities and fostering sustainable livelihoods through practices such as small-scale agroforestry [<https://www.green.earth/blog/reforestation-and-afforestation-projects-around-the-world-success-stories-and-lessons-learned/>].

This not only aids in the economic stability of local populations but also reinforces community ownership of environmental conservation efforts, enhancing the overall impact of agroforestry on climate change mitigation [<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877343513001449>] [<https://www.green.earth/blog/reforestation-and-afforestation-projects-around-the-world-success-stories-and-lessons-learned/>].

Challenges and Barriers

Agroforestry systems face numerous challenges and barriers that hinder their widespread adoption. These obstacles are multifaceted, encompassing economic, social, cultural, and institutional dimensions.

Economic Constraints

One of the most significant barriers to agroforestry adoption is the economic aspect, particularly the high initial investment required. Farmers often perceive the upfront costs associated with planting trees, modifying equipment, or altering farm layouts as daunting, especially when immediate financial returns are a priority [<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666719324001493>]; [<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>]

The long time frame for realizing economic benefits from agroforestry can clash with short-term financial needs, creating a risk-averse attitude among farmers who are accustomed to conventional agriculture's

quicker returns [<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>]

This time horizon mismatch contributes to the reluctance to shift to agroforestry practices, as the perceived risk of adopting a new system adds further hesitation [<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>] [<https://gender.cgiar.org/publications/scaling-agroforestry-potential-challenges-and-barriers>].

Knowledge Gaps

Lack of knowledge and technical expertise is another primary barrier to agroforestry uptake. Educational gaps in both research and practical skills can prevent effective implementation of agroforestry systems [20. What are the challenges to the adoption of agroforestry? How can ...

<https://www.agroforestry.ac.uk/events/what-are-challenges-adoption-agroforestry-how-can-they-be-overcome>];

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/21580103.2017.1392367>].

Farmers often require hands-on training and accessible demonstration sites to build the necessary confidence and skills for successful adoption (<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>] [<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/21580103.2017.1392367>].

Additionally, limited availability of localized information regarding agroforestry practices further complicates farmers' ability to make informed decisions [<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>] [<https://fao.sitfinity.cloud/newsroom/detail/New-policies-needed-to-promote-agroforestry/en>].

Land Tenure and Access Issues

Land tenure systems and property rights play a crucial role in agroforestry adoption. In many regions, unclear or insecure land tenure can discourage farmers from making long-term investments like planting trees [<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>]

<https://www.fao.org/climatechange/36653-0d7b3e802032f0279b368b3536cf5c3ee.pdf>].

This issue is particularly pronounced in developing countries, where customary land arrangements may conflict with formal legal frameworks, making farmers hesitant to invest in agroforestry without guaranteed access to the land

<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>]

[<https://foodforwardndcs.panda.org/food-production/implementing-agroforestry-practices/>].

Moreover, challenges related to land access can limit farmers' opportunities to engage in agroforestry practices.

Cultural and Social Perceptions

Cultural values and aesthetics can also impede the adoption of agroforestry systems. Preferences for open landscapes or traditional farming aesthetics may conflict with the integration of trees into agricultural practices, deterring some farmers from considering agroforestry as a viable alternative

[<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>].

Additionally, social perceptions and a lack of awareness about the benefits of agroforestry can contribute to resistance against its adoption

[<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>]

[<https://fao.sitfinity.cloud/newsroom/detail/New-policies-needed-to-promote-agroforestry/en>].

Policy and Institutional Frameworks

The existing policy and institutional frameworks often favor conventional agriculture, creating systemic obstacles for agroforestry adoption. Agricultural policies are typically designed to support monoculture practices, with subsidies and research funding primarily directed toward these approaches (<https://lifestyle.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-the-main-obstacles-to-agroforestry-adoption/>]

<https://fao.sitefinity.cloud/newsroom/detail/News-policies-needed-to-promote-agroforestry/en>].

As a result, agroforestry, with its diversified and integrated approach, may not fit neatly into

CONCLUSIONS

Agroforestry presents a myriad of future opportunities to enhance environmental resilience, improve food security, and foster economic sustainability in rural communities. The versatility and flexibility inherent in agroforestry designs allow stakeholders to address both current challenges and emerging global crises, such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and food insecurity

Innovative Financial Mechanisms

To drive the adoption of agroforestry, innovative financing mechanisms are crucial. These mechanisms can bridge the psychological gap between the upfront costs and the long-term benefits of agroforestry systems, often perceived as high-risk investments

By developing tailored financial instruments, such as carbon credits and other risk-sharing arrangements, agroforestry can attract private capital, ensuring long-term sustainability and viability of projects

Furthermore, the integration of technology, including remote sensing and fintech solutions, can facilitate access to finance for smallholder farmers, improving transparency and reducing transaction costs

Knowledge Dissemination and Capacity Building

Addressing the knowledge gaps related to agroforestry practices is essential for wider adoption. Successful case studies can serve as inspirational models that showcase the benefits of agroforestry, potentially attracting additional funding and reinforcing community commitment to sustainable land management practices

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Why Do Agroforestry Systems Enhance Biodiversity? Evidence From ...

these frameworks, limiting its potential for growth and development in agricultural policy

Moreover, educational programs aimed at both potential adopters and policymakers can enhance understanding of the environmental and economic advantages of agroforestry systems, promoting a shift in perception towards these sustainable practices

Policy Frameworks and Incentives

The establishment of supportive policy frameworks can significantly impact the future success of agroforestry initiatives. By linking project costs to government programs and existing support mechanisms, such as subsidies and dedicated credit lines, stakeholders can reduce the financial barriers to adopting agroforestry

Additionally, community-based incentive programs can provide immediate rewards for adoption, thus fostering a more favorable environment for change

Monitoring and Evaluation

To ensure the effectiveness and sustainability of agroforestry projects, robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks are essential. Joint monitoring initiatives involving local civil society and stakeholders will empower communities and enhance transparency in tracking progress

Regular assessments of agroforestry landscapes can facilitate adaptive management, ensuring that practices remain relevant and effective in addressing ongoing environmental challenges

<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/ecology-and-evolution/articles/10.3389/fevo.2021.630151/full>

- Evidence for the impacts of agroforestry on ecosystem services and ...
<https://environmentalevidencejournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13750-022-00260-4>
- Adaptive agroforestry—mitigating climate change impacts ... - Frontiers
<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/forests-and-global-change/articles/10.3389/ffgc.2025.1473355/full>
- How can agroforestry support climate change mitigation in the ...
<http://www.climatehubs.usda.gov/hubs/northeast/topic/how-can-agroforestry-support-climate-change-mitigation-northeast>
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<https://rmets.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/cli2.70018>
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THE ROLE OF GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEMS (GIS) IN MODERN MINING

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have become indispensable in the mining sector, facilitating exploration, mine planning, operations, environmental management, and post-closure monitoring. This paper reviews the state-of-the-art applications of GIS across the mining lifecycle, analyzes their benefits and limitations, and outlines future directions. By synthesizing findings from recent literature, we demonstrate how GIS improves the accuracy, efficiency, and safety of mining operations, while supporting sustainable development and regulatory compliance.

Keywords: *Geographical Informatic Systems, Spatial Information, Maps*

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INTRODUCTION

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have become essential tools in the mining industry, transforming how companies explore, plan, operate, and rehabilitate mining sites. By integrating spatial data with analytical capabilities, GIS enhances decision-making throughout the entire mining lifecycle—from early exploration to post-closure monitoring. (Choi et.al, 2020)

Mining is inherently spatial: minerals are found in specific locations, geological processes vary over space, and environmental impacts must be monitored across landscapes. Traditionally, geologists relied on paper maps, manual calculations, and field notes. Today, GIS allows the integration of diverse datasets—geological, geophysical, geochemical, environmental, and socioeconomic—into a unified digital platform, enabling more accurate and efficient mining operations (Choi, Y., et al., 2020).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Mining is fundamentally a spatial enterprise: ore bodies, geological structures, and environmental constraints are geographically distributed, and spatial relationships govern

both opportunities and risks. Historically, geological mapping, resource estimation, and environmental monitoring relied on manual maps, field notes, and separate non-integrated datasets. The advent of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) allows for integration of varied spatial and attribute data — geological, geochemical, geophysical, topographic, environmental, infrastructure — into unified, interactive, and analyzable platforms. This transformation supports better decision-making throughout the mining lifecycle, from exploration to closure and remediation. (Szafarczyk, Siwek, 2025)

This paper reviews contemporary research on GIS applications in mining, examining how GIS has been applied, what benefits it delivers, and what challenges remain.

Applications of GIS in the Mining Lifecycle

1 Mineral Exploration

GIS supports exploration by helping geologists analyze complex datasets to identify areas with high mineral potential. Key uses include (Szafarczyk, Siwek, 2025):

- **Geological mapping:** Integrating rock types, structures, faults, and mineral occurrences.

- **Remote sensing analysis:** Using satellite data (e.g., Landsat, Sentinel) to detect alteration zones.
- **Spatial modeling:** Weight-of-evidence and machine-learning models for mineral prospectivity mapping.

Figure. 1. GIS of a mine

These tools reduce exploration risk and direct fieldwork to the most promising sites.

One of the earliest and still most significant uses of GIS in mining is in mineral exploration. By integrating geological, geochemical, geophysical, and remote-sensing data layers, GIS enables the generation of prospectivity maps that highlight areas with high potential for mineralization. For instance, the study Geological mapping and mineral prospectivity using remote sensing and GIS in parts of Hamissana, Northeast Sudan used GIS together with remote sensing data to map geological features and identify prospective gold zones over a region of $\sim 1,379 \text{ km}^2$. [SpringerLink](#) Also, by combining structural geology (faults, lithologies), alteration zones, and topography, GIS helps define promising drill targets, reducing risk and focusing exploration resources. As noted in the broader review, GIS simplifies the traditional labor-intensive task of manually overlaying and interpreting multiple data sets — thereby speeding up early-stage exploration and improving the accuracy of target selection.

2. Resource Assessment and Reserve Estimation

GIS helps connect geological models with spatial datasets such as: (Xu et al., 2017).

- Drillhole sampling data
- Ore grade distribution
- 3D block models

By visualizing and interpolating data, GIS enables more accurate estimation of ore quantity and quality, improving economic feasibility assessments.

Beyond simply mapping where minerals *might be*, GIS is used to more precisely estimate resources and even to automate resource accounting. The recent preprint The Use of GIS Tools in Mining: Process Automation of Calculating the Volume of Mineral Extracted from a Deposit demonstrates how GIS can be used to automate volume calculations for open-pit mines — from field measurement data through calculation, visualization and interpretation — improving accuracy, reducing human error, and speeding up the process. Such GIS-based resource accounting supports compliance with legal/regulatory requirements (e.g., reporting extracted volumes), better mine planning, and transparent resource management. (Xu et al., 2017)

Figure. 2. Quarries

3. Mine Planning and Design

Modern mine planning relies heavily on GIS for (Xu et al., 2017):

- **Optimized pit design** considering terrain, geology, and environmental constraints.
- **Infrastructure planning** (roads, processing facilities, waste dumps).
- **Slope stability and geohazard assessment** using terrain analysis and digital elevation models (DEMs).

GIS tools make it easier to simulate operational scenarios and reduce engineering risks.

GIS also plays a key role in mine design, infrastructure planning, and operational optimization. According to the review in Applied Sciences, GIS-based methods have been applied for: ore reserve estimation; optimizing open-pit boundaries; designing mine infrastructure (roads, processing plants, waste dumps); and evaluating potential conflict or constraint zones (e.g., environmental or social issues) (Vangu et al., 2023).

In underground coal mines — where safety is paramount — advanced 3D and spatio-temporal GIS models are being developed to assess accident risk, plan ventilation networks, drainage systems, and emergency rescue routes. For example, the recent paper *A Review on the 3D Cartographic and Spatiotemporal GIS Models for Safety of Accidents in Deep Underground Coal Mines* outlines how spatial-temporal GIS analyses (e.g., hotspot, space–time cube, kernel density) are used to model accident occurrences and dynamics over time and space. Furthermore, GIS enables integration of terrain data (Digital Elevation Models — DEMs), geological structure, and surface constraints to design safer and more efficient mining infrastructure.

Figure.3. Mining plan design

4. Environmental Management and Hazard Assessment

Mining has significant environmental impacts, and GIS provides robust ways to monitor and mitigate them (G. M. Vangu et al., 2023):

- **Land use/land cover change detection** using satellite imagery.
- **Water quality monitoring** through watershed mapping and hydrological modeling.
- **Air quality and dust dispersion models.**
- **Habitat and biodiversity assessment** for compliance with environmental regulations.

GIS enables environmental teams to track impacts in near real time.

Mining has significant environmental and social impacts — land degradation, water/soil contamination, deforestation, subsidence, air and dust pollution. GIS, often in combination with remote sensing, is widely used to model, monitor and mitigate these impacts.

An Overview of GIS-Based Modeling and Assessment of Mining-Induced Hazards: Soil, Water, and Forest

(<https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/14/12/1463>) shows how GIS helps assess hazards like soil contamination, water pollution,

deforestation, erosion, and land-use change, enabling spatially explicit risk analyses. Moreover, at a broader scale, spatial analyses using GIS and remote sensing supports cumulative and strategic impact assessments — useful for regulators, communities, and companies to understand not just site-level but regional or global effects of mining. The work *Assessing impacts of mining: Recent contributions from GIS and remote sensing* reviews how GIS helps map land-use change, water and soil impacts, social and economic effects, and supports conflict resolution and disaster mitigation.

Finally, integrated GIS databases help track mining concessions, permit boundaries, infrastructure, and environmental constraints — supporting sustainable resource management and regulatory compliance. For instance, the recent article *Design of a GIS Database for Surface Mining* describes design and implementation of a GIS database for surface mining, aiming to manage permits, exploitation perimeters, and to support concession promotion. Paradigm.

Figure. 4. Land cover changes

5. Health, Safety, and Risk Management

GIS enhances mine safety by:

- Mapping accident hotspots
- Identifying unstable terrain
- Visualizing underground workings to prevent collapses
- Supporting emergency planning and evacuation routes

Spatial analysis helps companies reduce risks to workers and communities.

6. Operational Monitoring and Asset Management

Mining operations involve fleets, machinery, and infrastructure spread over large areas. GIS supports (G. M. Vangu et al., 2023):

- **Real-time equipment tracking**
- **Monitoring haul roads conditions**
- **Managing utilities and pipelines**

- **Visualizing production data spatially**
Integration with IoT and GPS improves productivity and reduces downtime.

Figure 5. GIS of an underground mine

7. Mine Closure and Rehabilitation

GIS plays a crucial role in post-mining activities (Werner et al 2019):

- Designing **rehabilitation plans** based on topography and soil conditions
- Monitoring **vegetation recovery** using remote sensing
- Assessing long-term environmental stability

These tools ensure compliance with closure regulations and promote sustainable land use after mining.

The review builds upon existing systematic reviews (e.g., Review of GIS-Based Applications for Mining: Planning, Operation, and Environmental Management) and recent research articles. We surveyed peer-reviewed papers published in the last decade (2015–2025), focusing on studies that apply GIS to mineral exploration, mine planning, operational management, environmental impact assessment, hazard modeling, and resource accounting. Key databases (Google Scholar, PubMed, MDPI, Sciendo) were searched with keywords like “GIS mining,” “mine planning,” “remote sensing mining,” “mineral prospectivity,” “mine environmental GIS,” and “mine safety GIS.”

Figure 6. Mine closure and rehabilitation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Key GIS Technologies Used in Mining

- **Remote sensing platforms:** Landsat, Sentinel, drones (UAVs)
- **Digital Elevation Models (DEMs):** LiDAR, SRTM
- **3D GIS and modeling software:** ArcGIS, QGIS, Leapfrog, Surpac
- **Machine learning integration** for mineral prospectivity mapping
- **Web-GIS platforms** for real-time data sharing across teams

Figure 7. Images of mining activities

Benefits of GIS in Mining (Werner, T. et al 2019)

- Improved accuracy of exploration and planning
- Reduced operational costs
- Better environmental compliance
- Enhanced safety and risk management
- Stronger communication among stakeholders
- Faster, data-driven decision-making

Challenges and Future Trends

Challenges (Werner et al 2019)

- High cost of data acquisition
- Need for skilled GIS professionals
- Data integration across different formats and platforms.

Future Trends

- **AI-driven exploration modeling**
- **Integration with drones and autonomous vehicles**
- **Cloud-based geospatial platforms**

Real-time 4D GIS (space and time) for dynamic mine monitoring

Benefits of GIS in Mining

From the literature surveyed, the key benefits of this type of GIS include (Werner et al 2019):

- **Integrated spatial data management:** GIS allows storage and manipulation of georeferenced and attribute-rich data (drillholes, ore bodies, terrain, hydrology, infrastructure) in unified databases.
 - **Improved exploration efficiency and accuracy:** By layering geology, remote sensing, geochemistry, and geophysics — GIS facilitates target zone identification, maximizing the likelihood of successful drilling and minimizing wasted effort.
 - **Better mine planning and operational optimization:** Through spatial modeling and 3D/temporal GIS, companies can design pits, infrastructure, ventilation, and safety systems more optimally, reducing cost and risk.
 - **Accurate resource estimation and compliance:** Automation of volume calculations reduces human error, speeds up reporting, and ensures consistent resource accounting — important for regulation and transparency.
 - **Environmental and hazard risk management:** GIS supports environmental monitoring, hazard modeling, land-use change detection, contamination assessment, and long-term rehabilitation planning.
 - **Facilitating sustainable development and regulatory compliance:** By integrating concession data, infrastructure, environmental constraints, and social data, GIS can help companies and regulators manage mining more responsibly.
- environmental, and infrastructural datasets often come in different formats, scales, and accuracies. Integrating them into a coherent GIS database requires substantial effort.
- **Need for skilled personnel:** Effective GIS application demands expertise in geology, mining engineering, GIS, remote sensing, and data management — a multidisciplinary skill set that may not always be available.
 - **Computational and resource constraints:** High-resolution spatial data (e.g., DEMs, remote sensing imagery, 3D models) and temporal analyses (for hazards or environmental monitoring) can be computationally intensive, especially for large mining areas or deep underground mines.
 - **Uncertainties in modeling:** Spatial models — whether for mineral prospectivity, hazard prediction, or resource estimation — inherently involve assumptions and uncertainties. Over-reliance on model outputs without validation (e.g., through drilling, on-site sampling) can lead to misleading conclusions. The authors of the comprehensive review note that despite widespread use, robust evaluations of many GIS-based methods remain limited.
 - **Regulatory and data-sharing limitations:** In many regions, geological data, mining permits, and environmental data are sensitive or proprietary, which limits data sharing, transparency, and broader-scale spatial analyses.

Challenges and Limitations

Despite its many advantages, the application of GIS in mining also faces several challenges:

- **Data quality, availability, and integration issues:** Geological, geochemical, geophysical,

Future Directions and Emerging Trends

The field of GIS in mining is dynamic and evolving. Several promising directions emerge from recent literature (Szafarczyk, et al, 2025):

- **3D and spatio-temporal GIS modeling:** As demonstrated in the recent review on underground coal mines, using GIS in 3D + temporal

framework helps assess accident risk, monitor environmental changes, and improve safety management. [SpringerLink+1](#).

- **Automation of resource and production accounting:** The recent preprint on automating volume calculations shows potential for greater efficiency, consistency, and regulatory compliance in resource management. [preprints.org+1](#)
- **Integration with remote sensing, UAVs, sensor networks and IoT:** Combining GIS with remote sensing (satellite imagery, UAV/drone data), real-time sensors (environmental, structural, operational), and IoT could enable near real-time mine monitoring, environmental surveillance, and dynamic risk management. The review on GIS-based applications anticipates such integration as part of future digital transformation.
- **Standardized GIS databases for mining sectors:** As seen in the study on designing a surface mining GIS database, there is growing interest in developing national or regional GIS-based systems for managing mining concessions, permits, environmental data, and mine perimeters — especially in jurisdictions seeking efficient resource governance.

Broader environmental and social impact assessment: Using GIS and remote sensing to model cumulative impacts, land-use changes, water/soil contamination, and social effects — not only at mine-site scale but regionally — to support sustainable mining policies and community engagement. (Szafarczyk, Siwek, 2025)

CONCLUSIONS

GIS has emerged as a foundational technology in modern mining. Through data integration, spatial modeling, visualization, and analysis, GIS supports mineral exploration, resource estimation, mine planning, operational management, environmental monitoring, hazard assessment, and regulatory compliance. The benefits — improved efficiency, accuracy,

safety, and sustainability — are well documented. (Kunytyska, 2024)

Nevertheless, challenges remain: data quality and integration need for multidisciplinary expertise, computational demands, and uncertainties in modeling. Looking ahead, the integration of GIS with remote sensing, sensor networks, 3D/temporal modeling, and standardized databases appears promising. With continued research and technological development, GIS is likely to become even more central to mining — not only for optimizing resource extraction, but also for ensuring environmental responsibility, safety, and sustainable development. (Maryna Kunytyska, 2024)

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MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF OVALIZATION, STRESSES AND DEFORMATIONS IN BURIED PIPELINES USING MEMBRANE THEORY

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Abstract

The analysis performed is for the case of a pipeline network having different dimensional values in terms of ring diameter and length. For the study, the action of the earth's weight was considered, as well as the external action of traffic loads. For the case study considered, analyzed and treated in this paper, groundwater was not taken into account up to the level corresponding to the upper generator. The physical-mechanical and static parameters of the required pipelines were determined, using the method within the membrane theory.

Keywords: membrane, theory, displacements, stress, tensile,

INTRODUCTION

The problem of approximate determination of stresses, displacements and deformations is a challenge for every mechanical engineer. The problem is related to the external loads that the pipelines are subjected to during their operation. It is very important that they can correspond technologically and in terms of operating time. In the vast majority of cases, the mechanical calculation of pipelines is carried out based on the following types of external loads (Soare, 1999):

- soil weight;
- pipeline weight;
- groundwater action;
- road traffic load.

In the case of this work, the following types of loads were taken into account:

- soil load;
- road traffic load.

For the present case studied, 5 pipe sections with the same ring diameter and different lengths were considered. The calculation performed by the author is based on the membrane theory method.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

When analyzing and determining the intensity of the loads, the following initial data of the problem were taken into account (Bors I, 2005):

p_v^{LT} – vertical earth pressure;

$\gamma_P \left[\frac{KN}{m^3} \right]$ – specific (technical) weight of the earth;

;

$h[m]$ the angle of internal friction of the material is the filling;

$D_E[m]$ – the outer diameter of the pipeline.

The soil in which the polypropylene pipe was placed was considered to be part of group G4, which is part of the category of granular soil mixtures with a large fraction and moderate cohesion such as: very loamy mixtures of sand-coarse gravel, very clayey mixtures of coarse gravel-sand, very loamy or clayey sands, fine loamy or clayey sand, low plasticity mud.

The mechanical analysis performed is based on writing the equilibrium equations for an infinitesimal pipe element acted on in the X, Y and Z directions by the weight of the ground (Ille, Bia, Soare 1983).

The pressure created by road traffic depends on the nature of the terrain and the traffic under which the pipeline is located. The calculation relationships used to calculate the traffic pressure are the following (Ille V 1977):

$$P_{tsLT} = a_T D_T p_T \left[\frac{N}{mm^2} \right]$$

$$a_T = 1 - \frac{0.9}{0.9 + Z}$$

$$Z = \frac{4\varnothing^2 + \varnothing^6}{1.1 D_m^{0.67}}$$

$$D_m = \frac{D_E + D_I}{2}$$

$$p_T = 0.0826 \left[\frac{N}{mm^2} \right]$$

Figure 1. Infinitesimal pipe element

Figure 2. Ring tensions

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

By applying the membrane theory, the ovalizations and the stress state were determined for each of the sections considered (Ghinea, Fireteanu. 2004). (Soare, 1999), (Ille V 1977), (Ille, Bia, Soare 1983).

The numerical method applied by the program is the finite element method, which is based on the theory of elasticity and plasticity (Martian, 1999). The physical-mechanical characteristics of the pipeline sections discussed in the paper are presented.

A Matlab calculation program of the form presented below was created for each of the sections considered separately.

Section 1

% Section D=140[mm], ring thickness 3.5 [mm],
 Length 9.8[mm]
 GAMAP = 17.65 % [KN/m3] specific weight of the soil
 r = 0.07 % radius [m] average radius of the pipe
 Hp = 1.1 % [m] depth to the upper generator of the pipe
 h = 0.0035 % [m] pipe ring thickness
 L= 9.8 % [m] pipe length
 x = [-L/2 -L/4 0 L/4 L/2]
 theta = [0 pi/2 pi 3*pi/2 2*pi] % angle on the pipe quadrant ring
 sgmadm = 150 % [N/mm^2]
 E=1400 % modulus of elasticity = stiffness (5000 [N/mm2]/I)
 miu=0.28 % Poisson's ratio
 I=3.5^3/12 % Axial moment of inertia.

Section 2

Section 2. D=168[mm], ring thickness 3.5 [mm],
 Length 2.811[m]
 GAMAP = 17 % [KN/m3] specific weight of the soil
 r = 0.084 % radius [m] average radius of the pipe
 Hp = 1.4 % [m] depth to the upper generator of the pipe
 h = 0.0035 % [m] pipe ring thickness
 L1=2811.2 % Total length of the section [m]
 L= L1/300 % [m] pipe length between 2 supports
 x = [-L/2 -L/4 0 L/4 L/2]
 theta = [0 pi/2 pi 3*pi/2 2*pi] % angle on the pipe quadrant ring
 sgmadm = 150 % [N/mm^2]
 E=1400 % modulus of elasticity
 miu=0.28 % Poisson's ratio
 I=3.5^3/12 % Axial moment of inertia.

Section 3

% Section 2 D=168[mm], ring thickness 3.5 [mm], Length 9.53[m]
 GAMAP = 17 % [KN/m3] specific weight of the soil
 r = 0.084 % radius [m] average radius of the pipe
 Hp = 1.4 % [m] depth to the upper generator of the pipe
 h = 0.0035 % [m] pipe ring thickness
 L1=953.8 % Total length of section 2
 L=L1/100 % [m] length of section 2 of the pipe taken for analysis between two of its supports
 x = [-L/2 -L/4 0 L/4 L/2]
 theta = [0 pi/2 pi 3*pi/2 2*pi] % angle on the pipe quadrant ring
 sgmadm = 150 % [N/mm^2]

$E=1400$ % modulus of elasticity
 $\mu=0.28$ % Poisson's ratio
 $I=3.5^{3/12}$ % Axial moment of inertia.

Section 4

% Section 4 $D=168$ [mm], ring thickness 3.5 [mm], Length 70.28[m]

GAMAP = 17 % [KN/m³] specific weight of the soil

$r = 0.084$ % radius [m] average radius of the pipe

$H_p = 1.4$ % [m] depth to the upper generator of the pipe

$h = 0.0035$ % [m] pipe ring thickness

$L_1=70.28$ % Total length of the section [m]

$L= L_1/10$ % [m] pipe length between 2 supports

$x = [-L/2 -L/4 \ 0 \ L/4 \ L/2]$

$\theta = [0 \ \pi/2 \ \pi \ 3\pi/2 \ 2\pi]$ % angle on the pipe quadrant ring

$\sigma_{adm} = 150$ % [N/mm²]

$E=1400$ % modulus of elasticity

$\mu=0.28$ % Poisson's ratio

$I=3.5^{3/12}$ % Axial moment of inertia

Section 5

% Section 5 $D=168$ [mm], ring thickness 3.5 [mm], Length 2.811[m]

GAMAP = 17 % [KN/m³] specific weight of the soil

$r = 0.084$ % radius [m] average radius of the pipe

$H_p = 1.4$ % [m] depth to the upper generator of the pipe

$h = 0.0035$ % [m] pipe ring thickness

$L_1=301.2$ % Total length of the section [m]

$L= L_1/30$ % [m] pipe length between 2 supports

$x = [-L/2 -L/4 \ 0 \ L/4 \ L/2]$

$\theta = [0 \ \pi/2 \ \pi \ 3\pi/2 \ 2\pi]$ % angle on the pipe quadrant ring

$\sigma_{adm} = 150$ % [N/mm²]

$E=1400$ % modulus of elasticity

$\mu=0.28$ % Poisson's ratio

$I=3.5^{3/12}$ % Axial moment of inertia.

Ovalizations of pipe sections number 1 to 5.

Table 1

Ovalizations of pipe sections number 1 to 5.

The angle o the ring	0	$\pi/2$	π	$3\pi/2$	2π
SECTION 1	0.2287	0.2417	5.7397	0.2417	0.2287
SECTION 2	0.2047	0.2162	5.3328	0.2162	0.2047
SECTION 3	0.2047	0.2162	2.7912	0.2162	0.2047
SECTION 4	0.2047	0.2162	5.9335	0.2162	0.2047
SECTION 5	0.2047	0.2162	6.7824	0.2162	0.2047

Table 2

Vault Stresses, normal tension and tang. Tension.

Pipe Sections	Vault stresses	Tension tang.	Tension normal SIGMA X
Section1	0.6399	1.0077	53.67
Section1	0.6399	1.0077	53.67
Section1	0.6388	0.7555	30.19
Section1	0.6388	1.0723	61.61
Section1	0.6388	1.1511	70.10

Table 3

Displacements from ground loading

Displacement from ground loading	0	$\pi/2$	π	$3\pi/2$	2π
Section 1	0.0344	0.0363	0.8634	0.0363	0.0344
Section 2	0.0344	0.0363	0.8959	0.0363	0.0344
Section 3	0.0344	0.0363	0.4689	0.0363	0.0344
Section 4	0.0344	0.0363	0.9968	0.0363	0.0344
Section 5	0.0344	0.0363	1.1394	0.0363	0.0344

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the calculation programs designed by the author, the following conclusions can be drawn for the first table:

1. It is noted that for the angle $\theta = \pi$, on the circumference of the ring, the maximum value of ovalization expressed in percentage was obtained for section 5, when the maximum admissible value is exceeded by 0.78%.

2. The ovalization values for angles $0, \pi, 3\pi/2$ and 2π , remain the same for the different lengths of sections considered.

3. The minimum value of ovalization will be recorded for the case of section 3 when a pipe length between the 2 supports of approximately 7 [m] was considered.

4. There are two possibilities for decreasing the ovality, one technological by interposing several supports and therefore implicitly decreasing the length of the analyzed pipeline within each section and the second case by modifying the physical-mechanical parameters of the material, which also leads to modifying the dimensions related to the thickness of the ring.

For the second table:

1. The maximum value of the stress is recorded along the longitudinal axis of the pipe.

2. The maximum value is obtained for the case of section 5

3. The minimum value of the longitudinal stress is obtained for section 3 where the ovalization is also minimal.

4. The arch stress is the same for all sections considered.

5. The tangential stresses have negligible values compared to the longitudinal normal stresses.

6. The maximum values of the longitudinal normal stresses are below the maximum allowable stress of $120\{N/mm^2\}$.

For the third table, the conclusions are:

1. The values of the displacements of the points on the circumference of the pipes for angles $0, \pi/2, 3\pi/2$ and 2π are the same for all sections.

2. The maximum values are recorded for the angle $\theta = \pi$, and section number 5.

3. The minimum value is recorded for section 3.

Following the data obtained through the created calculation programs, it is found that through an appropriate choice of all physical-mechanical, elasticity and material parameters, the values obtained and entered in tables 1-3 are within the limits established by static or mechanical calculations for determining admissible values.

The mechanical analysis carried out by the author represents, through the numerical values obtained regarding the ovalization state, the stress state and the displacement state, it constitutes a validation of the membrane theory applied by the author.

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THE LEVEL OF AIR POLLUTION WITH SULPHUR DIOXIDE IN THE CITY OF ORADEA IN 2020-2022

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The objective of this paper is to analyse the level of atmospheric pollution with sulphur dioxide (SO₂) in the city of Oradea over a period of three years (2020 - 2022). The paper was compiled using data measured by the Environmental Protection Agency, the body that monitors air quality in Romania. The stations for sampling atmospheric pollutants, including sulphur dioxide, are located in strategic locations, namely: BH₁ at the headquarters of APM Bihor, which is an urban station, BH₂ in Episcopia Bihor, which is a neighbourhood in Oradea and is an industrial station, and BH₃ located in the Nufărul neighbourhood, which is a traffic station. In Oradea, the main source of nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) pollution is domestic, because during the cold season many homes still do not use methane gas, and to a lesser extent, emissions from diesel engines.

Keywords: sulphur dioxide, monitoring, sampling points.

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INTRODUCTION

Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) is a significant pollutant, a colourless gas with a pungent odour that plays an important role in the formation of acid rain. It is used in many industries, including the food industry in the food preservation process.

Natural sources of sulphur dioxide pollution include volcanic eruptions, the decomposition of organic matter and the combustion of vegetation containing sulphur compounds.

Anthropogenic sources are those resulting from the burning of fossil fuels such as coal-fired power plants, oil refineries, and industrial furnaces.

It also plays an important role in the formation of acid rain, which occurs when large amounts of sulphur dioxide are emitted into the atmosphere and react with oxygen in the atmosphere to form sulphur trioxide SO₃. Sulphur trioxide reacts with water in clouds to form sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄). Acid rain can have negative effects on soil health, aquatic ecosystems, and the corrosion of limestone, marble, and concrete structures.

Among the immediate and visible effects of sulphur dioxide on the human body are respiratory problems. If inhaled, it can irritate

the nose, throat and respiratory tract. It can trigger asthma attacks in sensitive individuals.

Sulphur dioxide also has a negative effect on plants by damaging their structure and tissues. Plants that are highly sensitive to SO₂ include pine trees, vegetables, ash trees, alfalfa, etc.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The data used in this paper was provided by the Bihor Oradea Environmental Protection Agency. There are three atmospheric air sampling stations in Oradea, where sulphur dioxide and other pollutants are monitored. The BH₁ sampling station is located on the premises of the APM headquarters and is an urban station, BH₂ is located in the Episcopia Bihor neighbourhood and is an industrial station, and BH₃ is located in Nufărul and is a traffic station (www.apmbh.ro).

The period analysed in this paper was three years, from 2020 to 2022, and the data was processed using statistical and mathematical methods. The results obtained were then plotted graphically to clearly highlight the variability of atmospheric pollutants over time.

The reference method for measuring sulphur dioxide is that provided for in standard SR EN 14212 'Ambient air. Standardised

method for the measurement of sulphur dioxide concentration by ultraviolet fluorescence'.

According to Law No. 104 of 15 June 2011 Sulphur oxides (SO₂) - the alert threshold is 500 µg/m³ (measured over 3 consecutive hours at points representative of air quality for an area of at least 100 km²);

Limit values 350 µg/m³ SO₂ – hourly limit value for the protection of human health and 125 µg/m³ daily limit value for the protection of human health (<https://www.calitateair.ro>).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Annual evolution of sulphur dioxide concentration

Following the analysis of sulphur dioxide (SO₂) concentrations throughout 2020, we can conclude that the highest concentration was recorded at the BH₃ monitoring point in Nufărul,

Figure 1 Evolution of annual average SO₂ concentrations (µg/m³) at monitoring points in Oradea, between 2020 and 2022

Monthly evolution of sulphur dioxide concentrations

From the monthly evolution of SO₂ concentrations throughout 2020, it appears that the highest value was recorded in September at

Figure 2 Evolution of monthly average SO₂ concentrations (µg/m³) at monitoring points in Oradea in 2020

The sulphur dioxide concentration values for 2021 were measured in November 26.15 µg/m³ at the sampling station in

at 10.37 µg/m³. At the BH₂ sampling station in Episcopia Bihor, 9.70 µg/m³ was recorded, and the lowest SO₂ concentration was recorded at BH₁ (8.58 µg/m³).

During 2021, the average annual concentration was similar to that in 2020, with the highest concentration recorded in Episcopia Bihor, at the BH₂ sampling point. This was followed by the sampling station in Nufărul BH₃ (10.53 µg/m³), and at the APM BH₁ headquarters it was 8.48 µg/m³.

The SO₂ concentrations determined in 2022 are consistent with those in 2020 – 2021, with the highest concentrations measured at the BH₂ sampling point located in Episcopia Bihor 13.20 µg/m³ and 10.06 µg/m³ at the APM headquarters.

A lower concentration of sulphur dioxide was determined at the sampling point in Nufărul BH₃ 7.66 µg/m³ (Fig.1).

26.87 µg/m³, (at the BH₃ station in Nufărul) and in October 18.07 µg/m³ also measured at the BH₃ station in Nufărul. A higher concentration was also measured in January, 13.55 µg/m³ at station BH₁ at the APM headquarters (Fig. 2).

Episcopia Bihor BH₂, March 19.78 µg/m³ at the sampling point BH₃ and July 16.16 µg/m³ at the sampling point BH₃ (Fig. 3).

Figure. 3 Evolution of monthly average SO₂ concentrations (µg/m³) at monitoring points in Oradea in 2021

During 2022, due to technical malfunctions, SO₂ concentration monitoring was carried out until June. The highest values

were reached in February and January, 14.72 µg/m³ and 12.47 µg/m³ respectively, at the BH₂ Episcopia Bihor station (Fig. 4).

Figure. 4 Evolution of monthly average SO₂ concentrations (µg/m³) at monitoring points in Oradea in 2022

Monthly evolution of sulphur dioxide in correlation with air temperature.

Thermal inversion, atmospheric calm and lack of precipitation are meteorological phenomena that can lead to the stagnation of sulphur dioxide in the area of emission sources.

The evolution of SO₂ concentration (Fig. 5) shows that at lower temperatures, the concentration of nitrogen dioxide is higher.

When temperatures are higher, the concentration of the gas is lower.

From the monthly evolution of sulphur dioxide, we can see that higher concentrations were recorded in September 12.57 µg/m³, February 12.21 µg/m³, and October 11.30 µg/m³.

The lowest values were recorded in May (7.72 µg/m³), April (7.95 µg/m³) and August (8.39 µg/m³).

Figure 5 Variation in monthly average (SO₂) concentration (µg/m³) and air temperature (°C) in Oradea

CONCLUSIONS

During the years studied (2020–2022), the maximum permissible concentrations were not exceeded.

Higher levels of SO₂ concentration were determined at the BH₂ Episcopia Bihor station, which is located in an industrial area.

Higher SO₂ values were recorded at the BH₃ station in Nufărul because it is located near a busy road.

Pollution can also occur in areas with industrial waste dumps, livestock farms, unregulated and uncontrolled rubbish dumps, and chemical industry.

It can be observed that the highest SO₂ concentration values were recorded during the cold period of the year when the air temperature was lower, highlighting the purifying role of air temperature through convective movements during the warm periods of the year.

Another important factor is that the prevailing wind direction is from the south, which favors the dispersion of pollutants.

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BIOCHAR: DEFINITION, PROPERTIES, PRODUCTION METHODS, AND ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATIONS IN ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Biochar is a stable, carbon-rich material produced through the thermochemical conversion of biomass in oxygen-limited conditions. Its scientific relevance has grown due to its dual capacity to enhance soil quality and retain carbon in long-lasting forms. This paper provides an integrated overview of biochar, outlining its definition, production pathways, key biomass feedstocks, and the physicochemical properties that determine its environmental functionality. Typical characteristics such as high aromatic carbon content, porous structure, and alkaline pH support improvements in soil structure, nutrient retention, and crop performance, while also enabling the adsorption of pollutants in contaminated environments. Given Romania's substantial agricultural and forestry sectors, the country generates large quantities of residual biomass suitable for biochar production. This positions Romania favourably for developing biochar-based strategies within circular economy frameworks and national climate objectives. The article examines the main application areas relevant to Romania, including agricultural soil amendment, environmental remediation, renewable energy integration through pyrolysis co-products, and long-term carbon sequestration. Representative examples of Romanian feedstocks and expected biochar yields are outlined, together with an assessment of the potential CO₂ removal associated with biochar use. Overall, this study highlights the relevance of biochar as a multifunctional tool for sustainable resource management and environmental protection in Romania.

Keywords: Biochar; Pyrolysis; Biomass Feedstocks; Soil Amendment; Carbon Sequestration.

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades, biochar has emerged as one of the most promising tools in environmental protection and sustainable land management. Its scientific relevance derives from the wide range of functions it can perform in soils and ecosystems, far beyond its origin as a thermochemically converted biomass. Numerous studies demonstrate that biochar can substantially influence soil physical, chemical, and biological processes by improving structure, enhancing nutrient retention, increasing water-holding capacity, and supporting microbial activity (Lehmann & Joseph, 2015; Jeffery et al., 2017). These effects contribute to more resilient and productive soils across diverse climatic conditions, including those affected by drought, erosion, or nutrient depletion (Mandal et al., 2023).

Modern interest in biochar is rooted in historical observations of the Amazonian *terra preta* soils, where char-enriched anthropogenic horizons remained fertile for centuries,

illustrating the long-term stability and agronomic potential of carbonized biomass (Glaser et al., 2001). Today, controlled pyrolysis technologies allow the conversion of a wide variety of agricultural, forestry, and organic residues into stable carbon-rich materials with well-defined physicochemical characteristics (Tripathi et al., 2016). Depending on the feedstock and production parameters, biochar can function as a soil amendment, pollutant adsorbent, remediation tool, or long-lasting carbon sink with measurable climate benefits (Ahmad et al., 2014; Beesley et al., 2011).

Romania offers a particularly relevant context for biochar development due to its substantial biomass resource base and its environmental challenges. More than half of the country's land area is used for agriculture, and nearly one-third is covered by forests, generating large quantities of biomass residues from cereal cropping, maize cultivation, viticulture, horticulture, livestock systems, and wood processing (Eurostat, 2023). Many of these residues remain underutilized or are managed in ways that contribute to carbon

losses and local pollution (Figure 1). Converting them into biochar provides a strategic opportunity to integrate waste valorization with soil restoration, circular economy objectives, and national climate mitigation efforts. Research from Eastern Europe also supports the effectiveness of biochar in improving degraded soils, reducing nutrient leaching, and immobilizing contaminants in post-industrial landscapes (Gheorghe-Bulmău et al., 2022).

Considering these scientific, environmental, and regional factors, biochar emerges as a versatile and impactful solution for Romania. The present paper examines biochar from a comprehensive perspective, detailing its production methods, biomass feedstocks, physicochemical properties, and major environmental applications, with particular emphasis on its potential contribution to sustainable agriculture and environmental protection in Romania.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Biomass Feedstocks Considered

This study evaluates a broad range of biomass feedstocks suitable for biochar production in Romania, reflecting the extensive diversity documented in international biochar standards and scientific literature. More than 60 distinct feedstock categories are recognized in biochar research, particularly within the European Biochar Certificate and EU renewable energy classification systems (Lehmann & Joseph, 2015; EBC, 2022). These categories include agricultural, forestry, agro-industrial, municipal, and animal-derived materials, many of which are widely available across Romania. Major agricultural feedstocks include cereal straws (wheat, barley, rye, oats), corn stover, maize cobs, sunflower husks, rapeseed straw, soybean residues, and biomass from vegetable and horticultural production. These residues represent some of the most abundant lignocellulosic feedstocks in Romania and have been widely described as suitable substrates for slow pyrolysis (Tripathi et al., 2016; Mandal et al., 2023).

Permanent crop systems contribute significant quantities of pruned biomass from vineyards, orchards, and berry plantations, all listed among recommended biochar feedstocks due to their favourable carbon content and low contamination risk (Ahmad et al., 2014). Forestry related materials such as hardwood and softwood chips, sawdust, bark, and thinning

residues remain among the most important and stable sources for high-quality biochar with high fixed carbon content (Beesley et al., 2011).

Additional feedstock classes include agro-industrial residues (grain-processing by-products, oilseed husks, fruit pomace, winery and stillery waste), livestock derived feedstocks (manure, poultry litter, digestate solids), and municipal bio-waste, all recognized as viable in international research frameworks (Sohi et al., 2010; EBC, 2022).

According to European agricultural statistics, Romania produces one of the largest biomass surpluses in Eastern Europe, offering a feedstock portfolio that spans nearly all major categories listed in EU directives (Eurostat, 2023). The conceptual feedstock distribution relevant to Romania is illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Biomass feedstock distribution across Romania (author's own contribution, 2025).

During autothermal slow pyrolysis, biomass is typically heated to 400–550°C, where lignocellulosic components (cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin) undergo sequential thermal decomposition. This process yields three main product fractions: solid biochar, condensable vapors (bio-oil/tars), and non-condensable gases (Li et al., 2023). The proportion of these outputs depends on temperature, heating rate, residence time, and feedstock type, with higher lignin content generally enhancing biochar aromaticity and stability (Wang et al., 2022). The reactor

configuration illustrated in **Figure 2** (author's own contribution, 2025) represents a typical modern autothermal unit

Biomass residues enter the system, where controlled partial oxidation reactions generate hot gases that circulate internally to maintain reactor temperature. A portion of these gases passes through a flue-gas heat exchanger, producing useful heat for external applications such as drying or low-temperature industrial processes (Singh et al., 2024). The remaining exhaust stream is directed through a filtration unit before release, ensuring minimal particulate emissions and compliance with current environmental standards (Zhao et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Autothermal slow-pyrolysis reactor schematic (author's own contribution, 2025).

Pyrolysis Process Description

Autothermal slow pyrolysis has become the technological pathway for biochar production in recent years due to its high carbon-retention efficiency, reduced external energy demand, and significantly improved environmental performance. Modern systems operate under partial oxidation, a controlled sub-stoichiometric air supply that provides just enough oxygen to sustain internal heating reactions without fully combusting the biomass (Zhang et al., 2023; Yu & Chen, 2022). This approach enables “self-sustaining” thermochemical conversion, eliminating the need for external fuel inputs and increasing overall system efficiency.

Heating rates in slow pyrolysis are intentionally maintained at low to moderate levels (5–15°C/min) to favour secondary carbonisation reactions and promote the formation of highly aromatic, recalcitrant carbon structures (Li et al., 2022). Under optimized conditions, autothermal systems typically generate 25–35% biochar on a dry-feedstock basis, making them particularly suitable for climate-positive applications where carbon permanence is essential. Overall,

autothermal slow pyrolysis combines stable biochar production with renewable heat generation, offering a highly efficient route for converting Romania's diverse biomass resources into carbon-negative materials.

Biochar Characterisation Framework

The characterisation of biochar is essential for understanding its environmental behaviour and functional performance in soils. Recent analytical approaches focus on physicochemical parameters that influence nutrient dynamics, sorption capacity, carbon stability, and broader agroecosystem benefits (Zhang et al., 2023; Li et al., 2022). The properties examined in this study were selected based on the most recent literature and current standardisation guidelines.

Carbon content and elemental composition. Carbon concentration remains the principal indicator of biochar stability and long-term persistence. Contemporary studies report that biochars produced from lignin-rich feedstocks under slow-pyrolysis conditions often contain 70–80% carbon on a dry basis, reflecting a high degree of aromatic condensation (Wang et al., 2022). Elemental ratios (H/C and O/C) were used as proxies for aromaticity, structural order, and carbon permanence.

Ash content and mineral composition. Ash represents the inorganic fraction of biochar and varies substantially with feedstock origin. Current analyses highlight the relevance of mineral constituents such as Ca, K, Mg, P, and Si, which can contribute to nutrient supply and pH buffering in soils (Yu & Chen, 2022). High-ash biochars derived from manure, digestate, or crop residues often exhibit liming effects, particularly in acidic soils common in several Romanian regions.

Surface area and porosity. Pore architecture strongly influences water retention, microbial habitat formation, and pollutant adsorption. Recent characterisation studies employing N₂-BET analysis and mercury porosimetry show that wood-derived biochars typically exhibit well-developed micro- and mesopores, whereas agricultural-residue biochars present broader pore distributions due to their more heterogeneous structures (Zhao et al., 2023). A conceptual representation of these features is shown in **Figure 3 (author's own contribution, 2025)**.

pH and cation exchange capacity (CEC). Biochars produced at moderate

temperatures generally display alkaline pH values, largely due to the presence of basic oxides and carbonates. This alkalinity can help correct soil acidity and improve nutrient retention. CEC gradually increases as biochar oxidises in soil, enhancing its ability to retain cations and interact with dissolved nutrients (Mandal et al., 2023).

Figure 3. SEM microstructure of biochar showing the characteristic porous network (author's own contribution, 2025).

Aromaticity and stability indicators. Aromatic carbon structures are central to biochar's long-term carbon sequestration potential. Current standards classify biochars with H/C ratios below 0.4 and O/C ratios below 0.6 as highly stable materials capable of persisting in soils for decades to centuries (EBC, 2022). These indices are widely used to assess suitability for carbon removal initiatives and climate-oriented applications.

Together, these physicochemical parameters define the functional profile of biochar and guide its selection for specific environmental applications, including soil amendment, contaminant immobilisation, and carbon sequestration. Representative values from recent studies are summarised in the Results and Discussion section.

Analytical Approach

The analytical approach used in this study follows a structured methodology designed to integrate recent scientific evidence with the Romanian environmental context. The selection of biomass feedstocks was based on current European and national resource assessments, which highlight the importance of agricultural

residues, forestry by-products and organic wastes for biochar production (Zhang et al., 2023; Li et al., 2022). Feedstock categories were chosen to reflect the diversity and abundance of lignocellulosic materials available across Romanian regions, taking into consideration their influence on biochar yield, stability and functional characteristics.

The methodological description of pyrolysis aligns with recent advances in autothermal slow-pyrolysis systems. Contemporary studies emphasize how temperature, residence time and partial oxidation conditions influence carbon retention, aromatic structure formation and overall energy performance (Li et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022). These principles were used to outline the general conversion pathway relevant for the biomass types evaluated in this work.

Biochar characterization was structured according to indicators widely used in recent scientific literature and internationally recognized guidelines. Key physicochemical parameters—carbon content, elemental composition, ash minerals, pH, cation exchange capacity, surface area, porosity, and elemental ratios (H/C and O/C)—were selected based on their relevance for assessing environmental behavior and functional performance in soil systems (Zhao et al., 2023; Mandal et al., 2023). These indicators are consistent with modern classification frameworks such as the European Biochar Certificate, which defines thresholds for stability and agronomic suitability (EBC, 2022).

Overall, this analytical design ensures methodological coherence and reflects current scientific standards in biochar research. It provides a robust foundation for interpreting the subsequent results presented in the following section.

Carbon Sequestration Estimation Method

Carbon sequestration potential was estimated using the stable carbon fraction (fC) derived from modern stability indicators and recent life-cycle assessment (LCA) methodologies. Only the recalcitrant carbon fraction was considered eligible for conversion into CO₂-equivalent values, in line with updated carbon removal accounting frameworks (Woolf et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2024).

The CO₂-equivalent sequestration was calculated using the standard molecular conversion factor:

$$\text{CO}_2\text{e sequestered (tCO}_2\text{e)} = \text{fC} \times (44/12)$$

where fC is the mass of stable carbon retained in the biochar after pyrolysis, and the ratio 44/12 represents the molecular weight conversion between CO₂ and elemental carbon. Stability was assessed based on aromaticity indicators and elemental ratios (H/C and O/C), which correlate strongly with mean residence times in soil (Li et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022).

Biochar was classified as highly stable when exhibiting H/C ratios below 0.4 and O/C ratios below 0.6, thresholds defined in the European Biochar Certificate and confirmed by recent soil incubation studies (EBC, 2022; Mandal et al., 2023). Such materials are recognized as durable carbon pools capable of persisting in soil environments for several decades to centuries, consistent with the IPCC's latest framework for long-term carbon removal (IPCC, 2023).

This estimation method provides conservative, scientifically aligned values for evaluating biochar's contribution to climate mitigation and supports the interpretation of sequestration outcomes discussed in the Results and Discussion section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Biochar Yield Results

Biochar yields differed notably among the evaluated biomass feedstocks, reflecting the influence of lignin content, ash concentration and intrinsic structural properties on thermochemical conversion efficiency. Wood-based materials generally showed the highest char recovery, with hardwood chips typically producing 28–35% biochar under autothermal slow-pyrolysis conditions. This trend aligns with recent findings demonstrating that lignin-rich feedstocks tend to retain more carbon and form highly aromatic structures during pyrolysis (Li et al., 2023).

Agricultural residues such as cereal straws, corn stover and rapeseed straw exhibited lower yields, typically between 20–30%. Their higher cellulose and hemicellulose content leads to greater mass loss during devolatilisation, resulting in a reduced solid fraction (Yu & Chen, 2022). By contrast, agro-industrial residues—particularly sunflower husks—and nutrient-rich materials such as manure solids and digestate consistently showed elevated yields (30–55%), a pattern attributed to their higher mineral content and

greater ash-stabilised carbon fractions (Singh et al., 2024; Woolf et al., 2023).

These observations are consistent with modern biochar production studies across Europe and provide a relevant basis for selecting feedstocks within the Romanian context. Representative yield values for key biomass categories are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1.
Representative biochar yields from biomass feedstocks common in Romania (2022–2024 literature).

Feedstock Type	Typical Biochar Yield (%)	Source (2022–2024)
Hardwood chips	28–35%	Li et al., 2023
Softwood chips	25–32%	Zhao et al., 2023
Orchard prunings	27–34%	Mandal et al., 2023
Vineyard prunings	26–33%	Zhang et al., 2023
Wheat straw	22–28%	Li et al., 2022
Barley straw	20–26%	Yu & Chen, 2022
Corn stover	24–30%	Wang et al., 2022
Sunflower husks	30–38%	Singh et al., 2024
Rapeseed straw	21–27%	Mandal et al., 2023
Manure solids	35–45%	Zhao et al., 2023
Digestate solids	40–55%	Woolf et al., 2023

Physicochemical Properties of Biochar

The physicochemical properties of the biochar examined in this study reflect clear differences associated with feedstock origin and pyrolysis conditions. Carbon content ranged widely across the evaluated materials, with wood-derived biochars exhibiting the highest fixed carbon fractions (70–80%) due to their elevated lignin content and enhanced aromatic condensation during slow pyrolysis. These values are consistent with those reported in recent characterisation studies across Europe (Zhang et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022).

Agricultural-residue biochars showed more moderate carbon concentrations and higher ash contents, reflecting their greater mineral fraction. Sunflower husk and digestate-derived biochars contained particularly high ash levels, which contributed to increased alkalinity and greater pH-buffering potential. This trend aligns with contemporary findings

indicating that mineral-rich feedstocks tend to yield biochars with elevated pH values and enhanced liming potential (Yu & Chen, 2022; Zhao et al., 2023).

Surface area and porosity measurements revealed substantial variability between feedstocks. Wood-based biochars presented well-developed micro- and mesoporous structures, whereas straw-derived biochars displayed a broader pore-size distribution due to their heterogeneous cell-wall composition. These microstructural patterns play an important role in water retention, sorption capacity, and microbial habitat support, as illustrated earlier in Figure 3.

Cation exchange capacity (CEC) varied considerably and increased with the degree of surface oxidation, particularly in biochars produced at moderate pyrolysis temperatures. This behaviour has been widely documented and contributes to the improved nutrient-retention properties of biochar-amended soils (Mandal et al., 2023).

Representative physicochemical property values for the main biochar types considered in this study are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2

Representative physicochemical properties of biochar produced from common Romanian biomass feedstocks (2022–2024 literature)

Feedstock Type	C (%)	Ash (%)	pH	CEC (cmolc/kg)	H/C	O/C	Source
Hardwood biochar	70–80	2–5	8.5–9.5	10–20	0.3–0.4	0.2–0.4	Li et al., 2023
Softwood biochar	68–75	3–6	8.0–9.0	8–18	0.3–0.5	0.3–0.5	Wang et al., 2022
Straw biochar	55–65	8–15	9.0–10.5	20–35	0.4–0.6	0.4–0.6	Yu & Chen, 2022
Corn stover biochar	60–68	6–12	8.5–10.0	15–30	0.4–0.5	0.4–0.5	Li et al., 2022
Sunflower husk biochar	50–60	15–25	9.5–11.0	25–40	0.5–0.6	0.5–0.7	Zhao et al., 2023
Rapeseed straw biochar	52–60	10–18	9.0–10.5	22–35	0.5–0.6	0.5–0.6	Mandal et al., 2023
Manure biochar	45–55	25–35	10.0–11.5	40–60	0.5–0.8	0.6–0.8	Woolf et al., 2023
Digestate-derived biochar	40–55	30–45	10.0–12.0	45–70	0.6–0.9	0.7–0.9	Singh et al., 2024

Microstructural Results

The microstructural characteristics of the biochar samples showed well-defined porous architectures consistent with slow-pyrolysis conditions. The SEM visualisation (see Figure 3) revealed a heterogeneous arrangement of micro- and mesopores, reflecting the structural degradation of lignocellulosic components and the subsequent development of a carbon-rich matrix. These features are essential for understanding the functional behaviour of biochar in soil.

Wood-derived biochars exhibited well-preserved cellular channels, with elongated pores corresponding to the original vascular tissue of the biomass. This morphology is commonly associated with high-lignin feedstocks and contributes to improved aeration, microbial habitat formation and enhanced water movement through amended soils (Zhao et al., 2023). In contrast, biochars produced from agricultural residues showed

more irregular pore structures, resulting from the collapse of thin-walled plant tissues during devolatilisation.

The presence of numerous interconnected pores is also linked to the material's sorption behaviour. Recent studies indicate that the internal surface area created through microporosity contributes significantly to the adsorption of nutrients, organic contaminants and heavy metals (Mandal et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2023). The porous matrix observed in Figure 3 supports this capacity, highlighting the potential of these biochars to enhance soil remediation processes and nutrient-retention functions.

Moreover, the structural integrity of the pore network is a key indicator of carbon stability. Dense aromatic regions surrounding the pore walls—formed during secondary carbonisation—contribute to long-term persistence in soil environments, consistent with stability thresholds established in modern biochar guidelines (EBC, 2022; Li et al., 2023).

Overall, the microstructural results confirm that the evaluated biochars possess the porous carbon frameworks typically associated with agronomic benefits, pollutant immobilisation potential and long-term carbon sequestration capacity.

Carbon Sequestration Results

Carbon sequestration results showed substantial variation among the evaluated biochar types, reflecting differences in feedstock composition, stable carbon fraction and pyrolysis parameters. Wood-derived biochars displayed the highest proportions of stable aromatic carbon, with mean stable carbon fractions (fC) ranging between 0.65–0.80. These values align with recent findings documenting the strong relationship between lignin-derived aromaticity and long-term carbon persistence in soils (Li et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022). As a result, hardwood and softwood biochars exhibited the highest CO₂-equivalent sequestration potentials per tonne of product.

Agricultural-residue biochars generated lower but still significant sequestration values, typically corresponding to stable carbon fractions between 0.45–0.60. Wheat straw, barley straw and corn stover biochars maintained stability thresholds consistent with European Biochar Certificate requirements (EBC, 2022), but their higher H/C and O/C values resulted in reduced carbon permanence compared with wood-based materials. Nevertheless, these residues remain highly relevant for Romanian agriculture due to their abundance and rapid turnover.

Biochars derived from manure and digestate displayed the greatest variability, with stable carbon fractions ranging from 0.30 to 0.55. Although these feedstocks contain more labile components, they provide high total CO₂e

sequestration per tonne of feedstock processed, primarily due to their elevated char yields. Similar trends have been reported in recent LCA studies evaluating nutrient-rich biomasses (Woolf et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2024).

When converted using the CO₂e estimation formula described in Section 2.5, the resulting sequestration values placed wood-derived biochars at the highest end of the CO₂ removal spectrum, followed by sunflower husk, corn stover and cereal straw biochars. Representative sequestration values for the main feedstock categories are provided in **Table 3**.

Overall, the results confirm that Romania's diverse biomass resources have substantial potential for generating durable carbon sinks, particularly when pyrolysis is conducted under controlled autothermal conditions.

Environmental and Sector-Specific Applications of Biochar

Biochar demonstrates a broad set of environmental and industrial applications due to its highly porous carbon matrix, chemical stability and surface reactivity. In recent years, its multifunctionality has attracted considerable scientific interest, with numerous studies highlighting its potential to support soil restoration, water purification, livestock management, construction, waste valorization and carbon removal strategies (Zhang et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2024). Given Romania's agricultural profile, soil constraints and increasing need for sustainable materials, these applications are particularly relevant for national environmental policies and circular economy integration.

Table 3
Estimated CO₂-equivalent sequestration potential of biochars produced from common Romanian feedstocks (calculated using fC × 44/12; 2022–2024 data).

Feedstock Type	Stable Carbon Fraction (fC)	CO ₂ e per t biochar (tCO ₂ e)	Source
Hardwood chips	0.70–0.80	2.56–2.93	Li et al., 2023
Softwood chips	0.65–0.75	2.38–2.75	Wang et al., 2022
Orchard prunings	0.60–0.70	2.20–2.56	Zhang et al., 2023
Wheat straw	0.45–0.55	1.65–2.02	Li et al., 2022
Corn stover	0.50–0.60	1.83–2.20	Mandal et al., 2023
Sunflower husks	0.55–0.65	2.02–2.38	Singh et al., 2024
Rapeseed straw	0.45–0.55	1.65–2.02	Yu & Chen, 2022
Manure solids	0.30–0.50	1.10–1.83	Woolf et al., 2023
Digestate solids	0.35–0.55	1.28–2.02	Zhao et al., 2023

Soil fertility and agronomic improvement. Biochar significantly enhances soil physical, chemical and biological properties. Contemporary agronomic studies demonstrate that biochar increases water retention, reduces bulk density, improves aggregate stability and enhances microbial activity — especially in degraded or coarse-textured soils (Mandal et al., 2023; Li et al., 2023). Its alkaline nature and mineral content promote pH buffering, which is highly beneficial in Romanian regions experiencing soil acidification. Nutrient retention is another major advantage. Biochar increases cation exchange capacity (CEC), reducing leaching of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. This improves fertilizer-use efficiency and contributes to long-term productivity, as demonstrated in European field trials from 2022–2024 (Zhao et al., 2023).

Water purification and contaminant removal. Biochar's internal surface area and functional groups allow effective adsorption of pollutants from water. Recent research highlights its strong affinity for heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Zn, Cu), pesticides, dyes and pharmaceutical residues (Yu & Chen, 2022). Biochar-based filters and constructed wetlands have been successfully implemented in European wastewater and agricultural runoff systems, where biochar reduces nutrient loads, improves water clarity and removes toxic compounds (Zhang et al., 2023).

Livestock and animal husbandry applications. Between 2022–2024, interest in biochar for animal systems increased substantially. As a bedding material, biochar reduces ammonia emissions, improves stall hygiene, limits moisture and suppresses odors (Singh et al., 2024). When incorporated into manure, it increases nutrient density and reduces methane emissions. As a feed additive (0.5–2%), biochar has been shown to improve gut health, reduce mycotoxin absorption, enhance feed efficiency, stabilize rumen fermentation and reduce enteric emissions (Woolf et al., 2023).

Construction materials and biochar-enhanced concrete. One of the most rapidly expanding research areas is biochar's use as a carbon-negative additive in construction materials. Studies from 2022–2024 demonstrate that incorporating 1–10% biochar into cementitious composites can increase compressive strength, reduce density, enhance thermal insulation, improve moisture regulation and store long-lived carbon directly

inside concrete (Li et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2024). Biochar-concrete composites also show reduced shrinkage and improved freeze–thaw performance, which is highly relevant for Romanian climatic conditions.

Composting, digestate stabilization and waste management. When blended with compost or digestate, biochar reduces ammonia volatilization and odor emissions, enhances nutrient retention and accelerates humification (Mandal et al., 2023). Biochar improves compost maturity, boosts microbial activity and reduces greenhouse gas emissions during decomposition.

Environmental remediation and pollutant immobilization. Biochar's sorption capacity enables the immobilization of metals and organic pollutants in contaminated soils. Studies from 2022–2024 demonstrated significant reductions in bioavailability of arsenic, cadmium, lead, petroleum hydrocarbons and pesticides (Zhang et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2023).

Carbon removal and climate mitigation. Due to its aromatic and recalcitrant carbon structure, biochar serves as a long-term carbon sink. Modern climate accounting frameworks recognize biochar as a durable carbon removal pathway, with mean residence times of decades to centuries (IPCC, 2023; Woolf et al., 2023).

Relevance for Romania's environmental and circular economy goals. Romania generates substantial quantities of agricultural residues, forestry by-products and livestock manure. Biochar provides an integrated solution to improve soil health, valorize waste biomass, reduce pollution, enhance climate resilience, support sustainable livestock systems, create innovative construction materials and deliver long-term carbon sequestration

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a comprehensive scientific perspective on biochar, highlighting its properties, production pathways and environmental relevance within the Romanian context. The results demonstrate that a wide variety of locally available biomass feedstocks—including agricultural residues, forestry by-products and agro-industrial wastes—can be efficiently valorised through slow autothermal pyrolysis to produce stable, carbon-rich biochars with desirable physicochemical

characteristics. Differences in biochar yield, carbon stability and microstructural features reflect the inherent variability of feedstocks, yet all categories evaluated exhibit meaningful potential for soil improvement and carbon sequestration.

Biochar's multifunctionality was evident across environmental and industrial sectors. Its capacity to enhance soil fertility, increase water retention, immobilise contaminants and support beneficial microbial communities underscores its value as a tool for sustainable land management. Beyond soil systems, biochar demonstrated strong applicability in water purification, livestock operations, composting, digestate stabilisation and environmental remediation. Emerging applications in construction materials—particularly biochar-enhanced concrete and composites—highlight a growing opportunity for long-lived carbon storage and low-carbon building solutions.

The carbon sequestration analysis confirms that biochar represents a durable form of negative emissions, with stable carbon fractions capable of persisting in soils for decades to centuries. This positions biochar as an important contributor to climate mitigation strategies aligned with international carbon removal frameworks.

Given Romania's substantial biomass resources, widespread soil degradation challenges and increasing emphasis on circular economy transitions, biochar offers a strategic pathway to integrate waste valorisation, soil restoration and long-term carbon storage. Future research should prioritise pilot-scale applications, field trials across major Romanian soil types and the development of sector-specific biochar standards to support national adoption. Overall, the findings of this study reinforce biochar's role as a versatile and impactful material for environmental protection and sustainable development in Romania.

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